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Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University

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Keynote of PhD invention in PhD school

Camouflage physics is still camouflage for defence protection. The invention of PhD thesis has camouflage theory, color engineering, camouflage engineering, camouflage materials and camouflage physics for camouflage assessment against multidimensional combat backgrounds in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for defence protection. The concepts of UV camouflage, adaptive camouflage against multidimensional combat backgrounds, and simultaneous camouflage in UV-Vis-IR spectrums are the invention of PhD thesis in camouflage engineering for defence protection. Photon theory of camouflage engineering has also been applied by imaging technology of hyperspectral camera and digital camera. This is a new concept for contribution of mankind (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f,

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2023g, 2023h, 2023i, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023u, 2023v, 2024g) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023g, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2024a, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g).

Keywords

Color engineering, camouflage engineering, camouflage physics, defence protection, camouflage textiles, defence textiles

Publication and peer review process related to Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics

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REVIEW ARTICLE

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Advancement in UV-Visible-IR camouflage textiles for concealment of defence surveillance against multidimensional combat backgrounds

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Abstract

Target detection of defence technologies is being rapidly upgraded with modern surveillance technologies. The latest techniques of surveillance are already being implemented for defence applications. Self-protection and hiding from opposing forces are the key principles for the protection of special team in defence. Camouflage textiles aim to create confusing objects for target detection of military personnel. These textiles are applied for military protection such as clothing, weapons, vehicles and location hiding nets/tents. The urgent need for camouflage textiles has been formulated with a technical solution and implementation of the right camouflage materials for concealment of defence target signature against dry leaves, green leaves and tree bark-woodland combat background; water-marine combat background; sand-desertland combat background; stone-stoneland combat background; snow-snowland combat background; sky combat background; ice-iceland combat background; and concrete-concreteland combat background (DGTWSICB) in ultraviolet-visible-infrared (UV-Vis-IR) spectrums. This hypothesis of optical and surveillance engineering, digital imaging and hyperspectral imaging has been coalesced for the advancement of UV-Vis-IR-DGTWSICB camouflage textile technology. The principle of camouflage engineering has been approached by broader spectrum probes in UV-Vis-IR rather than Vis ranges only. Furthermore, camouflage materials, camouflage weapon designs, and formulations of camouflage textiles have been proposed for multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. The electromagnetic spectrum, reflection, electron energy, photonic signal and imaging mechanism in UV-Vis-IR have been presented for optical engineering of concealment, detection, recognition and identification of target signature against DGTWSICB. The spectrum relationship of camouflage materials and DGTWSICB materials has been illustrated and compared in UV-Vis-IR spectrums. Camouflage material design, method design and spectral design; textile colorants and technologies; adaptive camouflage; techniques for camouflage textile assessment for digital camera and hyperspectral camera imaging; image processing techniques; and a hierarchical model have been demonstrated for augmentation of camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-IR illumination. Therefore, the anticipated design of camouflage textiles may enhance high-performance innovation for modern surveillance of military protection related to digital camera, hyperspectral camera and radar. This hypothesis includes advanced guidelines for the advanced design of camouflage textiles for multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. The challenges, limitations, innovation and defence applications of camouflage engineering for multidimensional combat backgrounds have been coalesced for concealment, detection, recognition and identification of defence target signature.

Keywords Camouflage textiles, Camouflage engineering, Color engineering, Camouflage materials-methods-spectral design, Combat backgrounds, Camouflage assessment, UV-Vis-IR, Defence protection, Target signature

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Introduction

Surveillance technologies in visible range camouflage and detection are practiced by military professionals. Modern battlefield has been a great challenge due to advanced surveillance of broad electromagnetic spectrums in ultraviolet–visible–near infrared (UV–Vis–NIR) ranges (Lu et al., 2022; Vitalija et al., 2008). Camouflage textiles designate an artificial masking process of target objects with combat backgrounds (CBs) by adaptation of pattern, texture and chromatic characteristics (Sujit et al., 2013). Concealment can be defined as the perceptive interface between the observer/digital camera/hyperspectral camera and target signature by which camouflage textiles are not visualized to detect the antagonistic (enemy) of the opposing team. Camouflage textiles would allow an object to blend into its surrounding combat environment by the optical mechanism of color matching or luminosity. The scale of concealment and detection is identified by its degree of adaptability which means the capability of an adapting object (appearance) to match its CB. The concealment of camouflage textiles can be designed by means of a spectrum probe under specific CB and/or multidimensional CB environments (Jiri et al., 2011). Camouflage textiles are the general practice by defence professionals for hiding weapons, locations and humans from opposition teams. Presently, surveillance technologies have been advanced in extended electromagnetic spectrums in UV–Vis–NIR.

There is an enormous limitation of technologies to fulfill the current requirements of camouflage textiles against multidimensional CBs such as dry leaves, green leaves, and tree bark–woodland combat background; water–marine combat background; sand–desertland combat background; stone–stoneland combat background; snow–snowland combat background; sky combat background; ice–iceland combat background; and concrete–concreteland combat background (DGTWSICB). It is necessary to improve camouflage textiles for target concealment and protection of defence professionals against multidimensional CBs–DGTWSICB in the UV–Vis–IR spectrum (Lu et al., 2022).

Figure 1 depicts the brief application field of camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage textiles, and camouflage weapon design. Figure 2 shows the whole advancement in UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles.

Overview of camouflage textile design and engineering of advancement

Camouflage materials and camouflage assessment have become a vibrant segment of defence research for the protection of special teams in defence who are always playing with the enemy as part of the daily responsibilities of defence profession, and this is an ongoing research headache to the defence and color scientist. There is an enormous lack in standardization of camouflage materials and methodology for the right concealment of the

Fig. 1 Applications of camouflage textiles against multidimensional CBs–DGTWSICB in the UV–Vis–IR spectrums

Fig. 2 Overview of the article on advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage textiles

target signature. An overview of deceiving material selection for camouflage textile formulation and methodological steps of camouflage textile assessment has been demonstrated for the concealment of target signature against CB. The properties of UV-Vis-IR reflection of materials, pigmentation, nanomaterials, thermochromic dyes, thermal insulation and synthetic dyes have been critically discussed in terms of camouflage material properties and their advancement for suitability of defence textile applications. The camouflage mechanism of concealment, detection, recognition and identification (CDRI) of defence target signature has been represented by the chromatic appearance of the target object and CB, digital camera/hyperspectral camera assessment and image processing technique. Therefore, a hierarchical model for camouflage textile formulation and assessment of CDRI has been proposed for simultaneous spectrums in UV-Vis-IR/specific spectrums in UV/Vis/IR for defence applications against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. Optical parameters in UV-Vis-IR are the critical challenge for developing camouflage textiles against multidimensional combat environments. There

are enormous factors that need to be considered to develop a camouflage product, but the core technologies of camouflage engineering are very limited in the literature. There is scope for broaden research for the development of camouflage technologies. This manuscript coalesces a whole optical meaning of camouflage engineering whole controllable and uncontrollable parameters of camouflage engineering to achieve concealment across UV-Vis-IR spectra to meet the multidimensional demands of combat environments. The author coalesces whole parameters, material engineering and color engineering for the optical design of UV-Vis-IR camouflage textiles. The optical phenomena have been represented to conceal camouflage textiles against combat environments.

Optical engineering of camouflage textile design against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB

Figure 3a shows the rough surface design, applicable for the bark camouflage of trees. Figure 3b signifies the disruptive camouflage pattern, applicable for the multi-color effect or tree bark effect. Figure 3c remarks on the

Fig. 3 Camouflage textile patented, patterned and designed for chromatic and achromatic matching against the CB environment

camouflage design of the broken lines, applicable to the design of the leaf of the tree. Figure 3d shows the camouflage design of the human body, the design is applicable for versatile CB. Figure 3e shows the camouflage design with the repeated unit of animal, applicable for woodland CB. Figure 3f reflects the chromatic matching between printed fabric and woodland CB. In Fig. 1, the design of camouflage textile has been patented in visible ranges having limitations with multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB and broader electromagnetic spectrums. Figure 1 prioritizes the different patterns for the design of camouflage textiles against selected CB. These patterns generate the idea about the chromatic and achromatic properties of camouflage textiles against selected CB. Current camouflage textiles (Don, 1989; Floyd, 2016; Marybeth, 1989; Ramli et al., 2012; Rodney, 2007; Sujit et al., 2013; Thomas, 1987) have been augmented in Vis and limited spectrum probe in IR, but the reflection is still visible due to the reflectance of CB materials such

as leaves, bark, branches, grasses and other background materials. Camouflage textile particularly depends on chromatic adaptation with CB in terms of spectral reflectance and its variations. The reflection profile of DGTWSICB materials is the demanding factor for the development of real concealment of camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-IR spectrums against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB (Goudarzi et al., 2014; Lu et al., 2022; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2020). Spectral reflectivity is the optical principle for chromatic and achromatic deviation of target signature. For example, marine camouflage textiles are influenced by the color of water and optical properties in terms of background (Chen et al., 2010). The reflection profile of every CB differs in UV-Vis-IR spectrums. Reflectance of woodland CB is a matter of “chlorophyll” referred to the chromatic adaptation of a green color (fresh leaves) background (Hui & Jianchun, 2007). Textile dyes such as vat, disperse, reactive, sulphur, acid, thermochromic materials, electrochromic materials,

IR reflective pigments, metal oxides such as iron oxide, and nanoparticles such as titanium dioxide are being practiced with textile coloration and coating/printing processes for the development of camouflage textiles. The combination of the right camouflage materials and the development of demanded camouflage textiles have been limited in multidimensional spectrums and CBs. It is necessary to establish actual deceiving material formulation and standard process for the concealment of the target signature in terms of reflection, gloss, texture and color with CB in UV–Vis–IR (Goudarzi et al., 2014; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022a). Spectral reflectance between the target signature and surrounding CB of geographical regions should match for the concealment of the defence target. The evaluation process of concealment and its accuracy is also considered a complicated process of assessment due to the time-consuming and labor-intensive way of field trialing. Spectral and photographic analyses in UV–Vis–IR are the optical advancement for CDRI of target signature against CBs–DGTWSICB (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Md Anwar Hossain, 2022; Kang et al., 2016; Vitalija et al., 2008).

Modeling of exponential pictograph

An exponential relationship is used to fit the optical phenomenon of camouflage materials against combat materials. The relation signifies the suitability of material applications, formulation of material and camouflage coloration. A software-generated value of γ and R^2 has been shown in an exponential relationship. The exponential model represents the optical parameters of camouflage physics such as electron energy, photonic response, reflection, irradiance, optical character in UV–Vis–IR spectrums, optical interference in CBs and imaging versus CDRI prediction in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. The exponential model partially predicts the outcome of R^2 between the value of 0 to 1. Hence, the exponential variation refers to any value of $1 - R^2$. R^2 means the relative predictive power. The nearest value of 1 determines a more accurate prediction of the outcome. In this manuscript, material properties in UV–Vis–IR spectrums have been reviewed and parallelly modeled for the development of UV–Vis–IR camouflage material. The values of reflection percentages have been shown for the remarkable graphical representation. This optical signification has no specific target to make a specific value of R^2 . R^2 values are the outcomes of material properties in UV–Vis–IR spectrums in existing literature. In this subsequent graphical and exponential hypothesis, there is no matter of control the R^2 value and/or make \pm of R^2 value which is the graphical state to simplify the correlation of optical design in terms of camouflage materials and combat materials. Every

value of R^2 is 0 to 1. “0” identifies a far distance from the exponential plot for actual probability; oppositely, “1” identifies the exact matching with the exponential plot in the graph for actual probability. Euler’s number, $e=2.71828$; the constant value represents the exponential function and the speed of increasing or decreasing trend of specific material. The exponential curve signifies the spectral relationship of camouflage material and the materials of CB in UV–Vis–IR spectrums which typically signifies the probability of material for camouflage in UV–Vis–IR under standard temperature and humidity for laboratory scale camouflage assessment. In this article, it is difficult to clarify to indicate the exact temperature and humidity due to the limitations of the review and literature. However, the proposed technologies of camouflage engineering and color engineering for processing textile materials were experimentally tested and presented in different published articles by the sole author, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, scientist; affiliated with RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia, in 2020–2023 (Hossain, 2023h). The final technical data and their optical effects of different climatic conditions are also remarked on, shown, and discussed for color engineering, camouflage engineering, image engineering, target signature and CBs. The nearest value of R^2 correlates with the maximum suitability and probability of camouflage materials against selected CBs. Exponential techniques were used to represent the concise reviewed data for the reader’s clarification in addition to original data and supplementary information under the limitation of review and idea generation for the next stage of research which also experimented by the author for more clarification and signification for camouflage textiles through the techniques of camouflage physics, color engineering, camouflage textiles and defence technologies of CDRI.

The framework of the innovative approach for UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles

The key contributions of camouflage engineering in UV–Vis–IR spectrums have been approached in terms of nine phases of advancement for camouflage textiles. This study has found a new direction of camouflage chemistry and camouflage physics focusing on camouflage material design, method design, CBs–DGTWSICB and extended spectrums which are beyond of existing idea and invention of present literature. This hypothesis of camouflage design is applicable to high-performance camouflage research for defence protection in digital imaging and hyperspectral imaging.

1. Advancement phase-1, illumination principle for CDRI of target signature in UV–Vis–IR spectrums against multidimensional CBs–DGTWSICB.

2. Advancement phase 2, UV–Vis-IR engineering for camouflage textile formulation against CBs-DGTWSICB.
3. Advancement phase 3, exponential relationships of multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB in UV–Vis-IR spectrums.
4. Advancement phase 4, the hypothesis of camouflage textile design in UV–Vis-IR illumination against CBs-DGTWSICB.
5. Advancement phase 5, material design for camouflage textile coloration against CBs-DGTWSICB under UV–Vis-IR spectrums.
6. Advancement phase 6, method design for CDRI measurement of target signature against CBs-DGTWSICB under UV–Vis-IR spectrums.
7. Advancement phase 7, significant advancement of camouflage textiles against modern defence surveillance in UV–Vis-NIR spectrums.
8. Advancement phase 8, the principle of optical approach for camouflage textile coloration for concealment against digital camera imaging/hyperspectral imaging in UV–Vis-IR spectrums.
9. Advancement phase 9, the hierarchical model for camouflage textile formulation and assessment of CDRI against CBs-DGTWSICB.

Advancement phase 1, illumination principle for CDRI of target signature in UV–Vis-IR against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB

The optical mechanism of CDRI in UV–Vis-IR camouflaging, chromatic appearance, spectral frequency, electron energy versus photonic signal for digital camera imaging and hyperspectral camera imaging have been demonstrated by the ‘reflection engineering’ and ‘imaging theory’ in the vein of wavelength-reflection-electron energy-photonic signal. Figure 4 and Eqs. 1–7; CDRI principle has been illustrated according to established theories

of wavelength-reflection-electron energy-photonic signal such as Einstein’s theory of energy (Okun, 2006), Broglie relation of wavelength (Masanoro, 2020) (Broglie, 1987), Snell’s law of reflection (Cole, 1973; Sun et al., 2005) and photon energy of Max Planck (Marburger, 2011). Illumination in the form of energy creates a photonic signal for surveillance and imaging of the target signature against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB.

Principle of optical engineering for CDRI in UV–Vis-IR spectrums

From Eqs. 1 and 2, we can find the difference between the angular momentum of the target signature and CB material-DGTWSICB for CDRI of the target signature.

$$\lambda = h/P = h/mv \tag{1}$$

where λ = wavelength of the electron; Planck’s constant, $h = 6.6 \times 10^{-34}$ kgm²/s; P is the momentum of target CB materials or target signature; the P value manipulates the value of λ in UV–Vis-IR and chromatic appearance of target signature or target CB materials; m = mass of electron of target signature; and v = velocity of the electron. By putting the values of h , m , and v in Eq. 1, we can signify the wavelength. Wavelength in UV–Vis-IR spectrums controls spectral frequency-electron energy-photonic signal for chromatic and achromatic appearance/digital imaging/hyperspectral imaging of target signature against CB material-DGTWSICB.

$$P = \frac{m v}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} \tag{2}$$

where P is the electron angular momentum of the target signature, m is the mass of the electron of the target signature, v is the velocity of the electron of the target signature, and c is the velocity of the light. By putting the values of m , v , and c , we can find the angular momentum of the target signature at different CB locations.

Fig. 4 Illumination principle of digital camera/red, green, blue (RGB) imaging-hyperspectral camera imaging-UV–Vis-IR- CDRI for defence target signature against CBs-DGTWSICB

Optical principle of refractive index and reflection for CDRI in UV-Vis-IR spectrums

By putting the values of i and r in Eq. 3, we can find the refractive index of target CB and target signature.

$$n = \text{Sin}(i)/\text{Sin}(r) \quad (3)$$

where i is the angle of incidence and r is the angle of refraction.

From Eq. 3, the difference in angle of refraction (Δn) for CDRI can be determined using Eq. 4:

$$\Delta n = n_1 - n_2 \quad (4)$$

where n_1 and n_2 are the refractive index of target CB and target signature. By putting the values of n_1 and n_2 , we can signify the CDRI of the target signature against the surrounding background in UV-Vis-IR. The value of n_2 will be almost zero or infinitive when the target signature is high reflective or zero reflectance; hence, the target will be concealed against CB. The minimum/maximum value will identify the CDRI of the target signature against CB.

The spectral and imaging signal of CDRI depends on the velocity of light. From Eq. 5, the difference in velocity of light between CB and target materials for CDRI can be determined.

$$\Delta v = c/n_1 - c/n_2 \quad (5)$$

where c is the constant speed of light, c/n_1 determines the velocity of light of CB materials, n_1 is the value of the refractive index of CB materials, c/n_2 determines the velocity of light of target signature, and n_2 is the value of the refractive index of target signature.

Optical principle of electron energy and photon signal for CDRI in UV-Vis-IR spectrums

By determining the energy of the photon signal of target CB and target signature, we can indicate CDRI of the target signature against surrounding CB in UV-Vis-IR spectrums. When the difference of electron state between the target signature and target CB is nearest to zero or infinitive, the photon signal will follow the energy response to the camera sensor for imaging and spectral frequency of target OB. Therefore, the target signature will be concealed or confused against background materials, CBs-DGTWSICB. The higher energy difference for target CDRI, ΔE , as shown in Eq. 6 will signify the higher number of photons to the camera sensor for detection, recognition, and identification, respectively.

$$\Delta E = hc_1/\lambda - hc_2/\lambda \quad (6)$$

where Planck's constant, $h=6.6 \times 10^{-34}$ kgm²/s; λ is the wavelength of the electron; the term $h c_1/\lambda$ determines the energy of photon signal of target CB materials; c_1 is

the velocity of the light for imaging of CB materials; the term $h c_2/\lambda$ determines the energy of photon signal of target signature; and c_2 is the velocity of light for imaging of target signature.

Optical principle of spectral reflectance for CDRI in UV-Vis-IR spectrums

If the target signature shows zero reflection, the electron energy of the photon signal states at the rest position of acceleration. At rest position of an electron is considered for a target signature of zero reflection materials or low reflection materials, and a voltage difference is considered V volts. The wavelength for identifying CDRI can be determined by using the De Broglie equation of wavelength Eq. 7.

$$\lambda = h/P = h/mv = h/\sqrt{2 \text{ meV}} = \frac{6.6 \times 10^{-34}}{\sqrt{2 \times 9 \times 10^{-31} \times 1.6 \times 10^{-19} \times V}} \quad (7)$$

where Planck's constant, $h=6.6 \times 10^{-34}$ kgm²/s; the constant mass of the electron, $m=9.1 \times 10^{-31}$ kg; constant electron charge, $e=1.6 \times 10^{-19}$ C; and v is the velocity of electron energy carried by photon for creation of imaging signal.

For low-reflection/zero-reflection materials, the electron velocity (v) will be almost zero; and for high-reflection materials, the electron velocity (v) will be infinitive. Therefore, the spectral signal will not be detected for the chromatic appearance and the target signature will be denoted as concealed. Accordingly, detection, recognition and identification of the target signature will be signified by the specific value of the velocity of electron energy.

Advancement phase 2, UV-Vis-IR engineering for camouflage textile formulation against CBs-DGTWSICB

Optical principle of electron energy versus sun radiation for the design of UV-Vis-IR camouflage textiles

In Figs. 5a, b, an exponential graph has been illustrated to simplify the spectral relationship between electron energy and sun radiation in UV-Vis-IR spectrums. Here, the total energy of sunlight is classified into UV-Vis-IR spectrums: UV band, 200–400 nm stores 5% of the total energy; Vis band, 400–720 nm stores 45% of the total energy; and NIR band, 720–2500 nm stores 50% of the total energy (Wake & Brady, 1993). Ninety-nine percent of the sun radiates between 200 and 4000 nm in the chromatic condition of visible 'red ray'. Electron energy, E (eV) of sun radiation changes in UV-Vis-IR spectrums. The summarized data information has been cited in Table S1(a, b). The vibration of electron energy shown in Fig. 5a and sun radiation shown in Fig. 5b are

Fig. 5 An exponential relationship of wavelength versus electron energy, 100–10000 nm (a) and sun radiation, 250–2500 nm (b) in UV–Vis–IR spectrums

significantly higher in UV–Vis spectrums and dramatically decline in IR spectrums. Electrons of object-background (OB) materials combine with the photon from the light of the surveillance device to form chromatic intensity versus imaging of target OB materials. Electron energy and photonic combination generate the intensity/imaging of target OB in the different wavelengths of UV–Vis–IR. The flow of electron energy is almost constant in the entire spectrum of UV–Vis–IR; comparatively higher in UV, medium in Vis and lower in IR spectrums. Photon direction is a matter of altering trichromatic reflection to the imaging sensor. This optical condition of imaging is controlled by the electron energy of OB materials and its related interferences. Choosing the reflection matching materials with multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB for textile formulation may signify the target concealment in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. In optical engineering, the replacement of wavelength changes the electron energy from the target signature to the camera sensor. Electron energy creates a variation of refractive index, which alters the appearance of the target signature to the imaging sensor. Lower electron energy is the limitation of conventional ‘color matching theory’ in IR camouflaging. Hence, the reflection-changing materials may be an optical solution of IR camouflaging or simultaneous camouflaging in UV–Vis–IR spectrums for optical matching of target signature against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB (Cui, 2011; Hossain, 2023; Loebich, 1972).

Reflection versus chromatic signal for the formulation of UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles

Snell’s law is much related illustration for reflectance characteristics of target OB. According to Snell’s law of reflection, the speed of light rays decreases when traveling to a refractive medium (Cole, 1973; Sun et al., 2005). The refractive indexes of the international commission on illumination (CIE)-RGB colors at different wavelengths in UV–Vis–IR are not similar. Such as the refractive index of red color is 1.50917 at wavelength 640 nm, yellow 1.51124 at wavelength 589 nm, green 1.51534 at

wavelength 509 nm, blue 1.51696 at wavelength 486 nm and violet 1.52136 at wavelength 434 nm. Illumination parameters such as refractive index, reflection angle (0° to 360°) and wavelength determine the chromatic signal of target signature and CBs-DGTWSICB to the sensor of digital camera and hyperspectral camera in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. Hence, the chromatic appearances of target OB are replaced when reflectance coefficients (0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0) are shifted as the spectrum probe shown in Fig. 6 (Sönke, 2016; Sun et al., 2005). In general, typical chromatic replacements have been remarked by the replacement of wavelength by the replacement of reflectance value by the replacement of reflection angle between the target signature and optical device. It is so tough to narrate exact optical parameters for camouflage engineering due to optical interference. Reflection coefficients are also related to OB properties in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. Surface gloss depends on surface smoothness or irregularity. Gloss is higher on smooth surfaces and lower on irregular surfaces (Md Anwar Hossain, 2022; Wake & Brady, 1993).

Geometrical theory of reflection for the design of UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles against CBs-DGTWSICB

The key principle of UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles is minimizing the difference in light scattering or radiating properties between the target signature and CBs-DGTWSICB. Hence, the concealment of camouflage textiles depicts a fake target to appear as an optical mechanism of artificial concealing with the opposition team (Tao et al., 2012). Sequentially, camouflage textiles are specified in terms of illumination of target signature and CBs. The angle of reflection depends on the direction of the incident light beam from OB. The ratio of speed difference of light striking denotes the refractive index of OB. The light obstacle is also a fact of camouflage objects as predicted by ‘geometrical ray theory’ when light passes through a tiny hole known as ‘diffraction’. This optical mechanism creates uneven shadow and reflection on the imaging device. Practically, light waves from sunlight

Fig. 6 Typical chromatic appearance (schematic) of six specified wavelengths (nm) in Vis (472 nm and 682 nm) and NIR (870 nm, 1036 nm, 1219 nm and 1273 nm) spectrums

and the camera sensor are not similar, so optical interference occurs when two overlapping of light from unlike sources. A maximum value of refractive index generates the high bending of light. Absorption is a process of transferring energy from the electromagnetic wave to the atom of the target signature and CB substances. The energy can create the excitation of electrons into a higher energy state, and it depends on the wavelength spectrums of light in UV–Vis–IR. Therefore, the absorption–transmission–reflection (ATR) of OB is the key principle behind the camouflage coloration. Optical scattering is an energy removal process of a light beam depending on the structural composition of OB. Optical transmission depicts the weakened absorption and scattering when OB states behind open space in a combat environment of CBs–DGTWSICB (Kulappurath, 2018; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2022).

Reflection principle for camouflage measurement in UV–Vis–IR spectrums

Camouflage textiles are possible to be designed to have irregular chromatic combination, reflection matching and perforation of the surface under consideration of specific CB (Gunnar, 1976). The ATR of the chromophore group differs in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. The intensity of ATR creates chromatic variation (Sudhakar et al., 2008). The design of camouflage textiles is related to color, contrast, lightness, shape, texture and depth of object–background (OB) materials. The hyperspectral camera captures the color outlook of every pixel in the image of the target object and CB. The color difference between OB can be depicted by hue, chromatic and lightness. Spectral behavior and reflection properties of the target signature

at a specific wavelength are the key facts for camouflage textiles with any CB as light is simultaneously reflected from the target OB. Reflection of OB is highly influenced by natural illumination, inter-reflections of existing molecules in the atmosphere, air density and temperature differences. The perceived/imaging color and the measured actual color may have some differences. So there are limitations of accuracy for camouflage measurement in a laboratory rather than field trialing (Baumbach, 2012). CB has many reflectance spectra depending on the angle of light falling on the background and the angle of illumination of the digital camera/hyperspectral camera (Sönke, 2016).

Advancement phase 3, exponential relationships of multidimensional CBs–DGTWSICB in UV–Vis–IR spectrums

Figures 7, 9, and 10 show the spectrum relationships of DGTWSICB such as woodland CB: grass/green leaves (Hossain, 2023aq; Leong, 2007) (Figs. 7a and 10c), dry leaves, tree bark (Asner, 1998; Hossain, 2023aq) (Figs. 7b and 10a, b), vegetation and deciduous tree (Leong, 2007) (Fig. 7c); snowland, iceland and marine CB: snow (Fig. 7d), ice (Fig. 7e) and water (Qunzhu et al., 1983) (Fig. 7f); desertland CB (Burkinshaw et al., 1996; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022c): sand (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022c; Winkelmann, 2015) (Fig. 7g, h) (Asner, 1998) (i); and sky and urban CB: sky (Bachmann et al., 2012) (Fig. 7j), red brick and concrete (Leong, 2007) (Fig. 7k). Spectral data information is summarised through published literature, a supporting information is attached in Table S1, c–m. Every exponential spectrum has been illustrated to represent a common

Fig. 7 Exponential relationship of multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB materials in UV-Vis-IR spectrums: (a) 700–1600 nm; (b) 500–2500 nm; (c) 300–1900 nm; (d) 400–1200 nm; (e) 400–1200 nm; (f) 400–1200 nm; (g) 400–1200 nm; (h) 2000–14,000 nm; (i) 500–2500 nm; (j) 300–1900 nm; (k) 300–1900 nm

spectral coefficient of CB in UV-Vis-IR (Hossain, 03 February 2023; Xu & Liang, 2001). These exponential spectra typically signify the expected spectra of camouflage materials under single/multidimensional

CBs-DGTWSICB. Spectral characteristics of individual CB need to be considered for camouflage coloration against single CB or simultaneous CB or adaptive CB under UV-Vis-IR spectrums.

Fig. 8 Spectral signals of high-reflection materials at 200–10,000 nm (a) and synthetic dyes at 350–950 nm (b) in UV–Vis–IR spectrums with the relationship of exponential coefficients

Advancement phase 4, hypothesis of camouflage textile design in UV–Vis–IR illumination against CBS-DGTWSICB

Optical principle of technical materials versus synthetic dyes for camouflage textiles in simultaneous spectrum probe

Figure 8a, b illustrates a general comparison of exponential relationships between high-reflection materials and synthetic dyes. Reviewed data are summarized and cited in Table S1 (o) (Cui, 2011). Figure 8a, aluminium, rhodium and titanium particle show an almost straight line in UV–Vis–IR spectrums as a sequence of aluminium > rhodium > titanium > copper > silver > gold. Such high-reflection materials may signify camouflage materials in UV–Vis–IR due to random/infinite photonic response to the imaging device. Figure 8b depicts the exponential relationships of synthetic dyes which

shows the completely reverse behavior in UV–Vis–NIR spectrums. Chrysoidine, orange 2 and lithol fast scarlet-rhodamine naphthol phthalein (RNP) are the synthetic dyes of the mono azo group; chrysophenine G is a synthetic dye of the diazo group; and flavophosphine is a dye of the acridine group. These groups of synthetic dyes are very common for textile coloration in terms of CB color matching in the Vis spectrum. Therefore, camouflage textile coloration in simultaneous spectrum probes needs to choose alternative materials rather than synthetic dyes only or technical formulation of synthetic dyes. The UV–Vis–IR spectrums of synthetic dyes and high-reflection materials have been classified as the low and high amplitude of the signal. Figure 8a, b in comparison, synthetic dyes are remarked as deviation of high amplitude, and high-reflection materials are signified as variation of low amplitude. Few high-reflection materials

Table 1 Summarised exponential relationship of electron energy/photonic response among multidimensional CB materials and materials for textile coloration in UV–Vis–IR spectrums

Multidimensional CBs materials	Electron energy or photonic response	Materials for textile coloration (dyeing or coating or printing)	Electron energy or photonic response
Woodland	NIR > Vis > UV	Synthetic dyes (five different)	NIR > Vis > UV
Snowland	UV > Vis > NIR	Aluminium	UV = Vis = IR
Iceland	UV > Vis > NIR	Rhodium	Vis = IR
Marine	UV > Vis > NIR	Copper	IR > Vis > UV
Desertland	IR > Vis > UV	Titanium	IR > Vis > UV
Soil	IR > Vis > UV	Silver	IR > Vis > UV
Sky	UV > Vis > NIR	Gold	Vis = IR
Urban	NIR > Vis > UV	Shiny surface	UV = Vis = IR

have almost zero deviation of amplitude and hypothetically remarked as $UV = Vis = IR$ and $Vis = IR$ referred to Table 1. Electron density significantly decreases when spectral amplitude/intensity is in the negligible range (Sark, 2002; Shengyue et al., 2015). There is a possibility of capturing a minor deviation of the photonic signal to the imaging sensor in UV–Vis–NIR illumination. Accordingly, the reflectance profile of CB varies in the UV–Vis–NIR region (Hui & Jianchun, 2007). The reflection factors of CB such as tree branches, leaves, soil, rocks and water differ by 10–80% for the CDRI mechanism (Puzikova et al., 2008). The difference in reflection between the target object (camouflage textiles) and CB determines the chromatic adaptation (CIE RGB, L^* , a^* , b^*) versus CDRI. The reflection properties of CB are the parameters of CDRI for the target signature (Muzaffer & Yavuz, 2010). The threat of reflection is also related to the surrounding CB materials rather than specific known materials of CBs-DGTWSICB (Thomas, 1987). Therefore, the optical hypothesis of simultaneous spectrum probe camouflage textiles in UV–Vis–NIR ranges is critical due to the deviation of reflection phenomenon from signature and CBs.

In Figs. 7g, h, and i and 9; the NSSD material and aluminium may be coated on textile substances for the reflection matching against desertland CB (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c). In Fig. 9b, c; laboratory and field trialing samples of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain have been shown for color matching for the concealment against desertland combat background. Figure 9b remarks on the concealing ability of silicon dioxide-coated textiles against desertland CB. Figure 9c signifies the concealing ability of aluminium-coated hollow fabric against desertland CB. In Fig. 10c, d; there is a reflection matching between chromium oxide-coated textiles and woodland combat material (green leaves). Chromium oxide material may be coated on textile material for concealment against woodland combat background (green

leaves) because of the symmetrical properties of synthetic chlorophyll and natural chlorophyll. In Fig. 10a, b, there is a deviation between the reflection of dry leaves and tree bark against chromium oxide-coated textiles due to the material properties of dry leaves and tree bark due to lack of chlorophyll existence (Hossain, 2023aq). In Figs. 7a–c, e, f, and 10g; NPND materials can be coated on textile materials for woodland camouflage textiles. Laboratory and field trialing samples of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain have been shown for color matching for the concealment against a woodland combat background. Figure 10e remarks on the concealment of Cr oxide-coated textiles against green grasses and stems against woodland materials. Figure 10f shows the deviation of color matching of Cr oxide-coated textiles against dry grasses and stems against woodland materials. Figure 10g signifies the deviation of color matching of Cr oxide-coated textiles against the simultaneous reflection of dry grasses, green grasses, dry stems, green stems, dry tree barks and dry tree leaves against woodland materials.

Optical principle of material design for camouflage textiles in simultaneous spectrum probe

In Fig. 11, Vis-IR coefficients of black color and high-reflection materials (shiny surface) are represented at similar pixel positions. A simultaneous photonic signal in Vis-IR is illustrated by the sum of Vis and IR amplitude. The data information has been attached in Table S1 (n). The variation of the photonic signal is significantly higher in Vis than in IR. Heat in the IR region increases the emissivity of OB and declines the reflectance of OB. This IR mechanism is responsible for minor photonic signals to remote sensing devices of digital imaging/hyperspectral imaging. In IR spectrums, the photonic response of black color is comparatively higher than in high-reflection materials as shown in amplitude. Oppositely, a photonic signal of black color is lower than high-reflection

Fig. 9 Exponential relationship of natural sand-based silicon dioxide (NSSD) and aluminium for desertland combat background from 400 to 700 nm (a), samples of NSSD-coated textiles (b), and aluminium-coated textiles (c) against desertland combat background

materials in Vis spectrums. Hence, the hypothesis states that the combination principle of such materials may signify simultaneous camouflage in UV–Vis–IR spectrums (Gao & Tian, 2018).

Optical principle of technical formulation of UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles

UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles are proposed by treating them with metallic reflection materials such as aluminum, copper and zinc. Camouflage pigment such as chromium oxide has reflection properties like ‘chlorophyll’ for adaptation of target signature with woodland CB. Alternatively, carbon black pigment (CBP) has high absorption and low-reflection properties in IR spectrums. Thermal transparent binders such as polyethylene vinyl acetate copolymer and chlorinated polypropylene are suitable for camouflage treatment as the binder cannot change the reflection. Currently developed camouflage textiles can be detected from CB in the NIR spectrum. The military vehicle produces heat by the internal combustion engine and

terrestrial thermal emissions. The adaptation of emission between OB needs to be maintained for the concealment of the target signature. Temperature is a cause for the contrasting between the target signature and CB. Thermal insulation can be used for camouflage textiles when the surface temperature difference from the environment is more than 10°C. The application of thermal insulation materials is an option for secure protection and structuring UV–Vis–NIR camouflage textiles such as vehicle nets. Such fabric also protects against radar spectrums (3 to 3000 GHz) (M. A. Hossain, 2021c; Hossain, 2023aq; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2020; Pusch et al., 1985).

Camouflage textile materials in the IR range are made from synthetic fiber having ‘chlorophyll’ like reflectance characteristics in IR range such as polyamide and polyester (Horst & Guido, 2003). High reflection in the multidimensional direction to the viewing angle depicts the concealment of the target location. The high-reflection light theory is applied to camouflage for submarine concealment as marine

Fig. 10 Exponential relationship of woodland materials for natural plant-based natural dyes (NPND) for camouflage coloration and comparison with Cr oxide-coated textiles from 400 to 700 nm (a, b, c, d) and samples of Cr oxide-coated textiles against woodland materials and woodland background (e, f, g)

camouflage. Reflective metallic coatings of aluminum copper or zinc on the base layer achieve high reflectivity in the entire IR spectrums, but the technology has limited applications of camouflage textiles for concealment in UV–Vis–IR spectrums against multi-dimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. The protection against radar detection is achieved with coated materials for effectively reflecting radar radiation in all directions (Li et al., 2020) (Barbier et al., 2002; Gancheryonok & Lavrinenko, 2002; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a).

UV-Vis-NIR camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral cameras against defence surveillance

Hyperspectral camouflage means the protection of the target signature from surrounding CB in terms of hiding hyperspectral surveillance in UV–Vis–NIR spectrums. Chromatic blending of objects (camouflage textiles) with CB environment is the first attribute of hyperspectral camouflage textiles. Camouflage depends on the shape, size, hue, color contrast and mobility of the target object with CB. Differences in ATR,

Fig. 11 Exponential of Vis-IR photonic signal versus design of camouflage materials for simultaneous spectrum probe

scattering, diffraction and polarization of light between target OB identify the detectability or adaptability of target object against CBs-DGTWSICB. Hyperspectral, thermal, NIR, multispectral and anti-radar camouflaging are the critical challenge for the technological matching versus survivability of defence professionals. UV and NIR sensors of the hyperspectral camera have created a great challenge of hyperspectral camouflage. Recent augmentation of camouflage textiles only covers Vis ranges camouflage although there is a limitation of concealment in multidimensional CB environments in terms of lacking the right materials, methodologies, camouflage technologies and standardization. Recently developed camouflage textiles cannot fulfill the protection of UV-IR ranges surveillance technology in the vein of hyperspectral cameras or digital cameras. Colorant manufacturers are also struggling with camouflage dyes, but the right formulation is still a challenging fact. NIR reflectance dyes or pigment coating, aluminum-coated glass thermally bonded into non-woven, glass fabric and nonwoven fabric combination can be comprised in terms of photochromic (light), and thermochromic (heat) mechanism of camouflage textiles for augmentation of NIR camouflage. The simultaneous camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-NIR ranges are also a critical challenge to the research community, and the technology needs to coalesce through the optical mechanism of OB and suitable material design for camouflage textile coloration (Alka & Priyanka, 2017; A. Hossain, 2021b; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Li et al., 2020; Shami et al., 2017). In Figs. 7, 8, 9, and 11, the reflection coefficients and exponential trends of multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB in UV-Vis-NIR have been remarkably noted and hypothetically categorized in Table 1. This concept can be hypothetically

implemented for the design of camouflage materials in UV-Vis-NIR spectrums.

Advancement phase 5, material design for camouflage textile coloration against CBs-DGTWSICB under UV-Vis-IR spectrums

Optical principle of camouflage pigmentation for Vis-IR range concealment

Simultaneous applicable Vis-IR camouflage technology is proposed based on the metal-based structure of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Ag}/\text{ZnS}/\text{Ag}$ (Dong et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020). For simultaneous pigmentation in Vis-IR, the pigment should have simultaneous transparency in Vis-IR ranges. Vis camouflage textiles can be designed with a dark color or minimum gloss pigmentation, such as CBP and perylene black as the selective absorber. Metal oxide increases the concealment in the NIR and thermal IR ranges. Metal oxide absorbs in the NIR range, and these are transparent in the thermal IR range. Metal oxides (CeO_2 , TiO_2 , MgO and ZnO) show high reflection in simultaneous Vis-IR spectrums. The reflection variations between Vis and IR are nearest to 5%. As a hypothetical example, Fig. 12 depicts the exponential relationship of ZnO pigment in Vis-NIR spectrums. Reviewed data information is cited in Table S1 (q). Metal flakes, such as aluminium, reflect strongly in both the Vis and IR spectrums. Red iron oxide and titanium dioxide have a minimum scattering effect on light without altering the reflectance shape. Particles of 1 mm of red iron and titanium dioxide scatter NIR radiation at 2.3 mm. The refractive index of titanium dioxide and chromium oxide is 2.81 and 1.90, and their scattering powers (square meters) are 1.90 and 1.28, respectively. Titanium dioxide (mean particle size 10 μm) reflects between 800 and 2300 nm, and

Fig. 12 Exponential spectra of ZnO pigment in Vis–NIR spectrums from 400 to 2200 nm

comparatively less reflection is noted at 400–800 nm. Such compounds have atomic mobility and the light-striking capability of a target signature at a very high incident angle. There is a possibility of electron trapping between the target signature and CB, which mechanism may generate minor energy for the photonic signal to the remote sensing device. Hence, the light is also expected to scatter very quickly in the surrounding area of CB. The photonic signal of metal oxides to the spectral sensor cannot capture enough photons to generate an appropriate imaging signal of the target signature against CB. The high-reflection spectral signal may defend the genuine pixel formation of the target signature on the imaging sensor. Therefore, the target signature may be confused or concealed by the modern remote sensing mechanism of the target detector (Fang et al., 2013; Groning, 2002; Lummerstorfer & Hoffmann, 2004; Wake & Brady, 1993).

Commercial pigments are available such as color index (CI) pigment green 17, 26 and 50; CI pigment brown 29 and 35, pigment blue 28 and 36, pigment black 12 and white pigment base are also available such as white pigment titanium dioxide or zinc white, calcium carbonate, barium sulphate, alumina, silica, clay and aluminum powder; metal oxides such as zirconium oxide and thorium oxide; metallic pigment such as aluminum and mica flakes; high refractive index pigments such as titanium dioxide, chromium oxide, zinc sulphide, zinc oxide, aluminium, gold, silver and copper. A combination of different IR-reflective pigments may enhance the total reflection of the coated

surface. Particle size can be selected from 0.35 to 0.55 microns (Ashwini & Malshe, 2008; Cui, 2011). Chromium oxide, iron oxide and carbozel violet pigments are referred to as camouflage pigments due to their reflectance properties both in Vis and NIR (Muzaffer & Yavuz, 2010). A deep-color camouflaging formulation is implemented on aircraft when the CB is considered as dark sea. Colors are formulated by titanium dioxide, organic perylene black and red, blue and yellow oxides based on polyurethane (PU) resin (hexamethylene diisocyanate). Microfine silica is also used as gloss reducing agent. A grey color formulation is used for countershaded aircraft (Wake, 1993). IR pigments (chrome oxide green, carbon black) have great advantages for simultaneous camouflage in Vis–NIR. The pigmentation technique allows color matching with specific CB in Vis, and the reflection principle allows to blending of the target signature with CB color in the NIR range (Muzaffer & Yavuz, 2010). Synthetic coloration with low-reflection materials such as CBP declines the detectability in the Vis range, and there is scope for NIR range experimentation (Rudolf, 1978). CBP is a traditional colorant. It absorbs UV–Vis–NIR wavelengths of light. The particle size denotes the physical properties of the pigmentation, such as color strength, stability and light scattering ability. Even a small amount of IR-absorbing material in total weight can significantly reduce IR reflectivity. The reflection of objects can be tested using a UV–Vis–NIR spectrophotometer in the optical mechanism of ATR (Cui, 2011; Jose et al., 2019).

Optical engineering of synthetic pigmentation for simultaneous camouflage in Vis–NIR against woodland CB

A synthetic pigmented surface has the properties of NIR reflection. Pigments are synthesized by the mixtures of metal hydroxide, nitrates, acetates and oxides at very high temperature ranges over 1000°C. Metal and oxygen ions are oriented in a stable crystal structure; the process is called 'calcination'. IR reflective coating is highly used for building construction; it can also minimize the surface heating of textile substances. IR-reflective pigments are suitable for NIR camouflage textiles to reduce the heating effect on color change. The remaining high percentage of mobile electrons depicts high reflection on the surface. The functional properties of calcinated pigments have a dual action of absorption and reflection. The pigment absorbs light in the visible region and is appropriate for Vis camouflage. The pigmentation technology of dual camouflaging seems more accurate for the concealment of Vis–NIR camera surveillance. For example, the 'chlorophyll' of green plants reflects IR light. The green plant of woodland CB contains 'chlorophyll', and it has organic pigment for IR reflection. 'Chlorophyll' is also termed a natural IR reflective material, applicable for woodland camouflage textiles. Practically, a tree background is cooler than the surrounding background in a hot summer (Ashwini & Malshe, 2008; Cui, 2011).

Optical engineering of thermal insulation for camouflage formulation

Planck's law states that the IR range is mostly related to thermal radiation. Hence, IR camouflage textiles need a combination of thermal insulation materials. Silica aerogel has thermal insulation properties which can reduce the surface temperature of camouflage textiles. Phase change materials (PCMs) have found limited applications for camouflage textiles. For consideration of concealment, germanium is a high IR reflective material for target confusing versus camouflaging response. A thermal insulation-reflection combination of silica aerogel and germanium is proposed for NIR range camouflage textiles for aircraft and missile target protection. High-temperature aircraft nozzles and high-temperature naval ship funnels are also challenging for the design of sky camouflage and marine camouflage. The real protection of fighting aircraft and marine ships is still challenging (Huanzheng et al., 2020). A combination of thermal insulation and high reflective coating has been commented to be more effective for defence target concealment (Anthony, 2005). NIR anti-reflection coating is formulated by the

combination of silicon and germanium (Cox & Hass, 1958). The concept of technology in NIR range camouflage textiles has been still limited. There is a feasibility of NIR range camouflage incorporating a combination of PCMs such as $\text{Ge}_2\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_5$ (Qu et al., 2018) and VO_2 . The combination has the phenomenon of phase transition and reflection changing for NIR camouflaging (Sayan et al., 2018). Surface reflection of camouflage textiles depends on treatment with suitable materials. The mechanism defines the reflection and transmittance of OB as referred by the theory of 'Augustin-Jean Fresnel'. Low-reflection coatings and fabrication design are another way of camouflage principle (Raut et al., 2011). IR absorbing CBP can be applied for enhancement of IR absorption.

Stealth is the act or characteristics that confuse the detection by chromatic replacement and/or shape. The animal has the camouflaging techniques of stealth skin (Hossain, 2023bj, 2023bk; Shim et al., 2022). Low emissivity denotes the IR shielding property of stealth skin (Li et al., 2022). The simultaneous development of smart textiles and camouflaging property can be developed by microfabrication and stealth skin. Surface dyeing and pigmentation, embedded additives, chromic materials, low emissivity coatings and fibers, PCMs, and shape memory materials are the existing technologies in smart camouflage textiles (Degenstein et al., 2021). Metasurface is also an optical engineering that can create negative refraction (Klar et al., 2006). Metasurface can be used to reduce optical scattering for camouflage (Joy et al., 2021; Klar et al., 2006).

Optical engineering of camouflage coloration with nanomaterials

TiO_2 , ZnO and Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles were applied for IR protection. Camouflaging nanobeads can be used with textile dyes for deceiving formulations of camouflage coloration. There is advanced suitability of nanomaterials for camouflage clothing. Nanomaterials can enhance defence textile properties such as fabric softness, durability, breathability, water repellency, fire retardancy, antimicrobial, UV protection and shrink-proof (Sawhney et al., 2008). Nano titanium dioxide increases surface reflection (Reza et al., 2018). Cotton-nylon blended fabrics are printed using a mixture of pigments and carbon black nanoparticles for camouflage coloration. Shading of brown, olive green and khaki was employed in the desert uniform. The printing formulation remarked a significant decline in limited ranges of NIR reflectance (Mehrizi et al., 2012; Mehrizi et al., 2015). The structure of camouflage coloration is also formulated by the core (chromophore materials)

and sheath (polymer) processes (Sudhakar et al., 2008). A polyvinylidene fluoride resin can be used as a transparent binder (Wake & Brady, 1993).

Optical engineering of camouflage coloration with thermochromic dyes

The thermochromic colorant can be blended with pigment to match the CB environment. Thermoplastic PU and graphite are mixed and coated for thermochromic coloration. Thermochromism and camouflage coloration can be tested by CIE red, green, blue, L^* , a^* and b^* . These values and imaging properties can be recorded before and after heating for assessment of infrared (IR) camouflaging against selected CB (Karpagam et al., 2016; Samolov et al., 2021). Liquid crystal is also a unique material for temperature-responsive fabrication. Chiral nematic liquid crystal changes its color in the presence of thermal, electrical and optical stimuli. This phenomenon is responsible for changing the refractive index or pitch. Formulation of indolyfulgide chiral dopants shows color stability adjustment. The color stability of chiral nematic liquid crystal has been observed for smart applications of camouflage textiles (M. A. Hossain, 2021a; Timothy J et al., 2012). The thermochromic dye 'crystal violate lactone' was used as core material, and silica was used as shell material. The thermochromic effects and color reversibility were observed at wavelength 610 nm under consideration of shifting color strength and K/S value from 12 to 2 (Wan et al., 2017). Hence, thermochromic colorants may have a feasibility for camouflaging against selected CB.

Optical engineering of camouflage coloration with synthetic dyes

Cotton, polyester, nylon and cotton-polyester blends are general applications of camouflage textiles (Ministry of Defence). Nomex and Kevlar are suitable for high-performance applications of camouflage textiles. Spun-bonded nonwoven fabric is experimented with random orientation of metal fibril on the fabric surface to obtain the expected camouflage formulation. Filling hollow fibers with liquid dyes and solid pigment is a proposed technique for adaptive camouflage textiles (Adanur & Tewari, 1997). Common methods of fabricating camouflage textiles are dyeing, coating and printing (Uranus et al., 2014). Coating and printing are suitable techniques for man-made or natural fiber-based camouflage textiles (Burkinshaw et al., 1996; Rudolf, 1978). Printing is a method of camouflage patterning. Camouflage patterns on the fabric are produced using low-reflectance dyes having thiazine at a relatively long wavelengths greater than 900 nm (Dale R, 2015). The reflectance profile of woodland

camouflage textiles is experimented by different disperse dyes, such as CI disperse black, CI disperse yellow 23, CI disperse blue 14 and disperse blue 56. The reflectance of camouflage-treated objects and greenish leaves background was compared with CIE L^* , a^* , b^* , c^* and h for chromatic variation. The process interprets a minimum level of woodland camouflaging; it has demanded a further level of experimentation. CI disperse blue 56 shows the effect of green leaves camouflaging on polyester fabric (Hui & Jianchun, 2007). Vat blue 13 dye has also green camouflaging properties in Vis and limited NIR regions (Goudarzi et al., 2013; Vitalija et al., 2008; Zhang & Zhang, 2008). Vat dyes have low IR reflectance and good fastness properties, making them suitable for camouflage applications on cotton textiles. Tetraaryldiamine dyes absorb in IR (Ramsey et al., 2019).

Advancement phase 6, method design for CDRI measurement of target signature against CBs-DGTWSICB under UV-Vis-IR spectrums Spectrometry and colorimetry versus CDRI assessment

In general, wavelengths more than 700 nm are considered as IR range. The visible spectrum covers wavelengths from 400 to 700 nm. The wavelengths 200 to 400 nm are depicted as the UV spectrum. Both UV and IR rays are invisible to humans due to a lack of receptors. Ray directions are a matter of light reflection, such as specular reflection and diffuse reflection. Single outgoing reflection is termed specular reflection, and multiple-angle reflection is termed diffuse reflection. A color measurement spectrophotometer can be used to measure the reflectance, transmittance or absorbance of target OB at different wavelengths. A specular included method is used for total reflection, and a specular excluded method is used for diffuse reflectance of OB substances. The color variation of specular included and specular excluded is verified by ceramic tiles of 12 standard reference colors (white, pale grey, middle grey, deep grey, orange, deep pink, black, red, bright yellow, green, cyan and deep blue) for colorimetry and spectrometry. This method is used by the British ceramics research association (BCRA). Hence, the mechanism of visual assessment of camouflage is more critical than the pass/fail decision of solid colors. CIE color difference is an established method of color deviation between OB, where luminance, hue and chroma are the contrast features of chromatic adaptation for variations of target OB. The chromatic adaptation of desert sand, urban grey and foliage green is experimented by CIE color parameters; the method cannot cover multidimensional angles (Gang, 2012). CIE colorimetry is the mechanism of color

matching and predicting the color difference between two stimuli for the identification of physical color. The technique has limitations for actual color appearance between OB due to structural variation of the object (camouflage textiles) and CB. Chromatic properties of camouflage-formulated textiles, camouflage materials and DGTWSICB materials are mostly demonstrated by the CIE trichromatic hue of RGB and the CIE L*, a* and b* color coordinates. The UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer cannot measure color directly; it measures the physical attributes of materials concerning their ATR of light. A digital camera or hyperspectral camera can be used to measure the chromatic appearance of OB in a controlled optical environment of OB. A digital camera can be used for the color measurement of OB when highly textured and printed materials cannot be measured by color measurement spectrophotometer. The light reflected from OB is passed through the lens, and imaging is captured through two-dimensional sensors covered with RGB color filters (Kulapurath, 2018).

Hyperspectral versus CDRI assessment of target signature against CBs-DGTWSICB

Hyperspectral imaging is an improved and modified version of multispectral imaging used for target detection and defence surveillance in the UV-Vis-NIR ranges. Captured target signatures and CBs in a hyperspectral image are difficult to characterize in terms of identification and quantification of concealment. Generally, target object (camouflage textiles) analysis of hyperspectral concealment needs to generate a spectral database of multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. Interfering elements of CDRI are not the same for all CBs. These interferences need to be identified for all CBs for camouflage textiles. A standard

spectral database identifies the discrimination of OB by means of a spectrum probe. Spectral properties are controlled by scattering effects on OB. Treated camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-NIR are classified as supervised target detection of hyperspectral cameras due to having known and predicted properties on textile substances. The target signature can be analyzed in terms of known CB for the experimental process. Spectral angle, spectral distance and spectral information are the properties of spectral symmetry. To avoid interfering reflection of imaging, the specification of the target is very important for camouflage assessment of hyperspectral imaging. A simulation of spectral symmetry was conducted for typical signatures including CB materials such as black brush, creosote leaves, sagebrush, red soil and dry grass. The reflection of the interferer varies from CB to CB. The spectral properties of DGTWSICB materials are not the same. A real experimentation of hyperspectral camouflage textiles for spectral symmetry is required. Spectral symmetry and its analyses between target OB are existing techniques in prediction, simulation and planning stages only. Target signature versus CBs-DGTWSICB measurement of spectral similarity and dissimilarity of hyperspectral imaging is still challenging in optical engineering and the unknown journey of camouflage researchers (Chang, 2003; A. Hossain, 2021b; Kent Andersson, 2014).

Mechanism of CDRI measurement for target signature against CBs-DGTWSICB

Pixel is another approach of camouflage signature evaluation for image segmentation and comparison of hyperspectral imaging between OB. The task is very challenging due to the lack of standardization for the comparison of hyperspectral imaging (Chang, 2003).

Fig. 13 Flow chart for the principle of camouflage assessment

Spectral imaging is a practicable technology for CDRI of target signature against CB. The signal of spectral imaging can provide strong performance for analyses of the optical properties of the target object (camouflage textiles) and CB (X. Briottet et al., 2006). Spectral discrimination has been remarked as a potential issue for day or night surveillance of military targets. The performance of CDRI is achievable in terms of high band-to-band multispectral and hyperspectral sensors (Michael T et al.). Electromagnetic optics, radiometry, photometry and human psychometrics are the technical areas for the assessment of CDRI. It is necessary to develop an accurate process of concealment measurement for supporting camouflage assessment. As summarized in Fig. 13, camouflage measurement on CB has been concerned with presumption, simulation, analysis and laboratory trialing, field experimentation and structural judgment. Simulation and prediction represent the decision based on the predetermined processes. Analysis and laboratory experiments include quantitative and partial measurements for camouflage assessment. Field experimentation and structural judgment are the process of the real game of concealment in multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB (Farrar, 1878; Stephen, 2015).

Image processing techniques for CDRI measurement against CBs-DGTWSICB

Every field experimentation for camouflage assessment is an expensive process. Natural illumination, target object, target CB and location of target OB are the real facts for every combat trialing of camouflage achievement (Peak et al.). Photographs of formulated textiles against CBs can be captured by digital camera or hyperspectral camera at a specified angle and illumination for comparison between the object (textile substances) and its surrounding CB. Lens changing of digital camera is an option for capturing photographs in different spectrums of UV-Vis-IR. The post-image analyses are conducted by image processing software such as Adobe Photoshop, ImageJ and environment for visualizing images. Digital images can be modified into CIE-RGB color space to CIE L^* , a^* and b^* color space under a black-white grey scale of chromatic hue. CIE L^* , a^* and b^* color space is defined between -127 and $+127$ for each axis of three-dimensional color space. Eight bits are suitable to interpret the color space. Color threshold is a chromatic and achromatic identification process functioned in ImageJ. This software covers CIE red, green, blue, L^* , a^* and b^* color coordinates in a black-white grey scale. The chromatic variation is a process applied for the identification of camouflage textiles against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. For

example, fractal design (a typical percentage of CB is matched with textile objects rather than matching the whole object with the background) is a common practice of defence professionals for forest and desert camouflage in the single background only. Recent research on camouflage textiles is mostly limited to the Vis range and chromatic assessment covers mostly photographic systems rather than establishing quantitative systems. Hyperspectral camouflage textiles have a great limitation for the right materials on textile substances for hyperspectral concealment and their quantitative and photographic/partial assessment process for camouflage textile performance. Hyperspectral images in multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB needs to generate an accurate view in specific lighting, angle and resolution for the detection of camouflage properties on textile substances (Mehrizi et al., 2012; Ramli et al., 2012; Yang et al., 2021). Color and intensity features of an image can signify the camouflage assessment and camouflage detection. Texture analysis with image processing is a very effective way of camouflage assessment for classification, segmentation and CDRI. Less intensity of an image depicts the appearance of dark camouflage and brighter intensity of an image creates the appearance of light camouflage (A. Hossain, 2021a; Hossain, 2009; Sujit et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2021).

Advancement phase 7, significant advancement of camouflage textiles against modern defence surveillance in UV-Vis-NIR spectrums

Camouflage textiles do not mean camouflage clothing only. There are enormous concepts of applications of textile-based camouflage by means of spectrum probe in UV-Vis-NIR such as temporary combat residence, vehicle and location hiding, radar protection, missile protection, parachute protection, nuclear weapon and ballistic protection. Camouflage textiles for multidimensional single CB, simultaneous CB and adaptive CB need to be well established for defence protection. Recent research on camouflage textiles is only intended for 'CB color matching' in terms of chromatic and patterning, but 'color matching theory' is only applicable to the visible range while camouflage engineering is also required in UV-NIR ranges. The reflection angle of the target signature changes the color appearance of the human observer or digital camera or hyperspectral camera. Surrounding environment colors of CB are not limited to any single CB. CB colors change with location, season, foggy weather, sunny weather, rainy weather and bushfire of woodland. Currently developed camouflage requirement concentrates on limited ranges of spectrum probes and a minimum number of CB environments. Target objects are still detectable by

the reflection of CB materials. Military camouflage textiles are already developed in the Vis range, and there is a limitation of camouflage textiles in UV-NIR against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. Furthermore, research on UV-Vis-NIR range camouflage textiles and the suitability of the right camouflage materials for concealment are limited in published literature. High-performance camouflage textiles can be achieved by proper implementation of deceiving materials on textile substances. Conventional textile coloration processes (coating, dyeing or printing) can be applied for the treatment of textile substances with advanced formulation of camouflage textiles. Existing camouflage textiles are not suitable for simultaneous camouflaging in UV-Vis-NIR ranges. There is a need for common textiles for camouflage in UV-Vis-NIR ranges. Temperature changing versus chromatic replacement or thermal changing versus chromatic stabilization created a demanding source of research and development in camouflage textiles for the protection of defence professionals. The establishment of proposed technological advancement and the right formulation of deceiving materials may generate an output of high-performance camouflage textiles in versatile

single CB environments, adaptive camouflage for multi-dimensional CB environments, UV-Vis-IR camouflage, hyperspectral camera and radar protective camouflage for concealment of defence target signature.

Limitation of camouflage research, review and related findings

This review of camouflage textiles shows a limited number of research and publications in the specific area of high-performance camouflage textiles, but most research demonstrates prototype experimentation in a limited condition of individual research deficient with a deeper concept of advanced analysis in UV-Vis-IR illumination against multidimensional CB material-DGTWSICB, methodology and materials for camouflage formulation and right spectrometry for CDRI. Some patents have been published with lacking a concrete credential of material, methods and real testing processes of camouflage formulation. The research and innovation in military camouflage might be a hidden activity of military scientist groups for keeping self-implementation of newly generated technology for any specific group and/or any country.

Fig. 14 Optical principle of concealment and detection (C & D) between observer (a, b, c, d) and target signature (a1, b1, c1, d1)

Therefore, materials, methodologies and real testing methods of camouflage textiles are not being widely published. This review may opine a framework of right camouflage materials, methods and target illumination for designing advanced camouflage textiles in terms of digital and hyperspectral imaging under UV–Vis–IR surveillance.

Advancement phase 8, the principle of optical approach for camouflage textile coloration for concealment against digital camera imaging/hyperspectral imaging in UV–Vis–IR spectrums

Camouflage coloration denotes altering the reflection of the textile surface by using technical coloration such as coating, dyeing and printing. Deceiving materials on textile substances are mainly termed as pigments, nanoparticles, dyes, and eco-friendly sources of natural materials. Figure 14a, a1 shows the structural similarity of expected camouflage materials between OB when the target signature is depicted as zero reflection against CB, the human observer or digital camera or hyperspectral camera will not obtain a clear image of the real target for detection. Textile materials can be directly treated with CB source of natural materials such as NPND and NSSD for concealment against woodland, desertland, rockland, concreteland or urban and water or marine CBs (A. Hossain, 2020; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022c; Hossain, 2023ck; M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018). In Fig. 14b, b1; high-light absorbency materials have been classified as low-reflection materials. The reflection of the target object will not be perceived as a low reflection of the object material. Therefore, minimum reflection of object materials has the feasibility of camouflage coloration due to negligible response of photonic signal to remote sensing devices such as digital imaging or hyperspectral imaging. In Fig. 14c, c1; similarly, the exact reflection of the target signature will not be perceived by the human observer or digital camera or hyperspectral camera for high-reflection materials. The photonic signal will be scattered in the multidimensional direction without reaching the actual signal to the sensor of a surveillance camera. Textile materials can be treated based on the functional mechanism of high-reflection materials such as selected nanoparticles, germanium, aluminium, and titanium dioxide based on selected CB. In Figs. 14d, d1; the combination of reflection of changing materials has the capability of altering reflection to the imaging devices. In this optical principle, light will be reflected at different angles which can be twisted by the reflection mechanism and

misperception of the image will be detected to signify the target signature against CBs–DGTWSICB. Typical angles are defined and remarked by showing arrow marks. For every UV–Vis–NIR surveillance, camera sensors of digital camera or hyperspectral camera generate imaging from photon signal of target signature and CB materials. Reflection and spectral signals of the target signature (camouflage textiles) may alter photon signals for deceiving the target signature against CB. In the thermochromic principle, the chromatic replacement will occur in a specific temperature range; the same camouflage textile is possible to implement in different CB environments in terms of chromatic matching in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. Thermal insulation is the opposite principle of the chromatic phenomenon. Color will not change in a specific temperature range; the same camouflage textile has the technical feasibility to use battlefield operations in different temperatures in terms of chromatic matching and UV–Vis–IR camouflaging (M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a).

Advancement phase 9, a hierarchical model for camouflage textile formulation and optical assessment for CDRI-target signature–DGTWSICB–UV–Vis–IR

Figure 15 shows the standardized process of UV–Vis–IR camouflage textile formulation and performance measurement steps, which are segmented into nine categories for CDRI assessment of target signature against CBs–DGTWSICB and its surrounding environment.

Segment 1: Target CB selection is a primary attempt for camouflage coloration. Single CB or simultaneous CB or adaptive CB can be selected for the target signature. DGTWSICBs are the common CB area for the technical formulation of camouflage textiles as per geographical combat—the province of the different countries (Kang et al., 2016).

Segment 2: The deceiving materials need to be selected for the concealment of specific CB environments. Reflection-changing materials, reflection-matching materials, thermochromic dyes, liquid crystal, crystal violet lactone, thermal insulation materials and CB source-based NPND–NSSD materials are selected as the main deceiving materials for UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles in multidimensional CB environment–DGTWSICB. Deceiving materials can be encapsulated by a transparent polymeric binder. Thermochromic and thermal insulation effects on chromatic stability and its camouflaging performance can be tested under different temperature ranges (M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a; Tözüm et al., 2018).

Fig. 15 Flow chart of technical formulation for design of camouflage textiles against DGTWSICB and optical assessment for CDRI in UV-Vis-IR imaging

Segment 3: The suitability of deceiving materials treatment for camouflage textiles can be experimented by coating, dyeing and printing processes of textile coloration. These techniques can be modified by the combination of coloration processes to achieve camouflage in different CB environment-DGTWSICBs.

Segment 4: The concealment properties of camouflage-treated textiles against the selected materials of DGTWSICB can be identified in Vis and limited NIR ranges by color measurement spectrophotometer. Both the specular included and excluded methods can be used for the chromatic analysis of formulated textiles and combat materials. For illumination measurement of glossy materials, the specular included option is the most suitable for capturing the highest reflection in diffuse illumination. Furthermore, the structural properties of camouflage, chromatic compound identification and related chemometric analysis can be executed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier transform infrared

spectroscopy (FTIR) and UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer for laboratory stage trialing (Aleksandra et al., 2019).

Segment 5: The evidence of target signature in UV-Vis-IR range surveillance can be implemented by a digital camera. The digital camera can reveal the target signature against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB (Garcia et al., 2013).

Segment 6: The captured photographs of the digital camera can be analyzed by image processing software (ImageJ) for confirmation of CDRI under CIE red, green, blue, L*, a* and b* chromatic hue of black-white grey scale. The OB image can be segmented by the color threshold method (A. Hossain, 2021a; Yang et al., 2021).

Segment 7: Quantitative color differences of OB can be judged by CIE L*, a*, b*, c* and h values. Achromatic features of target signature and CBs and their effects can also be identified for CDRI assessment. Hence, the chromatic and achromatic assessments of target signature versus DGTWSICB can be

experimented by photographic illumination in UV–Vis–IR (Garcia et al., 2013; A. Hossain, 2021a; M. A. Hossain, 2021c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Liu et al., 2008; Samolov et al., 2021).

Segment 8: Hyperspectral camera can be used for high-performance applications of camouflage assessment in UV–Vis–NIR ranges from 200 to 2500 nm (Lu et al., 2022; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2020; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2022).

Segment 9: Optical accuracy of spectral design for spectral symmetry, chromatic appearance and illumination properties can signify the CDRI of target signature against selected CB. The ATR properties of camouflage-treated textiles and CB materials can be experimented in UV–Vis–NIR ranges from 200 to 2500 nm (Ko et al., 2007; Lu et al., 2022; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2022). Target signature against DGTWSICB captured by hyperspectral camera can also be assessed by image processing software. Therefore, the chromatic aberration of multidimensional color and texture of the target signature and CBs can be assessed for CDRI.

Concluding remarks

ATR properties of the formulated textile surface, ATR properties of selected CB materials, chromatic appearance of digital or hyperspectral imaging, CIE trichromatic hue, structural features, sun radiation related to weather conditions and humidity, illumination angle, imaging sensors of digital camera, or hyperspectral camera and electromagnetic spectrums in UV–Vis–IR are the key principle for every CDRI evaluation of target signature against dry leaves, green leaves and tree bark-woodland combat background; water-marine combat background; sand-desertland combat background; stone-stoneland combat background; snow-snowland combat background; sky combat background; ice-iceland combat background; and concrete-concreteland combat background (DGTWSICB) and its surrounding combat environments. Imaging signals of CDRI mostly depend on electron energy and photonic signal of target signature in UV–Vis–IR illumination. Camouflage textiles can be detected by human eyes (Vis) or instrumental investigations such as spectroscopy, microscopy, digital cameras and hyperspectral cameras. The reflectance profile of a target signature (camouflage textiles) can be matched with the reflectance profile of CB in the vein of chromatic, achromatic and spectral illumination. For chromatic matching between target objects and CBs, the selection of correct deceiving materials is the first task for camouflage textile formulation. Hence, appropriate treatment of camouflage materials on textile substances may signify the concealment of the target signature in multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB under

UV–Vis–IR illumination. Camouflage materials can be treated on textile substances by the conventional technology of dyeing-coating-printing-padding. The chromatic standardization of CB materials in the laboratory stage has been opined for chromatic assessment of CB versus camouflage-treated textiles. The core materials of CB and camouflage-formulated textiles can be considered for CDRI assessment in the laboratory stage as real CB materials have variations due to known and unknown interference in CB environments. These unknown parameters of CBs can be controlled sequentially if textile-treated materials can be concealed or matched against CB materials under selected illumination in UV–Vis–IR spectrums, and it may have the core achievement for the design of camouflage textiles. Therefore, the target signature can be concealed under the interference of the CB environment and natural illumination in field trialing. Reflecting the color of the target signature and CB creates the imaging signal rather than the absorbed color. White CB of the natural environment reflects the entire wavelength of visible light. Other CB absorbs light at specific wavelengths. Such as the green leaves background of woodland CB reflects green color and absorbs another color; the snow background of snowland CB reflects in full spectrum of visible wavelength. Electron energy of camouflage materials of target signature can replace the wavelength and imaging signal in digital and hyperspectral imaging. Textile substances can be treated with zero reflection materials, natural materials, CB source-based natural materials such as NPND and NSSD, minimum or maximum reflection materials, multi-reflection materials for replacement or matching of electron energy against CBs and/or confusing the target signature. The electron energy of target signature generates the energy of the photon signal to be detected by imaging sensors and surveillance cameras. Therefore, the spectral signal of zero-reflection or high-reflection materials may create simultaneous camouflaging in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. A hyperspectral camera can be used for chromatic and spectral observation of CDRI using a wide proportion of electromagnetic spectrums in UV–Vis–NIR ranges. The concealment of the latest surveillance in UV–Vis–NIR illumination can be premeditated by altering or symmetrization of surface reflection of the target object with CB. The distance between the camera and the target signature creates a variation of the photon signal. The position of the target object vibrates the velocity of electron energy and photonic signal to the imaging sensor. Reflection of the target object, conditions of the CB environment, single CB or simultaneous CBs, and the right selection of deceiving materials

Table 2 Camouflage materials design, method design and testing formulations against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB

Expected outcome-01: Design of woodland camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
Total Trials (Ts)	Formulations	Materials	Methods	Lab/Field Testing
T-01	Formulation-01	Chromium oxide	Deceiving beads formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-02	Formulation-02	Aluminium nanoparticle		
T-03	Formulation-03	Chromium oxide + Aluminium nanoparticle		
T-04	Formulation-04	Natural materials of woodland, NPND		
T-05	Formulation-05	Chromium oxide + CBP		
T-06	Formulation-06	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
Expected outcome-02: Design of desert camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-07	Formulation-01	Mica powder	Camouflage bead formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-08	Formulation-02	Titanium dioxide + Aluminium nanoparticle		
T-09	Formulation-03	Mica powder + Aluminium nanoparticle		
T-10	Formulation-04	Natural materials of desertland, NSSD		
T-11	Formulation-05	Selected acid Dyes		
T-12	Formulation-06	Mica powder + CBP		
Expected outcome-03: Design of water/marine camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-13	Formulation-01	Titanium dioxide	Deceiving bead formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-14	Formulation-02	Germanium nanoparticle		
T-15	Formulation-03	Titanium dioxide + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-16	Formulation-04	Titanium dioxide + CBP		
T-17	Formulation-05	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
T-18	Formulation-06	CBP + Germanium nano particle		
Expected outcome-04: Design of snowland/sky camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-19	Formulation-01	Lead oxide	Deceiving beads formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-20	Formulation-02	Titanium dioxide		
T-21	Formulation-03	Germanium nanoparticle		
T-22	Formulation-04	Lead oxide + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-23	Formulation-05	Titanium dioxide + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-24	Formulation-06	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
T-25	Formulation-07	Titanium dioxide + CBP		

Table 2 (continued)

Expected outcome-05: Design of iceland camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-26	Formulation-01	Zinc oxide	Deceiving beads formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-27	Formulation-02	Titanium dioxide		
T-28	Formulation-03	Germanium nanoparticle		
T-29	Formulation-04	Zinc oxide + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-30	Formulation-05	Titanium dioxide + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-31	Formulation-06	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
T-32	Formulation-07	Titanium dioxide + CBP		
Expected outcome-06: Design of stoneland/concreteland/urban camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-33	Formulation-01	Natural materials of stoneland	Deceiving beads formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-34	Formulation-02	Germanium nanoparticle		
T-35	Formulation-03	Pumic powder + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-36	Formulation-04	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
T-37	Formulation-05	Pumic powder + CBP		
Expected Outcome-07: Design of temperature adaptive camouflage textiles for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-38	Formulation-01	Thermochromic leuco dyes + liquid crystal	Deceiving beads formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer SEM, FTIRs Digital camera Hyperspectral camera Image processing software
T-39	Formulation-02	Thermochromic leuco dyes + PCM		
T-40	Formulation-03	Thermochromic leuco dyes + PCM + Liquid crystal		
T-41	Formulation-04	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
T-42	Formulation-05	Thermochromic leuco dyes + PCM + Liquid crystal + Germanium		

are the matter of altering the electron state or photon signal for the accuracy of concealment under UV-Vis-IR spectrums. Hence, the advancement of camouflage textile technology can be implemented for concealment of modern defence surveillance in UV-Vis-IR spectrums against multidimensional CBs-DGTWS-ICB. Furthermore, the principle of material design versus optical engineering has outermost applications of camouflage weapon design against hyperspectral or digital camera surveillance in UV-Vis-NIR spectrums. Camouflage product developers need to consider

spectral signals for every high-performance concealment as upcoming surveillance is gradually vibrating from more sophisticated to sophisticated. Table 2, in terms of a review of the optical hypothesis, the author coalesced '42 possible formulations' for advanced design of camouflage textiles/CDRI trialing against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB in UV-Vis-IR illumination and expected outcomes (1-7) have been tabulated. In general, camouflage bead formation is proposed by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on polyamide 6,6 (PA

Table 3 A summary of research output and analysis of the sole author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University for camouflage materials design, optical design, method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering and camouflage textiles against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB since 2019-2020

Name of Titles	Invention in camouflage analysis
<p>➤ Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination. <i>International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations</i>, 10(117), 1–11, Article 1,011,721–01. http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf; https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242827; https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487</p>	<p>➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, and camouflage assessment in general ➤ Color analysis for camouflage engineering, color engineering, and camouflage assessment in general ➤ Environmental facts and weather for CDRI, camouflage engineering, color engineering, and camouflage assessment in general</p>
<p>➤ Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV–Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background. <i>The Journal of the Textile Institute</i>, 1–12. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074</p>	<p>➤ Optical design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage textiles, and camouflage assessment ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage textiles, and camouflage assessment</p>
<p>➤ Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection. <i>American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology</i>, 9(1), 31–47. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.12691/materials-9-1-3</p>	<p>➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage textiles, and camouflage assessment ➤ Thermochromic material design for CDRI camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage textiles, and camouflage assessment ➤ A concept of adaptive camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications. In A. K. Samanta (Ed.), <i>Colorimetry</i> (pp. 1–22). IntechOpen. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.95699</p>	<p>➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Carbon black coated camouflage textiles in terms of low reflection textiles</p>
<p>➤ Camouflage Assessment of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV–Vis-IR Background Illumination. <i>Defence Science Journal</i>, 72(3), 359–370. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.14429/dsj.72.17731</p>	<p>➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Aluminium coated desertland camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. <i>Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square</i> https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1</p>	<p>➤ Natural material and method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Silicon Dioxide coated desertland camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background. <i>Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology</i>, 1–16. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759</p>	<p>➤ Key optical parameters for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), <i>Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments</i> (pp. 151–170). IntechOpen. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.92360</p>	<p>➤ Natural material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. <i>Scientific Reports</i>. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2</p>	<p>➤ Optical design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ A concept of natural plant based natural dyes (NPND) coated woodland camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. <i>MRS Communications</i> https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3</p>	<p>➤ Optical design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV–Visible–IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging. <i>Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square</i> 1–18. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1</p>	<p>➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. <i>Advance Research in Textile Engineering, Austin Publishing Group</i>. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36504.98560; https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297554</p>	<p>➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles in terms of low reflection textiles</p>

Table 3 (continued)

Name of Titles	Invention in camouflage analysis
➤ Advancement in UV–Vis–IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. <i>Preprint (Version 2) available at Preprint.Org; Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square.</i> https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2549022/v1 ; https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648 ; https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117436	➤ Optical theory for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles
➤ Advancement in UV–Visible–IR Camouflage Textiles and Camouflage Physics. In <i>Scholarly Community Encyclopedia.</i> https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/history/show/112736	➤ Optical theory for camouflage engineering

6,6) and/or other selected fabric required by defence professionals for combat action of camouflaging.

The exact brightness or dullness of materials depends on atomic number in general. The atomic number relates to the optical engineering of electrons (Eby et al., 2010). The responses of electron energy relate to the responses of photons. The photonic response generates UV–Vis–IR imaging of the surveillance mechanism in the defence platform. The responses of photons cause the deviation between target objects and combat backgrounds. The responses of photons relate to camouflage engineering in general. The camouflage engineering signifies the CDRI of objects against multidimensional combat backgrounds, DGTWSICBs.

Tables 2 and 3 are cited to support this review. The approach of research has also contents of experiment-based suggestions and self-cited literature of the author for the next stage practice of research and development in color engineering and camouflage engineering. The author has some self-cited-self-experimented reviews for the support of this review work mentioned in Tables 2 and 3. The author briefly reviewed in 2020, gradually self-verified and self-experimented for the support of this review article (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anwar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023c, 2023g, 2023h, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023aq, 2023au, 2023az, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bn, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023cj, 2023 cl) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anwar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023g, 2023h, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023au, 2023az, 2023bd, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bn, 2023bu, 2023cj, 2023cl; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024k, 2024l).

Abbreviations

UV-Vis-IR	Ultraviolet-visible-infrared
DGTWSICB	Dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark-woodland combat background; water-marine combat background; sand-desertland

CBs	combat background; stone-stoneland combat background; snow-snowland combat background; sky combat background; ice-iceland combat background and concrete-concreteland combat background
CDRI	Combat backgrounds Concealment, detection, recognition and identification
NIR	Near infrared
Target signature	Camouflage textiles for concealment and detection
Woodland combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in woodland background such as dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark, etc.
Water/marine combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in water/marine background
Desertland combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in desertland background
Stoneland combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in stoneland background
Snowland combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in snowland background
Sky combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in sky background
Iceland combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in iceland background
Concreteland/urban combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in concreteland background
Single background camouflage	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in specific background environment-DGTWSICB
Simultaneous background camouflage	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in few background environments-DGTWSICB
Adaptive camouflage	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in few background environments-DGTWSICB in terms of chromatic replacement against combat background
Temperature adaptive camouflage	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in temperature changing environments against few background-DGTWSICB
NPND	Natural plant-based natural dyes
NSSD	Natural sand-based silicon dioxide
PCMs	Phase change materials
CBP	Carbon black pigment
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
FTIRs	Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
PU	Polyurethane
PA 6,6	Polyamide 6,6
CIE	International commission on illumination
RGB	Red, green, blue
OB	Object-background
PhD	Doctor of philosophy

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8>.

Additional file 1: Table S1. Summarized spectral coefficients of sun radiation, CB materials and camouflage materials for design of camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-IR illumination.

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Peer Review Process of Institutional Review Board, RMIT University, Australia

This manuscript was reviewed and passed by the two individual Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) committees of the School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University by the two individual conferences of the School of Fashion and Textiles,

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Authors' contributions

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Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection

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Abstract Adaptive camouflage textiles with color changing and blending into the combat background (CB) and surrounding environments have been a great challenge for the color scientist. Defense professional urgently needs adaptive camouflage textiles for personal protection in extreme weather conditions and multidimensional CB environments. A technical approach of adaptive camouflage textiles can be formulated by using a novel combination of thermochromic colorant and liquid crystal. Absorption of heat can rapidly accelerate the thermal response of thermochromic liquid crystal (TLC) by changing molecular structure with thermo-color-light (TCL) mechanism of absorption and reflection of light at different wavelength. TLC shows chameleon performance of color tone which changes the light reflection of surface color; thus, target objects can be artificially confused by the replacement of chromatic appearance in multidimensional CB environments. TLC can be applied as deceiving mechanism and surface modification of textile substances with combination of dyes/pigment. TLC modified camouflage textiles have possibility of diverse applications in different weather of combat zone for defense actions and different CB environments. A single formulated camouflage textiles may be suited with different CB environments under TLC mechanism. Chameleon type of color tone in cooling and heating conditions of thermochromic changes automatically in both reversible and irreversible way. Therefore, the technical colorant combination has been preached for suitability of adaptation with surrounding CB. TLC treated textiles can be experimented with spectroscopic, microscopic, and photographic illumination. The applications of adaptive camouflage textiles are not only limited to military textiles, but also the principle of technologies have versatile applications for clothing of personal protection including fashionable garments production.

Keywords: *adaptive camouflage textiles, thermochromic liquid crystal (TLC), thermochromic dyes, pitch length, combat background, defence protection*

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1. Introduction

Research and innovation on surveillance technology is being augmented hurriedly under the genuine growth of imaging technology in terms of hyperspectral and digital imaging. Advancement of surveillance technology is being used for both pessimistic and optimistic implementation as per needs of individual groups mainly implemented by special workers in defence. Oppositely researchers and scientists are also demanding to innovate anti-surveillance technology in different fields of engineering and developing chameleon camouflage textiles is one of them. Research and development have

been found in literature review in anti-surveillance technology in terms of camouflage textiles but research in liquid crystal-based chameleon type camouflage textiles is still at the early stage. Chameleon camouflage textiles can change the color for adapting with surrounding environment in different temperature for pessimistic and optimistic implementation as per needs of human being. For example: snow/ice combat background (CB) needs low temperature adaptive camouflage and desert CB demands high temperature background camouflage. Toet [1] reported that army professional needs multi-environment camouflage textiles for single mission of different CB. Neider et al. [2] reported that spectral radiance depends strongly on the illumination incident of the target signature and the atmospheric conditions of CB environment.

2. Background of Technical Approach for Adaptive Coloration Technology

2.1. Natural Existence of Adaptive Camouflage and Theories

Adaptive camouflage has the numerous ways of concealment and disguise in the animal for natural adaptation against surrounding background [152]. In nature, animal has adaptive capability by changing color in different environment. Cuttlefish, octopus, squid, and other cephalopods are the natural examples of adaptive camouflage for the protection of predators [3,4,48,100]. Hanlon et al. highlighted that [153] young cuttlefish use patterning primarily for concealment, such as general colour resemblance, disruptive coloration, obliterative shading, shadow elimination, disguise, and adaptive behaviours. Older cuttlefish also conceal themselves but increasingly use patterns for signalling, both interspecifically (warning or 'deimatic' displays) and intraspecifically (sexual signalling). Nokelainen et al. [111], Thayer et al. [149], Stevens et al. [151] established the concepts of animal concealment from predators. Josef et al. [176] remarked that octopuses have the ability of camouflage creation with surrounding. Stevens et al. [178] investigated that ghost crab (*Ocypodecer atophthalmus*), Singapore can change the color for adaptation with environment. Stuart-Fox et al. [150] remarked the animal color changing pattern and adaptive camouflage in terms of thermoregulation. Rafael C. Duarte [108] studied that some species, rhythms may facilitate thermoregulation and concealment. Merilaita, Lind, investigated that background is an important aspect for concealment and probability of detection by the predator [175]. Rosenholtz [159] commented that shape and orientation of a surface impacts the object recognition, scene perception, and many visual-cognitive tasks. Cuthill et al. [174] studied the bird disruptive and background matching coloration. Silbiger and Munguia [176] experimented that color versus temperature changes of uca pugilator. Therefore, natural existence of adaptive camouflage may motivate the actual development of adaptive camouflage textiles, but the reality of such camouflage textiles still in earlier stage of research and development.

2.2. Basic Phenomenon of Adaptive Camouflage Textiles

Thermochromic colorant may meet the performance requirements of chromatic materials and thermochromic liquid crystal (TLC) acts as deceiving mechanism of adaptive camouflaging under temperature changing against CB [49]. Chromatic materials change the color by the external stimuli like photochromic (light), thermochromic (heat), electrochromic (electricity), solvatochromic (liquid), carsochromic (electron beam). Normally the molecular structure of thermochromic colorant is altered and color changes above room temperature but liquid crystal temperature changes (5-15)^oC and cholesteric type liquid crystal is more suitable for thermochromism, and the pitch of the helical arrangement is responsible for temperature

and reflection in wavelength [85]. Sudhakar and Gobi N [130] proposed chameleon textiles in terms of pH changes, electric or magnetic field effects, mechanochromism, bond breaking/making, oxidation state changes. Polymer binder/resin and pigment for control of gloss, heavy metal pigment, lead, chromium, iron oxide, silica, polyurethane are the materials for camouflage textiles development [88]. Still now, thermochromic materials have limited application in camouflage textiles. Most thermochromic materials are organic having short lifetime and limited range of temperature in combination with liquid crystal. There is need of research for developing wide range of temperature and lifetime properties of thermochromic materials [87,91]. Sudhakar and N. Gobi [88] supported the opinion of Alvenmaa [87] that chromophore with polymeric materials may enhance the stable field of color change process. Adaptive camouflage [43] was proposed by color changing leuco dyes and advised for coupling color changing ability with high stimuli responsive study. Scott [5] claimed that CB environments (temperature, weather, etc.) are the prime question for augmentation of camouflage textiles in terms of adaptation. Joshi [6] also supported for making the chameleon type camouflage fabric by the implementation of light reflection engineering [7]. Heating mechanism influences the thermochromic system for temperature responsive camouflaging [7,8,9,20]. Conner [32] patented a camouflage textile with a material capable of different chromic states at different ambient light levels. The patent also observed the color changes of heat sensitive dyes in terms of both controllable (heat) and uncontrollable temperature (sunlight). Karpagam [62] experimented chemelyon type printing on cotton fabric with thermochromic colorant. CIE L*, a*, b* were measured before and after heating with spectrophotometer. Out of textile engineering, researchers [50] in mechanical system developed adaptive camouflage devices capable of producing black and white patterns for matching with its surrounding. Tianzhi et al. [134] investigated electrical field-based color changing mechanism with invisible sensors. Ying Liet al. [135] developed device for adaptive camouflage with background temperature. US army institute of environmental medicine (USAIEM) experimented the effect of temperature and wind chill on human body such as hot (32^oC), pleasant (28^oC), cool (22^oC), very cool (16^oC), cold (10^oC), very cold (5^oC), bitterly cold (0^oC), fresh freezes (-5^oC), exposed area of fresh freezes within one min (-24^oC) [81]. Temperature mechanism can be used for adaptive camouflage garments in desert (high temperature) camouflage, snow/iceland (low temperature) camouflage, common camouflage textiles in different season, and additionally for fashion textiles. This technology of adaptive camouflage textiles is not limited for garments implementation only, it has versatile applications in defense.

2.3. Selection of Textile Materials versus Thermal Conductivity for Adaptive Camouflage Formulation

Ajeeb [44] suggested higher heat transfer of wool and polyester than cotton. Hearle [80] noted the thermal conductivity of different textile fibre when packing density 0.5m/cc. Cotton (71), wool (54), silk (50), PVC

(160), cellulose acetate (230), nylon (250), polyester (140), polyethylene (340), polypropylene (120). Jassim and et al. [113] mentioned that thermal conductivity in (k)W/(m. K) of materials like acetone (0.16), acrylic (0.2) air, atmosphere (gas) (0.024), alcohol (0.17), carbon (1.7), cellulose, cotton, wood pulp and regenerated (0.23), cellulose acetate, molded, sheet (0.17-0.33), cellulose nitrate, celluloid (0.12-0.21), cotton (0.04), polyester (0.05), polypropylene (0.1- 0.22). Thermal conductivity of textile materials should be selected accurately for temperature responsive coloration of protection textiles.

2.4. Applications of Thermochromic Colorants for Principle of Thermochromism

Diverse applications [11-21,38] of thermochromic colorant has been investigated and successfully applied for commercialization like kitchen aprone and hand gloves, laboratory aprone, safety shoes, medical textiles, flexible display for clothing, transportation of sensitive goods, garments to detect disease and physiological conditions of the wearers, firefighting garments for the protection of extreme temperature, sports wears and building paints.

2.5. Applications of Liquid Crystal for Principle of Thermochromism

Liquid crystal and thermochromic colorants have versatile applications for the principle of thermochromism.

Hallcrest mentioned a brief applications of liquid crystal: a) general temperature indication/digital thermometers: room/household, refrigerator/freezer, infant bath/bottle, aquarium, hot/cold warning indicators b) battery testers and other voltage measuring devices c) temperature indicators for medical applications: forehead thermometers/fever

indicators, hypothermia warning indicators, drug testing; temperature indicating labels for urine specimen authentication d) medical thermography: sub-cutaneous cancer detection, diagnosis of vascular diseases, placenta location, pharmacological tests, skin grafting and vein location, veterinary applications, chiropractic applications e) radiation detection: infrared, microwave, ultraviolet, ultrasonic, electromagnetic f) aesthetic: advertising and promotions, decoration, jewelry, badges, fabrics, clothing and other novelties g) ingredients in cosmetic formulations h) non-destructive testing/thermal mapping: surface and sub-surface flaw detection in metals, welded metals, bonded and other composite structures, fault/short location in electric components and electronic circuits i) aerospace and engineering research: heat transfer studies, flow visualization in fluids and on solid surfaces in airflows j) gas/liquid level indicators k) miscellaneous: chemical and gas detectors, pressure sensors, information displays. Novel applications for liquid crystal are continually under advancement [94]. Application of thermochromism of liquid crystal is not a new approach of thermal engineering. The application of liquid crystal for camouflaging on textiles substances is an innovative approach.

2.6. Principle of Thermochromic Colorant for Color Changing

Thermochromism opined by Andy Town [49], Aitken and et al. reported [155], Eds H.R Mattila [86], J.E Gilligan [28] mentioned and summarized the thermochromic principle in Figure 1. A (green), B (red), C (yellow) are three schematic phases of colorant in three possible temperature ranges. Phase transition occurs under multi-phase heating mechanism in terms of geometrical and molecular structures.

Figure 1. Typical mechanism of thermochromism of thermochromic materials

Thermochromic materials [86,118-121,123,124,127,128] and color changing principle [129] have been used thermal technology but limited for adaptive camouflaging on textile substances [86,118-121,123,124,127,128]. Organic compound shows the variation in crystal structure,

stereoisomer, and molecular rearrangements. Liquid crystal shows different color at different temperature due to variation of reflection in wavelength from low temperature crystalline phase to high temperature isotropic liquid phase. Molecular rearrangement can create new

chromophore for changing color like acid base, keto-enol. Inorganic thermochromism has found drawback in textile application that color often changes at high temperature [86]. Fujita et al. [156] claimed that thermochromic microencapsulated pigment shows a color change temperature regulator. In the same way, Aitken et al. reported [155] that phase transition, geometry and molecular structures influence the thermochromic system. Henry [164] Conner patented coating materials to produce color changes in the camouflaging pattern include light and/or heat sensitive dyes and/or inks. Ramlow et al. [45] recommended that there is still too much to be explored and discovered in the field of chromic textiles [46]. Cheng et al. [53] supported that thermochromic materials are memory functions to the temperature. Thermochromic materials can be used for anti-counterfeiting technology. Geng et al. [54] microencapsulated crystal violet lactone as thermochromic colorant and observed reversible thermochromic properties, improved thermochromism was also investigated when silver nano particle added for modification. In this investigation, microencapsulation was studied by microscopic analysis. Shibahashiet and et. al. [157] opined and patented that the electron donating organic compound for microencapsulated thermochromism. Wilusz [85] reported that Nanta from Toray Industries reported temperature sensitive fabric in 1988 with trade name SWAY by microencapsulation and resin coating. The microcapsule was made of glass and dye chromophore agent was electron acceptor and color neutralizer were alcohol showed color and decolor in terms of environment temperature. Phillips developed fabric changing color from white to blue with ultraviolet (UV) irradiation at 350-400 nm. Ladendal [22] investigated thermochromism of thermochromic leuco dyes and proposed an outcome of color changing with uncontrollable parameter (sun) in print design process. Bourque [23] also studied temperature dependent color changes and experimented the tendency of thermochromism when color density increases with the increasing temperature. Llyod [31] and Rao [24] are also supported thermochromism who developed TLC [25] coated fabric for biomedical application by using leuco dyes for extended temperature range. Vikovaet al. [27] suggested the research scope of light fastness for color changeable thermochromic ink and thermochromic pigment [29]. Borque and researcher team [193] experimented that alkyl chain lengths were poorly matched, the dye-developer interaction dominated in the solid state, and melt-lightened thermochromism was observed. Jin and other researchers [60] experimented a heat stimulated luminous fibre at 30°C-20°C temperature by using heat sensitive pigment TF-G through wet spinning method. Heat stimulation was verified in naked eye by the researchers. Jinet al. [61] investigated a thermosensitive luminous fibre by thermochromic pigment. Researchers observed a rose red at room temperature and fibre sample showed colorless with blue light emission. In this study researchers claimed that phosphorescence of color is responsible for thermochromism. Potucket al. [64] experimented physiological changes of skin temperature range between 33°C and 38°C with artificial microencapsulated leuco dyes named as thermochromic pigment and applied on nylon & spandex blended fabric. Thermochromism

behaviours also studied by Martins [63] at 10°C-60°C. Jassim et al. [113] found that thermochromism showed different colors like orange 30°C, light orange 32°C, light pink 36°C, colorless 41°C. Kulčar and his researchers group [112] proved that the stability of decolorized state was examined at cooling for 10 hours. Ramigand et al. tested [65] thermochromism by reflectance spectra and calorimetry data. Thus, smaller particle tends to create bluer shade and larger particle tends to create redder shade. Z. Ahmed et al. [52] reported that printed thermochromic ink on polyester and cotton blended fabric changes color from black to green in 10.8 s using 1.46 W DC power at 30°C temperature. Researchers recommended that the technology can be extended by choosing right formulation for specific purpose of thermochromism. Dean et al. [154] discovered that FriXion erasable pens contain thermochromic inks that have colored low temperature forms and colorless high-temperature forms. Thermochromic coloration [40,41,42,78] is not a new concept but thermal responsive and adaptive camouflage is a new approach. Kulcuret al. [95] confirmed the reversibility of color change for leucodye-based TC ink. In 2019, thermochromic microcapsule by cationic dye was studied by Ma [68]. Ahmed and his team at IIT, Delhi, India [2,26] experimented the thermochromic colorant on cotton fabric [10] and fabric shade was changed in term of heat. Bristetet al. [70] patented that thermochromic materials produces a visual change of the visible (Vis) surface when an activation temperature of thermochromic materials is reached. Wan Zhang [71] examined the thermochromism performance on polyester fabric at 20°C, 45°C, 80°C with thermochromic leuco dye loaded silica nano capsule. The color reversely changed from dark blue (K/S =12) to light blue (K/S = 2) at 610 nm for more than 50 times. Zhang et al. [72] experimented temperature responsive thermochromic textiles between 5°C and 35°C. Jakovljevic and researcher team [74] studied thermochromism based on leuco dyes and liquid crystal. Choudhury et al. [75] remarked that ultraviolet temperature, p^H is the responsible for color changing of thermochromic colorant. Basnec and his researcher team [101] opined that temperature-dependent colour of thermochromic (TC) materials originates in phase transitions and changes in the geometry of the material when thermochromic composites were prepared using crystal violet lactone (CVL) dye, benzyl 4-hydroxybenzoate (B₄HB) developer and 1-dodecanol (DD) solvent and strongly suggested future study. Thermochromism exhibits with temperature versus color change [103]. Mary et al. [102] stated that temperature decreasing and wavelength increasing like 400 nm, 500 nm, 600 nm, 700 nm, and color change accordingly. Mary et al. [102] focused that neither thermochromic liquid crystals nor thermochromic organic dye mixtures can be applied directly for use in coloration: both require microencapsulation. Schubert et al. [114] focused and supported antireflection coating of four-layer (TiO₂/SiO₂)/nanoporous SiO₂ for the broadband and directional reflection. HULSEY and his team [117] designed temperature versus color change with leuco dye and the product was sold by color change corporation streamwood. Panak et al. [108] experimented CIE lab [126] thermochromism with crystal violet lactone as a colour former, bisphenol A as a developer and tetradecanol as a

co-solvent and researchers suggested thermochromic system based on color change. Bašneć et al. [109] also used lucodye-based composite for thermochromism. Vikova [116] proceeded kinetic model verification on color changeable textile sensor by the process of dyeing and printing. Serenet et al. [73] analyzed thermochromism of thermochromic pigment on leather finishing at 15°C and 31°C. The color measurement was studied by spectrophotometer. Candas et al. [66] investigated thermochromism in leather finishing by UV absorber and cross linker. The evidence was supported by spectrophotometer and ageing test. Heet et al. [59] observed bisphenol A risk for thermochromic textile product and tested by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method for bisphenol identification.

2.7. Principle of Liquid Crystal for Thermochromism

Dave and Patel [140] mentioned that molecular diameter decreases when temperature raises under the investigations on 4-n Alkoxybiphenyl-4 Carboxylic acids and its 3-substituted derivatives. White [141] reviewed that the use of cholesteric liquid crystals (CLCs) as color changing optical materials. Liquid crystal has phase transition nature [96, 122]. Thermochromic liquid crystals have numerous applications [94] for color changing but the implementation in adaptive camouflaging have not been explored. Ian sage [96, 122] reported the nature of phase transition of liquid crystal technology. Qi Hong [84] investigated cholesteric liquid crystal and suggested that the number of pitches required for the stimulation of reflection. Yu Guan and other researchers [55] used cholesteric liquid crystal 3-30 μm microcapsules as thermochromic materials with electrospinning method and the structure of microencapsulation was determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images, core size was studied by TG. This study investigated the thermochromic property from red to blue chromatic hue. Gilligan et al. [28] are critically proposed temperature versus color change properties [33] of cholesteric liquid crystal for reversible, controllable, and reproducible. Aguirre [39] illuminated the reversible color changing property of colloidal photonic crystal. Nadia et al. [197] studied thermochromic liquid crystal for heat transfer. Choudhury et al. [51] commented that temperature can influence the reflection of light by liquid crystal due to having the structure of helices. Therefore, the wavelength of reflected light is altered causing progressive change in color spectrum. Seeboth and Lotzsch [76] mentioned in their book that liquid crystal can flow like fluid. The length of helical pitch depends on the molecular structure and concentration of the chiral compound, phase type and its temperature. Therefore, pitch length influences the thermochromic properties. Choudhury et al. [51] remarked that the liquid crystal materials can be microencapsulated and microcapsules can be used like pigment on the fabric surface with resin binder. Christie et al. [77] experimented thermochromic print based microencapsulated liquid crystal. The effect is most suitable over a black background. Treated nylon and lycra blended fabric was analyzed in terms of wavelength of reflected light, $L^* a^*$

b^* values, lightness, chroma and hue. Christie et al. [91] also remarked that leuco dye and liquid crystal for temperature sensitive environment using thermochromic color change by careful formulation with proposed technology of microencapsulation. Maclaren et al. [83] used crystal violet lactone dyes for reversible thermochromic system. Similarly, Panak and other researchers [93] supported the color change mechanism with CIE lab [42] by demonstrating thermochromic composite in formulation with crystal violate lactone as a color, bisphenol A as developer and tetradecanol as co-solvent.

2.8. Nano Materials for Thermochromism

Smith et al. [35] patented the material coloration using particle scattering and Hemant Kumar et al. [30] reported the feasibility of anti-reflective coating for thermochromism. Kumar et al. [37] studied the thermochromism with vanadium pentoxide coating and suggested the possibility of chromium for thermochromism. Yan and other researchers [98] investigated by x-ray diffraction (XRD) that the degree of crystallization of colored luminous fibre was decreased inorganic pigments when inorganic pigment and luminous materials were used. Xiao et al. [132] opined that the possibility of adaptive infrared camouflage which consists of a vanadium dioxide (VO_2) layer, with a negative differential thermal emissivity, coated on a graphene/carbon nanotube (CNT) thin film. Plan et.al [99] remarked high refractive index of grapheme oxide. Zhu [133] studied for high temperature thermal management in infrared camouflage by combining a silica aerogel for thermal insulation.

2.9. PCM for Thermochromism

Krishna et al. [97] studied that PCM dispersed with different types of nano particle for high thermal storage in terms of microencapsulation and researcher recommended the microencapsulation technique for high thermal storage with nano-PCM. Qu et al. [58] reported that camouflage technique has not adequately explored the ability to continuously camouflage objects either temperature variations or wide observation angle. Researchers developed a thermal camouflage device by PCM $\text{Ge}_2\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_5$ in 30°C to 50°C and 0° to 60° angle. Wu [67] was studied simultaneous process of color changing and heat changing behavior after 100-time heating and cooling cycle by using spiro lactone color former, phenolic hydroxyl compound as color developer, 1-hexadecanol as PCM and the microencapsulation was achieved by gelatin containing vinyl group and gum arabic to form glutaraldehyde for making stability and encapsulation. Sari et al. [79] experimented with emulsion polymerization method for solid-liquid microencapsulated phase change material (PCM). The chemical and thermal characterization was done by SEM, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) where the DSC showed energy storage capacity and the TGA confirmed the thermal stability of microencapsulated PCM. The microencapsulated n-heptdecane with polymethylacrylate confirmed 5000 thermal cycles. Burkinshaw et al. [82] experimented with p^H sensitive spiro lactone derived

functional dyes and phase changes occurred during heating and cooling in terms of thermochromic effect. Wbendkowska [90] studied that PCM has latent heat storage capability for thermal application.

3. Materials, Methods, and Experimental Design for Adaptive Camouflage Textiles

Materials, methods, analysis, and observations need a technical combination for adaptive camouflaging on textile substances against multidimensional background environments. The materials, methods, analysis, and observations are not established for adaptive camouflage textiles. Table 1 denotes the selection of suitable textile materials for thermochromism and adaptive camouflage textiles. Common textile materials have been mentioned by defense professional. Table 2 has been listed with thermochromic colorant for chromatic appearance with background environments; and TLC for deceiving

mechanism (Figure 3) at different temperature. Table 3 demonstrates the method of textile treatment for thermochromism as camouflage coloration. Table 4 exhibits the assessment method of thermochromism, and analysis of textile treated samples. Table 5 has been mentioned with color changing parameters for background color matching at different temperature/weather conditions/background environments.

3.1. Textile Materials for Thermochromism

Table 1. Textile materials for thermochromism

References	Textile Materials
Potucket et al. [64]	Nylon & spandex blended fabric.
Ahmed et al. [52]	Polyester and cotton blended fabric
Ahmed et al. [26,190]	Cotton fabric
Zhang [71]	Polyester fabric
Wu et al. [69]	Cotton & polyester blended fabric
Christie et al. [77]	Nylon and lycra blended fabric

3.2. Materials for Thermochromism

Table 2. Materials for thermochromism

References	Materials
Geng et al. [54]	Crystal violet lactone
Ladendal [22]	Thermochromic leuco dyes
Rao [24]	TLC, leuco dyes
Salek et al. [25,55]	TLC, Zn ₃ (PO ₃) ₂ S (irreversible)
Odwa et al. [57]	Polydiacetylene (reversible color blue), 10, 12 pentacoadiynic acid group of urea
Jin and other researchers [60]	Pigment TF-G
Jin et al. [61]	Pigment
Potuck et al. [64]	Leuco dyes
Kulcar et al. [95]	Leuco dye-based TC ink
Jakovljevic et al. [74]	Leuco dyes and liquid crystal
Wu et al. [69]	3,3-bis(4 dimethylaminophenyl)-6 dimethylaminophthlate, 2,2-bis (4-hydroxyphenyl) propane and alepheticalkohol as thermochromic core materials, melamine formaldehyde
Candas and other researchers [66]	UV absorber and cross linker.
Hong [84]	Cholesteric liquid crystal
Guan and other researchers [55]	Cholesteric liquid crystal
Gilligan and associate researchers [28]	Cholesteric liquid crystal
Aguirre [39]	Colloidal photonic crystal
Nadia et al. [197]	Liquid crystal
Choudhury et al. [51]	Liquid crystal, resin binder
Christie et al. [77]	Liquid crystal
Christie et al. [91]	Leuco dye and liquid crystal
Maclaren et al. [83]	Crystal violet lactone dyes
Panak and other researchers [93]	Crystal violate lactone, bisphenol A, tetradecanol.
Yan and other researchers [98]	Inorganic pigment and luminous materials
Qu and researcher team [58]	PCM Ge ₂ Sb ₂ Te ₅
Geng et al. [54]	Nano particles
Ramig et al. tested [65]	Carbon nanotube
Kumar et al. [37]	Vanadium pentoxide
Wu [67]	Spirolactine color former, phenolic hydroxyl compound as color developer, 1-hexadecanol as PCM, gelatin, gum arabic
Geng et al. [54]	Nano particles
Ramig et al. [65]	Carbon nanotube
Kumar et al. [37]	Vanadium pentoxide
Dean et al. [154]	Thermochromic ink
White [141]	Cholesteric liquid crystal
Patel [140]	Liquid crystal
Kristina Bašneć [109]	Leuco dyes

References	Materials
Panak et al. [108]	Crystal violet lactone as a colour former, bisphenol A as a developer and tetradecanol as a co-solvent
Hulsey and his team [117]	Leuco dyes
Schubert et al. [114]	TiO ₂ /SiO ₂
Basnec and his researcher team [101]	Crystal violet lactone (CVL) dye, benzyl 4-hydroxybenzoate (B4HB) developer and 1-dodecanol (DD) solvent
Zhu [133]	Silica aerogel
Xiao et al. [132]	Vanadium dioxide (VO ₂), graphene/carbon nanotube (CNT)
Amin et al. [158]	Parafin as PCM, Fe ₃ O ₄ , CuO, TiO ₂ , and ZnO nanoparticles for improving latent heat. Fe ₃ O ₄ and CuO are black while TiO ₂ , ZnO are white.
Shibahashi et al. [165]	9-(diethylamino)-1-spiro 12-H-benzoaxan thene2, 1'(3'H)-isobenzofuran)-3'-one, bisphenol A, myristyl alcohol and stearyl caprate, epoxy resin-amine
Borque et al. [193]	A leuco dye, a phenolic colour developer
Larnet et al. [191]	Crystal violet lactone as dye; propyl gallate, octyl gallate or lauryl gallate as developer; 1-tetradecanol, 1-hexadecanol or 1-octadecanol as solvent.
Shibahashi et al. [157]	Crystal violet lactone, malachite green lactone, michler'shydrol, crystal violet carbinol etc.

3.3. Methods for Thermochromism

Table 3. Methods for thermochromism

References	Methods
Geng et al. [54]	Microencapsulation
Rao [24]	Coating
Jin et al. [60]	Wet Spinning
Potuck et al. [64]	Microencapsulation
Zhang et al. [72]	Melt Spinning
Wu et al. [69]	Microencapsulation
Wu et al. [69]	Coating
Feng et al. [30]	Coating & Microencapsulation
Krishna et al. [97]	Microencapsulation
Guan and other researchers [55]	Microencapsulation, electrospinning
Choudhury et al. [51]	Microencapsulation
Christie et al. [77]	Printing, Microencapsulation
Christie et al. [91]	Microencapsulation
Kumar et al. [37]	Coating
Bozhen Wu [67]	Microencapsulation
Sari et al. [79]	Microencapsulation, emulsion polymerization
Wilusz [85]	Microencapsulation, coating
Vikova [116]	Dyeing and Printing
Schubert et al. [114]	Coating
Xiao et al. [132]	Coating
Fujita et al. [156]	Microencapsulation
Shibahashi, Y., [157]	Microencapsulation Size: 2-30µm
Shibahashi et al. [165]	Microencapsulation, coating, interfacial polymerization
Patra et al. [34]	Coating and microencapsulation
LCR Hallcrest smart technology [122]	Color changing crystal and microencapsulation

3.4. Methods of Thermochromism Analysis

Table 4. Methods thermochromism analysis

Geng et al. [54]	Microscopic
Odwa et al. [57]	UV-Vis, DSC, XRD, TG
Jin et al. researchers [60]	Naked eye for color changing
Jin et al. [61]	SEM, XRD, DSC, TG, SEM
Ramig et al. [65]	Spectrophotometer, SEM
Brist et al. patented [70]	Visual
Zhang et al. [72]	SEM
Seren et al. [73]	Spectrophotometer
Candas et al. [66]	Spectrophotometer
He et al. [59]	HPLC
Hong [84]	Finite element
Guan et al. [55]	SEM, TEM, TG

Christie et al. [77]	Spectrophotometer
Chowdhury et al. [42]	Spectrophotometer
Lin et al. [145]	Spectrophotometer
Yan and other researchers [98]	XRD
Sari et al. [79]	SEM, DSC, TGA, DSC
Panak et al. [108]	Spectrophotometer
Bamfield et al. [126]	Spectrophotometer
Wen et al. [136]	Target detection by hyperspectral imagers
Volonakis et al. [143]	Target detection by human participants
Laren, et al. [191]	Diffuse reflectance spectrophotometry

3.5. Observations for Color Changing Parameters

Table 5. Observations for color changing parameters

References	Color changing parameters
Wilusz [85]	(100-200)°C, (5-15)°C
Salek et al. [55]	400°C, 600°C and 1000°C
Odwa et al. [57]	150°C
Jin and other researchers [60]	30°C-20°C
Yang jin [61]	Rose red at room temperature and colorless for blue light emission
Potuck et al. [64]	Between 33°C and 38°C
Martins [63]	10°C-60°C
Ramig et al. [65]	Bluer, redder
Ahmed et al. [52]	30°C, black to green
Zhang [71]	At 20°C, 45°C, 80°C, dark blue, light blue, 50 Times
Zhang et al. [72]	5°C and 35°C after 60 temp cycles
Seren et al. [73]	15°C and 31°C
Guan and other researchers [55]	Red to blue chromatic hue
Gilligan and researchers [28]	Color change reversible, controllable, and reproducible
Qu and researcher team [58]	30°C to 50°C
Wu [67]	100-time heating and cooling cycle
Burkinshaw et al. [82]	p ^H
Choudhury et al. [75]	Ultraviolet temperature, p ^H
Wilusz [85]	Color white to blue
Anne et al. [102]	Pitch length in liquid crystal and color changed
Basnec et al. [101]	Changes in the geometry of the material and color
Kulčar et al. [112]	Decolorized state at cooling for 10 hours
Jassim et al. [113]	Orange 30°C, Light orange 32°C, Light Pink 36°C, Colorless 41°C.
Tianzhi et al. [134]	Electrical field-based color changing
Fujita et al. [156]	Color changes from 5°C to 80°C
Shibahashi et al. [165]	Pink color below 25°C and colorless above 25°C

4. Camouflage Identification Methods

Adaptive camouflage can be investigated by spectroscopic, microscopic, photographic illumination and human participants as evidence of different branches of research and developments. Wen et al. [136] commented that target signature can be experimented by hyperspectral imagers and detection can be assessed in different distances [146]. Chang et al. [189] experimented that camouflage target can be identified at different angle of target. Gupta [163] remarked that spectral features can be detected the material properties of objects because of the emission, reflection, and absorption of light. Hyperspectral imaging can be used for photographic and spectral illumination in UV-Vis-infrared (IR) ranges [159,160,162,172,189]. Manolakis et al [181] experimented on hyperspectral image analysis for the operation and performance of detectors. Akkaynak et al. [170] suggested an image processing technique in perception science for color

calibration from digital camera. Animal scientists are doing camouflage research with hyperspectral imaging technology. Pinto et al. [182] successfully experimented on frog skin reflectivity in hyperspectral imaging between 400-2500 nm and spectral reflectivity between 700-1100 nm. Chiao et al. [180] investigated the color formation camouflage of cuttlefish with hyperspectral imaging technique. Akkaynak et al. [166] studied in color change for flounder camouflage with hyperspectral imaging Hultgren et al. [167] studied color change camouflage in marine isopod. Edelaar et al. [168] studied color changing of grasshopper. Russell et al. [173] experimented spectral camouflage of two crab species (*Portunus sayi* and *Planes minutus*) was assessed using hyperspectral imagery in 400-550 nm. Manolakis et al. [191] remarked that hyperspectral sensing can increase the detectability of pixel and subpixel size targets by exploiting finer detail in the spectral signatures of targets and natural backgrounds. Photographic illumination with digital camera and

hyperspectral camera, and its image analysis have versatile applications [171,179,185,186,200,201] including colored materials [187] but limited for camouflaging of textile-based target signature. Muller and Muller [196] studied that camouflage is a practicing issue of army operations in UV-Vis-IR spectrum. Reflection is a consideration of UV-Vis-IR ranges camouflage [183]. Hamilton et al. [184] performed liquid crystal analysis using CIE lab and image. Lin et.al confirmed that color analysis of camouflage can be investigated by CIE Lab color space in both specular [137] and diffuse components [148], its related calculation can be done by calorimetry [139,145]. Volonakis et al. [143] designed a human observer model for camouflage identification and its detection and recognition behavior was compared with human participants. Merilaita and other researchers [198] remarked that camouflage target influences target feature, edge, surface, and objects. Ruxton GD and researcher team [199] suggested that dorsum and ventral issues are responsible for background matching. Bhajantri et al. [195] developed a model of camouflage defect identification based on texture feature. Stenet et. al. [194] studied that background area selection for target detection influence the assessment of camouflage. Joe et al. [144] studied the eye movement behaviors on camouflage pattern which may influence the precision surveillance of detection when digital camera is used by different personnel.

5. Research Limitations and Development Approach for Thermal Camouflage

Defense professionals are working at different weather and diverse CB. Adaptive camouflage textiles with surrounding CB are great challenge of different situations. Sometimes defense soldier needs to shift urban to desert, desert to urban, urban to forest, forest to urban, forest to desert and desert to forest in a single operation and/or multi operations. Thermochromic colorant had been studied in literature for color changing but still researchers had not been studied the techniques for the suitability of camouflage purpose for modern surveillance technology and limited research have been observed for the suitability of simultaneous thermochromic and liquid crystal based textiles for color changing. Limited research had been found on adaptive camouflage textiles in literature, although sensor based preliminary stage research on adaptive camouflage textiles had been seen. But limited research on adaptive textiles has been reported for the color changing behaviors of textile substances in terms of details investigations of pitch length changing and wavelength changing of liquid crystal under heating mechanism, but the reviewed mechanism of thermochromism and liquid crystal have been positively argued for the feasibility of pitch length changing and wavelength changing of liquid crystal, thus the technology can be studied for the augmentation of color changing and adaptive camouflage textiles with thermochromic colorant and liquid crystal. Furthermore, adding liquid crystal-based technology for the adaptive camouflage textiles may generate an invention of proposed technology in Vis and IR spectrum of

camouflage technology for the concealment of modern surveillance technology including digital camera and/or hyperspectral camera.

6. Significant Approach for Adaptive Camouflage Textiles Technology

Burkinshaw et al. [138] remarked that concealment from day light surveillance is a most established practice of camouflage technology in which different hues are employed to overcome the contrast of object and its surrounding. Thermochromism in color changing is already being used in textiles and leather engineering but this is a new approach for the application in adaptive camouflage textiles by the simulation of heat-light-camouflage mechanism in terms of liquid crystal technique. Researchers studied thermochromism in color changing for high temperature based applications by using metallic particle finishing but the technology has limitations for clothing based applications where needs a comfort range of temperature but reversibility of color, numbers of color changing, numbers of sensitive temperatures, tolerance levels of human body temperature like 0°C to 45°C range or other purpose in different temperature ranges, suitable application of colorants in terms of heat and illumination, accurate thermochromism materials like nanoparticles and/PCM for sustaining thermochromism in color changing are still a hidden issue. Review shows that color changing application has been found for maximum two colors having a limitation with a very minimum temperature difference for clothing, but still the technology has not been used for camouflage. So proposed technology will have a temperature dissimilarity in different wavelength and different reflection in wavelength in terms of camouflage with surrounding background. Application of liquid crystal is not only limited to develop digital technology [142], textile and material scientists are also using liquid crystal for improving different technical properties on textiles substances but liquid crystal applications for the purpose of camouflage textiles are still in development stage/new to the textile and material scientists. Thermochromism mechanism can change the surface illumination in wavelength and color formation of textile substances. Liquid crystal can circulate in different angle when altering molecular orientation is occurred. No detailed studies have been observed for the illumination of color in different molecular orientations and its proposed effect of color changing in different wavelength. Thus, there is so much feasibility of doing liquid crystal-based camouflage textiles which may have an impact in the research and development of anti-surveillance technology in terms of designing and developing camouflage textiles. Figure 2 shows the adaptation of adaptive camouflage textiles with multidimensional surrounding CB. CB environments are illustrated as CB-01, 02, 03 and observers are termed as predator-01, 02, 03, 04. Adaptive camouflage textiles will be a single textile-based target signature, will be able to match with CB 01, 02, 03 under temperature versus chromatic replacement.

Figure 2. (Schematic) Thermochromic adaptive textiles shows color changing for surrounding background color to the predators or observers.

Figure 3. Principle of adaptive camouflage textiles coloration with thermochromic liquid crystal (TLC)

Figure 4. Typical principle for pitch length changing and chromatic replacement for thermochromism of liquid crystal

Figure 5. Proposed methodology for adaptive camouflage textiles formulation

7. Technical Approach of Liquid Crystal Mechanism for Adaptive Camouflage

Technical approach of adaptive mechanism [25,77,76,94] of liquid crystal have been demonstrated and interpreted in Figure 3. Established Bragg's law [104,105,106] has been used to signify the structure of color changing approach in liquid crystals molecules:

$$n\lambda = 2d\sin\theta, \lambda = 2d\sin\theta / n$$

where λ is the wavelength of the illumination Vis-IR ranges, d is the spacing of the liquid crystal layer (path difference of wavelength), θ is the incident angle (the angle between incident ray and the scatter plane), and n is an integer. By putting the value of d , θ and n , we can get the value of λ and the changing value of λ identify the replacement of wavelength and changing of wavelength clarify the altering of chromatic appearance of target signature. Thermochromism mechanism in liquid crystal will change the value of distance, d , the distance will change the angle, θ ; and wavelength λ will be changed which will create new reflection in specific temperature range and new color formation to the observer Figure 4 demonstrates the chromatic replacement principle by TLC mechanism. The order of molecular distance, angle of wavelength will be adjusted by temperature. Anne et al. [102] supported that the typical value of pitch length in liquid crystal phenomenon can be the order of wavelength can follow Bragg reflection theory. Therefore, color will change from black to red through orange, yellow, green, and blue, violet, and again black.

$$\text{Reflectance spectrum } (\lambda) = \frac{\text{reflected radiation at band } (\lambda)}{\text{incident radiation at band } (\lambda)}$$

Reflectance spectrum or spectral signature shows the function of incident energy, typically natural illumination such as sunlight, that is reflected by multidimensional CB material as a function of the wavelength (λ) of the energy [181]. Figure 5 signifies the proposed methodology for adaptive camouflage textiles formulation and design, applied by thermo-chromatic mechanism and coloration technique.

8. Conclusion

Liquid crystal shows precision of color change, but their color change range is limited. In contrast leuco dyes shows wider range of color but difficult to set with accuracy [125]. So, review can be strongly recommended for combined applications and formulations for thermochromic dyes and liquid crystal. Hypothesis of review undoubtedly states that there are enormous applications of thermochromism technology for color changing, liquid crystal mechanism for color changing and the combination of those techniques have been applied in different purposes for the development of color changing behaviors but the research and developments in the camouflage textiles applications have been limited. The technology of thermochromism and liquid crystal combination is not a new technology but the applications in camouflage and particularly in adaptive camouflage textiles are an original contribution in terms of leuco dyes, liquid crystal related to thermal engineering Adaptive camouflage for the surrounding CB and color matching is still a new technical approach for the implementation of defense professional. On the basis of review, it can be suggested that thermochromic liquid crystal can be implemented for future experimental study of adaptive camouflage, furthermore TLC based technology can be extended for the personal protection of different technical workers in extreme weather conditions including fashionable textile design although right formulation of liquid crystal

may spawn a new invention in the area of thermal camouflage engineering and its related branches of textile technology. Crystals mechanism of birefringence may split the refracted ray into two rays in anisotropic media [115]. The theory also can be applied for color changing of thermochromism and its feasibility with adaptive camouflage textiles. Proper percentage of liquid crystal (cholesteric liquid crystal, nematic liquid crystal and combination of both for color changing), appropriate selection of dyes (leuco dyes or other heat sensitive dyes), heating process for controlling and reversible process (conductive metallic yarn and/or nano particle, PCM), heating process for uncontrolling parameters (sun light) and a suitable process selection for textile coloration/finishing may generate expected color changing with surrounding and its right adaptation needs for the purpose of defense applications. Geometrical change will form an artificial wavelength and reflection on textile substances which is responsible for liquid crystal-based color changing process. Controlling geometrical change on temperature will create the expected color for adaptive camouflage textiles. Two reversible and irreversible color, multi-reversible and irreversible color, distance of temperatures and color changing, CB color and adaptive color can be developed by the controlling of rotation engineering and its pitch length of liquid crystal. A minimum percentage of liquid crystal needs to remain on the surface of textile substances for getting an outcome of pitch length changing, wavelength changing, color changing. Molecular size and distribution on the surface of textile substances will influence the surface modification in terms of heat changing, consequently wavelength changing and color changing accordingly. The amount of light scattered depends upon the size of molecules and the wavelength of light. Color change is occurred due to the absence of specific wavelengths of light reflected to the observer due to differences in molar absorptivity [31,107].

Nanoparticle/metallic-yarn/PCM/paraffin can be used for thermal storage in adaptive textiles for the camouflage formulation at different temperature. Research can be carried out by "Bisphenol A" free thermochromism process. Reflection can be changed artificially to the observer in UV-Vis-IR spectrum for making artificial confusion of target signature against surrounding CB environments. Color and temperature need to identify for thermochromism and color matching with surrounding CB. Color matching spectrophotometer can be applied for Vis camouflage, but the assessment of camouflage textiles with hyperspectral spectrometry and imaging is still new technology in review but animal scientists are also using hyperspectral camera for animal camouflage identification.

Declaration

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REVIEW

Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background

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ABSTRACT

Camouflage textile assessments are limited in defense research for single and multidimensional combat background (CB) against hyperspectral imaging (HSI). The development of camouflage textiles needs to be upgraded for the capabilities of modern battlefield surveillance. The purpose of this simulation work is to design remote sensing methodology and desired spectral properties of camouflage textiles. A spectral signal (SL) of camouflage textile was hypothetically simulated against dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark-woodland, water-marine, sand-desertland, stone-stoneland, snow-snowland, sky and ice-iceland CB (DGTWSIB), and a simultaneous CB of woodland-marine and marine-desert for camouflage textiles assessment. This simulation is to establish SL assessment technique of object-background (OB) in ultraviolet (UV), visible (Vis) and infrared (IR) illumination in terms of HSI spectrometry, near infrared spectrophotometry (NIRS) and Fourier transform infrared spectrometry (FTIRS) for the advancement and establishment of camouflage textiles assessment. The broad geographical DGTWSIB of camouflage textiles has been contemplated for spectral reflection in OB environments for concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI). Theoretical simulation of SL has been derived for assessment of camouflage textiles compared with single, simultaneous, and adaptive backgrounds from military CB or locations. The hypothetical and methodological model will direct advanced formulation of camouflage textile measurement for combat mechanism of reflection-SL-CDRI-OB-DGTWSIB-UV-Vis-IR (100–10,000 nm) against defense threat of HSI.

Abbreviations: HPC: Hyperspectral camera; OB: Object and background; CB: Combat background; Multispectral: Multispectral imaging measures light in a small number (typically 3 to 15) of spectral bands; Hyperspectral: Hundreds of contiguous narrow bands over a spectral range; Spectral power distribution (SPD): Spectral power distribution is the power emitted by a light source per unit wavelength; Adaptive/active camouflage: The camouflage textiles that change color with changing surrounding backgrounds; DGTWSIB: Dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark-woodland CB; water-marine CB; sand-desertland, stone-stoneland, snow-snowland, and sky CB; and ice-iceland CB.; ATR: Absorption-transmission-reflection; CDRI: Concealment, detection, recognition, and identification; SL: Spectral signal

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1. Introduction

Physical properties of object and background (OB) materials are correlated with advanced imaging signal for concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI) of target signature (Xu et al., 2018). Reflectivity of OB and spectral ranges are the foremost characteristics of a spectral signal (SL) for target concealment. The SL of camouflage textiles in ultraviolet (UV), visible (Vis) and infrared (IR) ranges depends on surface treatments and their illumination properties on textile substances. Matching of spectral behavior of target signature (treated textiles) versus combat background (CB) signify camouflage textiles (Winkelmann, 2015). A combat location of OB is possible to capture at different incident angles by hyperspectral imaging (HSI). OB adaptation is easily achievable by imaging signal and/or SL (Russell & Dierssen, 2015). HSI assessments on camouflage

textiles has already been implemented in recent literature (Jianxin et al., 2021; Jianxin, 2020). Modern remote sensing surveillance in UV-Vis-IR has been depicted as technological threat to the defense professional (Jenerowicz, 2019). Therefore, SL and CDRI of military target signature (camouflage textiles) is a demanding assessment process for defense protection. HSI has been reviewed and a methodological platform of camouflage textiles has been designed for remote sensing applications of camouflage engineering in UV-Vis-IR.

1.1. Recent advancements of HSI

Hyperspectral camera (HPC) captures a physical scene and spectral information of target signature over a broad-spectrum range. It is described as the combination of

spectroscopy and a modern imaging system in 400–2500 nm spectral range through an optical absorption-transmission-reflection (ATR) mechanism (Yuen & Richardson, 2010). HPC is a precise and rapid analysis, requiring little specimen preparation of OB, and capable of imaging and SL measurement with a single scan of OB environment against dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark-woodland combat background (CB); water-marine CB; sand-desertland CB; stone-stoneland CB; snow-snowland CB; sky CB and ice-iceland CB, DGTWSIB (Jenerowicz, 2019; Williams & Sendin, 2019). HSI has already been implemented for L^* , a^* , b^* analysis of object (textile treated surface) (Jianxin et al., 2021). The imaging technique is also accepted for spectral and imaging signal of CB such as vegetation, natural leaves (Badaro, 2020; Lowe et al., 2017; Ren et al., 2020; Xu & Ye, 2020). Mineral identification and mapping of CB (Manna, 2018), environment protection satellite (atmospheric/water quality/pollution), earth observing (disaster monitoring and mitigation), coastal ocean information (optical properties and on-shore CB mapping), radio detection and ranging (RADAR) and light detection and ranging (LIDAR) are also advance application areas of HSI against DGTWSIB (Yuen & Richardson, 2010; Wang et al., 2010). HPC applications are already found in defense as a target identification technique in OB environment (Andersson, 2018). HPC sensing technique is performed for tracking and identification of military target signature. HPC has specialized function to convert pixel information of imaging to SL compared to other spectroscopic signals and suitable mechanisms for CDRI assessment in OB environment. Both pixel and SL of HPC in UV-Vis-IR surveillance range have been depicted as modern tools for OB assessment in opposed to DGTWSIB (Yuen & Richardson, 2010). Camouflage textiles in any OB environment need to make concealment for defense protection against HPC surveillance. Therefore, CDRI-HPC has been a prominent part of camouflage engineering and curiosity of such investigation has been reached at peak level.

1.2. HSI-SL mechanism for CDRI assessment of camouflage textiles

Figure 1 illustrates the HPC mechanism. An HPC scanning output consists of light source, lens, specimen holder, wavelength dispersion devices, frame grabber (Willoughby et al., 1996). In a hyperspectral scan, the spectral features are produced by specific light scattering and ATR properties of the OB materials that are recorded at each image pixel, and the pixel intensity is recorded as SL (Heist et al., Heist et al., 2018). HPC acquires data in bandwidths of 1–15 nm in place of a conventional multispectral bandwidth 50–100 nm. An HPC sensor gathers data through either passive sensing (to collect and record electromagnetic energy (E) that is reflected or emitted by OB features and ATR mechanism) or active sensing (to generate their own illumination E and then collect the signal that is reflected from OB) (Borengasser et al., 2007). When light penetrates deeper into any OB materials, the light is altered by differences in path length and creates SL containing chemical compound

information (Grahn & Geladi, 2007). Chemical bonds of OB are determined by their spectral frequencies in terms of atom, shape of molecule, microstructural properties of bond and vibrational distance between atoms. The spectral properties/chemical compounds of any OB material are detected by the ATR mechanism (Cozzolino, 2014). A chromophore group is detected by its spectral intensity of optical mechanism of ATR (Field et al., 2007). For CDRI and camouflage textiles assessment, spatial, spectral and polarimetric information reveals the different characteristics of target signature and backgrounds DGTWSIB. Spectral information shows the distribution of OB components in a scene; polarimetric information shows surface feature, shape, shading and roughness (Zhou, 2011). A spatial resolution is defined as the smallest discernible detail of an image (shown as number 1–13 in Figure 1). It is described as a measure of smallest part of an object. OB is distinguished as a separate entity in every imaging signal. A spectral resolution is defined as the number of spectral bands and ranges of electromagnetic spectrum measured by the HPC sensor. An imaging sensor might respond to a large frequency range, but it still has a low spectral resolution for a small number of spectral bands (Khan et al., 2018). A spectral power distribution (SPD) is the power emitted by a light source per unit wavelength S (λ). It is referred as the relative spectral distribution of sensor at specified wavelength (Equation 1),

$$S(\lambda) = X(\lambda)/R(\lambda), \quad (1)$$

where $X(\lambda)$ is the radiant flux per wavelength; $R(\lambda)$ is a fixed reference value and it is an average value, a maximum value or an arbitrarily chosen value of this distribution (Durmus, 2000).

HPC light reflected or scattered by OB materials relative to the incident light. Every SL is generated at specified wavelength (Striova et al., 2020). SPD and spectral reflectivity generate appearance variation of a target scene (Tian et al., 2016; Winkelmann, 2017). SPD depicts the chromatic characteristics of a target object of a light source as a function of wavelength in terms of ATR. Different SPD of light can result in similar apparent colors of light, but quite different color quality (Chuang, 2015). The SPD phenomenon creates spectral and pixel signal of OB. The data information can be assessed for CDRI assessment of camouflage textiles.

A hyperspectral digital image includes dimensions, resolution, file type, color mode and color encoding (color management). It is evaluated as a piece of graph paper and the number of squares on the sheet of paper indicates the resolution. Imaging of digital camera imaging has a different number of pixels. For example, a 24-megapixel camera has 24 million pixels, usually arranged as 6000 pixels in one direction and 4000 pixels in another direction, $6000 \times 4000 = 24,000,000$. Color mode defines the number of channels. Modes include grey scale, one channel; RGB (red, green, and blue), three channels; CMYK (cyan, magenta, yellow, black), four channels; and Lab (L^* , a^* , b^*), three channels, which are the functional parameters of image analysis for CDRI of target signature in the OB

Figure 1. HPC mechanism for spectral and spatial information of target object (a typical camouflage treated textiles) against DGTWSIB.

environment (Berns, 2019). HPC imaging increases the information density for each spatial position within target OB environments, from which the spectra originate. Hyperspectral images are composed of hundreds of bands with a very high spectral resolution, generally from the UV to IR region. Every recorded pixel shows a complete spectral description and a better characterization of OB (Chen et al., 2017). Instead of a color or intensity of OB at each pixel on the image, an entire spectrum is captured for that pixel and absorbances arise primarily from harmonic oscillations of surface compounds of OB in ATR mechanism (Anderson et al., 2008). An HPC digital image (Figure 1) has a large spectral dataset (Fu, 2010). Image quality is influenced by linear size, area angle, resolution, geometrical correctness/

distortions, depth of field, grayscale or color (Grahn & Geladi, 2007). An OB analysis is also possible by using thermal images (Dulski, 2007) but the thermal behavior in IR ranges influences the OB assessment (Goldberg et al., 2003). Accuracy of HPC image may be enhanced by black and white based equation (Equation 2) for OB assessment.

$$I_c = \frac{I_r - I_b}{I_w - I_b} \times 100\%, \quad (2)$$

where I_c is the corrected image, I_r is the raw image, I_b is the black reference image (almost 0% reflectance) acquired by covering the camera lens completely with its cap, and I_w is the white reference image (>99.9% reflectance) acquired by reflecting a standard Teflon white tile (Ren et al., 2020).

HPC spectra are acquired by counting particles of target OB materials like photons, electrons, or ions. A chemical bond absorbs light energy at specific wavelength, so some compositional information is determined from HSI spectra. HPC analyses of OB appearance are obtainable with line scan, area scan and point scan methods (Dong et al., 2020). Qin et al. (2013) mentioned the point scan, line scan and area scan methods for acquiring three dimensional hyper-spectral cubes with both spatial and spectral information. Furthermore, the HSI technique is utilized for pixel and SL analysis of OB for CDRI compared to DGTWSIB in laboratory and field scale applications as HPC cannot provide color value (L^* , a^* , b^*) directly (Jianxin, 2020; Lowe et al., 2017).

1.3. Near infrared spectrophotometry (NIRS) for SL-CDRI assessment of camouflage textiles

NIRS has been widely used for spectral component analysis of OB materials (Manley, 2014; Ng, 2007). The energy band is defined for convenience of OB assessment in NIR as the spectral range covers $12,821$ to 4000 cm^{-1} (780 – 2500 nm) (Ng, 2007; Weyer, 2012). NIR spectra contain physical and compositional information relating to differences in bond strengths, chemical species, electronegativity, and hydrogen bonding with respect to scattering, diffuse reflection, specular reflection, surface gloss, refractive index, and polarization of reflected light. NIR energy stimulates the vibration of molecules and generates stretching (inter-atomic distance along the axis between two atoms) and bending (change in bond angle between three atoms). NIR spectral features arise from the molecular ATR of the overtones of vibrations when molecules are excited from the ground state to a higher energy excited vibrational state. In-plane bending consists of scissoring and rocking while out-of-plane bending (wagging) consists of twisting and rocking. Specific molecular bonds are most active in the NIR which differs Vis camouflage compared to NIR camouflage textiles under CB materials. Other functional groups related to NIRS can include hydrogen bonding, carbonyl carbon to oxygen stretch, carbon to nitrogen stretch, carbon to carbon stretch, and metal halides. C=O bonds have weak overtone because of having low molecular weight C (12) and O (16). This means almost symmetric vibration between C and O, whereas C–H have asymmetric vibrations leading to strong overtones. C=12 g/mol is much larger than H=1 g/mol. C–H bonds will absorb energy in the NIR region and provide a spectrum. The established equation of energy (E) (Equation 3) and the Robert Hooke law (Equation 4) identify the molecular mechanism of vibration and reflection in NIR. The potential energy for a bond is shown by Equation 3.

$$E = \frac{1}{2}kx^2, \quad (3)$$

where k is the force constant for the bond holding the two atoms together, and x is the change in displacement from the centre of equilibrium.

The Hooke law (Equation 4) is aligned with spring behavior of atoms such as stretching, scissoring, bending, and wagging.

$$V = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{\frac{1}{m_1} + \frac{1}{m_2}}}, \quad (4)$$

where k is a force constant that varies from one bond to another, m_1 is the mass of atom 1, and m_2 is the mass of atom 2 (Weyer, 2012).

SL technique has already been applied for CB materials but limited applications in OB-CB materials. Woodland (Haba, 2013; Holser, 2014; Sundaram et al., 2015), marine and iceland (Weyer, 2012) materials are experimented for SL (Toledo-Martín et al., 2018) using the techniques for OB-CDRI analysis of camouflage textiles against DGTWSIB. The vibrations of ATR mechanism of atomic bonds identify the spectral changes and hence the altering of chromatic signal. From the above, it is commented that NIRS can be applied for SL of color forming groups of camouflage treated textiles (target object) against DGTWSIB.

1.4. Fourier transform infrared spectrometry (FTIRS) versus SL analysis for CDRI assessment of camouflage textiles

OB materials as small as $10 \times 10\text{ pm}$ (i.e. a single crystal/fiber/dyes/nanoparticle/CB materials) are analyzed by FTIRS in terms of ATR technique of light (Gillard, 1994). FTIRS spectral interpretation of OB spectra revealed valuable data information about the identification and characterization of each group of dyes, pigment, nanoparticles and CB materials (Weyer, 2012). In NIR range, C–H vibration occurs between 1700 and 1800 nm , 1150 and 1210 nm , 880 and 915 nm , 1300 and 1500 nm , 2200 and 2500 nm ; but the combination of C–H stretching with various bands occurs between 2200 and 2500 nm (Weyer, 2012). Important chemical structures for chromatic identification and assessment of camouflage textiles as FTIRS absorbance are in mid infrared (MIR) such as aliphatic amine 7812 nm , 8474 nm , aromatic amine 7407 nm , 8000 nm , –NH stretching (urethane) 2985 nm , –NH–COO– (urethane) 5952 nm , 6060 nm , 6097 nm , C=C (aromatic) $12,500\text{ nm}$, 6211 nm , 6066 nm , –OH (hydroxyl) 3125 nm , 2941 nm , C–O–C (ether) 8695 nm , 9345 nm , 9416 nm , –CH vibration 3448 nm , –NH 5871 nm , 5885 nm , –CN 6583 nm , –CN–CO stretching 8517 nm , –C=O 9803 nm (Chevali & Kandare, 2016; Garside, 2002). OB materials vibration differs in NIR and MIR. Therefore, chromatic compound identification and SL assessments of camouflage treated textiles (object) and multidimensional background, DGTWSIB can be analyzed by FTIRS. OB spectra can be compared for CDRI assessment of camouflage textiles in a physical analysis process of OB materials.

2. Technical approach of SL-CDRI-OB-DGTWSIB-UV-Vis-IR for advancement of camouflage textiles

Camouflage textiles are needed for personal protection of special workers like snipers in land defense, marine defense, and air defense. Protection of land defense vehicle/shielding of temporary residence requires camouflage textiles for concealment of UV-Vis-IR illumination in multidimensional CB, DGTWSIB. Covering of marine defense ship/pavilion of temporary location necessitates camouflage textiles under UV-Vis-IR in the vein of marine. Air defense needs camouflage textiles for aircraft protection and parachute safety. Recent developments on HSI versus camouflage textiles have not been extended still now although the investigation of HPC camouflage textiles is a real need of time and technological demand for the protection and service satisfaction of special military forces in defense. The practical implementation may be an outcome of etiquette for camouflage textiles assessment in UV-Vis-IR illumination.

Camouflage techniques, analyses and assessments have been introduced in different branches of research in terms of HPC. Identification and analysis techniques of camouflage textiles are currently practiced in Vis range but there are limitations in standardization of such camouflage textiles. So far single background camouflage textiles are practiced in Vis range only but still not succeeded for every CB like DGTWSIB. Camouflage textiles in simultaneous CB are still a new concept. Up to now adaptive/active camouflage textiles in simultaneous background in Vis range have not been introduced. So far UV and IR range camouflage textiles are not established in literature and there are significance research gaps for the development of such camouflage techniques, suitability of materials and their standardization in textile science and technology. Hence, the techniques of adaptive camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage textiles need to be investigated in UV-Vis-IR ranges.

Researchers developed camouflage textiles in few single backgrounds of Vis range only but the camouflage textiles production, analysis, characterization, standardization, and academic research-based studies in UV-Vis-IR are still in initial stage. Augmentation of camouflage textiles has been demanded to investigate deep analysis in terms of SL-ATR-chromatic compound analysis for CDRI. OB imaging, color quantity, color quality on textile in UV-Vis-IR are not similar. There is significance lacking in methodological improvement of color deviation, color aberration and achromatic variation of OB materials both in RGB imaging and hyperspectral imaging. Practical and theoretical implementation of chromatic and achromatic camouflage is a challenging task due to individual properties of camouflage textiles (target object) and natural and/or artificial background. The contribution and solution of camouflage assessment is a technological demand for CDRI of hyperspectral based surveillance technology.

Figure 2 outlines the SL mechanism of camouflage textiles assessment. Camouflage textiles are definitely feasible to assess by the observation of optical ATR and scattering phenomenon in UV-Vis-IR illumination. Hyperspectral

spectrometry 400–2500 nm is proposed for spectral analysis of colored compounds on textiles. HSI, 400–2500 nm is also proposed for photographic analysis of camouflage textiles against DGTWSIB. A NIRS 750–2500 nm, FTIRS 1000–25,000 nm has suitable applications for spectral analysis for chromophore group identification on textile substances for the chromatic variation of OB surfaces. Therefore, it can be summarized that chromatic and achromatic analysis can be experimented by HSI spectrometry in UV-Vis-IR illumination. Color chemometric analysis between OB in NIR ranges is also obtainable to test by NIRS. Color chemometric analysis between OB in MIR range is also feasible to observe by FTIRS.

3. SL-CDRI-DGTWSIB methodology and simulation for camouflage textiles assessment

The chromatic mechanism for camouflage textiles assessment has been hypothetically defined and simulated in the vein of OB environment. The plot of HPC has been stated for concealment of camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-IR against DGTWSIB. The simulation was conducted based on hypothesis of camouflage textile assessments. Refractive index (n) and reflection (R) was synthesized as SL data information of DGTWSIB. SL-HPC technique was hypothetically and typically implemented to make a prediction and clarification of experimental outcome and investigation of camouflage assessment in UV-Vis-IR under DGTWSIB. SL symmetry and simulation for data representation was supported by hypothesis and literature review when SL symmetry may generate a concealed object against DGTWSIB (Andersson, 2018; Jenerowicz, 2019; Leong, 2007; Russell & Dierssen, 2015; Winkelmann, 2015). Spectral characteristics of 2% difference from OB were generated as a camouflaged target under CB (Yuen & Richardson, 2010). Human observer plot and data prediction with “oracle software” also showed SL similarity detection technique (Toet & Hogervorst, 2021). HSI sensor needs CDRI assessment technique by SL. Spectral vibration can be compared with the contrast level between target object (camouflage treated textiles) and its background in terms of CDRI. Hence, simulation of spectral signature assessment for camouflage textiles has been mentioned under consideration of SL symmetry for concealment against DGTWSIB. This simulation of camouflage textile assessment has been performed under reflection 100–10,000 nm and reflection coefficient has been considered as SL. Single background, simultaneous background and adaptive background have been signified for concealment of camouflage target signature in reflection versus SL symmetry.

Chromatic appearance depends on wavelength and the wavelength depends on the momentum of electron energy of photon signal. Hence, reflection between target camouflage textiles and CB materials was simulated in terms of electron energy in UV-Vis-IR. Electron energy is higher in UV, medium in Vis and lower in IR (Loebich, 1972). SL is changed by electron energy of OB materials, and it may be influenced by uncontrolled parameters of CB such as texture, unknown substances of CB, natural illumination, season, weather, and angle of target measurements for CDRI.

Figure 2. SL mechanism of camouflage textiles assessment.

Figure 3. Framework of methodology for simulation of camouflage textiles in DGTWSIB/combat location against DGTWSIB.

Therefore, this SL symmetry (Lafferman, 1976) is a method of partial fulfilments of CDRI measurements. Under consideration of SL theory, spectral assessment, materials of combat location, and individual OB in CB environment were typically simulated against DGTWSIB.

3.1. Calculation of SL simulation against DGTWSIB

UV (100, 220, 300, and 380 nm), Vis (500 and 700 nm), NIR (810, 1000, and 2500 nm) and MIR (10,000 nm) ranges were selected for SL simulation. Figure 3 shows the framework of methodology for simulation of camouflage textiles in DGTWSIB/combat location. Theory based experimental data of electron E (eV) in 100–10,000 nm and refractive index (n) of DGTWSIB were implemented for simulation. Depending on sun radiation, E in different wavelength are assumed: 12.4 (100 nm, velocity of light, $\nu = 3 \times 10^{15}$); 35.6 (220 nm, $\nu = 1.4 \times 10^{15}$); 4.0 (300 nm, $\nu = 1 \times 10^{15}$); 3.26 (380 nm, $\nu = 7.9 \times 10^{14}$); 2.47 (500 nm, $\nu = 6 \times 10^{14}$); 1.77 (700 nm, $\nu = 4.3 \times 10^{14}$); 1.53 (810 nm, $\nu = 3.7 \times 10^{14}$); 1.24 (1000 nm, $\nu = 3 \times 10^{14}$); 0.50 (2500 nm, $\nu = 1.2 \times 10^{14}$) and 0.12 (10,000 nm, $\nu = 3 \times 10^{13}$) (Kerekes & Baum, 2003; Loebich, 1972). The common refractive index (n) in UV-Vis-IR, 100–10,000 nm (Figure 4a) was assumed by Equation 5 (Sturge, 1962), where, $A = 53$; $\epsilon_0 = 2.26$; energy (E) = ϵ . Calculated coefficients of n are cited in Table SI 1.

$$n = \frac{A}{\epsilon_0^2 - \epsilon^2} + 1 \quad (5)$$

By putting the value of n , the “reflection coefficient of UV-Vis-IR, 100–10,000 nm” (Figure 4b) and “reflection coefficient of DGTWSIB” were determined by Equation 6, where, $n =$

refractive index, $R =$ reflection (Casey et al., 1974). Reflection coefficients (R) are mentioned in Table SI 1.

$$n = \frac{1 + \sqrt{R}}{1 - \sqrt{R}} \quad (6)$$

A standard R-SL spectrum was simulated for UV-Vis-IR spectrum (Figure 4b). Refractive index and reflection of multidimensional CB materials were implemented for SL simulation. Reflection coefficient of DGTWSIB was simulated for concealment of predicted camouflage textiles. The data information is referred to Tables SI 2 and SI 3. In Figure 4(c), refractive index of dry leaves, 1.53 (Wooley, 1975); green leaves, 1.4; water, 1.33 (Jacquemoud & Baret, 1990); sand, 1.50 (Kusaka et al., 2000); stone, 1.50 (Noda, 1955); snow, 1 (Sadiku, 1985); tree bark, 1.58 (Needham, 1924); sky, 1.50 (Yamasoe et al., 1998), ice (Gosse et al., 1995) of DGTWSIB was synthesized against n value in UV-Vis-IR spectrum. The calculation and simulation were exposed without consideration of wavelength variation (Jacquemoud & Baret, 1990; Sadiku, 1985), instrumental deviation related to illumination, density of materials (Dararutana et al., 2009), temperature (Jellison & Burke, 1986), moisture (Sadiku, 1985) of n -DGTWSIB due to limitation of data information. Mean reflection (Kerekes & Baum, 2003) between UV-Vis-IR (Figure 4b) and reflection of CB materials (Figure 4d) were assumed as reflection of DGTWSIB in UV-Vis-IR. Reflection difference, R_n ($\pm 3\%$) of SL-DGTWSIB, was simulated as camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-IR in terms of SL symmetry. The assuming value of R_n (Yuen & Richardson, 2010) was supported by related research output in literature. 5% error was also considered

Figure 4. Calculated spectra of n in UV-Vis-IR (100–10,000 nm) illumination based on sun radiation and E (a); modelled spectra of R in UV-Vis-IR illumination based on sun radiation (b); n spectra of DGTWSIB (c); R spectra of DGTWSIB (d).

for every calculation of n , R and R_n . Accordingly, n - R -DGTWSIB-wavelength (nm) spectra were illustrated.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Theoretical model of HSI-SL-OB-CDRI identification in UV-Vis-IR

In Figures 5, 6 (left), A, B, C and D are as simulated “eleven CB/location” and camouflage textiles (middle) as “combat target signature” in every OB environment of combat location. Typical reflection versus SL symmetry between OB is represented by “arrow-angle” mark. HSI, FTIRS and NIRS can be implemented for spectral analysis of camouflage textiles (target object) and DGTWSIB materials when absorption spectra are related to concentration and pathlength by the Beer–Lambert law (Equation 7).

$$A_\lambda = \epsilon_\lambda c l, \quad (7)$$

where A_λ = absorption at wavelength λ ; ϵ_λ = extinction co-efficient at wavelength λ ; c = concentration; l = path-length through OB.

The value of A_λ , ϵ_λ , c , l are the factors of ATR-SL for CDRI against DGTWSIB in UV-Vis-IR illumination, as indicated in Figure 5 (right; b, d, f, h, j, l) and Figure 6 (right; b, d, f, h, j, l) (Garside, 2002). Unlike other spectroscopic method, HSI spectrometry can be implemented for spatial/physical scene analysis of OB environment which is theoretically and typically defined in Figure 5 (left; a, c, e, g, i, k) and Figure 6 (left; a, c, e, g, i, k). Thus, HSI spectrometry may be a newly practiced method for SL synthesise, pixel analysis and CDRI assessment of camouflage properties on textile substances and CB environment. Camouflage treated textiles can be scanned by a point scanning method. Hyperspectral images can be assessed by image analysis of different pixel and sub-pixel of image and the analysis can be converted to quantitative color analysis for CDRI because HPC cannot provide quantitative color directly like color measurement spectrophotometer. Identification of chromophore components like carbonyl group ($>C=O$), azo group ($-N=N-$), nitro group ($-N=O$), thio-ketone group ($-C=S$), nitrite group ($-NO_2$), benzene group

(C_6H_6), conjugated dienes ($-C=C-C=C-$), conjugated trienes ($-C=C-C=C-C=C-$), conjugated tetraene ($-C=C-C=C-C=C-C=C-$), auxochromic components like hydroxyl group ($-OH$), amino group (NH_2), aldehyde group (CHO), methyl mercaptan group ($-SCH_3$), carboxylic group ($-COOH$), sulfonic group (SO_3H) and/or other groups in different spectral band of UV-Vis-NIR-MIR may clarify the intensity of chromatic compound versus spectral signal for CDRI on textile surfaces against DGTWSIB. The composition of colored complexes with multidimensional RGB chromatic hue are also ascertained by spectrophotometry. The molar absorptivity of OB materials can be calculated as sensitivity S in Equation 8.

$$(S) = n \left(\frac{M}{\epsilon} \right), \quad (8)$$

where M = molecular weight; n = number of atoms of the element; and ϵ = molar absorptivity of OB materials (Khopker, 2004).

The value of molar absorptivity/reflectivity indicates the spectral identification of colored compounds on the surface of camouflage textiles (target signature) and DGTWSIB/surrounding environment. Thus, the critical color variation, R-SL similarity (Figures 5, 6), R-SL dissimilarity may elucidate the OB-CDRI assessment for camouflage textiles.

4.2. Model of camouflage textiles-DGTWSIB and simultaneous combat location

4.2.1. Adaptive camouflage textiles against DGTWSIB

In Figure 5(a) (b), the perception of adaptive camouflage textiles has been generated for camouflage textiles in different environment and combat location. In the primary stage, laboratory scale assessments of adaptive camouflage textiles may be supported by optical-ATR of CB materials, DGTWSIB and other surrounded background materials for CDRI measurement. The SL and color compound analysis of physical background can be compared with camouflage treated textiles. Reflection of OB materials should be related to imaging signal of HPC sensor. The materials contrast/chromatic properties

Figure 5. Simulation of OB-R (left; a, c, e, g, i, k), and SL (right; b, d, f, h, j, l) for camouflage textiles assessment of adaptive (a, b); desertland (c, d); stoneland (e, f); marine (g, h); sky (i, j) and ice-land (k, l) CB.

can be analyzed by SL in UV-Vis-IR. In the secondary stage, the laboratory scale experimentation can be validated by field trialling, and it can be done by HPC. A symmetric SL may signify the adaptive camouflage textiles against DGTWSIB. Adaptive camouflage textiles can be assessed by HPC in different combat location and environment. Figure 5(a) (b) depicts the SL-R and simulation of camouflage textiles in multidimensional CB, DGTWSIB, 100–10,000 nm. The simulation of adaptive camouflage textiles has been remarked as target signature. The R-SL of DGTWSIB have been simulated with target signature (camouflage textiles). The SL-CDRI of CB and camouflage treated textiles can be evaluated by R assessment. SL symmetry may signify concealment of target camouflage textiles. The simulated plot shows a gradual variation in R-SL, i.e.

$UV < Vis < NIR < MIR$. This model seems theoretically validated for CDRI assessment of OB materials and/or OB environment. Reflection in 220 nm looks higher due to n variation of DGTWSIB.

4.2.2. Camouflage textiles for desertland and stoneland CB

In Figure 5(c, d, e, f), the sand and stone surrounded OB environment is compared with desert camouflage textiles. In laboratory scale assessments, SL and chromatic compound analysis can be demonstrated by SL. Sand and stone CB is simulated for light R, transmittance, and scattering in OB environment. For field trial simulation in combat location,

Figure 6. Simulation of OB-R (left; a, c, e, g, i, k); and SL (right; b, d, f, h, j, l) for camouflage textiles assessment of multidimensional CB/location. Snowland (a, b); woodland-tree bark (c, d), green tree leaves (e, f), dry tree leaves (g, h); simultaneous marine and woodland (i, j) and simultaneous marine and desertland (k, l).

the sand surface may have different wave due to winding, and the stone surface has structural deviation. In addition, sunlight and temperature also affect such CB. Texture of background surface creates wavelength variation which may influence SL-CDRI. The SL vibration of HPC can be evaluated in OB environment for CDRI of desertland and stone-land camouflage textiles.

4.2.3. Camouflage textiles for marine CB

In Figure 5(g, h), water background is considered as marine background against marine camouflage textiles. R and chromatic analysis are possible to evaluate by SL. Chromatic hue of water in marine environment is normally and

significantly influenced by sky background. For marine camouflage, sky color effect and weather should be considered. Wind speed and water wave are also key factors for the assessment of marine camouflage textiles. Therefore, field trials are a more appropriate technique for marine camouflage textiles. Figure 5(g, h) identifies the CB of water. SL has been depicted from 100 to 10,000 nm for concealment of target signature. The spectral vibration can be evaluated for CDRI of marine camouflage textiles.

4.2.4. Camouflage textiles for sky CB

In Figure 5(i, j), the OB environment of sky was simulated for sky background camouflage textiles. For assessments of

sky camouflage textiles, a simultaneous process of laboratory and field trials should be conducted. In laboratory scale assessment, the sky color in different environment can be photographed by hyperspectral camera. The SL and imaging signal may be the data information for designing such camouflage textiles. Refractive index of sky background was partially considered for this simulation and discussion. Photographic color can be assessed by imaging and color measurement, and chromatic group can be assessed by SL. For field trialling, aircraft/parachute/artificial kite can be used for placing camouflage textiles as a target object. Figure 5(i, j) shows the simulation of sky background. The SL-R technique has been implemented for assessment of sky background camouflage textiles. Similarly, the spectral vibration can be evaluated for CDRI of sky camouflage textiles.

4.2.5. Camouflage textiles for iceland CB

In Figure 5(k, l), ice background is considered as a military combat zone in a geographical region. In laboratory scale assessments, spectral analysis between camouflage textiles and ice surface can be scanned in the initial development process to clarify the spectral trend. There is a difference between individual typical surface of ice and the original natural view of ice in the actual location of surrounded background. Texture is not the same due to structural variation of ice surface, but SL of compositional behavior should be almost similar. Hence, assessment of ice land camouflage textiles needs field trialling for ice texture, location and environmental effect for SL and its contrast level identification. HPC-SL and physical scene are the right way of such types of camouflage assessment in UV-Vis-IR. Figure 5(k, l) depicts the model of ice background. CDRI-SL-OB has been illustrated for camouflage textiles assessment in different wavelength. The SL vibration has been depicted for CDR measurement of iceland camouflage textiles.

4.2.6. Camouflage textiles for snow and woodland CB

In Figure 6(a, b), the SL and contrast level has been matched with simulated camouflage textiles for CDRI. In nature, snow is related to multidimensional features of texture on background surface (trees, soil, sand, stones, houses, seaside, etc.), where field trials are needed for experimentation. The HPC-SL assessment process can be used for contrast level identification of snowland camouflage textiles. Figure 6(a, b) shows the SL of simulated camouflage textiles in different wavelength. The spectral vibration can be evaluated for CDRI of desert camouflage textiles.

In Figure 6(c, d, e, f, g, h), camouflage textiles in the woodland/forest-OB environment were simulated as woodland camouflage textiles. Laboratory scale assessments of woodland camouflage textiles are related to SL between camouflage textiles and woodland parameters (tree barks, green and dry tree leaves, etc.). In field trialling, texture, location, environmental effect, and chromatic hue can be assessed by HPC-SL in UV-Vis-IR. Figure 6(c, d, e, f, g, h) demonstrate the SL of camouflage textiles in 100-10000 nm. The spectral vibration can be evaluated for CDRI of woodland camouflage textiles.

4.2.7. Camouflage textiles for simultaneous CB

Every simultaneous CB should consider materials reflection properties of both backgrounds. In Figure 6(i, j, k, l), the target signature shows camouflage in simultaneous environments of water and woodland background. The OB was simulated as simultaneous combat zone of marine and woodland camouflage textiles. In the same way, a combined environment of sand and water background camouflage textiles was also considered for simultaneous military fighting location of desert and marine OB environment. Sometimes, a target object that is behind woodland area and marine zone needs simultaneous marine and woodland camouflage textiles in different geographical position. In laboratory stage, chromatic hue, structural and spectral analysis should be experimented for simultaneous material properties OB-CDRI. Field trialling and SL in different distances may clarify the validity of camouflage in terms of texture of OB, environmental effects (like wind), sky conditions, weather, chromatic hue etc. Sand and water background represent the surrounding background for simultaneous concealment of desert and marine camouflage textiles. Similarly, woodland and water demonstrate the background for simultaneous concealment of desert and woodland camouflage objects. Similar reflection between background (sand, water, woodland) and target object (camouflage textiles) may generate SL symmetry and camouflage identification in terms of CDRI.

5. Conclusion

Every DGTWSIB material is a component of R-SL for remote sensing technique and CDRI. Sun radiation is also common parameters for defense CDRI. Therefore, R-sun radiation-SL-CDRI was prioritized in this theoretical simulation. The simulation of R-SL-DGTWSIB may generate an innovative solution for concealment of hyperspectral imaging spectrometry. Sequentially a laboratory and field trialling concept has been presented. SL assessment of camouflage textiles and surrounding CB (natural/artificial substances) can be performed using HPC, NIRS, and FTIRS. This theoretical explanation represents that HPC-SL can make use of laboratory scale assessment and field trialling assessment of camouflage textiles using the same chromatic, achromatic and illumination parameters in UV-Vis-IR, which cannot be experimented by other methods of spectrometric assessment. HPC-SL assessment is the proposed way for CDRI measurement in UV-Vis-IR against modern sensor practiced by defense surveillance. FTIRS provides colored compound data versus SL data in the spectral range 1000–2500 nm, while HPC and NIRS cannot cover more than 2500 nm. NIRS provides color compound data in the spectral range 750–2500 nm and HPC also covers the spectral range 400–2500 nm. As per discussion of hypothesis and DGTWSIB-SL-OB-UV-Vis-IR simulation of combat location, SL-CDRI has been technically clarified for camouflage textiles assessment. In addition, SL based lab trialling and field trialling may clarify expected outcome which may be an efficient way of method design for camouflage textiles. This simulation covers a possible outcome and guideline for assessment technique against DGTWSIB. Therefore, step by step implementation of CDRI needs to continue in a broader scale and it may enhance

CDRI technique of camouflage textiles to defend any modern optical sensor in UV-Vis-IR.

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Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background

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Abstract

Chromatic and achromatic (AC) assessments of camouflage textiles have been critical to the defense researchers for concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI) of target signature against multidimensional combat background (CB). AC assessment and camouflage measurement techniques are simulated and experimented for assessment of camouflage textiles against CB. This model has been demonstrated for color measurement spectrophotometer, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), digital imaging, hyperspectral imaging, and image processing software (ImageJ) for the advancement and establishment of AC camouflage textiles assessment. The chromatic variations of 48 artificial target objects (TOBs) have been synthesized by image processing; the technique can be implemented for defense CB-CDRI assessment. Microstructural variation versus optical signal of woodland, desertland and stoneland CB materials have been elucidated by SEM magnification. The achromatic variation of CB materials have been demonstrated for the replacement of optical signal against modern remote sensing device to the imaging sensor. Color difference (ΔE), microstructural variations, pixel variations to imaging signal and standard deviation of CB materials have been represented for remote sensing surveillance of defense applications against TOB-CB-CDRI. Technical simulation of color, texture, gloss, and pixel intensity has been derived for AC-CDRI assessment of camouflage textiles in TOBs-CB environment.

Keywords

Camouflage textiles, chromatic, achromatic, hyperspectral, combat background, image processing

1. Introduction

Chromatic and achromatic (AC) assessments are the most important part of camouflage engineering versus modern remote sensing for contrast and matching between target object (TOB) and combat background (CB) environment in terms of concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI) of target signature.¹ Camouflage assessment with field trailing is a common technique for defense applications, but the accuracy of AC assessment is a critical task due to interference of natural illumination (sun light). AC assessment model have been designed for accuracy of color measurement versus image processing, texture deviation versus textile objects, and CB materials against simulated TOB-CB. Illumination of CB materials have been characterized to generate a concept on structural deviation for CDRI against woodland, desertland, and

stoneland CB. This research concept is very vital for every critical assessment of target signature against CB and the simulated model can be implemented for every CDRI assessment against high-performance photometric device, which are being applied in defense surveillance. Therefore, this article has been designed as laboratory stage research platform for AC research technique against camouflage textiles and CB.

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Image segmentation and pixel information are the acceptable technique for AC analysis in every combat environment.² Texture, standard deviation, color matching are the prime consideration of optical engineering to measure CDRI for assessment of AC adaptation between TOB and CB. Combat location of TOB can also be captured at different incident angles by digital camera imaging or hyperspectral imaging. TOB adaptation and AC assessment is achievable by image processing technique.³ Modeling of color measurement, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), hyperspectral imaging, image processing–segmentation–pixel intensity have been represented for AC assessments of camouflage textiles in TOB environment. The evaluation process of optical signal versus camouflage engineering needs to consider versatile AC parameters related to color intensity, color difference (ΔE), texture, spectral signal, pixel information, imaging technique, ultraviolet–visible–near infrared (UV–Vis–NIR) illumination, natural illumination, TOB materials, surrounding materials of target TOB, combined intensity of simultaneous combat location and surrounding materials, single CB, multidimensional CB, climate, season, and so on. Establishing the whole parameters in a single platform is a challenging task to design camouflage textiles for defense protection, but the constraints need to settle for designing and advancement of camouflage textiles, a laboratory stage decision may minimize the time to find the real constraints of concealment against multidimensional CB.

1.1. Chromatic assessment of CDRI for camouflage textiles against CB

Spectrophotometers can typically recover high-resolution spectral data, but the spatial component/physical scene of chromatic TOB is difficult to record simultaneously. Chromatic profile of woodland CB materials (woody stem materials, green leaves, and soil) are possible to scan by spectrophotometer from 300 to 700 nm.^{4–7} Imaging signal of woodland CB is determined by the type of leaf, absorption of chlorophylls, and microstructure of tissue.⁸ The concepts can be directly implemented for chromatic comparison between multidimensional CB and camouflage-treated textiles in TOB environment.

Total ΔE between target TOB can be assessed by CIE ΔE , Equation (1), as follows:⁹

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{(\Delta L^*2 + \Delta a^*2 + \Delta b^*2)} \quad (1)$$

NIR diffuse reflectance of TOB environments can also be analyzed by Kubelka–Munk theory, Equation (2), as follows:¹⁰

$$K/S = \frac{(1 - R_\infty)2}{2R_\infty} \quad (2)$$

where K and S represents absorption and scattering coefficients, respectively, and R_∞ denotes reflectance factor from an opaque object. Kubelka–Munk equation defines a relationship between spectral reflection (R) of TOB environment and its absorption and scattering characteristics. K/S shows spectral data in individual wavelength measurements. K/S tends to infinity when reflectance decreases to zero. Scattering of textile dyes or pigments depends on the properties of the substrate and absorption–transmission– R (ATR) mechanism of light depends on the properties of colorant.^{11–13} Gloss and color are associated with specular R of TOB surface. The change of specular R factors are manipulated by altering the specular angle,¹⁴ thus the view of TOB influences the CDRI for camouflage assessment.

1.2. Achromatic assessment of CDRI for camouflage textiles against CB

ATR mechanism of target TOB depends on their microstructural composition and texture.¹⁵ SEM can be used to characterize the surface, interface, and dynamic properties of TOB materials at the micron scale.^{16,17} SEM allows imaging the topography of surfaces both a greater resolution and higher depth of field to be studied in great detail of TOB and multidimensional CB materials.¹⁸ The image appearance depends on the surface structure and composition of TOB materials.¹⁹ Magnification of image may depict the structural deviation of TOB materials for microstructural intensity versus camouflage assessment. The resolution and depth of field have been mentioned in Equations (3) and (4) as follows:

$$\text{Resolution, } R = \frac{(0.61)\lambda}{\mu \sin(\alpha)} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Depth of field, } h = \frac{(0.61)\lambda}{\mu \sin(\alpha) \cdot \tan(\alpha)} = \frac{R}{\tan(\alpha)} \quad (4)$$

where, λ = wavelength of incident radiation (nm), μ = refractive index of medium between object and objective, and α = convergence semi-angle (rad). The measurement range 0.007–0.010 nm (approximately) differed to Vis–NIR (400–2500 nm), modern imaging sensor. Due to high vacuum and dehydration, wet CB materials cannot be fixed under electron beam.¹⁸

Imaging and measurement of gloss is also another part of TOB-CDRI.²⁰ Gloss is a visual attribute of color; gloss is determined by the surface smoothness and refractive index of the TOB materials. CB materials may be included in the glossy R of TOB. Surface provides qualitative information of TOB for CDRI.^{21,22} Depiction of CDRI appearance cannot be achieved by color alone; color, gloss, translucency, and texture may influence the microstructural appearance of TOB for CDRI.¹⁴ Standard gloss at

Figure 1. Methodology for AC assessment in TOB environment.

multidimensional angle is experimented by American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standard method D523.²³ A commercial glossmeter (Elcometer 400 Novo-Curve, Nova, MI, USA) was tested and evaluated for measuring the gloss appearance of CB at angle of 60° as specified in the ASTM D523 standard.²⁴ In 1971, CIE recommended four types of illumination and observation condition standards for the measurement R of TOB materials; they are $0^\circ/45^\circ$, $45^\circ/0^\circ$, $0^\circ/\text{diffuse}$, and $\text{diffuse}/0^\circ$.²⁵ Spectrophotometers are usually built based on one of these two kinds of geometry: $d/8^\circ$ (diffuse/8) and $45^\circ/0^\circ$ (specular excluded), so spectrophotometer cannot measure gloss reflectance at multidimensional angle of TOB materials.²⁶ Gloss characteristics critically influences TOB for CDRI measurement.²⁷ CIE lightness L^* falls with increasing gloss, except for the $0^\circ/\text{diffuse-IR}$ geometry, where L^* remains constant. The change occurs at relatively low gloss for the $0^\circ/45^\circ$ geometry, but at significantly higher gloss for the $0^\circ/\text{diffuse-IR}$ geometry. CIE chroma, C^* increases with increasing gloss.²⁸

In Figure 1, color measurement spectrophotometer (400–750 nm) can be used for quantitative analysis (L^* , a^* , b^* , ΔE) of TOB materials. Similarly, color quantitative analysis, color strength, and ΔE between TOB in limited NIR range are also achievable to assess by modification of diffuse reflectance in color measurement spectrophotometer. TOB image of hyperspectral or digital camera can be analyzed by image processing technique in terms of quantitative value (L^* , a^* , b^* , ΔE). SEM is an achromatic assessment technique, which is suitable for surface structure, texture, R , and scattering assessment of TOB materials in laboratory stage. Microstructural comparison of TOB materials is possible to experiment for CDRI measurement. Therefore, AC assessments of camouflage

textiles has been suggested in terms of quantitative analysis of color, surface texture analysis and image analysis.

2. Methodology of simulation for AC assessment

Chromatic synthesis of TOB, surrounding and patterning color; achromatic analysis of gloss, texture, and its chromatic replacement mechanism for camouflage assessment have been hypothetically defined, simulated, and experimented. Three-dimensional assessment (quantitative, qualitative, and partial) has been represented for CDRI of target signature.

2.1. Chromatic synthesis of simulated TOB for CDRI assessment of camouflage textiles against CB

A total of 48 artificial TOB environments were generated with color rendering (Vis–day light) when defense target is influenced by multidimensional background color of CB. The concept of scene geometry of TOB environment was supported by published model of imaging.²⁹ Forty eight “digital object of color” were placed against multidimensional CB color. CB was considered in terms of chromatic adaptation with surrounding CB color patterning which are the CDRI criteria of camouflage textiles. ΔE was experimented by image processing (ImageJ software) for CDRI measurement. A uniform gradient of object color was also maintained for imaging and ΔE . Therefore, the ΔE of CDRI was shown in both pictorial and graphical state. TOB simulation and camouflage assessment was supported by scene simulation of defense.³⁰ Chromatic properties of TOB environments are conceivable to characterize by color measurement spectrophotometer in Vis. Hyperspectral photographic image can be captured in UV–

Figure 2. Simulation of SEM magnification of TOB materials against CB.

Vis–NIR against multidimensional CB. ΔE , hue, saturation, and brightness are possible to calculate by image processing. Thus, quantitative ΔE of CIE L^* , a^* , b^* between TOB color was analyzed for artificial TOB environment.⁹ CIE ΔE of hyperspectral imaging was supported by Ariana and Lu.³¹ Chromatic differences of CIE L^* , a^* , b^* between camouflage objects (camouflage textiles) and CB substances (if the material is solid such as woodland, sand, ice, and so on) of visible and limited NIR ranges can be assessed by color measurement spectrophotometer. Image processing versus chromatic (L^* , a^* , b^*) analysis is also applicable for digital imaging and hyperspectral imaging. The value of n identifies (Equations (5) and (6)) the chromatic difference for CDRI of target signature against combat materials/imaging of TOB environment as follows:

$$\Delta E_{vis_{Camouflage}} = \Delta E_{vis_{Object}} - \Delta E_{vis_{background}} = n \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta E_{NIR_{Camouflage}} = \Delta E_{NIR_{Object}} - \Delta E_{NIR_{background}} = n \quad (6)$$

2.2. Achromatic analysis of simulated TOB for CDRI assessment of camouflage textiles against CB

Figure 2 shows simulation of SEM assessment with glass surface reference. The discrepancy of surface R has been defined with multiple texture for achromatic camouflage performance. A standard glass has been referred for microstructural deviation compared to surface. A_1 , A_2 , B_1 , B_2 , C_1 , and C_2 show simulated geometric surfaces of TOB-

CB, which can be illuminated by SEM magnification. A standard glass surface reference is shown in the middle for texture identification between TOB (camouflage-treated textiles) and CB materials. A_1 and A_2 identify similar surface of TOB as specular R. B_1 and B_2 indicate dissimilar surface of TOB as diffuse R. C_1 and C_2 depict the combination of specular and diffuse R. The electron interactions of specular and rough surfaces are not same due to polarization behavior of light R.^{22,32}

3. Methodology of experimentation for AC assessment

3.1. Chromatic (L^* , a^* , b^*) assessment of digital imaging and hyperspectral imaging for CDRI

A total 150 GSM, 100% cotton knitted fabric was dyed (exhaustion process – 60 °C to 60 min) with Remazol red RB-133 (Dystar Co., Ltd.). A piece of fabric; size: 4 inch \times 2 inch; chromatic value: $L^* = 31.89$, $a^* = 50.50$, $b^* = 23.44$; (45°/0°/400–700 nm/D₆₅/18 °C/colorflex EZ) was scanned (distance, 12 inch) by 13MP camera in 400–700 nm. Hyperspectral camera (30 cm focal lens, distance 208 mm), SWIR-384, Raymax Application Pty Ltd. was performed for NIR (1000 nm) scanning of fabric. Chromatic adaptation of NIR imaging (hyperspectral) and Vis imaging (digital camera) of a similar fabric surface have been presented for simulation of TOB assessment in Vis and IR ranges. L^* , a^* , b^* variation of Vis and NIR imaging has been compared on red color dyed fabric. Knitted fabric both in Vis and NIR image have been divided into L^* , a^* , b^* stack. The chromatic values were recorded by image analysis process with ImageJ software. The intensity of Vis and NIR imaging has been assessed by color threshold in ImageJ.³³

3.2. Achromatic assessment of CB materials for CDRI

SEM, TM 4000Plus, Tabletop Microscope, HITACHI, Japan was performed for achromatic assessment of CB materials. Woodland, desertland and stoneland CB materials were considered for achromatic assessment of CB materials. The sample of woodland CB, scientific name: *Ulmas minor* was collected from Princes Park, Melbourne in Autumn 2021, washed thoroughly, and dried. The samples of desertland and stoneland CB were collected from a local supplier. Green tree leaf, adaxial; green tree leaf, abaxial; dry tree leaf, adaxial; dry tree leaf, abaxial; tree bark; sand; and stone surface were scanned without further purification of materials after collection from natural sources. CB morphology (texture) was captured by SEM in 100 magnifications. For microstructural analysis of materials, a high acceleration of voltage (15 KV) was fixed for every scanning. SEM image of 1 mm thickness

glass surface was taken for comparison of texture/sharpness with CB materials. Image of glass surface was tried to be captured with 100 magnifications, but it was impossible due to lowest electron acceleration from the glass surface. The imaging signal of glass surface showed a white image in 100 magnifications, so the glass surface image was kept at only 25 magnifications to get a minimum visible imaging signal. Multidimensional CB materials (woodland, desertland, and stoneland) have been scanned with respect to incident electron beam to identify micro-structural deviation of CB surface. ImageJ software was performed for AC analysis of specular and diffuse R. Color threshold of SEM image was generated by ImageJ software. Red background, method-Otsu, color space—red, green, blue (RGB) are the parameters of color thresholding. Standard deviation of TOB can signify CDRI.³ Standard deviation of surface intensity was measured by histogram, ImageJ. SEM image was selected by rectangular shape and measured standard deviation of intensity. Pixel versus gray scale value was exported by plot profile of selected image in pixel range 0 to 255.^{2,34} The pixel range was automatically captured by software. Both standard deviation and pixel to pixel intensity³⁵ was recorded for the proportional R and chromatic signal concepts of CB in TOB environment.

3.3. Simulation of chromatic synthesis of TOB for CDRI assessment against CB

Figure 3 shows the pictorial variations of chromatic adaptation against multidimensional TOB. Figure 4 demonstrates the graphical variation of TOB- ΔE for quantitative measurement of CDRI. The chromatic values of L^* , a^* , b^* are recorded by image analysis process³⁶ of ImageJ software. Figures 3 and 4 show a common gradient principle of chromatic adaptation in terms of visual and quantitative practiced against CB environment in UV-Vis-IR camouflage textiles. Every CB color creates the tonal variation of TOB to the remote sensing device. Black, white, RGB are the common CB colors of CB. The CB colors black, white, and RGB depict the chromatic variation of a located “digital scene TOB” color.

In Figures 3(a) and 4(a), tonal variation of TOB color (day light) between A_1 and A_2 , B_1 and B_2 , C_1 and C_2 , D_1 and D_2 , E_1 and E_2 when different TOB of “grey color” tone ($A_1 = A_2$, $B_1 = B_2$, $C_1 = C_2$, $D_1 = D_2$, $E_1 = E_2$) are positioned on black CB on the left side and white CB on the right side. The principle of chromatic adaptation can be considered for camouflage assessment in TOB environment against CB. When the CB color black is darker than TOB color, the TOB looks lighter enhancing the visibility. When the CB color is lighter than the TOB color, the

TOB looks brighter and contrast. Variation of gray value (CIE L^* = the values from 0 to 100) between TOB and CB color depicts the lighter or brighter visibility of TOB. Lower the value of gray CB illuminates the lighter TOB to the remote sensing device. Higher value of gray CB shows the brighter TOB to the remote sensing device. In CIE coordinates, gray percentage (CIE L^* = the values from 0 to 100) moderates the absorption and R criterions of RGB color hue. It can be said that the value of L^* from 0 to 100 is controlling chromatic hue of a^* and b^* like red, green, yellow, and blue. When the chromatic hue of gray value of CB increases, absorption of light of TOB decreases, and light R accelerates. This mechanism changes the R of TOB color. Therefore, the TOB seems brighter against CB in day light. Oppositely when the chromatic hue of gray value of CB declines, absorption of light increases, which changes the R of TOB color and TOB looks lighter against CB in day light. Chromatic adaptation of black CB color is perfectly matched with TOB color A_1 , which creates the TOB completely in concealment with CB. Therefore, CDRI of target signature against CB can be rationalized in terms of chromatic variation between TOB and CB. CDRI of target signature = $\Delta E (n)$ = absorption and R difference between TOB. Practically zero ΔE between TOB in CB environment may be unattainable due to uncontrollable absorption and R of light between TOB. Minor ΔE between TOB may create invisible TOB. For same CB color, TOB- B_1 , C_1 , D_1 , E_1 are sequentially lighter in tonal variations like $B_1 < C_1 < D_1 < E_1$ and TOB visibility has been increased in same order as $B_1 < C_1 < D_1 < E_1$. In CIE color theory, $L^* = 0$ indicates black; $L^* = 100$ indicates white. The variation of L^* between 0 and 100 signifies the tonal variation of TOB. A black TOB absorbs all visible color tone and reflects a negligible amount of color to the observer; a white TOB reflects all visible color tone in an even combination manner to the TOB observer and the viewer cannot see any color, thus the color tone looks white. Hue and chroma of both TOB colors are changing when different shading effect of black/gray has been mixed with RGB. Therefore, chromatic adaptation of TOB should be considered for camouflage assessment of imaging signal. Grey scale, black to white controls the variation of different RGB color for making the TOB contrast or visible.

In Figures 3(b) and 4(b), tonal variation of TOB color (day light) between A_1 and A_2 , B_1 and B_2 , C_1 and C_2 , D_1 and D_2 , E_1 and E_2 when different TOB of “grey colors” tone ($A_1 = A_2$, $B_1 = B_2$, $C_1 = C_2$, $D_1 = D_2$, $E_1 = E_2$) are positioned on green CB on the left side and red CB on the right side. The basic principle of chromatic adaptation of RGB color can be considered for CDRI assessment against CB. Figures 3(c) and 4(c); tonal variation of TOB color

Figure 3. Simulation and synthesis of chromatic adaptation for TOB-CDRI against CB environment. Multidimensional chromatic hue of TOB against black and white background (a), green and red background (b), blue and yellow background (c), multidimensional surrounding color (d) and patterning principle of green tone as woodland CB (e, f) under RGB grey scale.

(day light) between A_1 and A_2 , B_1 and B_2 , C_1 and C_2 , D_1 and D_2 , E_1 and E_2 when different TOB of “grey colors” tone ($A_1 = A_2$, $B_1 = B_2$, $C_1 = C_2$, $D_1 = D_2$, $E_1 = E_2$) are placed on blue CB on the left side and yellow CB on the right side and the chromatic adaptation of RGB color is also variable for CDRI assessment. Surrounding unknown color of CB can also create tonal variation of CB. Figures 3(d) and 4(d) practically demonstrate that the critical variation in visual assessment on surface color when

surrounding color differs. “Round orange circle” is placed between A_1 and A_2 , B_1 and B_2 , C_1 and C_2 , D_1 and D_2 , E_1 and E_2 against multidimensional surrounding color. This creates a tonal variation of “round orange circle” color in visual assessment due to the R of surrounding CB. Tonal variation of TOB color “round orange circle” in visual assessment have been exposed when “round orange circle” is positioned between surrounding color ($A_1 = A_2$, $B_1 = B_2$, $C_1 = C_2$, $D_1 = D_2$, $E_1 = E_2$). The simulation of

Figure 4. ΔE -TOB-CB for quantitative color measurement of CDRI recorded by imageJ. Chromatic deviation between TOB-CB referred to Figure 3a (a), 3b (b), 3c (c), 3d (d), 3e (e), 3f (f).

“round orange circle” TOB color (day light) have been observed. The TOB appearance has been found a little bit changing in eye glance (the hue of first round circle, then second round circle, and hence one after one for observation of chromatic appearance) although the true color of “round orange circle” (object) is similar everywhere. The basic principle of chromatic variation of TOB on surrounding color may be considered for camouflage assessment against CB. The actual reflection of TOB color is trapped by reflection of surrounding color. Hence the trapping reflection between TOB signify CDRI against CB.

In Figures 3(e) and (f), 4(e) and (f), A_1 , A_2 , B_1 , B_2 , and C_1 and C_2 shows the TOB color on solid green CB (a chromatic simulation of woodland camouflage). B_1 and C_1 (two different light color) are solid color TOB and B_2 and C_2 (patterning with two color of B_1 and C_1) shows the patterning of TOB nearest tone (lighter) of CB. Both A_1 (black marked rectangular area and A_2 (black marked rectangular area) shows camouflage due to positioning the similar color TOB in middle of CB surface. The simulation represents the chromatic adaptation for indistinguishable TOB. Therefore, the chromatic deviation of camouflage-treated textiles (object darker or lighter) influences the CDRI. A lighter TOB on darker CB creates lighter background. Similarly, darker texture on lighter background creates lighter background. This mechanism is also influenced by geometry of TOB. TOB color A_1 , B_1 , C_1 shows the solid TOB on green background. TOB color B_2 and C_2 shows the patterning on green background. Solid color TOB A_2 and patterning TOB B_2 are concealed on green background color when TOB color is similar. The appearance of TOB color to the remote sensing device may be same when TOB colors are considered on same surface but practically it would be tough to be same appearance of TOB color due to different gloss of surface texture when dissimilar surface is considered in CB environment. For chromatic adaptation of TOB against CB, it can be recommended that background and TOB color should be nearest toning or TOB patterning color should be closest harmonizing with CB and surrounding of CB. Number of patterning/designing/texture color can be predicted for camouflage patterning based on the number of CB/surrounding color. Fabric can be treated with solid color for matching between TOB colors when CB and surrounding color depicts a single color. If CB is projected as multidimensional color, then it is difficult to make the fabric camouflage with solid color TOB if stimulus-changing materials/R-changing materials are not used on fabric surface in terms of CB environment.

3.4. Achromatic and microstructural (texture) simulation for CDRI assessment against CB

ΔE between A and B is found to be 4.12. The AC variation of C and D have been highlighted by “red color

Figure 5. Achromatic versus ΔE simulation for CDRI assessment against CB. a and b are almost same color surface, but texture is different. c, d identifies the color variation of a, b in threshold color red in image; e and f shows the structural deviation (three dimensional) of a and b surface in image].

background” in color threshold of ImageJ. The structural variation of E and F has been illustrated by three-dimensional surface plot in ImageJ. Changing of surface R illuminates the surface hue lightness or darkness, so the surface hue of same color on dissimilar surface is not same when the TOB is captured by hyperspectral imaging/digital imaging/color measurement spectrophotometer.²⁵ Rough surface creates artificial light trapping and replaces the ATR mechanism to the remote sensing device, hence chromatic/spectral signal is also changed in TOB environment. A standard glass surface can be used for comparison as reference of surface texture. The magnification of glass surface can be compared with the surface of camouflage textiles and its CB for identification of structural deviation. Therefore, the structural (texture) features between camouflage-treated textiles (TOB) and its CB substances may signify the achromatic behavior of camouflage assessment. A specular surface creates polarized R, and the

rough surface generates unpolarized R of light, hence the polarization changes color vision and imaging signal on TOB.²² Surface R alters the spectral signal and gloss of surface. Furthermore, chromatic aberration in rough surfaces (diffuse R) is normally higher because equal electrons cannot absorb all the surface and it may generate a blurred output of chromatic signal for the observations of TOB. Camouflage textiles and CB can be prejudiced by surface material properties in terms of color, gloss, translucency, transparency, and surface texture. The simulation of surface variations but tonal similarity in RGB (daylight) have been mentioned for structural effect of color in camouflage assessment.

4. Results and discussion of experimentation for AC assessment

4.1. Chromatic (L^* , a^* , b^*) analysis of digital camera imaging and hyperspectral camera imaging

Figure 6 describes the chromatic intensity versus ΔE versus color threshold of Vis–NIR image. Image was captured by two different cameras applied for defense surveillance. The chromatic intensity of Vis imaging shows $a^* > L^* > b^*$ and NIR imaging depicts $L^* > a^* > b^*$. The intensity of L^* , a^* , b^* is higher in Vis imaging than NIR imaging due to huge numbers of discernible unit (distortion of color) of color such as white and black (gray), red, green, yellow, blue. The blue portion of NIR image has been remarked as “zero” photon signal to the hyperspectral sensor. Unexpected crimping of fabric surface may generate such signal when fabric was scanned in continuous line scanning process. The blue portion of fabric surface captured by hyperspectral image has been mentioned by red color thresholding. A little portion of chromatic hue of red, green (a^*) and yellow, blue (b^*) captured in RGB aeromatic point of NIR imaging when the entire image is selected by ImageJ. Red ($+a^*$) is more prominent in Vis image. Green ($-a^*$) and gray (L^*) illuminates higher in NIR image. The intensity of red (a^*) and yellow (b^*) declined highly and the intensity of green ($-a^*$) accelerated in comparison with Vis image. The breakdown portion of different colors in hyperspectral imaging is not captured by L^* , a^* , b^* stack. The discernible unit of multidimensional colors have been captured as gray value in L^* , a^* , b^* stack, hence the L^* shows the maximum value in NIR image due to concentration of distorted color. The ΔE between Vis and NIR image has been found a value “116.24” with higher chromatic deviation which value is clearly defining that hyperspectral completely distorts the image compared in Vis image. So spectral signal is the more suitable way for CDRI measurement rather than image processing of hyperspectral

TOB. A partial assessment of TOB may be signified by color assessment process. The chromatic intensity concepts of L^* , a^* , b^* can be implemented in UV–Vis–NIR TOB for high-performance CDRI assessment.

Figure 7 image analysis method of hyperspectral image has been proposed by image analysis method of six standard references. The experimentation needs standard reference of black (L^*), white (L^*), red ($+a^*$), green ($-a^*$), yellow ($+b^*$), and blue ($-b^*$) color for comparison of NIR image (OB) with L^* , a^* , b^* stack. The more standard references of color and its hyperspectral imaging can signify the maximum accuracy of comparison between TOB images. The standard reference can identify the basic intensity of specific colors of hyperspectral imaging. Two-dimensional standard TOB, white and black substances,³⁷ can be used for RGB assessment of CDRI. For hyperspectral image assessment in UV–Vis–NIR; six-dimensional chromatic TOB (Figure 7) can be used for R and chromatic hue comparison between TOB (camouflage textiles) and CB environment/surrounding. The technique can be implemented for CDRI of camouflage textiles in laboratory and field experimentation.

4.2. Achromatic analysis of CB materials by SEM and image processing

Achromatic analysis of woodland, desertland, and stoneland CB materials have been represented by SEM and image processing. The structural variation of CB is related to chromatic signal to remote sensing device for defense surveillance. Figure 8 shows SEM image of woodland, desertland, and stoneland CB materials, which are green tree leaf, adaxial, Figure 8(a); green tree leaf, abaxial, Figure 8(b); dry tree leaf, adaxial, Figure 8(c); dry tree leaf, abaxial, Figure 8(d); tree bark, Figure 8(e); sand surface, Figure 8(f); stone surface, Figure 8(g); and glass surface, Figure 8(h). SEM stubs and sample preparation as shown in Figure 8(i) has been shown on the right side of SEM image. The microstructural variations of SEM image are also demonstrated by three-dimensional structural variation of “CB-glass surface.” Color thresholding (Figure 9), gray value versus pixel (Figure 10), and standard deviation (Figure 11) of SEM image (Figure 8) have been illustrated as more clarification and optical indication of microscopic view. These methods can be implemented for structural versus optical indication of camouflage-treated textiles against CB. Every optical signal is related to specular or diffuse reflection, which are generated by microstructural condition of TOB against CB. An accurate structural assessment of CB-OB materials has limitation by field trailing due to limitation of known and unknown interference in CB environment. The optical indication of digital camera or hyperspectral camera has influence of

Figure 6. L^* , a^* , b^* versus ΔE versus color threshold interpretation of Vis–NIR image.

outside illumination. There is also issue of unknown interference in specific CB environment. Hence the accuracy of optical indication may be hampered for CDRI against CB. SEM magnification of CB-OB has feasibility of more

accurate optical indication under specified optical condition in laboratory. Figure 9 clearly illustrates the structural variation of multidimensional CB materials such as green tree leaf, adaxial, Figure 9(a); green tree leaf, abaxial,

Figure 7. A technical approach of CDRI measurement for hyperspectral imaging.

Figure 9(b); dry tree leaf, adaxial, Figure 9(c); dry tree leaf, abaxial, Figure 9(d); tree bark, Figure 9(e); sand surface, Figure 9(f); stone surface, Figure 9(g); and glass surface, Figure 9(h); recorded by ImageJ. Microstructural variations of CB materials have been remarked with arrow sign against glass surface. The significant concept of energy versus optical signal has been depicted for variation of imaging signal against CB.

The intensity variation of “microstructural gray value versus CB versus glass surface” has been marked with arrow sign. Figure 10(a) and (b), gray value of green tree leaf, adaxial; and green tree leaf, abaxial differs due to cuticular line mark on the surface of leaf. Figure 10(c) and (d), similarly, adaxial and abaxial of dry leaf also changed due to angular variation of electron signal. It has been shown that electron angle is changed in same leaf surface between adaxial and abaxial. Gray value vibration of green tree leaf, abaxial is higher from 50 to 150 pixels and completely opposite direction has been observed. Comparatively, gray value difference was significant in 50–200 pixels for dry tree leaves, abaxial. Figure 10(e), gray intensity of tree bark was completely different at 100-pixel region. The change of intensity may materialize because of micro trapping of electron on uneven tree bark surface, hardness of surface, and lignin in wooden materials. In Figure 10(f), intensity of sand particle has been clearly highlighted due to fine particle size; electron beam covered the whole area of sand particle. In Figure 10(g), electron on stone surface was scattered in the entire pixel of imaging signal. Sand and stone surface signify various textures of desertland and stoneland CB. It may be

depicted that scattering of electron channel is predominantly accelerated on sand and stone surface. In Figure 10(h), scattering of electron is remarkably vibrated on glass surface. “Standard glass surface” showed a significant comparison with CB materials in microstructural variations. The intensity of “standardized glass surface” may confirm the correct value of gray scale and the intensity variation in microstructural texture against CB. The intensity of glass surface is very minor at whole pixel region from 0 to 180. Therefore, the microstructural parameters of camouflage-treated textiles can be compared with CB materials in laboratory scale. Microstructural variations of TOB-CB materials signify the scattering type of reflection. Reflection of TOB-CB is a core parameter of CDRI assessment. The structural variation is possible to attain in a specified energy signal of SEM magnification, which is directly related to light striking capability of optical engineering and CDRI of target signature against CB.

Figure 11 has been depicted as standard deviation of intensity of SEM image of multidimensional CB such as green tree leaf, adaxial, Figure 11(a); green tree leaf, abaxial, Figure 11(b); dry tree leaf, adaxial, Figure 11(c); dry tree leaf, abaxial, Figure 11(d); tree bark, Figure 11(e); sand surface, Figure 11(f); stone surface, Figure 11(g); and glass surface, Figure 11(h). The standard deviation of intensity is also signifying the microstructural deviation between glass surface and CB materials. Standard deviation of intensity also confirms the imaging variation in gray scale. The intensity of tree bark and sand is significantly higher than woodland and stoneland CB materials. Pixel versus gray value variation refers to intensity

Figure 8. SEM image of woodland, desertland, and stoneland CB. (a) Green tree leaf, adaxial; (b) green tree leaf, abaxial; (c) dry tree leaf, adaxial; (d) dry tree leaf, abaxial; (e) tree bark; (f) sand surface; (g) stone surface; and (h) glass surface.

variation. The intensity deviation refers to chromatic variation to the imaging sensor against CB. The variation of electron response of SEM imaging differs between TOB materials and signify the CDRI. Imaging color is the

intensity of pixel. Intensity of few pixels generates imaging signal of TOB to the sensor of remote sensing device. Pixel intensity of SEM imaging is obviously correlated to the imaging signal and chromatic appearance of CB-OB

environment.³⁴ The intensity of woodland, desertland, and stoneland CB materials need to be considered for every designing aspect of camouflage textile.

Figures 8(a)–(g), 9(a)–(g), 10, and 11; adaxial and abaxial of leaf in both green and dry condition, and tree bark of woodland CB; sand surface of desert CB; stone surface of stoneland CB demonstrates the microstructural variation of texture. Consequently, different surface of CB generates optical variability and spectral replacement;⁷ spectral changing reinstates the chromatic signal of TOB-CDRI. Every scattering occurs beginning with electron interaction of materials particle from TOB source. The engineering of electron behaviors (OB) impacts any surveillance imaging for CDRI against CB. TOB imaging response mostly depends on texture.¹⁵ Furthermore, physical and micro structural characterization of particle diameter, morphological effect of TOB surface can be analyzed by SEM imaging for the assessment of CDRI. In laboratory assessment, surface texture of TOB (solid materials) can be critically analyzed by cone-shaped convergent electron beam of SEM magnification. Discrepancy of particle size on textile or CB surface creates diffuse scattering; whereas, a smooth surface creates specular scattering. Scattering creates pixel variation and standard deviation of intensity. Structural mechanism on TOB (camouflage-treated textiles) and CB (solid materials such as sand, stone, leaves/bark) generates altering the R and color hue changing in UV–Vis–IR imaging. Angle of R changes the wavelength and wavelength replaced the pixel variation to the chromatic appearance of TOB. Therefore, chromatic changing can be assessed in terms of microstructural surface/texture variation. Image processing technique is applicable to measure sharpness and intensity between selected TOB and selected CB materials in terms of standard glass surface. SEM and its image processing discriminate the intensity of CB materials for CDRI assessment of target signature. The detector of SEM captures the genuine image through radiation of TOB materials in a controlled angle, which cannot be measured by any other instrument. In general, microstructural texture/surface analysis of TOB, compositional characteristics, structural appearance of camouflage materials on textile surface, high resolution imaging can characterize the physical and chemical mechanism of CDRI, and microstructural and optical assessment in laboratory.

5. Conclusion

AC characteristics of TOB-CB materials are essential for design of camouflage textiles. Method design confirms that AC variation of TOB creates the replacement of optical intensity. The intensity may generate wavelength variation to the imaging sensor. Hence the replacement of chromatic signal is reflected to the imaging sensor/

Figure 9. Structural variations of woodland, desertland, and stoneland CB. (a) Green tree leaf, adaxial; (b) green tree leaf, abaxial; (c) dry tree leaf, adaxial; (d) dry tree leaf, abaxial; (e) tree bark; (f) sand surface; (g) stone surface; and (h) glass surface.

perception of TOB appearance. A complementary combination between TOBs is the key mechanism for design of camouflage textiles. AC camouflage textiles assessment criteria depends on TOB-CB and combat location. The AC assessment of target signature (textiles) against CB can be performed using digital camera, hyperspectral camera, color measurement spectrophotometer, SEM, gloss meter, and image-processing software. Color measurement spectrophotometer offers a quantitative color analysis for TOB, but this instrument has a limitation in providing gloss/surface R data of TOB under different angles of incidence. Glossmeter can be used for measurement of surface gloss at different angles. Thus, the critical analysis of AC camouflage textiles can be assessed using existing instruments. Color measurement spectrophotometer for RGB chromatic hue assessment with CIE L^* , a^* , b^* ; glossmeter for achromatic assessment of light R at different angles, SEM for microstructural deviations between TOB materials. Image analysis is a quantitative analysis method that can be used for AC camouflage textiles assessment in

Figure 10. Grey value versus pixel of woodland, desertland and stoneland CB. The grey value versus pixel of multidimensional CB materials green tree leaf, adaxial (a); green tree leaf, abaxial (b); dry tree leaf, adaxial (c); dry tree leaf, abaxial (d); tree bark, (e); sand surface, (f); stone surface, (g) and glass surface, (h); recorded by image].

UV-Vis-NIR imaging. It can be summarized that CDRI has been clarified in multidimensional way for camouflage textiles assessment in terms of physical properties of TOB in laboratory stage such as TOB synthesized,

microstructural analysis, image analysis. Every laboratory stage decision is expected to be correlated for real outcome of field experimentation against remote sensing device.

Figure 11. Standard deviation of intensity of woodland, desertland, and stoneland CB.

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Author biography

Md Anowar Hossain started his coloration research in 2010 as coloration professional in Mascom Composite Ltd. Dhaka, Bangladesh. He did his MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) from Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India. He started his academic platform of research on textile coloration in 2014 under Professor AK Samanta, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta. He did his coloration research practice in Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh under Professor Md. Nurul Abser and Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. He also did his coloration practice as coloration professional/academician in different reputed industries/universities in Bangladesh. He self-designed his ongoing research on camouflage coloration versus CB, which is a new concept of camouflage engineering. He has few publications of research article, book chapter, books as contribution of first author/single author circulated by national and international publishers, mostly focused on color science and camouflage technology. Currently, he is a registered PhD researcher under the supervision of Professor Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor Robert Shanks in the area of defense textiles and coloration concentrating on camouflage textiles and primarily focusing on camouflage physics in terms of textile coloration and combat background.

Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums

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Abstract

Visible and near infrared spectra of “sixteen materials for textile coloration/finishing/patterning” such as titanium dioxide, calcium oxide, aluminum, tin metal, tin oxide, iron powder, boron carbide, magnesium powder, carbon black pigment, titanium carbide, isolan black 2S LDN, isolan orange, telon blue A 2R, telon red A 2R, telon violet 3R, and telon yellow A 2R; and ‘nine materials of combat backgrounds (CBs) such as dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark-woodland CB; water-marine CB; sand-desertland CB; stone-stoneland CB; snow-snowland CB; sky CB; and ice-iceland CB (DGTWSIB) are obtained by Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometry and colorflex EZ spectrophotometer. A method of ‘Monte Carlo cross validation’ was applied for spectral simulation in visible and near infrared spectrums through experimental data information. The characterized reflection spectra of zero reflection (ZR), low reflection (LR), high reflection (HR), and HR–LR (HLR) materials are coalesced and simulated for camouflage materials design and textile applications against multidimensional CBs, DGTWSIB. The reflections of aluminum, titanium dioxide, calcium oxide, tin metal, tin oxide, and iron powder are irradiated as HR materials. Oppositely boron carbide, magnesium powder, carbon black pigment, and titanium carbide are illuminated as LR materials. Consequently, the mixing principle of HR and LR materials are also classified as HLR materials. Spectral properties of CB materials are also depicted as ZR materials against selected CBs. Spectral signal of ZR, LR, HR, and HLR materials are identified as more expedient camouflage materials for concealment of target signature than six selected synthetic dyes such as Isolan Black 2S LDN, Isolan Orange, Telon Blue A 2R, Telon Red A 2R, Telon Violet 3R, and Telon Yellow A 2R. The reflection spectra of ZR, LR, HR, and HLR materials are simulated and correlated against DGTWSIB in visible and NIR spectrums. Simulated spectral signals are considered for camouflage materials design and camouflage textiles formulation against DGTWSIB combat location, the CBs are mostly practiced by defence professional. Furthermore, the reflection principle of camouflage textiles coloration/finishing/patterning has been accumulated under spectral signal of DGTWSIB, camouflage materials and synthetic dyes, synthetic dye–metal and synthetic dye–pigment combination. Therefore, depth analysis and graphical results of ZR, LR, HR, and HLR materials are the potential findings for selection of camouflage materials, right development of camouflage textile products, and camouflage assessment of hyperspectral imaging for defence protection in the entire spectrums of UV–Vis–IR. This optical parameters of ZR, LR, HR, and HLR materials have also applications to the materials community of multidimensional branches of material research.

Introduction

Recent technologies of camouflage textiles are not limited to eye vision and color matching because of modern sensor-based surveillance in ultraviolet (UV)–visible–near infrared (NIR) spectrums.^[1] Spectral comportment in object-background (OB) environment is a very significant part for defence analysis of concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI) of target signature.^[2,3] Spectral signal matching is the method of target concealment against modern sensor-based defence surveillance. Spectral reflection of textile dyes, pigment, nanomaterials, and CB materials are not symmetrical, it depends on material properties.^[4–6] So, the spectral reflectivity and camouflaging physics need to be measured at first attempt for camouflage textiles coloration against every OB material of combat environment. It is conceivable to invent chromatic materials spectra against dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark-woodland CB; water-marine CB; sand-desertland CB; stone-stoneland CB; snow-snowland CB; sky CB and ice-iceland CB (DGTWSIB). Spectral signal of visible–NIR need

to consider simultaneously for camouflage textiles coloration in visible–NIR.^[7–17] Spectral reflection is a very correlated term for CDRI measurement, similar spectral signals are required for matching/concealment and oppositely contrast signals are responsible for CDRI measurements in any OB environment. Color differences of large number of wavelengths cannot be contrasted/matched like spectral signals. Spectral matching and concealment techniques are correlated to the imaging signal for CDRI. Reflection spectra of OB materials are also correlated to CDRI.^[18–21]

Physical properties measurement is the acceptable way for CDRI measurement.^[22] Camouflage textiles coloration and camouflaging mainly depends on absorption–transmission–reflection (ATR) mechanism of target signature against CB materials.^[23] The technique of spectral simulation and camouflage materials design have been experimented for reflection of OB materials, it is mostly applied in combat environment.^[19,24–26] Hence, the technique of spectral matching and simulation of camouflage materials design are the most

appropriate approaches of camouflage textiles coloration compared with DGTWSIB* when the real experimentation and field trialing needs enormous time and cost involvement; still the ending stage of experimental work may not be succeeded for the expected outcome of camouflaging.

Spectral reflectivity of physical object-background materials are critically compared for the development of realistic concept on camouflage textiles formulation for simultaneous spectrum probe in visible–NIR spectrums. Synthesized spectral signal of synthetic dyes, zero reflection (ZR), low reflection (LR), high reflection (HR), HR–LR (HLR), and DGTWSIB materials will explore the appropriate camouflage materials design for camouflage textiles coloration aligned with single CB, simultaneous CB, multidimensional adaptive CB, and simultaneous spectrum probe in visible–NIR spectrums. An innovative method of spectral simulation is proposed for high-performance materials design of camouflage textiles coloration versus spectral formulation. The direct combat experimentation of DGTWSIB has uncertainty, complexity, cost involvement, and the decision making is a time-consuming process for defence professional. This materials design is applicable for design of camouflage textiles against modern remote sensing surveillance. Spectral matching and reflection mechanism is a prime consideration for the designing of high-performance camouflage textiles against hyperspectral camera. The utmost technique of spectrum probe-materials design will perform against any aspect of high-performance combat surveillance including hyperspectral camera. This is one of the leading approach of camouflage materials design and spectral analysis against reflections of DGTWSIB for camouflaging in visible–NIR spectrums without considering compound identification in spectral signal. The synthesis of materials reflection will signify the future movement of material design.

Experimental design and camouflage materials simulation against DGTWSIB

Exemption note of DGTWSIB materials (desertland and woodland) collection for trialing experimentation

Table SI, a minimum amount of desertland and woodland materials, around 100 g of each sample was collected from non-commercial sources and applied for an academic platform of camouflage research to propose a practicability for broader scale implementation in terms of combat materials, a fully non-commercial application. Therefore, permission of sample collection may not be required to conduct registered research located in Australia. The exemption may be supported by environment protection and biodiversity conservation (EPBC) act

* DGTWSIB: dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark-woodland CB; water-marine CB; sand-desertland CB; stone-stoneland CB; snow-land CB; sky CB and ice-iceland CB.

1999, compilation no: 52 is satisfied that the terms and conditions of the requirement for approval of activities involving the marine environment (23.1) “a person must not take in a Commonwealth marine area an action that has, will have or is likely to have a significant impact on the environment.” All experiments of woodland materials were conducted with accordance to relevant regulations and guidelines. Therefore, permission of woodland sample collection is not required. This exemption is supported by ‘3.1.2, assessment requirement’ for collection of woodland materials quoted as below, registered research located in Australia:

“A permit is not required to collect native plant material from private land, unless: the species for collection are listed threatened species or form part of a threatened ecological community under the EPBC Act, under such circumstances a commonwealth permit may be required.”^[27]

Materials overview for experimentation and simulation of camouflage textiles

Titanium dioxide, British Drug Houses Limited, England; calcium oxide, Unilab; aluminum, tin metal, tin oxide, iron powder, boron carbide, magnesium powder, carbon black pigment, titanium carbide, Sigma-Aldrich; isolan black 2S LDN, isolan orange, Bayer, Australia; telon blue A 2R, telon red A 2R, telon violet 3R, telon yellow A 2R, Dystar (Table SI. 1) were experimented for materials design of camouflage textiles coloration/formulation in visible–NIR spectrums. Deionized water; ice, snow, 100% water based; dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark, scientific name: *Ulmas minor*, Melbourne were collected in May 2021. Dry sand from Melbourne Sea beach and stone from local supplier, Melbourne were selected as target CB materials. DGTWSIB were included all possible combat location which are practiced by defence professional although combat environment depends on geographical region of country to country all over the world.

Spectral reflection measurement for camouflage materials design

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIRS), PerkinElmer, spectrum-400, NIR sample port: PODL 10033119 was performed for NIR (1000–2500 nm) reflection measurement. Reflection properties of sixteen materials (Table SI. 1) were performed for design of camouflage textiles coloration as textile materials. FTIRS of CB materials (Table SI. 1) were performed for physical reflection spectra of CB materials in combat location. All samples were scanned for NIR reflection from 1000 to 2500 nm. FTIRS of samples were tested by single scan and resolution 16 cm^{-1} . A common single striking data process was applied due to high level of infrared absorption for different materials such as carbon and carbonyl-based compounds.^[24] FTIRS glass container was used for measurement of diffuse reflections of liquid and powder samples.^[28] Woodland CB materials were simply washed by water and dried in sunlight until the surface water vanishes. Dry leaves, green leaves, and tree bark were cut into $3.81 \text{ cm} \times 3.81 \text{ cm}$. Deionized water

was scanned, and ice was also prepared by deionized water. Freeze-generated snow was used due to unavailability of natural snow during this experimentation. In visual appearance, snow looked brighter white like original snow. Every scan was conducted by covering with a standardized sample cup of spectrophotometer. A standard NIR background of energy was generated for NIR reflection measurement. Five-time spectral signal was compared for the confirmation of actual peak of every sample and one sample spectra was registered for spectral analysis under visual symmetry of spectral curve and accuracy of reflection measurement. Similarly, color measurement spectrophotometer, Colorflex EZ, HunterLab (A60-1016-344ver1.0) was used for visible reflection spectra of CB materials (Table SI. 1). Reflection properties of sixteen materials (Table SI. 1) were also tested for simulation of camouflage materials design. All materials were directly scanned by 45°/0°/400–700 nm/D₆₅/18°C method. Reflection spectra were recorded in terms of chromatic features of material surface. All powders and liquid materials were scanned by glass container. Although two different spectrophotometers have dissimilar relationship with different physics (such as specular, diffuse, illumination), there are some specific correlations which are compared in terms of visible–NIR reflection. The original reflection spectra of CB materials and textile materials have been cited as Supporting Information, Figs. 1–36.

Data acquisition versus spectral simulation for camouflage materials design

The modeling and data acquisition of mean reflection, mean wavelength, mean spectra, and spectral variables were validated and implemented by ‘Monte Carlo cross validation,’^{**} of spectral information, when data quantities were higher to interpret spectral model.^[29] Every FTIRS spectra were generated 3001 data value of reflections from 1000 to 2500 nm in 0.5 nm interval. It was difficult to implement every data value for best prediction and clarification of spectral signal in entire spectrums from 1000 to 2500 nm. Each FTIRS data were averaged at 100 nm interval from 1000 to 2400 nm. 1000 nm value is the mean reflection of 1000–1099.5 nm, 2400 nm value is the mean reflection of 2400–2499.5 nm, and subsequently mean data are generated to minimize spectral noise, accuracy, and clarification of real reflection spectra in NIR spectrums.^[30] Original value of every CB material and predicted textile materials were recorded in Tables SI 3, 4. All reflection value of Colorflex EZ was exported at 10 nm interval. Reflection spectra were represented from 400 to 700 nm in 20 nm interval for increasing the spectral clarification and minimizing the spectral noise, Tables SI 5,6.^[30] Reflection spectra of DGTWSIB were signified as ZR materials. After scanning few materials, aluminum,

titanium dioxide, calcium oxide, tin metal, tin oxide, and iron powder were characterized as HR materials.^[31] Similarly boron carbide, magnesium powder, carbon black pigment, and titanium carbide were categorized as LR materials which can be encapsulated-coated/printed on textile surface by suitable selection of synthetic binder.^[32–35] Established textile dyes of six different colors were selected which cover maximum spectral range of chromatic intensity in visible spectrums. Telon Violet 3R, Telon Blue A2R, Telon Yellow A2R, Isolan Orange, Telon Red A2R, and Isolan Black 2S LDN were identified as standard synthetic dyes.^[36] Mean spectra of ZR, LR, HR, and synthetic dyes were calculated for acquisition of simulated standard spectra of ZR, LR, and HR under spectral comparison with mean spectra of synthetic dyes.^[36,37] Simulated spectra of LR and HR were also labelled as combination of HLR. HLR spectra were developed by mean spectra of HR and LR. HLR materials have been predicted for simultaneous formulation of camouflage textiles coloration/finishing/printing. Therefore, mean reflection spectra of CB materials,^[1] dyes, metal, nanoparticle, and pigment materials were categorized into four-dimensional standard reflection for camouflaging such as ZR, LR, HR,^[31] and HLR. Camouflage reflection spectra were also predicted for the combination of HR materials and synthetic dyes, mixing of LR materials and synthetic dyes in terms of metal–dye coloration/finishing on textile surface.^[5,38,39]

Figure 1 shows the comparison of mean spectra of HR materials; mean spectra of LR materials; mean spectra of HLR materials; mean spectra of CB materials, ZR; mean spectra of synthetic dyes; mean spectra of synthetic dyes and LR materials; mean spectra of synthetic dyes and HR materials in visible–NIR spectrums. Therefore, four-dimensional reflection spectra of ZR, LR, HR, and HLR materials were typically considered for prediction of camouflage textiles against DGTWSIB. The original data information related to whole simulation have been mentioned in supporting information, Tables SI 3–6.

In graphical representation, reflection spectra were denoted as predicted camouflage textiles, ZR; predicted camouflage textiles, HR; predicted camouflage textiles, LR; and predicted camouflage textiles, HLR. Mean spectra of ZR were generated by mean reflection of CB materials^[36,37,40] in terms of spectral symmetry^[18] against dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark, sand, stone, sky, water, snow, and ice. Predicted camouflage textiles of every single CB were considered as mean reflection of $CB \pm n$,^[18] simulated value of n was calculated as 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and finally the value of n was signified as 5% when the simulated spectra showed almost nearest to single/mean CB spectrum.^[18,41] Two nearest simulated spectra of camouflage textiles were exported by putting the value of (\pm) 5% of mean CB, DGTWSIB. Therefore, the generated spectra of $CB \pm n$ were termed as ZR-1 and ZR-2 for concealment of target signature against CB.

Mean reflection spectra of LR materials were exported by mean reflection of boron carbide, magnesium powder, carbon black pigment, and titanium carbide. The arithmetic

^{**} Monte Carlo cross validation: ultraviolet and near infrared spectra of chemical compound are recorded to give more than several hundred variables.

Figure 1. Principle of methodology for simulation of camouflage textiles in visible (Vis) and NIR spectrums.

mean spectra of HR materials were formed by mean reflection of aluminum, titanium dioxide, calcium oxide, tin metal, tin oxide, and iron powder. Mean spectra of HLR materials were represented by mean reflection of HR and LR materials. Mean reflection spectra of textile-based synthetic dyes were created by Isolan Black 2S LDN, Isolan Orange, Telon Blue A 2R, Telon Red A 2R, Telon Violet 3R, and Telon Yellow A 2R. Similarly mean reflection spectra of synthetic dyes and LR materials were illustrated by mean reflection of synthetic dyes and LR materials. Mean reflection spectra of synthetic dyes and HR materials were also depicted by mean reflection of synthetic dyes and HR materials. Visible reflection of synthetic dyes was observed higher from 580 to 700 nm. NIR reflection of synthetic dyes were significantly higher in entire spectrums from 1000 to 2500 nm. The reflection spectra of synthetic dyes were identified almost nearest in related published results.^[2,42]

Mean reflection spectra of woodland CB were generated by mean reflection spectra of dry leaves, green leaves, and tree bark; ZR spectra of simultaneous woodland and marine CB were performed by mean reflection of woodland and water CB spectra. Consequently, ZR spectra of simultaneous woodland

and desert CB were designed by mean reflection of woodland and desertland CB. Mean reflection spectra of LR, HR, and HLR materials were signified as almost straight line than mean reflection spectra of synthetic dyes. Spectral signals of LR, HR, and HLR materials have less peak intensity for compound identification of target signature. Such materials can be experimented for camouflage textiles coloration/finishing/patterning. ZR materials are used as hypothetical term of camouflage textiles coloration in terms of CB materials. ZR materials are simulated for a speciality combination of similar reflection materials against specific CB. Textile materials can be directly treated with CB source materials or any other artificial materials which may signify almost similar reflection against CB. For example, natural plant-based natural dyes can be implemented for woodland CB and natural sand-based silicon dioxide can be applied for desertland CB.^[16,17]

Reflection measurements of snow and sky CB materials have been facing a critical issue for experimentation and simulation. Snow reflections were considered 5% higher than actual value as the whiteness index of snow is reduced at very few second. Due to technical limitation of sky CB measurement, the reflections of sky CB have been predicted

based on CB materials of sky. The average reflection of sky background materials were considered to signify sky reflection as the collection of original sky spectra is still limited in research.^[43] Therefore, snow, water, and ice reflection^[44] have been considered for cloud reflections. Sky CB is mostly covered by cloud.^[45] The reflection properties of sky CB are related to snow–water–ice reflection in general^[46,47] without considering other parameters related to interference of sky background. Sand, stone, water (sea), and water vapor reflection have been considered for earth surface reflection of sky.^[36,43,47,48] Nitrogen, mineral, and water containing green leaves reflection (green leaves have higher percentage of nitrogen) have been considered for atmospheric scattering of sunlight due to remaining higher percentage of nitrogen in atmosphere.^[47,49] Simulated spectral reflections of sky also support the spectral signals and water absorptions from 400 to 2000 nm.^[36] Therefore, sky CB was predicted based on the mean reflection value of snow, water, ice, sand, stone, and nitrogen containing green leaves reflection. The reflections of such materials are scientifically and putatively correlated with the reflection of sky CB. Deionized water reflections^[44] were used for simulation and considered as marine water reflection without considering salinity, and other properties of marine water such as reflection of water phytoplankton and ATR^{***} of mineral materials (such as salt) in marine water are out of this consideration. Two simultaneous combat locations were also considered for this simulation such as simultaneous marine and woodland CB, and simultaneous desert and woodland CB. Woodland CB was simulated as mean reflection of tree bark, green leaves, and dry leaves rather than individual comparison and data complexity. But with the seasonal consideration of woodland CB, it is also logical to compare individual reflection of CB in terms of tree bark, green leaves, and dry leaves. Spectral simulation^[49] and spectral reflection measurement of dyes, metal, nanoparticle, and pigment materials in 400–2500 nm can be adjusted with the analysis of spectral model which is also experimented by scholars.^[7,37]

Results and discussion

Established optical mechanism of Visible–NIR–OB–CDRI–ATR has been derived as the absorption of OB+ transmission of OB+ reflection of OB=1. Here, reflection is the core function for photonic response to the imaging device of hyperspectral/digital camera for CDRI of target signature against DGTWSIB in laboratory and field experimentations of camouflage textile assessment. Hence, spectral simulation of reflection has been approached for material design of camouflage textiles in terms of ZR–LR–HR–HLR property of materials.^[38,50]

Spectral simulation of adaptive, desertland, stoneland, and marine camouflage textiles in visible–NIR spectrums

Figure 2(A) (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h), a parallel vibration peak of reflection was generated by LR, HR, and HLR materials in visible–NIR spectrums. The variation of mean LR, HR, and HLR materials were depicted as minor. The reflection data are mentioned in Table SI. 5. A little stretching vibration of HR and HLR materials was recorded in NIR at 1400 nm and 1900 nm. It seems that LR materials have light striking capability of target signature at a very low ratio of angle. On the contrary, HR materials have light striking ability of target signature at very high incident angle,^[25] and scattered the light very quickly to the surrounding area. A combination mechanism of LR and HR materials is also applicable for HLR materials. The photonic signal of LR, HR, and HLR materials to the spectral sensor cannot capture enough photon which is needed to generate an appropriate imaging signal of target signature against DGTWSIB. Spectral signals of LR, HR, and HLR materials may defend for right pixel formation of target signature to the imaging sensor. Hence, the target signature may be confused or concealed by the remote sensing mechanism of target detector. Based on the mechanisms of LR, HR, and HLR, materials design may have an appropriate option for camouflage textiles formulation. Such materials design and spectral concealment techniques are also a high-performance approach for the concealment of modern defence surveillance against hyperspectral imaging spectrometry.

Figure 2(A) (a), the mean variations of DGTWSIB spectral signal are comparatively lower in visible spectrums, cited in Table SI 2. In general, the spectral signals have also signified a gradual increase in visible spectrums. Figure 2(A) (b), oppositely reflections of DGTWSIB are higher in NIR cited in Table SI 2. The reflections of DGTWSIB are depicted as gradual lower in NIR. The observed reflections in NIR were also supported by the published result in literature.^[40] Figure 2(A) (a, b), harmonized spectral reflections of DGTWSIB (except water, ice, snow) have been observed due to biochemical similarity of CB as natural source materials. Spectral reflections of DGTWSIB are more symmetrical in NIR than visible, water absorptions, which are highly prominent in 1400 nm and 1900 nm. The spectral reflections were also found to be almost similar with the related published results.^[44,51] V-shaped spectral signals have been detected in 1400 nm and 1900 nm except the lower reflection of water, ice, and snow.

Figure 2(A) (a, b), reflections of tree bark and woodland CB are significantly higher in both visible–NIR ranges due to the hard structure of lignin–cellulose combination and dead tissue of outer sheath. There is also a possibility of light trapping because of unevenness on wooden surface at the outermost layer of stem in tree bark. Reflection may be replaced in the same CB materials due to structural deviation of plant species, mineral composition, and atmospheric particles. Green leaves

*** ATR: absorption–transmission–reflection.

Figure 2. (A) Spectral simulation of adaptive (a, b); desertland (c, d); stoneland (e, f); and marine (g, h) camouflage textiles against multidimensional CBs in visible (Vis)–NIR spectrums. (B) Maximum reflection of CB materials, DGTWSIB in visible (Vis)–NIR spectrums.

have chlorophyll and natural wax materials which absorb light, and the reflection is noted comparatively lower at 675 nm than dry leaves and tree bark. These findings are also supported and reported by literature.^[1] Chlorophyll content in woodland CB is mostly controlled by the existing nitrogen percentage in green leaves.^[52] On the contrary, dry leaves and tree bark

have lacking of chlorophyll component which reflects more than the green background of woodland at 540 nm to 700 nm. Green leaves are reflective at NIR mostly in 1000–1800 nm due to chlorophyll.^[31] Maximum reflection of CB is considered for the physical structure intended for concealment and detection of any target signature. Figure 2(B) shows the

B

Figure 2. (continued)

recapitulated maximum reflection of CB materials, DGTWSIB in visible–NIR.

Figure 2(A) (c, d), sand reflections are higher from 540 to 700 nm. Comparatively elevated reflections are also signified from 1000 to 2400 nm. Related results are comparatively harmonized with the published literature.^[53] Water has observed relatively low reflection in visible–NIR spectrums. These experimented results are also supported by literature.^[36] Ice reflections are prominent at 540 nm (12.87%) and 550 nm (13.78%) due to hard surface (in terms of higher density) as vibration frequency depends on bond strength.^[24] Hence, reflection intensity is higher in blue–green region of visible spectrums at 540 nm to 550 nm. In visible spectrums, the reflection of ice and snow has been found a little bit higher than water as they appear almost white, snow looks more whitish than ice. In maximum spectrum region, ice has lower reflection than snow and sky CB as the background looks brighter (whiter) than ice, Fig. 3(A). Density of ice and snow may differ reflection due to bond variation and sequentially replacement of vibration frequency.^[24] Water droplet of cloud and atmospheric nitrogen (70%) are related to reflection of sky CB. Reflections of sky CB are found partly prominent in blue

to red region at 540 nm to 700 nm. It may be influential factors of existing nitrogen, oxygen, and dust particles in atmosphere which are scattered in blue and red spectrums. Similarly, the simulated reflection spectra of predicted camouflage textiles ZR, LR, HR, and HLR materials have been compared with sand, stone, and water CB mentioned in Fig. 2(A) (c, d, e, f, g, h). Sand and stone reflection looks almost similar due to structural symmetry and surface glossiness. It seems that all desert camouflage textiles may be comparatively suitable for stoneland camouflage textiles in terms of reflections. In marine background camouflage textiles, the spectral signals of water CB and predicted camouflage textiles (ZR-1 and ZR-2) are found in a same spectral line due to minor spectral difference in ratio of low reflection signal in visible–NIR spectrums when reflection difference (3%) is considered for concealment of predicted camouflage textiles. High reflection materials have low emissive property and low reflection materials have high emissive property which may generate a concealed/less responsive signal to the remote sensing sensor. In graphical state, spectra of ZR, HR,^[54] LR, and HLR materials have been found almost straight line in terms of mean reflection. It can be said that photon signal and compound

Figure 3. (A) Sky, ice, and snow as CB materials in visible and NIR spectrums. (B) Simulation of iceland (a, b); snowland (c, d); sky (e, f); and woodland, tree bark-a (g, h) camouflage textiles against CBs in visible (Vis) and NIR spectrums.

identification will be significantly less. The detection of target signature will be difficult to the modern imaging sensor. Every remote sensing device captures photon, convert photon signal to pixel, and sequentially generate photographic scene to the remote sensing detector. Hence, ZR, LR, HR, and HLR category of materials have been considered as adaptive properties of camouflaging against multidimensional CBs and/or single CB. Textile substances can be treated with such materials for more efficient way of camouflage textiles coloration.

Spectral simulation of iceland, snowland, sky background, woodland, simultaneous marine and woodland, simultaneous marine and desertland camouflage textiles in visible (Vis) and NIR spectrums

Figure 3(B) (a, b), ice reflections are comparatively lesser in NIR than visible spectrums. Reflection peaks of ice are 12.87% at 540 nm, 13.78% at 550 nm, and 10.84% at 610 nm. NIR reflections are almost 5% lower than visible in entire measured spectrums from 1000 to 2400 nm. This reflection synthesis may clarify that reflection signals of ice between visible–NIR spectrums are not symmetrical and there will be variations of photonic signal to the imaging sensor. The results of ice reflections are compared and supported by the published results in terms of higher reflection in visible spectrums and lower reflection in NIR spectrums although the entire process of reflection mechanism is also directly related with the density of ice.^[55] The controlling of ice reflection mechanism may be significantly complicated in field trialing of camouflage textiles by which ice structure (related to density and ice crystal) of CB may replace ATR mechanism of photon signal to the imaging sensor.

Figure 3(B) (c, d), snow reflections are higher at entire spectrums, 400–700 nm. Snow reflection looks almost straight line like LR, HR, and HLR materials and it remains almost 11% to 12% at whole spectrums from 400 to 700 nm. In NIR region, snow signal declines around 10% to 5% from 1000 to 1400 nm; the signal continues in a symmetrical vibration from 1400 to 2400 nm. Therefore, significantly lower reflections in NIR spectrums from 1000 to 2400 nm such as 9.17% at 1000 nm, 8.07% at 1100 nm, 6.01% at 1200 nm, 4.81% at 1300 nm, 2.44% at 1400 nm, 2.47% at 1500 nm, 2.76% at 1600 nm, 2.91% at 1800 nm, 2.78% 1900 nm, 2.35% at 2000 nm, 2.43% at 2100 nm, 2.56% at 2200 nm, 2.5% at 2300 nm, 2.4% at 2400 nm, and 2.28% at 2500 nm. Increasing density of snow declines the whiteness, hence unlikely other materials (such as ice), snow density declines the original reflection of snow. A relative part of snow reflections are also supported by published result.^[55] Comparatively, the spectral signals of predicted camouflage textiles coloration with LR materials are more appropriate with snow reflection in NIR spectrums.

Figure 3(B) (e, f), sky CB has been observed comparatively low reflection of variations between visible and NIR

spectrums such as 7.04% at 400 nm, 8.42% at 440 nm, 12.39% at 550 nm, 10.18% at 630 nm, 11.23% at 700 nm, 14.42% at 1000 nm, 13.10% at 1300 nm, 10.93% at 1400 nm, 7.53% at 1900 nm, and 9.90% at 2100 nm. Sky CB has higher reflection at 540 nm in blue region and absorption is higher at 400–420 nm due to intensity of existing nitrogen and oxygen in atmosphere. The reflections are found prominent in 1000–1300 nm and the reflection is lower in 1900–2400 nm due to the prominence of sun radiation. This observed result is also supported by the related published research.^[36] Figure 3(B) (g, h) shows that a gradual reflection mechanism has been found in the upward direction (400–700 nm) in woodland CB (tree bark) such as 8.71% at 400 nm, 13.19% at 430 nm, 19.84% at 460 nm, 24.76% at 490 nm, 29.1% at 520 nm, 34.08% at 550 nm, 39.09% at 580 nm, 43.62% at 610 nm, 47.58% at 640 nm, 51.78% at 670 nm, and 54.82% at 700 nm. On the contrary, gradual declining state of absorption and reflection spectra has been observed in NIR, such as 58.64% at 1000 nm, 57.88% at 1100 nm, 56.41% at 1200 nm, 52.47% at 1300 nm, 32.92% at 1400 nm, 34.89% at 1500 nm, 37.95% at 1600 nm, 36.23% at 1700 nm, 34.8% at 1800 nm, 19.19% at 1900 nm, 23.31% at 2000 nm, 23.35% at 2100 nm, 22.93% at 2200 nm, 19.98% at 2300 nm, and 16.31% at 2400 nm. It seems that reflections of woodland CB (tree bark) are signified as higher deviation to the spectral response in visible and NIR spectrums. Therefore, materials design of LR, HR, and HLR materials based on spectral frequency may be a significant textile coloration approach of camouflaging. ZR materials/natural source of materials may have limitation for ice, snow, marine, and sky CB but identification of real materials related to ZR needs to continue for further experimentation. LR, HR, and HLR materials have been signified for camouflage textiles formulation against ice, snow, marine, and sky CB.

Figure 4(a, b), green leaves absorptions are significantly higher in visible ranges in comparison with NIR spectrums. Stretching of vibrations are observed at 1300 nm, 1400 nm, 1500 nm, and 1900 nm. Such stretching may be due to nitrogen and water remaining in green leaves. ZR, LR, HR, and HLR materials spectra may contribute spectral signal of camouflage textiles due to balanced stretching vibrations of ZR materials. LR, HR, and HLR materials spectra were remarked as almost straight line against the spectra of green leaves CB. Figure 4(c, d), a similar principle is also applicable for camouflage textiles coloration against dry leaves CB. A gradual rising curve (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%) has been found for visible reflection of dry leaves CB. Dry leaves stretching has been signified at 1300 nm, 1400 nm, 1600 nm, and 1900 nm. Figure 4(a, b, c, d), almost symmetrical vibration trend of dry leaves and green leaves have been identified in NIR due to biochemical symmetry, but chlorophyll reflections in green leaves are higher in NIR. Natural wax/lignin on green leaves surface may create higher reflection in NIR. Therefore, water and nitrogen absorptions have been noted significantly less in NIR region rather than visible spectrums. Spectral reflections

Figure 4. Simulation of woodland, green leaves-b (a, b); woodland, dry leaves-c (c, d); simultaneous marine and woodland (e, f); simultaneous marine and desertland (g, h) camouflage textiles against CBs in visible (Vis) and NIR spectrums.

may fluctuate because of is happened due to lacking of chlorophyll in dry leaves. Different conditions of natural drying of dry leaves may change the spectral vibrations of woodland CB. Say, 20%, 50%, 80%, 100% drying creates the compositional replacement of tree leaves which will replace the nitrogen%,

water%, biochemical (such as chlorophyll, natural wax), and structural response to the imaging sensor.^[24]

Figure 4(e, f), water and woodland CB shows different reflection in visible–NIR spectrums. Water reflection declines gradually (6% to 5.9%, 5.8%, 5.7%, 5.6%, 5.5%,

5.4%, 5.3%, 5.2%, 5.1%) from 400 to 660 nm and almost 5% reflection continues until 700 nm. On the contrary, the reflections of woodland CB (mean reflection of tree bark, dry leaves, green leaves) are always increased from 400 to 700 nm (10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%) due to the intensity of biochemical structure (lignin–cellulose–water–nitrogen). In NIR, the reflection of water CB almost touches the base line of 0% reflection due to higher absorption, but the reflection of woodland CB declines slowly 40.90% at 1000 nm, 27.95% at 1400 nm, 32.44% at 1600 nm, 29.45% at 1800 nm, 16.18% at 1900 nm, 22.54% at 2100 nm, and 15.16% at 2400 nm. A gradual decreasing of reflection has been signified from 1000 to 2400 nm. It seems that the reflection effect of lignin–cellulose–natural wax–mineral materials of woodland are less prominent to the NIR signal. Water absorptions are always higher in analytical instrument related to illumination.^[24] Due to different reflections of water and woodland CB, there is a possibility to increase the target visibility in the middle point of simultaneous CB environment. The photon response of water and woodland CBs are not symmetric to the imaging sensor. ZR materials have limitations for simultaneous spectrum probe camouflage coloration against multidimensional CBs, but those materials can be applicable for single background camouflage coloration in simultaneous spectrum probe in visible–NIR spectrums. For example, selected solid CB materials can be directly coated on textile substances, but the ZR materials are not applicable for liquid materials such as ice, snow, and water. LR, HR, and HLR materials spectra are more precise to a straight line which may defend to illuminate a contrast signal against single and simultaneous CB. Similarly, ZR spectra may generate a matching signal with natural CB. Therefore, treated textiles with ZR, LR, HR, and HLR materials may be significantly less responsive and concealed to the imaging sensor. Water and sand reflections also have variation in visible–NIR spectrums. Figure 4(g), sand reflections are gradually increased in visible spectrums such as 8.9% at 400 nm, 10.96% at 430 nm, 14.43% at 480 nm, 20.07% at 540 nm, 25.58% at 620 nm, 26.62% at 670 nm, and 27.28% at 700 nm. Figure 4(h), sand reflections in NIR spectrums start from 24.64% at 1000 nm. Then stretching vibrations of sand are limited from 20.69 to 29.27%, which are 25.25% at 1400 nm, 29.16% at 1600 nm, 29.27% at 1700 nm, 20.69% at 1900 nm, and 21.49% at 2400 nm. Figure 4(g, h), oppositely water reflections are very minor in visible–NIR spectrums. Visible reflections of water CB are 5.49% at 400 nm, 5.72% at 430 nm, 5.62% at 460 nm, 5.63% at 490 nm, 5.58% at 520 nm, 5.5% at 550 nm, 5.25% at 580 nm, 5.07% at 610 nm, 4.89% at 640 nm, 4.27% at 670 nm, and 4.48% at 700 nm. Minimum reflections of water are 4.27% at 670 nm and maximum reflections of water are 5.78% at 430 nm. A negligible percentage of gradual decreasing are identified in NIR spectrums. Stretching vibrations are 1.39% at 1000 nm, 0.95% at

1100 nm, 0.8% at 1200 nm, 0.79% at 1300 nm, 0.79% at 1400 nm, 0.78% at 1500 nm, 0.77% at 1600 nm, 0.77% at 1700 nm, 0.77% at 1800 nm, 0.75% at 1900 nm, 0.77% at 2000 nm, 0.78% at 2100 nm, 0.74% at 2200 nm, 0.75% at 2300 nm, and 0.75% at 2400 nm. Hence, reflection dissimilarity of water and desert CB materials have been observed which may signify the contrast imaging signal of target signature to the imaging sensor if the single CB camouflage technique is applied for concealment against simultaneous background in OB environment. ZR, LR, HR, and HLR material spectrums may be simulated for simultaneous camouflaging in visible–NIR against desert and woodland CB.

Conclusion

Visible–NIR spectra of ZR–LR–HR–HLR materials state the spectral prediction and optical hypothesis versus CDRI against DGTWSIB under laboratory stage trialing; although field trialing may have variations due to known and unknown interference which is critical to measure by a single formulation of optical design in the platform of camouflage research. Therefore, camouflage textile is simulated by means of visible–NIR–ZR–LR–HR–HLR–CDRI–OB–ATR–DGTWSIB principle of illumination theory for technical formulation and coloration such as coating, dyeing, and printing. For this hypothesis of ZR–LR–HR–HLR materials, the photonic signal to the imaging device may be simulated as ZR materials < LR materials < HR materials < HLR materials for CDRI against DGTWSIB. However, combination/mixed principle of LR/HR and synthetic dyes such as Isolan Black 2S LDN, Isolan Orange, Telon Blue A 2R, Telon Red A 2R, Telon Violet 3R, and Telon Yellow A 2R can also be implemented as per expected design of camouflage textiles for specific location of CB. Simulation of ZR–LR–HR–HLR materials refer to the contribution of camouflage assessment against hyperspectral imaging spectrometry and suitable materials design for camouflage textiles coloration under four-dimensional concealment theory of ZR, LR, HR, and HLR. The model has an innovative addition of camouflage materials design in visible–NIR spectrums. This model is not only applicable for design of high-performance camouflage textiles, but also spectral matching theory, which is relevant for broader area of camouflage engineering related to weapon and vehicle design for defence protection. This experimental simulation clearly directs a guideline of optical versus spectral mechanism for the development of camouflage textiles under versatile CB environment, DGTWSIB in visible–NIR spectrums. Spectral model clarifies the development of real camouflage textiles against modern remote sensing threat of advance surveillance technologies in UV–Vis–IR. CB selection, dyes choice, categories of nanoparticle, pigment selection and its right formulation for camouflage textiles, spectral data, spectral signal, spectral contrastness, compound variation, compound identification,

chromatic variation, spectral versus photon signal analysis, spectral versus pixel data/imaging signal evaluation, ATR signal, quantitative measurements, performance measurement of laboratory and field trialing, physical properties versus texture, physical properties versus camouflage patterning, ZR/LR/HR/HLR materials for camouflage patterning, and/or chromatic reflection matching with CB which can be synthesized for camouflage textiles coloration. The major limitations of this simulation are also noted that all the CDRI parameters are not considered here due to experimental limitations and its complexities. There is enormous complexity of making coalesce of every CDRI parameters in a single platform of simulation although physical materials and wavelengths were critically covered for this prediction in visible–NIR spectrums which are practiced by defence professional. Every CB and reflection theory need to be trialed in laboratory and field trialing process for establishment and genuine verification of the present simulation. The reflections of OB characteristics are not only limited to physical and chemical state of materials but also surface roughness, illumination angle, illumination type, camouflage patterning, weather conditions in combat environments need to continue for the real experimentation of high-performance camouflage textiles coloration under multidimensional CBs and extended wavelength in UV–Vis–IR spectrums.

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Data availability

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during this experimentation and simulation are briefly attached with this manuscript as Supporting Information, Figs. 1–46 and Tables 1–6.

Declarations

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest to publish this article.

Glossary

DGTWSIB	Dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark-woodland CB; water-marine CB; sand-desertland CB; stone-stoneland CB; snow-snowland CB; and ice-iceland CB
Zero reflection	The term ‘zero’ has been hypothetically used when the textile substances are directly treated with CB materials/similar reflection materials; and target signature (textile substances) is compared with same CB for CDRI
CDRI	Concealment, detection, recognition, and identification
ZR	Zero reflection
LR	Low reflection
HR	High reflection
HLR	High reflection and low reflection
ATR	Absorption-transmission-reflection
CB	Combat background

Supplementary Information

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Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination

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Abstract- Natural illumination is a common attribute and uncontrollable intimidation for concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI) of defense surveillance. Every research outcome of camouflage engineering needs to conduct field experimentation under natural illumination. CDRI versus natural illumination necessitates considering for every combat location such as woodland, marine, desert land, stone land, snow land, sky and ice land. The intensity of natural illumination and surveillance technique determine CDRI due to irrepressible illumination angle and intensity among sunlight, object-background (OB) environment and detector in ultraviolet, visible, and infrared spectrum. Camouflage field assessment of real OB environments, different weather conditions, season and its variation in natural illumination is also cost involvement and achievement headache for continuous improvement of research. Natural illumination versus CDRI has been investigated in visible range (400-700 nm) using different universal conditions of OB environment in winter season such as foggy morning light (FML), morning sun light (MSL), noon sun light (NSL), evening sun light (ESL), dusk evening light (DEL). A simulation of CDRI of marine target signature was experimented by using “animal object (*Anas Platyrhynchos*)” as target signature. “Water background in water reservoir” was selected for controlled features of background environment as alternative of marine zone. Natural illumination of CDRI has been methodically explained in terms of Lab (L^* , a^* , b^*) color intensity, key factors of water background and its surrounding in OB environment. The partial protection factors of target signature against marine surveillance were signified based on key rudiments of water background environment such as illumination of sun-position/sunlight-angle, weather condition in winter season, wind speed, target detection angle, shadow, wave of water surface, the chromatic intensity of OB and its surrounding background. The illumination of FML-MSL-NSL-ESL-DEL was indicated as CDRI factors in OB environment. MSL-NSL was remarked as predominant effect of target concealment. The experimental concept and procedure can be implemented for design and assessment of marine camouflage objects in

different areas of camouflage engineering in terms of natural illumination against water background. The investigation proposed a model named CDRI for target OB in natural illumination.

Keywords- *Natural Illumination, Concealment, Detection, Recognition, Identification*

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI) represents the most important natural behaviours for preventing target signature in object-background (OB) environment, the assumption has attracted the attention of visual psychology and surveillance [1]. Natural illuminations such as sun and sky are stimulated from above and animals are darker from their backside which is a strategy for animal CDRI, the concept is most vibrant for every target signature in marine backgrounds [2]. Most species of duck are counter shaded to sunlight when the birds are in their natural characteristic position like vertical habitat [3]. Dark dorsa and light on animals are often attributed to an adaptive effect of shape-obliteration when illumination is from above [4]. Colors of different animals seems adapted to their purpose of concealment such as background matching, disruptive coloration and countershading [5, 6]. Target detection is more difficult to identify when color intensity of OB are similar [5]. Object detection and countershading changes under cloudy and sunny environments, [7] luminance distribution of the sky depends on the condition of weather [8]. Luminance of distribution changes with the position of the sun, [9] even detection is complicated in winter [10]. Darker pigmentation on animals exposed to the lighting, which reduces detectability of prey [11] Detection and countershading vary with natural lighting [2]. Optical information, optic flow, which breaks camouflage and specifies target locations as optic flow is responsible for image structure of OB [12]. Light reflected from a surface depends on the scene geometry, the incident illumination, and the material surface [13]. In addition to

natural illumination; water waves, shadow are the illumination features for water background, those hamper target detection [4, 14-16] and concealment [17]. Lighting effects on water and shadow enhances the visibility and detection [18, 19]. In different lighting conditions, animals protect from predation by compensating their own shadows [20]. Shadow generates a brightness contrast between the dorsal and ventral surfaces [21]. OB depicts contrast or conceal as a function of viewing angle, [14] size, texture, color [22]. Natural illumination and target properties of animals were experimented with a computational model [23] but digital photography was considered an efficient method for recording luminance intensity and achromatic contents of target signature [20, 24]. Therefore, a hypothesis of this investigation was depicted that sunlight, shadow, wind on water background has an impact for CDRI mechanism. Natural illuminations are key characteristics for CDRI and defence surveillance. Luminance and illumination of sun, sky and cloudy environments have been experimented and reported in the literature. Currently, natural illumination of OB of a specific daylight in time intervals have not been investigated in terms of CDRI, chromatic and achromatic intensity of color imaging. CDRI investigation on target object-duck (TOD) has been undertaken for natural illumination of foggy morning light (FML), morning sun light (MSL), noon sun light (NSL), evening sun light (ESL), dusk evening light (DEL) that have not scientifically been reported in the literature.

II. METHODOLOGY

CDRI was experimented in natural OB environment against water background. Water reservoir was considered as alternative to marine background to keep the constant feature of water background. Animal objects were selected for CDRI in replacement of a marine target signature such as a marine ship. The movement of each TOD was simulated as an uncontrolled movement of a marine ship. The photographic illumination/surveillance angle (35° - 45°) was implemented as target detection from a land area beside the marine zone (simulated as a water reservoir).

Natural illumination of birds was experimented based on Thayer theory and discoveries [3, 4] of lighting and background contributions to countershading. A few black colored and almost similar colored bird scenes, Australian

duck, scientific name: *Anas Platyrhynchos*, were used to investigate CDRI behaviours in a water reservoir, Princes Park, Melbourne with capacity of water 38 ML, water height 35 cm, construction: semi-circular with brick wall and two water pumps. A digital camera, 13 MP, F 1.8, phase detection auto focus (PDAF) was used as observer to view from one side in the visible range 400-700 nm at 45° angle. TOD and water surface was considered as background in ambient illumination of day light [25]. Digital photography [20] is a convenient method for chromatic information and achromatic content of animals. According to the opinion of researcher Stevens, few TOD movements in a reservoir were observed under specific natural illumination.

Figure 1 illustrates the phenomenon of image capture for CDRI mechanism under natural illumination. TOD-CDRI was observed in "five phases" of day light illumination for chromatic matching of TOD with water background. FML, MSL, NSL, ESL, DEL were used for demonstrating the optical influence of sunlight for CDRI. The angle between observer (digital camera) and TOD was kept almost 35° - 45° . Photographs were captured at distances ranging from 4 to 5 m. TOD scenes were captured using the camera on the same day in winter during June 2020. The whole day had no visible clouds in the sky. Photographs were captured with the digital camera under different conditions of natural illumination for observations of lighting effect on TOD-CDRI.

The experiments were performed in a water reservoir at Princes Park, a public park at Melbourne, Australia. There were few trees beside the water reservoir at different distances such as 2, 5, 7, 10 m. The results and discussion have been included without considering the exact length of tree shadow, since trees of varying height were located at different distances. During photo capture, the TOD movements were unpredictable due to the natural behavior of ducks. The photographic distances between TOD and camera were kept almost constant without causing any disturbance of the ducks in their natural and relaxed movements. So, all images of TOD did not show the same number of TOD. Similarly, the direction of TOD was not constant due to their tendency for unpredictable movement.

Lab (L^* , a^* , b^*) of TOD and water background for color intensity, three dimensional surface plot of water background for water waves were presented using an image analysis process and it was performed by imageJ software (Fiji Is Just) developed by National Institute of Health (NIH), USA [26].

Figure 1. Schematic of CDRI-OB-TOD mechanism in natural illumination against water background and color imaging in OB environment

Figure 2. CDRI-TOD at five-dimensional natural illumination under water background

A global thresholding method (mean), Lab was used to distinguish foreground and background under natural illumination Figure 3. Red color thresholding was selected to identify intensity of sunlight. For Lab of OB, original captured photographs were uploaded into imageJ by file and open selection process; and converted into 8-bit depth, wavelength 400-700 nm. TOD and water background was separated by polygon and rectangular shapes. Every CDRI object under different illumination were selected by plugins and color inspector 3D individually for generating diagrams in Lab. Similarly, every background at FML, MSL, NSL, ESL and DEL were selected for background Lab, Figure 3. Water backgrounds at five-dimensional illumination were chosen by “analyze” and three-dimensional water surface plot. “3D surface plots” of water background was exported by selection of background area, Figure 5.

III. INVESTIGATIONS OF TOD FOR CDRI IN WATER BACKGROUND

Detection (ability to distinguish TOD from the background), recognition (ability to classify TOD class) and identification (ability to describe TOD in detail) technique [27]; and camouflage-TOD, detection-TOD, and identification-TOD theory [4] were implemented for CDRI of TOD in water background. Color imaging versus CDRI technique was applied under natural illumination such as FML, MSL, NSL, ESL and DEL. TOD was investigated on water background for CDRI in terms of five-dimensional illumination. The distinctiveness of CDRI were investigated by color imaging in terms of CDRI parameters of TOD such as natural illumination, shadow, angle of water wave, water bubbles.

A. Investigation-01, Figure 2 (A & B) shows FML for CDRI-TOD

In figure 2, A and B are similar photograph of FML. A signifies the captured photograph in natural illumination of FML and B illustrates the symbol for identifications of target CDRI parameters on water background. Marking with “1” demonstrates the identification of TOD. “2”, “3”, “4”, “5” depicts the minor proportion of shadow on a foggy morning, minor water wave, whitish effect of foggy morning environment in winter and water bubbles on water background, respectively. In this condition, the TOD was observed to be almost motionless.

B. Investigation-02, Figure 2 (C & D) shows MSL for CDRI-TOD

In figure 2, C and D are unchanged photograph of MSL. C denotes the captured photograph under natural illumination of MSL and D demonstrates the marker identifications of target CDRI and its background. Marking with “1”, “2” and “3” indicates the concealment, recognition, and identification of TOD. “4” indicates the sun illumination when the sun is rising from east side of the water reservoir, “5” defines the shadow of an outside tree and “6” specifies water wave and “7” mentions water bubbles on water background.

C. Investigation-03, Figure 2 (E & F) shows NSL for CDRI-TOD

In figure 2, E and F illustrates an alike photograph of NSL. E mentions the captured photograph in natural illumination of NSL and F illustrates the mark identifications of target CDRI and its background, water surface. Marking with “1”, “2”, “3” states the concealment, detection, and recognition of TOD. “4” reveals the effect of sunlight, “5” demonstrates water bubbles, “6” signifies shadow of outside tree, “7” generates a CDRI effect of water wave.

D. Investigation-04, Figure 2 (G & H) shows ESL for CDRI-TOD

In figure 2, G and H shows an unchanged photograph of ESL. G implies the captured photograph under natural illumination of ESL and H means the pointer identifications of target CDRI and its water background. Marking with “1” and “2” indicates identification of TOD. “3” identifies sunlight directly falling on the surface of water background. The ESL illumination signify whitish/shiny stimulus. Marking “4” shows the shadow and “5” indicates water waves at different angles.

E. Investigation-05, Figure 2 (I & J) shows DEL for CDRI-TOD

Figure 2, I and J shows same photograph of DEL. I signify the captured photograph under natural illumination of DEL and J illustrates the marker identifications of target CDRI and water background. “1” indicates identification of TOD, “2” remarks recognition of TOD, “3” implies concealment of TOD, “4” indicates the shadow of an outside tree and marking with “5” indicates water wave and the shadow free zone of water background.

Figure 3. Lab (left) and color threshold (right) between TOD and water background at five-dimensional natural illumination

Figure 4. Three dimensional variations of water background captured at FML, MSL, NSL, ESL and DEL and represented with imageJ

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3a, 1 = Lab of TOD, identification of TOD; 2 = Lab of water background; Figure 3b, 1 = Lab of TOD, concealment of TOD; 2 = Lab of TOD, recognition of TOD; 3 = Lab TOD, identification of TOD; 4 = Lab of water background; Figure 3c, 1 = Lab of TOD, concealment of TOD; 2 = Lab of TOD, detection of TOD; 3 = Lab of TOD, recognition of TOD; 4 = Lab of water background; Figure 3d, 1 = Lab of TOD, identification of TOD; 2 = Lab of water background; Figure 3e, 1 = Lab of TOD, identification of TOD, 2 = Lab of TOD, recognition of TOD; 3 = Lab of TOD, concealment of TOD; 4 = Lab of water background; Figure 3f, color threshold of OB at FML; Figure 3g, color threshold of OB at MSL; Figure 3h, color threshold of OB at NSL; Figure 3i, color threshold of OB at ESL; Figure 3j, color threshold of OB at DEL.

Deeply shaded water background showed a dark bottom against TOD. Shadow and underwater substances created darker surface on water background. The black color of TOD on top was blended with deeply shaded water background and revealed as weak reflection in photographs of color imaging. Water caustic and sunlight position at FML-MSL-NSL-ESL-DEL critically replace the wavelength and illumination on TOD. Dappled light influence was also signified although there was no tree, wall or other obstacle remained close to the surrounding of OB during this experimentation.

Comparison of Lab of TOD and water background has been represented with imageJ at five-dimensional natural illumination. Color threshold (red) of OB environment was illustrated at FML, MSL, NSL, ESL, DSL. Reddish area of color threshold identifies the sunlight intensity at FML, MSL, NSL, ESL, DSL. Red thresholding signifies the intensity of natural illumination in natural OB environment. Red threshold clearly differs the significant area from water background due to intensity of sunlight at MSL, NSL and ESL. Therefore, the prominence of shadow was higher at MSL, NSL and ESL. Red threshold color did not appear at FML and DSL due to minor intensity of sunlight.

A. TOD in natural illumination at FML

Figure 3a, RGB grey value (L^*) of TOD-1 (Lab-1) was lower than water background (Lab-2) grey value that seems in contrast due to remaining whitish effect in the water background at FML. Figure 4a depicts the minimum level of water surface changing at FML because of winding effect and surface water wave was poor and there was a minor proportion of water wave angle. Figure 3a illustrates the negligible effect of surrounding shadow due to absence of sunlight at FML. It can be signified that TOD was less impacted by shadow because of reduced intensity of sunlight. Water bubbles create a whitish caste, and a foggy morning generated a whitish reflection, so the water bubble effects were not visible, Figure

4a. TOD identification was slightly influenced by water wave by the reason of minimum effects of remaining natural wind. Therefore, the object may signify the trouble-free identification although TOD looked blurred at FML.

B. TOD in natural illumination at MSL

Figure 3b, the grey value sequence can be mentioned as $TOD-1 < TOD-2 < TOD-3$. The grey value of TOD-1 signifies almost similar proportion of grey value compared to water background. Hence TOD (Lab 1) remarked as concealed. TOD (Lab 2, 3) is lighter due to morning sunlight and shadow prominence. Figure 3b, 4b; the combination of shadow and water surface creates a darker TOD with less prominence to the water background. Therefore, TOD-2, 3 (Lab-2, 3) can be identified in terms of recognition and identification, but the TOD appearance is not as clearer as FML.

C. TOD in natural illumination at NSL

Figure 3c, the sequence of grey value can be identified as $TOD-1 < TOD-2 < TOD-3 < TOD-4$. TOD-1 illuminates lower grey value which identify black appearance of TOD and water background. The shadow was more prominence at NSL due to higher degree of sunlight at noon. The combined outcome of shadow and noon sunlight was the mechanism of concealment of TOD (Lab 1). The grey value of TOD-2 (Lab 2) was higher because of whitish effect when sunlight was directly fall; and water wave was recorded as elevated because of air speed, Figure 4c. Consequently, same CDRI parameters were affected the third TOD (Lab 3). The target was less impacted by shadow and sunlight, created the TOD lighter with higher grey value to the water background and third TOD was identified as recognition of target object.

D. TOD in natural illumination at ESL

Figure 3d, the grey value of TOD was less than water background, the contrast mechanism of TOD and water background created the identification of TOD. Figure 4d, surface water movement at ESL was higher, it confirms that the airflow was elevated at evening. The grey value and TOD were not influenced by water wave as well as shadow was less affected the target at ESL.

E. TOD in natural illumination at DEL

Figure 3e, the grey value can be signified as $TOD-1 < TOD-2 < TOD-3$. Water background was lighter than TOD-1, hence the target was illustrated as identification. The shadow and underside ground of water background was generated a clearer water surface. Water surface movement was recorded at minimum level due to lacking intensity of air speed (natural phenomenon) at DEL, Figure 4e. The reflection mechanism of shadow and water background demonstrated the TOD-2,3 (Lab 2, 3) recognition and its concealment.

F. CIE, RGB stimulus of TOD in natural illumination

As per RGB-TOD theory of color science [1]; if red, green, and blue are the primary colors represented by the symbol [R], [G], [B]. Tristimulus values are denoted by symbol R, G, B, stimulus value is denoted by S, “matched by” is denoted by equal sign (=). So, it can be written for any matching condition of CDRI of target signature against background:

$$S = R[R] + G[G] + B[B] \tag{1}$$

In naked eye color assessment process or color imaging, the same theory can be applied for color comparison or photographic comparison or concealment comparison or TOD-CDRI for different color matching in different illumination of day light. Stimulus of FML is denoted by S₁, stimulus of MSL is denoted by S₂, stimulus of NSL is denoted by S₃, stimulus of ESL is denoted by S₄, stimulus of DEL is denoted by S₅.

$$S_1 = R_1 [R] + G_1 [G] + B_1 [B] \tag{2}$$

$$S_2 = R_2 [R] + G_2 [G] + B_2 [B] \tag{3}$$

$$S_3 = R_3 [R] + G_3 [G] + B_3 [B] \tag{4}$$

$$S_4 = R_4 [R] + G_4 [G] + B_4 [B] \tag{5}$$

$$S_5 = R_5 [R] + G_5 [G] + B_5 [B] \tag{6}$$

Stimulus of S₁, S₂, S₃, S₄, S₅ are the dependable for the CDRI of TOD. The gradient of RGB increases the visibility of TOD. So, the simple formulation CDRI-*RGB* can be written as *RGB* of TOD for any concealment < *RGB* of TOD for any detection < *RGB* of TOD for any recognition < *RGB* of TOD for any identification. Thus, zero stimulus of *RGB* may create concealment of TOD to the sensor of detector in terms of digital camera or Lab, Figure 2, 3. In this experiment, *RGB* of S₂ and S₃ are more prominent for the response to the digital camera and S₁ shows less prominence. Therefore, the sequence can be formulated as S₃ > S₂ > S₄ > S₅ > S₁, Figure 2, 3, 4.

More accurate spectrophotometric analysis can be performed for specific wavelength as per computational theory of color science [1]. If the tristimulus values are measured separately each wavelength of visible spectrum then the tristimulus R, G, B will be replaced by λ.

$$S = R(\lambda) + G(\lambda) + B(\lambda) \tag{7}$$

The same theory can be applied for the comparison of color or photographic or TOD-CDRI of different color matching in different illumination of day light. Stimulus of FML is denoted

by S₁, stimulus of MSL is denoted by S₂, stimulus of NSL is denoted by S₃, stimulus of ESL is denoted by S₄, stimulus of DEL is denoted by S₅.

$$S_1 = R(\lambda_1) + G(\lambda_1) + B(\lambda_1) \tag{8}$$

$$S_2 = R(\lambda_2) + G(\lambda_2) + B(\lambda_2) \tag{9}$$

$$S_3 = R(\lambda_3) + G(\lambda_3) + B(\lambda_3) \tag{10}$$

$$S_4 = R(\lambda_4) + G(\lambda_4) + B(\lambda_4) \tag{11}$$

$$S_5 = R(\lambda_5) + G(\lambda_5) + B(\lambda_5) \tag{12}$$

Similarly, maximum color band of spectral and color imaging can be experimented by multispectral/hyperspectral imaging system due to having highest color response in a broader wavelength.

G. TOD versus CDRI assessment on water background

Figure 5 (a, b, c) illustrates the TOD assessment of water background under five dimensional natural illuminations such as FML, MSL, NSL, ESL and DEL in terms of CDRI. Comparison of major CDRI characteristics has been presented by scoring policy (1-4) based on partial assessment, Figure 2; chromatic (L*, a*, b*) analysis and color threshold analysis of sunlight intensity, Figure 3; wind effect on water surface, Figure (4). Figure 2, 3, 4 demonstrates the TOD versus CDRI characteristics such as shadow effects, sunlight intensity, wind effect (water wave) and accordingly summarized in Figure 5 (a, b, c). CDRI was graded as identification (1), recognition (2), detection (3), concealment (4) and CDRI parameters were also scored as zero (0), minor (1), moderate (2) and major (3). Illumination of sunlight moderated the target detection both in MSL and NSL. Reflection of sunlight at mid-day light was higher. It may be the reason for sunlight falling from top side at 90° angle on the surface of water and illumination of sunlight was distributed at multi-angle on water background. Shadow is more prominent when stimulus of sunlight is higher. The shadow effect of surrounding environment and the shadow of TOD was influenced the illumination and its target CDRI. Oppositely the surrounding shadow showed less prominent effect for target CDRI when observed at FML and ESL although FML showed minor effect in shadow. Sunlight creates shadow of TOD and the surrounding materials of water background. Both TOD-shadow and water background-shadow are responsible for CDRI. Wind effect has also been depicted as minor effect for CDRI.

H. An approach of TOD-CDRI model for camouflage assessment

The color intensity (L^* , a^* , b^*) of OB environment was represented for CDRI model of camouflage assessment. Figure 5d represents the symbolic amplification of CDRI. Striking with blue color illustrates the TOD on water background. Pink color demonstrates the concealment of TOD, orange color indicates the detection of TOD, green color depicts the recognition of TOD, red color shows the identification of TOD

with water background. Color imaging of target signature have been impacted by CDRI parameters of TOD and its water background. Hence, altering of illumination versus CDRI effect of sunlight have been demonstrated at FML, MSL, NSL, ESL, DEL. Light falling angle on OB, detector, and target angle; its relationship with sun light direction, OB color matching, shadow of TOD, shadow of water background, shadow of surrounding OB environments is the natural mechanism for CDRI assessment.

Figure 5. a) CDRI versus sunlight intensity, b) shadow and c) wind effect and d) an approach of CDRI model

V. CONCLUSION

It is recommended that TOD color, surrounding color and water background color are strongly influenced by lighting conditions of natural illumination at different time of a specified day. Therefore, natural illumination should be considered for every research and development of CDRI. It is also vital for CDRI in ultraviolet, visible, and infrared spectrum. Photographic investigation on natural illumination in different day lighting can clarify the effect of environmental conditions for decision making of CDRI. Therefore, known,

and unknown features of OB may influence CDRI of target signature against combat background. Every target signature is affected by natural illumination. Major natural features of water background have been remarked for CDRI of target signature such as shadow, water wave angle and winding speed, and the movement of target signature. The concepts, technology, and applications of RGB and Lab color imaging, quantitative and qualitative image analysis in OB environment can be implemented at marine zone for every CDRI in OB environment.

TOD is a natural phenomenon for adaptation with water background because of cryptic coloration of animals. But natural illumination was remarked as uncontrolled parameters. Similarly, CDRI and natural illumination are the challenging task for all branches of camouflage engineering and protection of surveillance against modern remote sensing technology. For example, camouflage textiles, camouflage ship, camouflage vehicle for countershading of multidimensional illumination and its variation of color imaging for CDRI. Accordingly, modern surveillance technology for identification of target signature needs to be improved under the consideration of natural illumination and its related parameters for CDRI.

ABBREVIATIONS

Foggy morning light (FML); morning sun light (MSL); noon sun light (NSL); evening sun light (ESL); dusk evening light (DEL); concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI); red, green, blue (RGB), L^* , a^* , b^* (Lab); object-background (OB), target object-duck (TOD).

DECLARATION

Authors declare no conflict of interest to publish this article.

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Chapter

Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications

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Abstract

Polyamide-6,6 (PA-6,6) knitted fabric was coated with a complex combination of liquid-phase oxidized carbon black pigment (CBP) as light absorber and mono-sulfonated telon violet 3R (TVR) as acid dyes. Nitric acid (NA) moiety was used as liquid-phase oxidation of CBP and hydrophilic transformation of CBP-TV. Thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) and N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF) were formulated as cross-linker between composite mixture (CM) and PA-6,6 fabric. Six different CMs were coded for coating of PA-6, 6 fabric such as TPU-DMF, CBP-TPU-DMF, TVR-TPU-DMF, CBP-TV-TPU-DMF, NA-TV-TPU-DMF, NA-CBP-TV-TPU-DMF. Structural, chromatic, and spectral reflection of CM coated PA-6,6 fabric was investigated by scanning electron microscopy, color measurement spectrophotometer, and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. CBP formulated PA-6,6 fabric was significantly remarked as maximum light absorber in both visible and near-infrared spectrum without allowing other parameters of treated PA-6,6 fabric. Therefore, minimum light reflection principle of CBP was indicated as camouflage material for camouflage textile coloration/finishing/patterning of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near-infrared spectrum. PA-6,6 fabric is very common fabrication for defense clothing, weapon, and vehicle netting against every combat background. This approach of simultaneous spectrum probe may be extended for concealment of target signature against high-performance defense surveillance.

Keywords: camouflage coloration, carbon black pigment, polyurethane, reflection, visible–near infrared

1. Introduction

Camouflage textiles are incorporated with clothing of special workers and multidimensional equipment in the vein of army, air force, navy, marines, coastal

guards, paramilitary forces, uniforms for officers and soldiers in defense forces, tents, shelters and sheets, sandbags, flak jackets, helmets, camouflaged combat and flight uniforms, covering airplanes, guns and boats, creating deceptions, making armored vehicles, and so on [1]. Key parameters of camouflage coloration are spectral bandwidth of target signature, spectral characteristics of combat background, and reflectivity [2, 3]. Reflection of pigment formulation must match with combat background for design of high-performance camouflage textiles. Polyamide and polyester fabric coloration were experimented with carbon black pigment (CBP). The camouflage effect of CBP was recommended in near infrared (NIR), 1000–1200 nm [4]. Camouflage coloration was trialed with CBP for formulation of colorant on synthetic and regenerated textiles [5]. Visible-camouflage coloration was also investigated with pigment, reactive and vat dyes. Combination of CBP with other synthetic colorant depicted more prominent hue of black [6, 7]. CBP was used for camouflage coloration of polyethylene terephthalate textiles in comparison with natural brown hue against desert combat background. Hence, CBP property was also suggested for NIR camouflage [8]. In this experiment, reflection of CBP was compared with a synthetic dyes telon violet 3R (TVR).

1.1 Properties of CBP for suitability of technical coloration

CBP has versatile industrial applications as a pigment, which imparts a black hue [9, 10]. CBP is the most suitable for defense textiles due to having maximum properties of protection textiles. CBP has weatherability, chemical resistance [11, 12], abrasion resistance [13], electroconductivity [11], alkali resistance, light fastness [7], hydrophobicity [14], which are major considerations for coloration of defense textiles. CBP has ester bond, thioester bond, amide bond, amino bond, carbonyl bond, thiocarbonyl bond, sulfonyl bond [12], aldehyde bond, hydroxyl bond, hydrogen bond [9]. Crystalline CBP shows a high order of reactivity [15]. Quantitatively more application of CBP is found in the rubber industry to accelerate its mechanical properties, such as resistance to abrasion. CBP is generally termed as active carbon for improving the mechanical properties of rubber. CBP is widely used for black coloration in paints, varnishes, carbon paper, ribbons, printing inks [13, 16, 17]. Plastic articles, metal articles, wood, paper, inorganic materials [11], and polyamide fabric coloration with 70% nitric acid (NA) [18]. Oxidization process was used to improve the coloring property of printing inks, paint, and black coloration [13, 16, 17]. Due to hydrophobicity of CBP, it is difficult to apply textile substances. So CBP needs to be oxidized for improving jetness by chromic acid, ozone, hydrogen peroxide, sodium hypochloride, potassium permanganate, NA [14, 19] and sulfuric acid [7, 14]. CBP was grafted with hydrophilic polymeric monomer (alkali or ammonium carboxylate) for improving water compatibility and dispersibility [20]. CBP has dusting tendency [21], it is combined with the carrier to impart chromatic hue. CBP constituted generally as a pigment [22]. CBP with acid surface groupings is particularly suitable with binders [23]. Particle size, surface structure, surface size, pH, and dispersibility of CBP need to be considered for every polymeric binding system [24–26]. Diameter and nigrometer index of CBP critically modify the color of CBP. CBP shows high color for diameter 13 and 15 nm and nigrometer index 63 and 68, respectively. CBP depicts medium color for diameter 17, 20 nm and nigrometer index 71, 76. CBP shows regular color for diameter 25 nm and nigrometer index 80 [11]. Different categories of CBP are fisher lamp-black (particle size 44 nm, p^H 7, carbon 96.7%, oxygen 0.9%, nitrogen 0.0%, sulfur 1.5%, hydrogen 0.6%), degussa special black (particle size 20 nm, p^H 7, carbon 85.6%, oxygen 13.1%, nitrogen 0.3%, sulfur 0.4%, hydrogen 0.6%) and degussa color black FW 200 (particle size 13 nm, p^H : 7, carbon 79.2%, oxygen 19.3%, nitrogen

0.4%, sulfur 0.4%, hydrogen 0.7%) [27]. Natural gas and hydrocarbon are the raw materials of CBP [28]. Coarser particle of CBP shows lower depth of color, and finer particle shows higher depth of color [23] due to its difference in scattering values with difference in size and surface area. Hence CBP can be applied for chromatic modification of textile substances such as PA-6,6, cotton, wool, and acrylic fabric.

1.2 Properties of TPU for suitability of textile coating

Thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) elastomers are a cross-linking agent having low density and high resiliency [29], dispersibility, and polymeric film forming ability was considered the criterion for applying in acid medium coating. TPU is also applicable for printing paste formulation of synthetic fabric coloration [30]. TPU creates capsule shell of CBP [31]. TPU was formulated for the dispersion of pigment [18]. TPU has structural form of hydroxy-terminated polybutadiene and polyether-ester based prepolymers with diisocyanates such as hexamethylene diisocyanate [32]. Chemical reaction between polyols and polyisocyanates compounds existing hydroxyl groups reacts with isocyanates [18]. Therefore, structural features and properties of TPU are suitable for textile coating, textile finishing and printing.

2. Technical approach of camouflage textiles formulation with CBP

Reviewed patent and publications of CBP-based coloration exhibit that CBP has enumerated applications of coloring agent but limited applications on textile coloration. Simultaneous spectrum probe camouflage coloration is almost new concept in camouflage engineering. CBP has harmonized with the demanded textile properties for defense textiles such as low reflection, weatherability, chemical resistance, good rubbing fastness, and light-fastness properties, etc. Light scattering/absorbing principle of CBP materials have been predicted the possibility of deceiving reflection against combat background. CBP has multidimensional color forming functional groups such as carbonyl group, amide group, carboxyl group, which can deceive the surrounding color. The color tone of this functional group differs in spectral responses in Vis–NIR absorbance or reflectance-based spectrophotometric color evaluation and Vis–NIR spectral responses against wavelength. CBP has possibility to modify the hue of other color forming functional group. Light falling on CBP treated fabric diffuses or light is absorbed by the CBP influencing the chromatic hue/hiding the color hue. Hence the chromatic behavior of CBP on textile surface and its moiety with other colorant need to be identified for camouflage coloration. Color combination with CBP may conceal the chromatic hue of red, green, yellow, blue. CBP can be applied on textile substances for special worker's clothing like camouflage textiles as defense wear or protection tents for special requirements. There is very limited research on CBP formulated properties introduced for augmentation of camouflage textiles. Camouflage textiles can be identified by illumination properties of chromatic hue by spectral responses in both visible and NIR ranges as the chromatic hue in Vis and NIR range are not same. The reflectance can be identified by simultaneous spectrum in Vis and NIR region easily by using VIS–NIR/UV–Vis/UV–Vis–NIR reflectance spectroscopy.

3. Materials

130 GSM PA-6,6 knitted fabric collected from local supplier was used for experimentation. Water-insoluble and laboratory-grade CBP was used for PA-6,6 fabric

coloration. TPU-Texalon 598 A in tiny pellet, white color in appearance was selected as cross-linking agent. N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF) was used as solvent for making a viscous solution of TPU. Laboratory-grade NA (70%) moiety was used for liquid-phase oxidation of CBP surface, functioning as hydrophilic vehicle of CBP-TV R into PA-6,6 and overall enhancement of rheopectic property in composite mixture (CM). The components of CM were used without further purification as received from supplier. Mathis laboratory hot plate, Werser Mathis AG, Rutisbergstrasse 3, CH-8156, Oberhasli/Zurich, Switzerland, automatic temperature controllable dryer, and a hand-operated coating processor with 2 mm roller were used for camouflage coloration.

3.1 Structure of CBP-TV R-TPU chemical compounds formulated for experimentation

The chemical structure of CBP [9], TVR [33], TPU compounds [29], and PA-6,6 fabric [34] have been shown below in **Figures 1–4**.

Figure 1.
Chemical structure of CBP used in this experimentation.

Figure 2.
Structure of TVR used in this experimentation.

Figure 3.
 Polymeric structure of TPU cross-linker used in this experimentation.

Figure 4.
 Polymeric structure of PA-6,6 used in this experimentation.

4. Methods and preparation

Solution of TPU-DMF and its other variant of five more composite-mixed-complex formation of TPU-DMF were categorized and coded by CM-01 (TPU-DMF), CM-02 (CBP-TPU-DMF), CM-03 (TVR-TPU-DMF), CM-04 (CBP-TV-TPU-DMF), CM-05 (NA-TV-TPU-DMF), and CM-06 (CBP-NA-TV-TPU-DMF).

4.1 Composite mixture-1

Tiny pellet of TPU (3%) was solubilized into DMF to form TPU-DMF solution, using a mini magnetic stirrer and an automatic shaker for 10 days in room temperature. The stirring and shaking periods were repeatedly checked and waited for maximum label of solubilization of TPU. The extended time was used for highest level of solubilization as no additional testing was implemented for this process of solubilization. TPU-DMF solution was added for each complex formation of CBP-TV-NA.

4.2 Composite mixture-2

CBP 0.50 g and solution of 3% TPU-DMF were mixed in a beaker. It was kept on hot plate for 40 min at 80°C temperature for complex formation of CBP-TPU-DMF. TPU shell wall was kept just higher than the softening point. The droplet of TPU-DMF solution was poured into CBP until the viscous paste formation of CBP. It was continuously stirred in heating condition for making globule formation of CBP-TPU-DMF.

4.3 Composite mixture-3

The mixing process of TVR, 1.50 g and solution of 3% TPU-DMF were continued in a beaker. TVR-TPU-DMF was kept on hot plate for 40 min at 80°C temperature for complex formation. The droplet stirring process was followed for making bead formation of TVR-TPU-DMF. The droplet of TPU-DMF solution was poured into TVR until the viscous paste formation of TVR and continuously stirred for making bead formation of TVR-TPU-DMF.

4.4 Composite mixture-4

CBP 0.50 g, TVR 1.50 g, and solution of 3% TPU-DMF were mixed in a beaker and kept on hot plate for 40 min at 80°C temperature for complex formation of CBP-TPU-DMF. Firstly, the droplet of TPU-DMF solution was discharged into CBP until the viscous paste formation of CBP and continuously stirred for making bead formation of CBP-TPU-DMF. Consecutively and individually, the droplet of TPU-DMF solution was poured into TVR until the viscous paste formation of TVR and continuously stirred for making blob formation of TVR-TPU-DMF. Finally, a simultaneous complex formation was generated with the CBP-TPU-DMF and TVR-TPU-DMF (1:1) and formed a complex of CBP-TV-TPU-DMF.

4.5 Composite mixture-5

TVR 1.50 g, NA (50%) and solution of 3% TPU-DMF were combined in beaker and heated for 40 min at 80°C temperature for complex formation of NA-TV-TPU-DMF. The droplet of TPU-DMF and NA solution was poured into TVR until the viscous paste formation of TVR and continuously stirred for making bead formation of NA-TV-TPU-DMF.

4.6 Composite mixture-6

CBP 0.50 g, TVR 1.50 g, NA (50%), and solution of 3% TPU-DMF were formed as paste in a beaker and kept on hot plate for 40 min at 80°C temperature for complex formation of CBP-TV-TPU-DMF. Firstly, the droplet of NA solution and the droplet of TPU-DMF (1:1) were poured into CBP for liquid phase oxidation of CBP and bead formation of CBP-TPU-DMF. The process was continued until the viscous paste formation, continuously stirred for making bead formation of CBP-TPU-DMF. Sequentially and separately, the droplet of TPU-DMF-NA was poured into TVR until the viscous paste formation of TVR and continuously stirred for making bead formation of NA-TV-TPU-DMF. Finally, the paste of CBP-TPU-DMF and NA-TV-TPU-DMF were combined for complex formation of CBP-TV-TPU-DMF.

4.7 Coating on PA-6,6 fabric

PA-6,6 fabric was cut into required sizes (width-3inch \times length-6inch) was uncontaminated with dipping in deionized water, then dried 50 min at 80°C in a heating chamber, and then the fabric was relaxed and cooled for 30 min at room temperature. Back part of PA-6,6 fabric was wrapped with aluminum foil paper, having thickness less than 0.2 mm for creating the artificial plain surface on the backside of fabric. This method can be repeated and applied for different types of plain roller surface of industrial coating machine. The fabric ends were tightly attached and laid on coating plate by thin adhesive paper and then the coating roller was used for hand coating system. This method was followed repeatedly for three-stroke coating process for even dispersion of TPU-DMF and its other variant of five more composite-mixed-complex mixture on fabric surface. Decontaminated PA-6,6 was coated with TPU-DMF, a three-stroke coating process following first stroke coating-by second stroke coating and then third stroke coating for even dispersion of TPU-DMF. Similar coating process was thus carried out with CM-02 (CBP-TPU-DMF), CM-03 (TVR-TPU-DMF), CM-04 (CBP-TPU-DMF), CM-05 (NA-TPU-DMF) and CM-06 (CBP-NA-TPU-DMF). Also, for further research experimentation purpose, sequential overlapped coating of one formulation over other was also carried out by coating sequentially CM-2 (CBP-TPU-DMF) in first stroke coating process, and then CM-03 (TVR-TPU-DMF) coating was made on it by second stroke coating and finally then CM-04 (CBP-TPU-DMF) was coated on it by third stroke coating process. Similarly, CM-02 (CBP-TPU-DMF) was coated by first stroke coating process and then CM-03 (TVR-TPU-DMF) was coated by second stroke coating and finally CM-06 (CBP-NA-TPU-DMF) was sequentially coated by third stroke coating process. All the coated PA 6,6 fabrics were dried at 60°C for 60 min to proceed for testing.

5. Testing methods

5.1 Color measurement spectrophotometer

CIE, color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^*) were measured by Hunter lab reflectance spectrophotometer, Color Flex EZ; model, 45/0 LAV; under testing conditions with geometry, 45°/0°; viewing area, large; D65 illuminant/10° standard observer; room temperature, 18°C. This hunter lab illuminant spectrophotometer uses a xenon flash lamp to illuminate the test specimen, PA-6,6. The tonal variation of PA 6,6 fabric was subjected to colorimetric evaluation for determining CIE color coordinates L^* , a^* , b^* values. The Hunter Lab reflectance spectrophotometer was calibrated in terms of highest darker and highest lighter by using standard black and white standard, for checking and matching standard values kept in machine software. To ensure sample opaqueness by minimizing the transparency of incident light; test specimen, fabric size (width-3inch \times length 6-inch) was single folded in lengthwise (width 3-inch \times length 3-inch) for placing on reflectance port.

5.2 Fourier transform infrared spectrometry

NIR scanning of treated and untreated PA-6,6 fabric was performed by FTIRS. A NIR background was standardized under diffuse reflection standard. Every sample is covered by sample cup to create reflection environment under a specified black standard, which is termed as “spectralon reflection.” The sample port has sapphire/crystal window to capture reflection of sample. Machine-specified glass vial was

Figure 5. Front view of FTIRS-NIR (a) uncovered diffuse sample port, (b) covered sample port with standardized black reference.

used for powder sample measurement of CBP-TVR. **Figure 5a** shows the sapphire window-sample port of FTIRS-NIR. **Figure 5b** shows the sample scanning condition under machine specified black standard.

5.3 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image was captured by TM 4000Plus model, Tabletop SEM, HITACHI, Japan. 15 KV electron acceleration was selected for every scanning of SEM. 100 magnification was performed for all image except NA treated fabric. NA-TPU-DMF and NA-TVR-TPU-DMF were captured at 25 magnifications to connote TPU effect in NA-CM-PA-6,6. Carbon conductive black tape was used for each sample mounting.

6. Results and discussion

6.1 Characterization and structural analysis by SEM

Figure 6, uncoated PA 6,6 fabric (a); TPU-DMF coated PA 6,6 fabric (b); CBP-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (c); TVR-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (d); CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (e); NA-TVR-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (f); NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (g); blended CBP in water (h); blended CBP after 24 hour precipitation (i); blended CBP after 48 hour precipitation (j); 3% TPU in DMF (k), 3% TPU in DMF after addition of five drop NA; 5% of 70% NA (l); solidification slice of TPU-DMF in the presence of NA (l); SEM magnification of CBP particle (m) and its color thresholding structure of CBP particle (n); particle size of CBP (o); SEM magnification of TVR particle (p) and its color thresholding image of particle size (q); SEM magnification of PA 6,6 uncoated fabric (r); TPU-DMF coated PA 6,6 fabric (s) and its color thresholding image to refine TPU-DMF on fabric surface (t); CBP-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (u) and its color thresholding image to signify TPU-DMF on fabric surface (v); TVR-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (w) and its color thresholding image to identify TPU-DMF on fabric surface (x); CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (y) and its color thresholding image to signify TPU-DMF on fabric surface (z); NA-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (z₁); NA-TVR-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (z₂); NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF coated PA-6,6 fabric (z₃).

Figure 6 (i, j), water medium diluted CBP has been shown to signify the dispersibility of raw CBP. 0.5gm CBP was blended (30 minutes) with 150 ml

Figure 6. Photograph of treated and untreated fabric (a-h), CBP and TPU-DMF derivative solution (i-l), SEM and color thresholding image of treated and untreated PA 6,6 fabric (m-z₃).

deionized water. The solution showed a precipitation/aggregation after keeping 24 and 48 hours in non-shaking condition. **Figure 6** (m) shows the structure of CBP. CBP particles are aggregated in different direction like a net structure which is demonstrated by red threshold, image **6** (n). The magnified cross section of CBP signifies the particle size, water insolubility, and randomly oriented microstructure of surface for diffuse reflection due to surface roughness, **Figure 6** (m-q). Particle size of CBP denotes the higher degree of cracking on CBP coated PA-6,6 fabric rather than TVR coated surface, **Figure 6** (u-x). The existing of CBP-TPU-DMF has been clearly identified on PA 6,6 coated fabric, **Figure 6** (u, v, z₃). The cementing of CBP-TPU-DMF-PA-6,6 is higher in comparison with NA-CBP-TPU-PA-6,6. CBP-TPU formed a darker appearance due to higher prominence of black region on CBP-coated surface. CBP coating with TPU-DMF binder showed a cross-linking in CBP-TPU-DMF-PA-6,6. The functional group of CBP (-COOH) and the functional group of TPU (-NHCO) was formed a CBP-TPU matrix on the surface of PA-6,6 fabric. **Figure 6** (t, v, x, z, z₁, z₂, z₃), TPU was visualized in SEM image as whitish color surface. The prominence of TPU was recorded as minor when it was formed matrix with CBP. TPU binder was almost uniformly distributed on PA-6,6 fabric surface, **Figure 6**, (t-z, z₃). TPU-CBP was implanted and well dispersed on

PA-6,6 surfaces. **Figure 6** (k, l), NA-TPU-DMF was also characterized in the presence of NA and TPU was showed freezing tendency. The application of TPU on PA-6,6 fabric was also confirmed by SEM, **Figure 6** (z_1, z_2).

6.1.1 Coupling of CM and SEM evidence of material suitability for visible-NIR camouflage

Figure 6 (o- z_3) shows the evidence of almost suitability of CBP material. The simultaneous applications of NA-TPU-CBP-TVR on PA-6,6 fabric surface have been confirmed by SEM image. The structural representation and coupling with similar functional groups have been revealed with individual coupling reactions with PA-6,6 **Figures 7–12**. Oxidized and aqueous CBP have amide group. PA-6,6 has also similar group, thus it may create a coupling of CBP-PA-6,6. CBP has amine group and TVR has also amine group. There is a possibility of bonding between CBP-TVR. Similarly, CBP has carbonyl group and TPU has also carbonyl group, thus CBP-TPU moiety may form in CBP modified PA-6,6 fabric. Carbonyl carbon of CBP may be bonded with two hydrogen atoms of TPU. Hence there is possibility of cross-linking. TPU may be adsorbed by CBP and dispersed the carbon black due to its structural formation of steric hindrance.

6.1.1.1 Coupling of TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6

Figure 6 (s, t) shows that polymeric coupling of PA-6,6-TPU, which are bonded with common functional group carbonyl (**Figure 7**). Structural resemblance of carbonyl and amine functional group in TPU-PA-6,6 may show the evidence of yellowish and greenish illumination on TPU treated PA-6,6 and without treated PA-6,6.

6.1.1.2 Coupling of CBP-TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6

Figure 6 (u, v) shows the coupling among PA-6,6-CBP-TPU. CBP shows multifunctional group including carboxyl, hydroxyl, aldehyde, carbonyl, ether, and it may have other functional group including color forming groups (**Figure 8**). CBP-TPU has amino group and carbonyl group. PA-6,6 has amino group and carbonyl

Figure 7.
Coupling of TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6.

Figure 8.
Coupling of CBP-TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6.

group. Amino group and carbonyl group remaining PA-6,6 surface may generate reddish and yellowish hue but the reflectance of yellowish may be weakened and, it may be turned to bluish coordinates. So, the mechanism of tonal variation on textile surface/hiding of color hue may have occurred due to multidimensional color reflection of different hue as CBP has various numbers of functional groups for different color formation on same surface. Structure of CBP surface may also vibrate the camouflage concept of illumination due to spherical surface of CBP. COOH, carbonyl group, and OH group presence in CBP may reflect reddish hue. Amine group may be an indication of yellowish hue. Therefore, color combination of CBP may show darker hue by reflecting almost black hue. When any group with colorant of yellow, blue, and red are mixed with CBP, it may hide the chromatic intensity of added colorant and makes the dull shade to the observer due to remaining multifunctional and multicolored forming group. The multifunctional mechanism of hiding tendency of color hue of CBP may be functioning as key principle of camouflage coloration on textile substances.

6.1.1.3 Coupling of TVR-TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6

Figure 6 (w, x) shows the coupling of amide group among PA-6,6-TPU-TV (Figure 9). TVR dyes has nitro group, amino group, and azo group. Nitro group may create blueish/yellowish hue, azo group may contain red/yellowish hue and amine group may prominent the yellowish reflection on the surface.

6.1.1.4 Coupling of CBP-TV- TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6

Figure 6 (y, z) represents the NH coupling between CBP and PA-6,6 (Figure 10). Benzene coupling may occur between CBP and TVR. Correspondingly

Figure 9.
Coupling of TVR-TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6.

Figure 10.
Coupling of CBP-TV- TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6.

carbonyl bonding is also evidenced between TPU and PA-6,6 due to structural view in SEM magnification. TVR dyes has nitro group, azo group and amino group. PA-6,6 and TPU has also amino group. Nitro group in TVR may create bluish and yellowish hue, azo group depicts red/yellowish hue and amine group may enhance the reflection of yellow hue. CBP and TVR has similarity in benzene group and amino group. TVR encompasses nitro group and azo group, which may reflect bluish and yellowish tone, azo group may illuminate red/yellowish hue and amine group may accelerate the yellow color reflection. Hydrophilic coupling between amine group of TVR and PA-6,6 may not be happened due to absence of hydrophilic vehicle NA. CBP has COOH, OH group, amino group, and carbonyl group, which may create chromatic change of color hue with another functional group.

6.1.1.5 Coupling of NA-TVR-TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6

Figure 6 (z_2) shows that amine group of TVR has related to both PA-6,6 and TPU, it seems the structural similarity (**Figure 11**). TVR has nitro group. Amino group of PA-6,6 and TPU may create a good color combination in NA-TVR-TPU-DMF when oxidized CBP has not been used in this process of coloration. For comparison, the reaction of oxidized carbon has been remarked with arrow sign connected with nitro group. In this coupling, there is no function of oxidized carbon due to missing of CBP in CM.

6.1.1.6 Coupling of NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6

Figure 6 (z_3) shows amide linkage between CBP and PA-6,6 (**Figure 12**). Amine bonding may create between TVR and PA-6,6. Carbonyl bonding may form among CBP-TPU-PA-6,6. Oxidized carbon produces NO_2 and it has been showed with

Figure 11.
Coupling of NA-TVR-TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6.

Figure 12.
Coupling of NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6.

arrow marked to mention the similar group of TVR dyes (NO₂). The structure of oxidized carbon may be changed due to NA oxidation of CBP. The mechanism may influence the altering of reflection/wavelength in visible-NIR spectrum. The simultaneous combination of oxidized carbon and CBP modified PA-6,6 may replace the surface reflection significantly. The color forming functional group has been predicted the changing factors of chromatic hue. PA-6,6 has carbonyl group and amine group. TPU has also carbonyl group. Remaining unusual functional group of CBP like COOH, OH may reflect reddish hue, carbonyl group may reflect greenish/yellowish hue and amine group may illuminate greenish/reddish hue. Spherical shape of CBP may hide the real illumination of nitro and azo group in TVR when nitro group may reflect bluish and yellowish tone and azo group may illuminate red/yellowish hue. Hence the actual prominence of hue is being decisively changed/hided by the multifunctional tonal group of CBP.

6.2 Camouflage and chromatic analysis in visible spectrum

Established Beer–Lambert law [35] of optical absorption of material, $A = \epsilon lc$, A = optical absorption of materials, ϵ = absorptivity of the materials, l = optical path length, c = concentration of the materials. The Beer–Lambert law can be implemented for the optical absorption on PA-6,6 fabric surface in different wavelength. The variation of optical absorption of CBP can be predicted for the feasibility of camouflage coloration. Optical absorption on PA-6,6 fabric surface versus replacement of CIE color hue is proportionally related for camouflage coloration. Higher degree of optical absorption depicts the reduced intensity of chromatic hue. In this experimentation, A = optical absorption of PA-6,6 fabric surface, ϵ = absorptivity of CBP-TVR-TPU, l = optical path length in 400–700 nm and c = concentration of CM which are TPU-DMF, CBP-TPU-DMF, TVR-TPU-DMF, CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF, NA-TVR-TPU-DMF, NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF. CIE optical absorption and reflection of chromatic hue have been studied in optical path length, 400–700 nm. The concept demonstrates that “more optical absorption on textile surface = less reflection on textile surface = altering the chromatic hue = deceiving the target detection”. Therefore, CBP can create chromatic variation on textile surface and confuse the target detection to the observer. But optical path length 400–700 nm and concentration of surface CBP materials can alter the chromatic behaviors of PA-6,6 fabric. Camouflage coloration was observed in complex formation of CBP for surface hue modification of PA 6,6 fabric. The color outcome was identified based on light absorption and reflection of CIE color hue, L^* , a^* , b^* . The reflection changing of CBP-NA-TVR-TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6 fabric was remarked in terms of CIE color coordinates. CBP-NA-TVR-TPU-DMF treated fabric showed comparatively less reflection of light and color hue hiding tendency.

6.2.1 Spectrophotometric color comparison of treated PA-6,6 and untreated PA-6,6

Figures 13–16 illustrate that CBP-TPU-DMF, CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF and NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6 fabric modified the light absorption and intensity of chromatic hue in CIE L^* , a^* , b^* due to existence of CBP. The value of L^* , a^* , b^* represents higher light absorption and minor reflection of chromatic hue, which may be elucidated the reflection changing of CBP modified PA-6,6 surface. The moderation of chromatic hue intensity identifies camouflage categories of reflection in visible range due to having a minimum value of lightness (L^*), minimizing the value of red-green coordinates (a^*) and blue-yellow coordinates (b^*). **Figures 13–15** demonstrate that NA oxidized CBP shows maximum absorption of light than other CBP treated PA-6,6. NA oxidized NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF reveals

Figure 13. CIE comparison of lightness hue (L^*) of treated and untreated PA-6,6 fabric.

Figure 14. CIE comparison of greenish/reddish hue (a^*) of treated and untreated PA-6,6 fabric.

Figure 15. CIE comparison of bluish/yellowish hue (b^*) of treated and untreated PA-6,6 fabric.

CIE, $L^* = 14.33$, $a^* = 0.15$, $b^* = 0.30$ in wavelength, 400–700 nm. CBP is practically insoluble in water. In NA-CBP-TVR-DMF, NA is functioning to form hydrophilic transformation of CBP-TVR, as well as same time TPU-DMF is performing as artificial cross-linker between CM and PA-6,6 without influencing color reflection of any other component in CM. Thus, oxidized CBP molecules may be hidden the

sulfonated group of TVR dyes in NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF mixture whereas CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF does not exhibit hiding of red and blue color hue due to absence of NA and lacking hydrophilic reaction. CM of CBP-TPU-DMF and NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF exhibit nearest of neutral value in three-dimensional CIE color coordinates. CBP-TVR-DMF mixture reveals the positive value of a^* remaining reflection of reddish hue although theoretically the CM cannot make a complex due to absence of NA. Here, NA is not acting as hydrophilic vehicle of CBP in this CM. A proper reaction of TVR-CBP colorant may be held in between polyamide-6,6 and NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF. In general theory of chromaticity, the color channel, $a^* = 0$ and $b^* = 0$ displays the true natural/neutral black color. The color wheel of NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF shows $a^* = 0.15$, $b^* = 0.30$, therefore CBP has a propensity to neutral black. Similarly, NA free mixture of CBP-TPU-DMF and NA-CBP-TVR-TPU-DMF may prove minimum L^* value due to having higher absorption of light and very minimum reflection of light. Therefore, CBP modified PA-6,6 may create a deceiving environment of color hue to the observers. Thus, a neutral or minimizing tendency of a^* and b^* value can create the effect of hiding reddish hue which have an outcome of declining reflection of color molecules and increasing the absorbency of light. CBP modified PA-6,6 fabric surface may conceal the reflection of remaining TVR coloring molecule of red, green, blue, yellow. CBP treated surface may be decisively reduced the formation of cone shaped receptor for visible range of color vision. Rough surface of CBP treated PA-6,6 may generate the properties of diffuse reflection. D65 light source measurement of the reflectance characteristics of CBP is the key phenomenon of camouflage have been demonstrated in visible range 400–700 nm.

6.2.1.1 Spectrophotometric color combination of untreated PA-6,6 and TPU-DMF-PA-6,6

Figures 13–16; TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6 fabric and untreated PA-6,6 fabric was compared for identification of three-dimensional chromatic hue (L^* , a^* , b^*) and its effects on PA-6,6 fabric surface. Spectrophotometric color combination of PA-6,6 shows greenish ($a^* = -0.79$) and yellowish ($b^* = 2.1$) hue, which are the nearest of

Figure 16. Tristimulus intensity for variations and comparison of CIE L^* , a^* , b^* and representation of spectrophotometric color combination on a (PA-6,6), B (PA-6,6 + TPU-DMF), C (PA-6,6 + CBP + TPU-DMF), D (PA-6,6 + TVR + TPU-DMF), E (PA-6,6 + CBP + TVR + TPU-DMF), F (PA-6,6 + NA + TVR + TPU-DMF), G (PA-6,6 + NA + CBP + TVR + TPU-DMF).

neutral hue. A maximum value of $L^* = 92.29$ indicates almost white color in gray hue on fabric surface. Hence color combination of PA-6,6 indicates the maximum reflection of hue. Oppositely TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6 depicts greenish ($a^* = -0.90$) and yellowish ($b^* = 1.96$) hue, which also identify the nearest of neutral hue. A maximum value of $L^* = 92.29$ indicates almost white color/gray hue on the surface of fabric. Therefore, the color combination of TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6 also remarks the maximum reflection in CIE color coordinates. So, it can be compared that the reflection properties of CIE color hue are almost nearest/similarity in untreated PA-6,6 and TPU-DMF treated PA-6,6 fabric. It can be strongly said that TPU-DMF has minor effect on color changing. This study can be simply recommended for application of TPU-DMF for cross-linking of camouflage materials on textile surface.

6.2.1.2 Spectrophotometric color combination of CBP-TPU-DMF-PA-6,6

Complex application of CM-2 shows red ($a^* = 0.08$) and bluish ($b^* = -0.84$) hue which are the nearest of neutral hue. A minimum value of $L^* = 14.21$ have been pointed to almost black color tone on the surface of PA-6,6 fabric. CBP-TPU-DMF treated fabric shows less reflection of color hue. It may clarify gray hue, which is tending to black and hiding the base color tone (yellow and green) of PA 6,6 fabric surface, which is replaced with opposite coordinates in color wheel.

6.2.1.3 Spectrophotometric color combination of TVR-TPU-DMF-PA-6,6

Complex application of CM-3 states reddish ($a^* = 22.45$) and bluish ($b^* = -13.30$) hue on PA-6,6 fabric. A maximum value of $L^* = 22.22$ signifies the actual violet color of TVR on the surface of fabric. TVR added CM-03 accelerates the reddish and bluish hue.

6.2.1.4 Spectrophotometric color combination CBP-TPV-TPU-DMF-PA-6,6

CBP added CM-04 indicates minor decreasing the R/color hue in reddish and bluish hue although it seems the combination of CBP-TPV was not properly dispersed on the surface due to absence of hydrophilic vehicle, NA. Spectrophotometric color combination shows reddish ($a^* = 13.06$) and bluish ($b^* = -12.95$) hue on fabric surface. A maximum value of $L^* = 32.34$ indicated the hiding tendency of reddish and bluish hue on the surface of fabric when CBP was mixed in CM. Even though proper reaction of complex formation was not found due to absence of NA vehicle.

6.2.1.5 Spectrophotometric color combination NA-TPV-TPU-DMF-PA-6,6

NA added CM-05 shows that reflection of color hue increases. Spectrophotometric color combination of NA-TPV-TPU-DMF depicts reddish ($a^* = 24.90$) and yellowish ($b^* = 26.75$) hue. A maximum value of $L^* = 28.2$ indicates the increasing of reddish and bluish hue when NA was mixed in the CM. This is clarified that dyes molecules showed higher affinity with PA-6,6 when NA was mixed with TVR dyes.

6.2.1.6 Spectrophotometric color combination of NA-CBP-TPV-TPU-DMF-PA-6,6

CBP added CM-06 may be concealed the red and yellow hue of PA-6,6 surface when gray color wheel tends to black color hue. It seems that NA is functioning as

hydrophilic transformation of CBP-TVR into PA-6,6. Combination of CBP mixture shows more absorbency of light as per less value of L^* . CBP modified PA-6,6 may be influenced the illumination of reflection of light/color hue. CBP modified PA-6,6 has an impact of camouflage creation and hiding factor of reddish and yellowish color under practical observation of CIE chromaticity-reflection mechanism. CBP may be acted as diminish behavior of reflection on PA-6,6 fabric surface which can create a camouflage effect of fabric under consideration CIE, L^* , a^* , b^* . It can be said that NA increased the thixotropic properties of CBP-TVR colorant for good level of CBP-TVR dispersion.

6.3 Camouflage and reflection comparison in NIR spectrum

Maximum reflection percentage of CM has been summarized in **Figure 17** for comparison among raw CBP, untreated and treated PA-6,6 fabric. The original FTIR spectra has been cited in supporting information, **Figures S1** and **S2**. FTIRS was used to reveal camouflage phenomenon of CBP in terms of low reflection principle in NIR, 1000–2500 nm. The range is covered by hyperspectral camera for target detection. CBP almost absorbs all spectrum in NIR, the intensity of color forming group is very minor for target identification. A narrow reflection profile is visualized for FTIRS scanning of raw CBP and CBP treated PA 6,6 fabric. CBP treated PA 6,6 fabric was detected as low reflection materials for camouflaging in NIR. CBP has maximum number of absorptions, and it has minimum intensity which may generate low reflection chromatic signal against combat background in NIR. Reflection of CBP spectra is always lower than any other combination of PA-6,6 fabric. Comparatively TVR combination cannot decline the reflectance of PA-6,6-TPU-DMF. CBP-TVR combination can highly decrease the reflection of PA-6,6-TPU-DMF. This concept of CBP-reflection can be implemented for synthetic dyes combination with CBP. It has been clearly signified that CBP treated fabric may act as target concealment under low reflection principle in NIR spectrum.

Figure 17.
Comparison of maximum reflection (%) in NIR spectrum.

7. Conclusion

L* coordinates reflect the lightness of color intensity to the observers ranges from 0 (completely black) to 100 (completely white). The luminous intensity and degree of lightness can be perceived by the target observers in remote sensing device. The amount of CBP adsorbed on PA-6,6 surface controls a* coordinates (red/green) and b* coordinates (yellow/blue), which identify the lightness of color perception for CBP modified PA-6,6 fabric to the observers. Hence, CBP influences a* coordinates for reflection of red or green hue to the target observers. Correspondingly CBP also effects on b* coordinates, which reflect yellow or blue color tone to the observers. The intensity of object reflection modifies the perception of red, green, blue, yellow color hue to the observers. Furthermore, CBP treated PA-6,6 fabric may generate diffuse reflection to hide the color hue of combat background. SEM, color measurement spectrophotometer and FTIRS have been confirmed the low reflection coloration of PA-6,6 fabric both in visible-NIR spectrum. The experimentation on CBP based camouflage textiles can confirm the feasibility of camouflage properties development on textile substances. So, it can be suggested that CBP can be implemented for camouflage coloration of textile materials in terms of low reflection principle. CBP can be combined with synthetic dyes of camouflage design for camouflage textiles in simultaneous spectrum probe in visible-NIR. CBP may be accepted for versatile applications of weapon/vehicle coloration in terms of low reflection principle of camouflage coloration. TPU can also be recommended as a suitable cross-linking agent due to transparent property of TPU without influencing the reflection properties of CBP on PA-6,6 fabric.

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Abbreviations

CBP	Carbon black pigment
CM	Composite mixture
NR	Near infrared
NA	Nitric acid

TVR Telon violet 3R
TPU Thermoplastic polyurethane
DMF N, N-dimethylformamide
PA-6,6 Polyamide-6,6

Appendix

Figure S1.
Comparison of reflection (%) in NIR spectrum (part-a).

Figure S2.
Comparison of reflection (%) in NIR spectrum (part-B).

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Camouflage Assessment of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination

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ABSTRACT

Aluminium powder (AP) formulated polyamide 6, 6 (PA 6, 6) knitted fabric, cotton woven fabric and hollow tubular polyester beg (HTPB) were experimented for spectral, chromatic, and imaging principle of woodland and desertland camouflage textiles in visible (Vis) and infrared (IR) spectrum under three-dimensional background illumination of ultraviolet (UV)-Vis-IR for concealment, detection, recognition and identification (CDRI) of target signature against selected combat background (CB) materials, and selected temperature was also trialled for IR radiation properties of target object (TOB)-CB in terms of CDRI. Cotton, PA 6,6 fabric and HTPB were coated and padded with AP powder formulated polyurethane (PU) based binder. Reflection profile of woodland CB and coated-padded textiles have been depicted in terms of multidimensional illumination properties of Vis imaging such as chromatic intensity, spectral reflection, Kubelka-Munk (K-M) reflectance, color rendering and photonic response related to surveillance imaging. A symmetrical chromatic value (L^* , a^* , b^*) of AP coated fabric has been portrayed for concealment of target signature against woodland CB. Spectral reflection, chromatic illumination, K-M reflectance and scanning electron microscopy have also been critically confirmed five-time durability of color fastness to wash, tested by AATCC method 61-2013. HTPB-phase change material (PCM) formulation has been found temperature controllable effect of TOB in terms of heat energy at limited temperature, 30°C. Heat energy versus target concealment of IR imaging principle can be implemented for high-performance camouflage textiles design. The reflection profile of AP coated fabric can be applied for multidimensional camouflage coloration/patterning/HTPB-PCM based IR camouflage technology and direct applications of defence pavilion/tents/clothing against woodland/desertland CB. Therefore, the key phenomenon of this article has been focused on remote sensing properties of *Eucalyptus* tree, scientific name, *Eucalyptus Mannifera*, a common CB of woodland and AP formulated fabric for defence application against woodland and desertland CB in terms of CDRI of defence surveillance under consideration of laboratory and field trialling of woodland and desertland camouflage textiles assessment in Vis-IR spectrum. Therefore, a standardised methodology of camouflage textiles assessment for CDRI has been established under a new technique with conformist machine and technology which may be a new contribution to carry out further research and development for the fighting protection in combat environment under maintaining a standardized sequence from laboratory trialling to field experimentation in a limited timeframe of research.

Keywords: Camouflage textiles; Woodland/desertland combat background; Ultraviolet; Infrared; Phase change material; Hollow tubular polyester beg

1 INTRODUCTION

Reflectance profile of woodland combat background (CB) and desertland CB is very important parameters for defence target signature assessment of concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI) of target signature. Selection of right camouflage materials for woodland/desertland CB may signify the nearest reflection and chromatic behaviors of greenish leaves/dry leaves/tree bark/sand in comparison with treated textiles. Reflection profile of green leaves (*Populustomentosa* and *Cedrusdeodara*) and disperse dyes treated textiles have been experimented for assessment of woodland camouflaging¹. The reflection profile of camouflage materials in laboratory trialling and implementation of

standardized process of chromatic adaptation in visible (Vis) and infrared (IR) spectrum can signify the indication of CDRI progress for field experimentation. The accuracy of field trialling of camouflage textiles cannot be maintained properly under specific illumination of sunlight due to lighting angle and environmental issue, and other related properties because of interference of CB chromatic hue and the combination of color of known and unknown CB materials. The reflection profile of camouflage textiles is firstly measured with color measurement spectrophotometer, later it is demonstrated with infrared and photo simulation process of camouflaging². The electromagnetic spectrums are replaced by changing the geometry of incident illumination. The geometry of incident illumination may be altered by weather, season, air, water, shadow, shape, moisture, material properties, specular components, diffuse components, etc. The properties of specular components surface (glossy,

intensity, spatial) alter repeatedly due to angular phenomenon of illumination. The properties of diffuse component allow stable properties of object and background. As example, specified tree bark of woodland CB, Eucalyptus tree has different structural features, but spectral characteristics of tree barks are same in terms of cellulosic component and different chromatic hue due to different composition. Spectral symmetry can be considered for concealment of latest surveillance³. Reflectance profile of CB in Vis-IR ranges differs significantly. Reflectance profile of sand and soil accelerates in IR ranges than Vis ranges due to temperature deviation influenced by natural illumination. IR reflectance is declined when moisture of CB materials are reduced⁴, so there is deviations of reflection in terms of properties of CB materials. A large number of experimentation has been conducted on aluminium powder (AP) in terms of electron, geometric, photonic and reflection, but CDRI concepts of AP reflection for special team in defence is still a new application of textile coloration under comparison with woodland and desertland CB⁵. Emissivity of CB-AP materials are the influencing fact for CDRI of AP treated textiles. Heat energy versus temperature is a medium for increasing/decreasing of emissivity, it is a vital fact for CDRI versus AP treated textiles. The AP materials have been significantly designated for CDRI and reflection under multidimensional angle of illumination which is a regular problematic issue to conduct defense research on camouflage textiles under multidimensional CB and CDRI⁶.

This concept of camouflage engineering for CDRI-AP treated textiles has been mainly concentrated on wavelength versus imaging signal versus selected woodland CB materials for CDRI of target signature. UV-Vis-IR is a major part of imaging signal captured by defence surveillance for target detection of opposition team. The sensor of hyperspectral/infrared surveillance is also related to the broader wavelength covered by UV-Vis-IR spectrum. Hence the textile coloration for special force of defence need to consider in broader spectrum in UV-Vis-IR for camouflaging in terms of weapon, tents, location covering, soldiers dress and multidimensional target of protection.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN OF FABRICATION, TECHNICAL FORMULATION, AND CBS

2.1 Materials

130 GSM polyamide 6,6 (PA 6,6) knitted fabric; 310 GSM cotton twill woven fabric; AP, chem-supply Ltd. Australia; polyurethane (PU) based tubicoat (Pu-tubicoat), water insoluble, CHT chemical company Ltd. Australia; PU and dimethyl formamide (DMF) were implemented for technical formulation and coloration in terms of coating-padding techniques. Green leaves, dry leaves, tree bark, scientific name, Eucalyptus Mannifera, Princes Park, Melbourne were used for chromatic and reflectance reference of woodland CB in laboratory stage and field trialling. Green leaves, semi-dried green leaves, dried leaves, dried tree bark were trialled as part of woodland CB materials. First samples of woodland CB were collected in Australian Summer, December-February 2020-21 and second samples of woodland CB were collected in Australian Spring, September-November 2021⁷. Dry sand was collected from Melbourne Sea beach as material of desertland CB. Hollow

tubular polyester beg (HTPB), fabric type: woven, height:14 cm, width: 14 cm was collected from Amer-Sil KETEX private ltd, India. Eicosane, Sigma Aldrich was used as phase change material (PCM) for the measurement of thermal imaging of AP coated HTPB under specified temperature ranges. In field trialling of CDRI, aluminium foil paper (AFP) was used for background reflection measurement as polished surface of AFP in comparison with unpolished AP treated textiles.

2.2 Coating and Padding of PA-6, 6 and Cotton Fabric

4gm AP and 206 g PU-tubicoat were mixed in a beaker by electric blender. Formulated AP paste was coated on PA 6, 6 and cotton fabric. 2 g AP, 74 g PU-tubicoat and 200 mL distilled water were blended in 500 mL beaker for 30 min. The viscosity of solution was measured by automatic viscosity control, Norcross corporation, Newton, Mass, USA. Viscosity was found 10 centipoise assessed by shell cup 3.5. PA-6,6 and cotton fabric were soaked into AP solution for 30 min. The fabric was padded with laboratory padding mangle under high pressure of 22 kp/cm. Similar procedure was repeated for two times. The treated fabric was further padded with 2.5 % PU solution in dimethyl formamide (DMF) followed by two dip and two nip processes of padding. Fabric was dried in drying chamber at 120 °C for 30 min.

2.3 Coating of HTPB and Loading of PCM into the Selected Channel of HTPB

Figure 1, a thin layer AP was formulated by coating process, a modified process of coating but the process can be reversed by industry procedure like coating polyester fabric-hollow fabric design-injecting PCM into HTPB. A 19 channel HTPB, readymade was used for the experimental design of PCM versus thermal imaging of AP coated textiles. 9 channel HTPB was loaded by eicosane for thermal imaging and 10 channel was kept blank for heat energy deviation of eicosane loaded HTPB and eicosane unloaded HTPB for comparison of thermal imaging. HTPB before AP treatment also shown in supporting information, figure S₂ for clarification of HTPB preparation process.

Figure 1. Methodology of thin layer AP coating on HTPB for PCM mechanism of thermal imaging.

3. METHODOLOGY OF TESTING AND IMAGING

PA-6, 6 and cotton fabric were scanned by colorflex EZ spectrophotometer, Hunter lab EasyMatchQC software under the conditions of viewing area geometry: 45°/0°, photometric reflectance: 0-150 %, port dia: 31.8 mm, view dia: 25.4 mm, light source pulsed xenon, number of layer of fabric: 2. TM4000/TM4000Plus, Hitachi, Japan and SC7620 sputter

coater, Quorum, UK were used as set up of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and the testing was conducted by 250 magnifications and 15kV. FLIR T440 camera, USA; IR lens, F = 18 mm; calibrated by national institute of standards and technology (NIST), USA was implemented for Vis (400-700 nm approximately)-IR (900-14000 nm approximately) imaging of target object (TOB)-CB materials. AP treated and untreated fabric strength was measured by Instron machine, capacity 5 kN, ISO 13934-1: 2013 (E), constant rate of extension. Color fastness to wash was conducted by AATCC test method 61-2013, ATLAS Launderometer. Fabric thickness was measured by digital thickness gauge, pressure 20 gm/cm².

3.1 Standardization of K-M Reflection for TOB-CB in Vis Spectrum

Kubelka-Munk (K-M) reflection of black, white, and green standard was implemented for standardization of color measurement and imaging of camera measurement for TOB-CB under standardized background color (black, green, and white) to minimize the interference of chromatic hue. Black standard was applied as higher K-M reflection from 0 to 1000, green standard was used as lower K-M reflection from 0.5 to 4 and white standard was also implemented as minor K-M reflection from 0 to 0.02.

3.2 Photometric Measurement in Vis-IR Imaging under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination

Assessment of Vis-IR imaging was followed by a standard equation for the measurement of photonic response in UV-Vis-IR background illumination through imaging signal of AP treated fabric against woodland and desertland CB.

$$D/S = SSR$$

D = distance from the camera to the TOB

S = smallest target dimension of TOB

SSR = spot size ratio

Vis-IR-TOB-CB imaging was captured in a light cabinet (verivide) under protection of outside interference of light. D65 and UV background was illuminated from the source of light box and an artificial IR environment was created by 240V temperature controllable heater. A 45° (<50° has comparatively less variation of emissivity), angular distance of 76 cm and 60 cm was maintained for capturing image in general. The field trialling image of TOB-CB was around 180° angle with the observer. In terms of thermal sensor of thermal camera, the captured temperature has been mentioned by instantaneous field of view (IFOV) or distance to spot ratio. The accuracy of imaging mostly depends on imaging of emissivity which is influenced by materials properties versus distance-to-spot ratio. The standard of temperature deviation was captured from blue to red color signal under the region of black to white from low reflection to high reflection mechanism of chromaticity. In the area of black to white chromaticity, the region of blue identifies a minor photonic response to the thermal imaging, the region of green/yellow identifies a medium range of photonic response and consequently the region of red signifies a maximum thermal response to the imaging of TOB-CB.

3.3 Standardization of Camera Measurement and Chromatic Value Measurement for TOB-CB in Vis-IR Spectrum

Three standard tiles were used as machine standard of colorflexEZ, color measurement spectrophotometer.

These color standards were used for chromatic accuracy of background of CB and AP treated textiles which signified the accuracy of testing and imaging without interference of CB reflection. Black tile was used as non-reflective background, white tile was used as reflective background and green tile was used as standardized chromatic hue as multidimensional CB color.

3.4 Standardization of IR Spot Temperature versus Temperature Deviation of TOB-CB for Chromatic Assessment in IR Spectrum

Spot temperature of thermal imaging is the average temperature of pixel in entire image, which is normally controlled by temperature deviation, minimum temperature, maximum temperature, these are automatically recorded by thermal sensor in terms of emissivity of TOB-CB and heat energy-radiation mechanism of thermal imaging. Spot temperature versus temperature deviation in IR imaging has been demonstrated in different combination of temperature generated by thermal sensor, which is graphically presented in supporting information, figure S₁.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Established optical mechanism of CDRI has been demonstrated for color value, reflectance, color rendering and K-M reflection against TOB-CB. The common optical mechanism is derived as $1 = \text{absorption of OB} + \text{reflection of OB} + \text{transmission of OB}$. If absorption of OB = 1, reflection of OB = 0 and transmission of OB = 0, the OB is depicted as zero reflection surface and oppositely if absorption of OB = 0, reflection of OB = 1 and transmission of OB = 0 which is considered for AP treated fabric surface. Kirchhoff's law defined as absorption of OB = emissivity properties of OB = photonic responses of OB in infrared wavelength, so the mechanism of AP treated fabric can be demonstrated by a standard relation, reflection of AP treated surface = 1 - emissivity of OB, reflection-AP/TOB-CB is related to refractory oxide of AP treated textiles surface⁶. Reflection properties of AP is controlled by the mechanism of refractory oxides in Vis spectrum and photon energy is inversely proportional to its wavelength. AP is a semi-transparent substance due to properties of refractory oxides⁸. In general, green leaves, dry leaves, and tree bark of Eucalyptus plant shows low reflection in visible spectrum due to high absorption of chlorophyll, but the reflection is also related to leaf pigment, carotenoids, xanthophylls and anthocyanin. There is also deviation of reflection when different parts of tree generate different reflection due to having plant structure and the scattering properties of illumination. Reflection of woodland CB = absorption of coefficient + scattering coefficient + background reflectivity + optical properties of individual leaf, bark and cell + geometry of background + air cavity of cell wall + season of CB location + affected condition of plant by diseases, insects, nutrient and salinity conditions + shadows/moisture of surrounding area, soil and branches of tree⁹. Similarly desert CB is also related to the properties of sand and its reflection mechanism against target signature.

4.1 Structural Mechanism of AP Coated Fabric in Terms of CDRI-SEM Imaging

Figure 2, the structure of SEM confirms the higher percentage of AP deposition on the fabric surface. The magnification of SEM validates the existing of AP on PA 6, 6 (b, c) and cotton fabric (e, f) before and after five time washing.

SEM magnification clearly denotes that AP treated fabric surface has photon scattering effect due to smoothness, it has also been clarified that the minor percentage of photon signal to the imaging sensor when the concentration of PU-tubicoat-AP has been well cemented due to polymeric combination of AP on the fabric surface, and as a result, the breaking load of cotton twill fabric was increased from 770N (untreated fabric) to 1062N (AP treated fabric). AP creates stable oxide which is depicted as hard surface on textile materials. The mobility of photon signal may be minor due to larger particle size of AP which creates less reflection in UV-Vis-IR illumination and the

combination may signify a confusing TOB to the observers. The whiteness area of SEM structure signifies that there is existence of PU on the fabric surface and PU effect is mostly declined by the AP deposition on the fabric surface, but the reflectance effect of PU has also been located very minor.

4.2 PCM Mechanism of AP coated HTPB in terms of Heat Energy in IR Spectrum

Emissivity has relation between wavelength of radiation versus the angle of emission, the emissivity of water is

Figure 2. (a) Uncoated PA 6,6 (b) AP coated PA 6,6 fabric (c) AP coated PA 6,6 fabric after five time washing (d) Uncoated cotton fabric (e) AP coated cotton fabric (f) AP coated cotton fabric after five time washing.

Figure 3. Temperature deviation of AP coated HTPB and PCM loaded HTPB from black to white chromatic hue in IR imaging for concealment mechanism of heat energy.

0.97¹⁰ and oppositely emissivity of AP is lower although the emissivity properties of AP depends on molecular properties of AP. A thermal imaging variation has been observed between eicosane loaded part of channel-HTPB and unloaded part of channel-HTPB. As the emissivity of water is higher than AP under selected temperature range, so the process has limitation of stable camouflage design to minimize the temperature impact for concealment of target signature, but the process can be implemented for limited temperature range around 25°C to 30°C.

Figure 3a shows 19 channel-HTPB, 9 channel loaded with melted eicosane and 10 channel was kept completely blank. The eicosane loaded part of channel-HTPB shows the bluish hue without impacting temperature but the eicosane unloaded part of channel-HTPB shows the whitish color due to higher emissivity area compared to eicosane loaded part of channel-HTPB. At temperature 33.0°C, 35.2°C; eicosane starts to melt and the reflection of AP coated channel of hollow fabric increases very slowly in thermal image of 3b-3c-3d-3e-3f-3g-3h-3i (left part-eicosane loaded channel of HTPB). Oppositely, thermal image of 3b-3c-3d-3e-3f-3g-3h-3i (right part-eicosane unloaded channel of HTPB) shows whitish chromatic hue, the mechanism has been purely demonstrated the maximum heat energy and the reflection is comparatively higher. Therefore, PCM can be used for controlling IR temperature under minimum temperature range at below 30°C to minimize the reflection deviation between TOB-AP coated fabric and the technology can be implemented for camouflage product development of IR camouflage textiles of simultaneous formulation of UV-Vis-IR camouflage textiles.

4.3 Chromatic Profile of Woodland CB and AP Treated Fabric in Vis Spectrum

Figure 4, L* of AP coated PA 6, 6 fabric (68.36) and cotton fabric (56.93) are nearest of woodland CB. L* value of green leaves (40.18), dry leaves (53.2) and tree bark (45.14) are comparatively lower than untreated PA 6,6 and cotton fabric. Lightness value is also fluctuated by the structural properties of fabric and woodland materials. L*, a*, b* value trend to symmetrical chromatic value before washing and five-time post washing. Green leaves is showing higher greenish hue (a* = -6.73) due to presence of chlorophyll, dry leaves (a* = 1.88)

and tree bark are remarking as reddish hue (a* = 13.87) due to existing of tannin in *Eucalyptus* plant materials¹¹. Green leaves and tree bark shows blueish hue (b* = 10.48 and 22.93) and dry leaves depicts highest blueish hue (b* = 25.20) due to possible presence of microscopic fungi on leaf surface. AP coated PA 6,6 exhibited a minimum value of greenish coordinate (a* = -0.29 and -0.23) before and after washing. AP coated cotton fabric also showed a minimum value of greenish hue (a* = -0.34 and -0.43) before and after washing. AP coated PA 6, 6 showed bluish tone (b* = 0.27 and 2.21) before and after washing due to existence of Al₂O₃ on fabric surface. AP coated cotton fabric appeared yellowish and blueish hue (-0.16, 2.99) before and after washing. Therefore, the color value of L*, a*, b* looks almost nearest chromatic coordinate between coated fabric and woodland background materials observed by CIE L*, a*, b*.

4.4 D65/10° Imaging of Woodland CB and AP Treated Fabric in Vis Spectrum

Figure 5 (f, g, h, i, j) denotes that AP treated fabric signifies a color tone of minor L* value and almost similar chromatic hue of green leaves, a core material of woodland CB in D65/10° imaging. In IR range, blueish tone of AP tends to replace by yellow/reddish/purple tone, green leaves are generally replaced to reddish/purple/yellowish color. Under transformation of IR, there is also possibility of matching woodland CB with AP treated textiles and it is also explained in subsequent explanation and mentioned in Fig. 8, 9 and 11 (a part of IR imaging).

4.5 Reflection Profile of Woodland CB and AP Treated Fabric in Vis Spectrum

Figure 6, reflection profile of AP for IR mechanism can be concluded as higher coating thickness of AP which depicts higher emissivity with minimum reflection, oppositely lower coating thickness of AP depicts minimum emissivity with maximum reflection, this photometric phenomenon generates a primary concept of lower reflection of raw whitish fabric of PA-6, 6 and cotton. Reflection profile of Vis mechanism has been demonstrated as higher coating thickness which signifies maximum oxidation and it is related to higher emissivity and minimum reflection, correspondingly lower coating thickness

Figure 4. Chromatic value of AP coated-padded PA 6, 6, AP coated-padded cotton fabric and untreated fabric against woodland CB.

generates minimum oxidation, which is connected to lower emissivity and higher reflection. The intensity of AP reflection depends on oxide percentage of AP coated fabric. There is also reflection difference between AP coated and padded fabric due to deviation of AP deposition on fabric surface. AP coated fabric has higher percentage of Al_2O_3 rather than padded fabric which generates uniform reflection, and the mechanism is highly responsible for a smaller number of photonic responses to the remote sensing device. AP coated PA-6,6 fabric has reflectance with minor variation from 37 % to 38 % without washing and post washing from 17 % to 19 % at 400 nm to 700 nm. Similarly, AP coated cotton fabric has found less reflection which is 24 % to 25 % without washing and post washing from 16 % to 20 % at 400 nm to 700 nm.

to the surveillance imaging captured by digital camera/infrared camera/hyperspectral camera in terms CDRI.

4.7 Relationship of UV-Vis-IR Illumination Background and TOB-Woodland CB under Controlled Illumination of Light Cabinet in Vis-IR Spectrum

Figure 8, Vis-IR reflection of AP treated fabric, green leaves, dry leaves and tree bark of Eucalyptus tree has been shown under three-dimensional standardized chromatic background of black-green-white reflection signal which are the common interference of CB, and furthermore the standardized backgrounds are considered for accuracy of chromatic reflection. Under three-

Figure 5. D65/10° imaging of green leaves: (a) Dry leaves (b) Tree bark (c) Untreated PA 6,6 (d) Untreated cotton (e) AP padded PA 6,6 (f) AP padded cotton (g) AP coated PA 6,6 (h) AP coated cotton (i) AP coated cotton after five time washing and (j) AP coated PA 6, 6 after five time washing.

Figure 6. 0-150 % Reflection (machine standard) profile of AP treated fabric against woodland CBs.

4.6 K-M Reflection of AP Treated Fabric against Woodland CB in Vis Spectrum

Figure 7, the accuracy of K-M reflection of AP coated fabric has been found a new application for direct comparison with woodland CB materials. The scattering reflectance of green leaves, dry leaves and tree bark has been found higher due to surface roughness. It seems that the whole scattering area of woodland CB may differ from textile surface if the combat location is situated inside the area of woodland CB. Due to diffuse reflection of green leaves and tree bark; K-M reflection of woodland CB of Eucalyptus plant (green leaves, dry leaves and tree bark) has been found more variation due to structural deviation and existing pigment. The K-M reflection of AP padded-coated PA-6,6 and cotton fabric has been found significantly lower and straight signal of reflection due to opaque surface. The K-M reflection of AP-CB can identify the remote sensing parameters of chromophore which properties are directly related to electron energy versus photonic signal

dimensional background illumination of UV-Vis-IR, woodland CB and AP coated fabric have been demonstrated for clarification of reflection when every CB has multidimensional variation of background materials rather than common background materials of woodland/desertland. Under low temperature AP treated fabric looks blurred in IR range for detection and identification of target signature. UV light of AP coated fabric has been reflected more due to single side coating of cotton fabric as white part of opposite side fabric has been illuminated in maximum range of reflection. Green leaves-dry leaves-tree bark are completely invisible except the intensity of white background in UV illumination. AP coated fabric was compared with woodland background under three-dimensional chromatic variation of background in UV-Vis-IR illumination from black to white chromaticity of thermal imaging scale. Under UV illumination, green leaves, dry leaves, tree bark are almost invisible except white reflection of white background tiles. AP coated fabric is little bit blurred in UV light background. Under D65 illumination of IR imaging,

the chromatic appearance of AP treated fabric and woodland CB materials are almost symmetrical. UV background illumination of IR imaging, the chromatic appearance looks minor deviation in comparison with D65 image.

4.8 Simultaneous TOB-Woodland CB Assessment of AP coated Cotton Fabric under Woodland CB in Vis-IR Spectrum

Figure 9, a simultaneous reflection of green leaves, dry leaves and tree bark imaging signal versus AP coated textiles have been captured in the chromatic deviation of D65, UV and IR background illumination. The Vis spectrum image shows less reflection of lightness of AP coated fabric against

woodland materials. AP coated fabric has brightly illuminated in UV background illumination when the imaging is compared with Vis and IR background. Under thermal imaging of IR at 46.6 °C and 33.9 °C, there is less reflection of AP coated fabric under woodland CB.

4.9 Assessment of TOB-Desertland CB Materials under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination, a Lab Trialling under Standardized Black and White Background in Vis-IR Spectrum

Figure 10, the reflectivity of AP coated fabric is comparatively similar against desert CB in UV-Vis-IR background. The increasing of temperature range generates an

Figure 7. K-M Reflection of AP treated and untreated fabric against woodland CB.

Figure 8. Aluminium (Al) coated cotton fabric and woodland CB materials at 22.1 °C, 21.7 °C, 19.7 °C, 22.2 °C, 23.2 °C, 20.3 °C, 20.3 °C, 22.0 °C, 22.6 °C under temperature deviation from black to white chromatic hue in Vis-IR imaging.

Figure 9. Scanned woodland CB materials and AP coated fabric in mixed combination under UV-Vis-IR background; Vis image of D65 background (a) Vis image of UV background (b) IR image of D65 background at 46.6 °C (c) IR image of UV background at 33.9 °C (d) Under temperature deviation from black to white chromatic hue in Vis-IR imaging.

Figure 10. AP treated cotton fabric scanned under desert CB at 22 °C, 21.6 °C, 43.9 °C, 53.6 °C, 61.4 °C, 64.7 °C, 102 °C, 98.7 °C, 99 °C, 99.9 °C and deviation from black to white chromatic hue in Vis-IR imaging.

effect of detection of AP coated fabric surface due to the technical mechanism of heat versus mobility of AP molecules when the intermolecular deviation of AP surface looks like “water droplet” under visual scene of camera screen and the surface is fabricated accordingly at 43°C, 53°C, 61°C, 62°C, 102°C, 98°C. AP surface have been seen atomic vibration in high temperature. These variations of temperature versus mobility generates the reflection of detection but the dimension of reflection differs in eye-glance due to AP molecules variations of “water like droplet” and the TOB can be detected/recognized in high temperature variations, but it is not possible to identify target for the right attack of opposition team for exact decision making of TOB. Under D65-desert background, AP coated surface looks reflective, but UV-desert background AP coated surface looks blueish due to deviation of illumination, D65-UV. At 22°C and 21.6°C, the TOB-AP surface looks yellowish chromatic hue without identification of TOB-AP surface, it seems AP coated fabric is concealed under desert background at low temperature. But higher temperature generates blueish hue due to heating tendency at 43.9 °C, 53.6 °C, 61.4 °C, 64.7 °C, 102 °C, 98.7 °C, 99 °C, 99.9 °C, 102 °C, 98.7 °C.

Figure 11. TOB-AP coated fabric assessment under woodland CB at different spot temperature-23.1 °C, 25.3 °C, 22.6 °C, 23.7 °C, 26.7 °C from black to white chromatic hue in Vis-IR imaging.

4.10 Field Trialling of Aluminium (Al) coated Cotton Fabric under Eucalyptus Tree and Surrounding Green CB Environment in Vis-IR Spectrum

Figure 11, under field trialling mechanism, there is an impact of multidimensional angular illumination under direct focusing of sunlight. The TOB is completely concealed in terms of chromatic deviation in surrounding CB. A polished aluminium surface, AFP was used in woodland background, it was almost visible due to shiny surface from 9 ft, 18 ft, 33 ft, 51 ft and 69 ft distance. AP coated fabric was found identification and recognition under woodland CB in Vis imaging when the detection was measured from 9 ft and 18 ft distance from target signature. Apparently increasing the distance was generated a gradual blurred image to the camera sensor when the target was measured from 33 ft, 51ft, 69 ft distance. Therefore, the partial assessment has been identified as identification = 9 ft distance, recognition = 18 ft distance, detection = 33 ft distance and concealment = 51/69 ft distance. The chromatic appearance of green leaves CB has also been observed a lower variation compared with AP coated cotton fabric. AFP has low emissivity; hence the surface shows high reflectivity in Vis-IR spectrum. Oppositely AP treated fabric-rough/unpolished surface has high emissivity which signify comparatively low reflection in Vis spectrum and significantly low reflection in IR spectrum. Figure 11(a), 11(b), green background tends to purple and reddish color at 23°C under thermal deviation from 16.3°C to 26.6°C. The AP-TOB generates the chromatic signal of reddish hue which is matching with woodland CB color hue of green leaves. The tree bark color shows bluish chromatic hue which is replaced to yellowish hue and the minor percentage of greenish layer tends to reddish hue. The grass reflection of ground surface, surrounding of *Eucalyptus* tree has the tendency of chromatic hue from reddish/purple to whitish due to high reflection signal in IR spectrum. At the corner of Eucalyptus tree, the bluish and yellowish combination of grass has been illuminated as greenish area. The surrounding area of TOB has been generated a darker bluish tone due to quick heat generation on the surface of AFP. Figure 11(d), 11(f), 11(h), 11(j); when the target distance is gradually increased from 9 ft (23.1 °C) to 18 ft (25.3 °C)-33ft (22.6 °C)-51 ft (23.7 °C)-69 (26.7 °C). The woodland CB-green leaves and tree bark transfer the chromatic hue from reddish/purple to yellowish and still the chromatic hue between woodland CB and AP treated textiles have been found similarity under natural illumination falling sunlight at afternoon. Figure 11f, 11h, 11j; the surrounding grass of ground surface depicts the blueish hue because of heating of soil CB and the actual chromatic appearance of green grass has been influenced to make it blueish, dry grass has been visualized as blueish rather than reddish. Therefore, it has been demonstrated that AP coated textiles has been observed as the concealing tendency in IR spectrum in limited range of temperature (<30°C) and the blurred chromatic hue of AP coated fabric has also been found in Vis spectrum.

5. CONCLUSION

This experimentation of AP coated textiles has been mainly conducted by the mechanism AP reflection technology of CDRI in woodland and desertland CB in Vis-IR spectrum under the illumination background of UV-Vis-IR. This subsequent trialling generates a concept of AP-woodland-desertland CB under proposing a standardized method of CDRI-Vis imaging-thermal imaging which can be implemented for

CDRI/camouflage materials research and its implementation for defense protection, a potential branch of technical textiles in terms camouflage engineering. The combination of AP treated patterning in UV-Vis-IR can be used for woodland CB in winter season/casual season for concealment of target signature when the temperature variation is less. The fabrication of AP textiles/PCM loaded textiles technology can be used for defence tents under simultaneous protection of heat and concealment. Similarly, the clothing textiles can also be implemented by HTPB-PCM as the range of body temperature has minor impact for IR-CDRI when the highest range of body temperature of a healthy man is around $36^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, approximately. The temperature of human tolerance limit is considered as simultaneous concealment of Vis-IR imaging. When the temperature is more than 30°C , the AP-HTPB-PCM treated target is detected due to temperature deviation between woodland background/desertland background and AP treated textiles.

In concluded point, the CDRI methodology of AP treated textiles versus combat background has been critically approached, experimented and tested under selected measurement process for camouflage materials versus methodological identification and investigation of defence professional in terms of laboratory and field trialling to get the accuracy of CDRI results in terms of cost and time minimization which are denoted as SEM imaging of TOB-CB materials for electron response of materials, chromatic and reflection measurement between combat materials and textile materials, UV-Vis-IR background measurement and imaging, heat radiation versus temperature versus PCM mechanism and camouflage materials identification under UV-Vis-IR spectrum.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION, FIGURE S₁

Figure S₁. Spot temperature versus range of temperature deviation, minimum temperature and maximum temperature in infrared imaging captured for this experimentation mentioned in Fig. 3 (b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i), 8 (i, j, k, l, m, n, o, p), 9 (d, c), 10 (c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j), 11 (b, d, f, h, j).

SUPPORTING INFORMATION, FIGURE S₂

Figure S₂. Hollow tubular polyester beg (HTPB) before AP treatment

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A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles

Anowar Hossain

Abstract

Marigold flower *Tagetes erecta* L., Arjuna Bark *Terminalia Arjuna*, Eucalyptus leaves *Eucalyptus Radiata*, Peach/Jam Leaves *Acacia acuminata*, Pecker leaves *Cinnamomum tamala*, Guava leaves *Psidium guajava*, Basil leaves *Ocimum basilicum*, Jackfruit wood *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, Catachu fruit *Senegalia Catechu*, Bohera fruit *Terminalia bellirica*, Betel nut fruit *Areca catechu*, Haritaki fruit *Terminalia chebula*, Mahogany fruit peel, Mahogany seed peel, and Mahogany seed *Swietenia macrophylla* are the common natural sources in Bangladesh, an Asian country which were experimented in terms of mordanting free natural coloration on cotton fabric under conceptual confirmation of referred journal where author has been picked the idea from the generation of available shade in his research laboratory and tested from different laboratories and it may be establish as mordant free natural dyeing for specific colorant on the basis of color fastness and shading behaviors. Fifteen standardized Ready Made Shade (RMS) has been presented with CIE color parameters, color fastness, wash fastness, and light fastness grading. A reproducing guideline for every Ready Made Shade (RMS) has been mentioned in this chapter.

Keywords: readymade shade (RMS), natural dyeing, eco-friendly dyes, natural extraction, mordant free dyeing

1. Introduction

A concept of readymade shade (RMS) has been developed by using numerous number of natural dyes which were collected from agri-production unit and different village sources in Bangladesh prepared and powdered in color processing unit, extracted with water solvent process, dyed and experimented the feasibility of coloration in textile chemistry laboratory to generate different hues of natural dyes after effective implementation on natural fiber based textiles which outcome of color may be beneficial for primary selection of color tone by the textile technologist of natural coloration cum customers for the decision-making of specific color tone both for product development and fashion concerns who are genuinely searching an eco-friendly dyes under the consideration of repeated hue without which the real output of natural coloration, sustainability of dyes and natural dyeing process as well as its actual production of different hue is being a challenged now as the textile technologists are habituated the essence of readymade shading behavior of synthetic dyes whereas toxicity is the main endangered for the human being.

2. Background

Environment pollution is the great challenge of color scientists in dyeing and finishing plant, so eco-friendly coloration is the key target of recent researchers and manufacturers. Natural coloration is being accepted by the environment scientist and related committee [1–3]. Researchers in the area of natural coloration have an immense intension to minimize pollution [4]. Focus on science and engineering on natural dyes based research, extractions, purifications, and implementations are rapidly climbing [5–9]. In this chapter, mordant free natural coloration and its feasibility was experimented to minimize environment pollution load which is not limited to synthetic dyeing but also natural dyeing in terms of mordant free coloration concepts for specific standardized shade. Author also experimented to establish an approach of green mordanting [10, 11] in natural coloration [12–16] although mordant [17] has an effect for the augmentation of fiber surface color and surface chemistry [18] and its appropriate affinity in terms of fastness properties [1, 19–24]. Light fastness [21–24] of natural dyed fabric is a critical issue for natural colorant if dyes sources and collection processes are not maintained accurately. There are many sources of natural colorant, using by the researcher as per availability of origin to origin in the world. Researchers are already invented and proposed like *Jatropha* flower [25], red sandal wood [26], wood of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* [27], *Acalypha* [28], areca nut [29], *Butea monosperma* [30], neem leaves [31, 32], *Gomphrena globosa* [33], *Onosmaechiodes* [34], *Nerium oleander* flower [35], Kesula flowers [36], Parijataka (*Nyctanthes Arbor*) flowers pigment [37], *Hibiscus ovalifolius* and *Sesbania aegyptiaca* [38], Bark of *Macaranga Peltata* [39], Cutch, Ratanjot and Madder [40], Mesta Calyx [41], Kapila, Onion, Tesu [42], myrobalan, gallnut, pomegranate [43], Marigold flower [44, 45], *Areca Catechu* [46], Eucalyptus leaves [47], Eucalyptus bark [48, 49], Jackfruit wood [50], Peach [51], Arjuna [52, 53], Catechu [54] and others. Developments of natural indigo shade in comparison with synthetic dyes [55] are not only prime objects for coloration but also maximum natural dyes have medicinal value [56, 57], noncarcinogenic, production-friendly, and environment-friendly. Research and development of natural dyeing on cotton, jute, and silk fabric was done by Samanta and his researchers team at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India have an technical output, research impacts and motivation for future researchers, and manufacturing unit for the contributions of dyes selection, extraction, analysis, standardization, and commercialization [58–68]. Color matching [69] and reproducing of shade is another challenging issue for the manufacturing company and colorists when natural dye is compared with synthetic dyes but there are so many colorants of natural sources that can be possible to reproduce almost nearest shade. Tolerating percentage/ acceptable range of color differences, ΔE value, and other properties can be standardized in a convincing way with local and foreign customer of any country as the real customer of any textile product is not going to sell the product after shade matching with spectrophotometer without enjoying its esthetic value, so a little bit lightness and darkness matter is not a trading challenge of dyer and manufacturing plant. Comparing to synthetic dyes, natural dyed fabric has a great market demand as the people who are concern about the intimidation of environment. Thus natural dyes have diverse applications and multi fiber based production options that are already available in literature for cotton [68], jute [66], wool [70], silk [34] based dyeing, processing in both laboratory stage and bulk production (**Figures 1–15**).

RMS of Marigold (Figure 1): Waste Marigold flowers were collected from flower garden, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

3. Standardized Ready Made Shade (RMS) of natural dyed textiles

3.1 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Marigold flower, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Marigold tree. scientific name: *Tagetes erecta*

Figure 1.
 RMS of Marigold.

3.2 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Arjuna Bark, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Arjuna tree, Scientific name: *Terminalia arjuna*

Figure 2.
 RMS of Arjuna Bark.

3.3 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Eucalyptus leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: scientific name: *Eucalyptus radiata*

Figure 3.
RMS of *Eucalyptus* leaves.

Coloring components Zeaxanthin and Lutein structural group of marigold flower may be responsible for good color combination has OH group may be showed good color fastness properties with cellulosic fiber. Lutein ($C_{40}H_{56}O_2$) and Zeaxanthin ($C_{40}H_{56}O_2$) molecules may prevent UV damage for its strong antioxidant properties.

RMS of Arjuna Bark (Figure 2): Dried Arjuna bark were plucked from Arjuna tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Ferrous ion of Arjuna Bark may be influencing the L^* , a^* , b^* , Y value for providing outcome of deeper color and OH group is responsible for good fastness properties. Arjuna bark has phytosterol, lactones, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and tannins, glycosides where tannin may be responsible for coloring agent.

RMS of Eucalyptus Leaves (Figure 3): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from Eucalyptus tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of cellulose can easily make a bonding with dyes group of Eucalyptus. Eucalyptol is a colorless compound which is responsible for antibacterial properties but may be remaining pigment or other phytochemical compound is making color on the fabric surface.

3.4 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Pecker leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Pecker tree, scientific name: *Cinnamomum tamala*

Figure 4.
RMS of Pecker leaves.

RMS of Pecker Leaves (Figure 4): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from pecker tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of cellulose can easily make a bonding with dyes group of Pecker leaves. Eugenol is the main constituent of antimicrobial properties and other components like pinene, camphene, and limousine may be responsible for color formation.

RMS of Guava Leaves (Figure 5): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of dyes is responsible for good color fastness properties. Mixed components of flavonoid and tannin are highly responsible for bluish color of cotton fabric. Acidic pH and phenolic compound of guava leaves may generate flammable characteristics of guava leaves colored fabric.

RMS of Basil Leaves (Figure 6): Fresh and green Basil leaves were plucked from tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

α terpineol remaining in dyes of Basil leaves may be responsible for dyeing of cotton fiber and OH group is making strong affinity with cellulose. Phytochemical constituents and medicinal properties of Tulsi leaves may create pathogen protective finish of cotton fabric like antimicrobial, COVID 19, and other viruses.

3.5 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Guava leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Guava tree, scientific name: *Psidium guajava*

Figure 5.
RMS of Guava leaves.

3.6 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Basil leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Basil tree, scientific name: *Ocimum basilicum*

Figure 6.
RMS of Basil leaves.

3.7 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Jackfruit wood, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Jackfruit tree, scientific name: *Artocarpus heterophyllus*

Figure 7.
 RMS of Jackfruit wood.

3.8 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Catechu fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Catechu tree, scientific name: *Senegalia catechu*

Figure 8.
 RMS of Catechu fruit.

3.9 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Bohera fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Bohera tree, scientific name: *Terminalia bellirica*

Figure 9.
RMS of Bohera fruit.

RMS of Jackfruit Wood (Figure 7): Powder of Jackfruit wood were collected from saw mill, filtered and 5 days dried with summer sun light. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Artocarpesin and Norartocarpetin group of golden yellow color jackfruit tree wood has phenolic compounds, apigenin, curcumin may be responsible for making a yellow color having an optimum value of L*, a*, b*, Y as well as OH group is improving color fastness properties.

RMS of Catachu Fruit (Figure 8): Semidried Catachu fruit were plucked from tree, washed, fruit peel were cut into small piece, 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Catachu is making off white color with soft hand feel and may be remaining natural pigment in the chemical components is responsible for dyeing without mordanting. Coloring component in the catechu is catechin having molecular formula C₁₅H₁₄O₆.

RMS of Bohera Fruit (Figure 9): Bohera fruit powder was purchased from herbal medicine shop, Tongi, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

3.10 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany seed, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 10.
 RMS of Mahogany fruit, seed.

3.11 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany fruit (outer peel), types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 11.
 RMS of Mahogany fruit, outer peel.

3.12 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany seed (outer peel), types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 12.
RMS of Mahogany fruit, outer peel of seed.

OH group and its tannin constituent may be created a natural shading environment on the surface of cotton fiber and its medicinal properties may create the dyed fabric antimicrobial. Flavonoid and falfvins constituent of Bohera fruit may have adaptive capabilities of viruses and microorganisms.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Seed (Figure 10): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruits were plucked from tree, washed, seeds were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group may be responsible for good dye-absorption and ferrous ion may be responsible for dyeing. Phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

3.13 Natural coloration of cotton natural coloration of cotton fabric with Haritaki fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Haritaki tree, scientific name: *Terminalia chebula*

Figure 13.
 RMS of Haritaki fruit.

3.14 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Betel nut, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Betel nut tree, scientific name: *Areca catechu*

Figure 14.
 RMS of Betel nut.

3.15 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Peach leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Peach leaves, scientific name: *Acacia acuminata*

Figure 15.
RMS of Peach leaves.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Outer peel (Figure 11): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruit were plucked from tree, washed, fruit peels were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Outer peel of Seed (Figure 12): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruit were plucked from tree, washed, seed peels were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding. Phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

RMS of Haritaki Fruit (Figure 13): Haritaki fruit powder was purchased from herbal medicine shop Tongi, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding. The plant is constituted of Glucoside, Tannins, Gallic acid, Ethyl gallate, and Chebulinic acid where tannin may be responsible for coloring the cotton fiber.

RMS of Betel Nut (Figure 14): Ripe Betel nut were purchased from local village shop, separated the peels, and grinded to make it powder form. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group can create a bond between dye and fiber and remaining curcumin may be responsible for coloration and dyed fabric may be slightly flammable due to having hydroxychavicol in the chemical constituent of betel nut.

RMS of Peach Leaves (Figure 15): Semi-dried Peach leaves were plucked from Peach tree garden. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Minimum color strength is found but fastness is lightly higher, increasing dye percentage may improve the color on the fiber surface. Remaining ferrous, copper, and zinc may be responsible for coloring the cotton fiber. As per chemical constituent, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory can be found.

4. Method of natural fixing for mordant free dyeing

Maximum natural dyes sources from natural tree leaves, roots or fruits have ferrous ion, tannin, curcumin, catechin, OH group, and other known and unknown phytochemical constituent. Ferrous ion, tannin, curcumin, and catechin are making various color formations, and OH group is creating affinity with cellulosic fiber as well as the fastness properties may be increased if the dyes have natural pigment which may influence the capability of remaining dyes on the fiber surface after washing. Drying/curing with higher temperature may impact the color making duller or brighter. So specific dye-fiber system of natural fixing for mordant free dyeing is also possible but exact curing/drying temperature should be fixed for getting expected outcome of shading. So expected mechanism of mordant free natural coloration may be proposed as below although dyes and fiber substances may create changing of it.

5. Testing process

5.1 Color fastness to wash method

ISO 105-C06:2010, color fastness to water method: ISO 105-E01 and color fastness to light was tested by AATCC TM16 in Q-SUN XE-2 Xenon Test chamber.

5.2 Machine used for color parameters

Color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* , Y) were measured by Hunter Lab Spectrophotometer, machine name: ColorFlex EZ, Model 45/0 LAV, Geometry

Figure 16.
Color Flex EZ, Spectrophotometer.

45°/0°, viewing area: large, visible spectrum (400–700 nm), testing condition: D₆₅/10°, room temperature of testing lab: 18°C (**Figure 16**).

6. Representation of dyed fabric and picture of dyes sources

All dyed shades were scanned with HUAWEI Smart Phone, Camera-13 MP, distance between fabric sample and camera position: 12–16 inch. So there is a possibility of having difference with actual shade. Picture of actual dye-fiber system was also scanned with HP Scanjet 4890 Photo Scanner. All sources of dyes pictures have been mentioned on the basis of grown trees in Asian Countries, specially in Bangladesh and scientific name was used accordingly. All the pictures of chemical structure mentioned here indicate the group of tree, not exactly indicating the chemical structure of specific parts of trees which one is extracted and dyed on cotton fabric.

6.1 Overcoming contradiction of natural dyeing

A huge number of researchers are working on natural dyes, still have a challenging for uneven dyeing, appropriate mordanting and dyes availabilities, shade matching where I can put a logic to protect our environment and human life as well.

6.2 Uneven dyeing

Automation in extraction and dyeing process.

6.3 Appropriate mordanting and dyes availability

Selection of specific dyes for commercial production and/or wastage can be used as dyes sources.

6.4 Shade matching

Customers are not always asking for shade matching when they are shopping although some natural dyes have attractive shading and repeated shading also possible.

7. Conclusion

Mordanting free coloration was practiced establishing the feasibility of environment friendly natural coloration which is the ongoing research of author and a part

of his research has been included here. Shade variation of natural dyed fabric may influence the uncontrollable factors for the collection of natural dyes sources on the basis of season to season, region to region and a same source but different parts of same dye sample source. So it is very tough to make a specific declaration of shading behaviors by the textile technologist but specific expertise in natural dyes extraction and natural dyeing may minimize the problem whereas expertise in dyeing with synthetic dyes and dyeing with natural dyes are not same for bulk production.

Following directions for the real shade development mentioned above:

1. Fabric should be well scoured and bleached.
2. Dyes materials should be clean, dried and powdered properly, improper drying and inappropriate powder formation may be responsible for unexpected shading and uneven dyeing.
3. Extraction time, dyes percentage may be maximized or minimized if the actual color is not observed.
4. Improper filtration of dyes may create uneven dyeing.
5. Dyes should not be powdered in wet or sticky condition which may effect the changing of light fastness and color shading.
6. Insect affected dyes source may create the changing of shade.
7. Synthetic mordanting and chemical medium dyes extraction may improve the shade but the concern of chemical and cost.
8. For open bath dyeing, liquor ratio should be higher, and stirred continuously to reduce color mark on the dyed fabric.

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OPEN UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection

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Woodland combat background (CB) is a common source of natural plant based natural dyes (NPND). *Swietenia Macrophylla*, *Mangifera Indica*, *Terminalia Arjuna*, *Corchorus Capsularis*, *Camellia Sinensis*, *Azadirachta Indica*, *Acacia Acuminata*, *Areca Catechu* and *Cinnamomum Tamala* were dried-grinded-powdered-extracted-polyaziridine encapsulated-dyed-coated-printed with leafy design on cotton fabric and tested against woodland CB under the reflection engineering of ultraviolet (UV)–visible (Vis)–near infrared (NIR) spectrums and photographic versus chromatic techniques of Vis imaging. The reflection properties of NPND treated and untreated cotton fabric were experimented by UV–Vis–NIR spectrophotometer from 220 to 1400 nm. Six segments of field trialling for NPND treated woodland camouflage textiles were also investigated for concealment, detection, recognition and identification of target signature against forest plants/herbs species; common tree of woodland CB such as *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*, *Bamboo Vulgaris*, *Musa Acuminata*; and a wooden bridge made by *Eucalyptus Citriodora* & *Bamboo Vulgaris*. The imaging properties such as CIE L*, a*, b* and RGB (red, green, blue) of NPND treated cotton-garments were captured by digital camera from 400 to 700 nm against tree stem/bark, dry leaves, green leaves and dry wood of woodland CB. Therefore, a colorful matching for concealment, detection, recognition and identification of target signature against woodland CB was verified by Vis camera imaging and UV–Vis–NIR reflection mechanism. UV-protection property of *Swietenia Macrophylla* treated cotton fabric was also investigated by diffuse reflection for defence clothing. Simultaneous ‘camouflage textiles in UV–Vis–NIR’ and ‘UV-protective’ property of *Swietenia Macrophylla* treated fabric have been investigated for NPND materials-based textiles coloration (dyeing-coating-printing) which is a new concept for camouflage formulation of NPND dyed-NPND mordanted-NPND coated-NPND printed textiles in terms of ecofriendly source of woodland camouflage materials. Therefore, technical properties of NPND materials and methodologies of camouflage textile assessment have been advanced in addition to coloration philosophy of natural dyed-coated-printed textiles.

Natural plant based natural dyes (NPND) materials are being introduced as ‘green dyes’ and ‘green mordanting’ for natural dye-based textile coloration. NPND materials^{1–6} are common foundation of woodland combat dye for textile coloration and presently being commercialized in home and abroad, but the concept of NPND based camouflage coloration is an innovative approach of defence textiles for combat applications. The main plants/species of woodland CB are *Swietenia Macrophylla*, *Mangifera Indica*, *Terminalia Arjuna*, *Corchorus Capsularis*, *Camellia Sinensis*, *Azadirachta Indica*, *Acacia Acuminata*, *Areca Catechu*, *Cinnamomum Tamala*, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* etc.¹. The analytical/optical assessment technology of camouflage textiles assessments^{7–11} are still a new approach in camouflage textiles technology for defence textiles rather than field trialling method of concealment, detection, recognition and identification (CDRI) of defence target signature¹². Presently spectral reflections of woodland CB have been considered by researchers^{13,14} but the spectral reflection versus camouflage assessment technique is still a new technology and ongoing platform of camouflage research^{8,11}. Simultaneous

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spectrum of ultraviolet–visible–near infrared (UV–Vis–NIR) reflection is a newly applied optical technology for assessment of UV–Vis–NIR camouflage textiles technology in terms of CDRI⁹. NPND materials-polyaziridine crosslinker-UV–Vis–NIR reflection-Vis imaging versus combat engineering-color engineering-woodland CB-optical assessment-ImageJ engineering are a new approach of environment friendly materials for camouflage textiles technology, an application for defence protection^{15,16}. In literature, there is enormous lacking of study related to NPND camouflage materials and its right application for camouflage textiles as nature-friendly source of NPND materials. Hence, chromatic and spectral matching were investigated between selected NPND and woodland combat background in terms of suitability for right function of camouflage materials in addition to 'ecofriendly source' and 'ecofriendly processing'. Therefore, the present innovation of camouflage property has been argued for selected NPND materials against selected woodland CB. In this research of NPND-camouflage engineering, the core outcome of NPND materials against woodland CB have been hypothetically and experimentally focused without making it more comprehensive to make it more reader friendly¹⁷.

Chromatic philosophy of NPND camouflage textiles against woodland CB. *Eucalyptus Radiata, Acacia acuminata, Cinnamomum tamala, Psidium guajava, Ocimum basilicum, Artocarpus heterophyllus, Terminalia Arjuna, Artocarpus heterophyllus, Terminalia bellirica, Areca catechu, Terminalia chebula, Swietenia macrophylla* are NPND materials applied for textile formulation and coloration. The chromatic chemistry between NPND materials and woodland CB are symmetric, hence the spectrometry, photometry & colorimetry of NPND dyed-coated-printed textiles have been assessed for CDRI against woodland CB^{1,17}.

Optical philosophy of photometry versus colorimetry for Vis camouflage textiles assessment in field trialling. RGB (red, 700 nm; green, 550 nm; and blue, 500 nm) light theory and three-dimensional color space L*, a*, b* were implemented for camouflage assessment in Vis wavelength under colorimetry of International Commission on Illumination (CIE). The grey scale and RGB scale of Vis imaging was analysed when L* = 0 signifies total absorption for perfect black, L* = 100 identifies total reflection for perfect white, + a* = red (700 nm), - a* = green (550 nm), + b* = yellow (600 nm), - b* = blue (500 nm). Therefore, saturation of color has been denoted by CIE colorimetry of red, green, blue, L*, a*, b* under day light illumination and image processing software, ImageJ^{7,11,12,15,18}.

Materials, formulations and methodology for camouflage textiles with NPND materials against woodland CB

Exemption note of NPND materials collection and approval for textile coloration. Table 1, a minimum amount of NPND materials including 'agricultural waste'¹⁹ were collected from non-commercial/commercial sources applied for non-commercial application. NPND application for camouflage textiles is an academic platform of research to propose a practicability for broader scale implementation in terms of eco-friendly source of camouflage materials. All experiment of NPND materials were conducted with accordance to relevant regulations and guidelines. Therefore, permission of NPND sample collection is not required. This exemption is supported by '3.1.2, assessment requirement' for collection of NPND materials quoted as below, registered research located in Australia.

Scientific name	Local name of sample collection zone/field trialling, Bangladesh	Used parts of tree in this experiment	Purpose of NPND in this experiment
<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i>	Mahogany tree	Wood	Dyeing-coating-printing
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Mango tree	Leaves	Dyeing
<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	Arjun tree	Barks	Dyeing
<i>Corchorus capsularis</i>	Jute plant	Leaves	Dyeing-coating-printing
<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Tea plant	Modified leaves powder	Dyeing
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Neem tree	Leaves	Dyeing
<i>Acacia acuminata</i>	Jam/Peach tree	Seeds	Dyeing
<i>Areca catechu</i>	Areca Palm/Supari tree	Seeds	Dyeing, Bio-Mordanting
<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i>	Pecker tree	Leaves	Dyeing
<i>Shorea Robusta gaertn</i>	Sal/Gajari	A group of trees in a forest area included tree stem/bark, green leaves, dry leaves	Woodland CB
<i>Bamboo vulgaris</i>	Bamboo tree	Woody stem for wooden bridge	Woodland CB
<i>Eucalyptus citriodora</i>	Eucalyptus tree	Wood for wooden bridge	Woodland CB
<i>Bamboo vulgaris</i>	Bamboo tree	A group of trees included tree stem/bark, mostly green leaves	Woodland CB
<i>Musa acuminata</i>	Banana tree	A group of trees included tree stem/bark, mostly green leaves	Woodland CB

Table 1. Experimental applications of selected NPND-materials for three-dimensional process of camouflage formulation and coloration (dyeing-coating-printing) and selected forest plants/herbs for comparison with woodland CB.

“A permit is not required to collect native plant material from private land, unless: the species for collection are listed threatened species or form part of a threatened ecological community under the environment protection and biodiversity conservation (EPBC) Act, under such circumstances a Commonwealth permit may be required”²⁰.

Experimental preparations in general. Table 1, nine-NPND materials of woodland CB were collected, washed, dried, powdered/grinded and extracted by water medium. Three-dimensional method of textile coloration was applied to signify the feasibility of NPND-camouflage coloration of dyeing, coating and printing^{21–23}. In terms of maximum and minimum reflection, standardized white and black background was used for comparison between target object, dyed-coated-printed textiles and selected woodland CB.

Coating and printing with NPND on cotton fabric. Table 2, a composite paste of Tubassist Fix 104W, a crosslinking agent of polyaziridine²⁴; NK binder, acrylonitrile copolymer^{25,26}; F53 glitter paste, acrylic copolymer and selected NPND-powder was formulated for coating and printing paste. Therefore, S/J knitted cotton fabric was coated with wooden scrubber and printed with rubber scrubber. Figure 1 identifies the complete coloration/preparation process of printing. Figure, 1a shows the formulated recipe of polyaziridine encapsulated NPND-*Swietenia Macrophylla*^{22,24,27,28}; Fig. 1b and c means the trialling conditions of printing; Figure, 1d shows the formulated recipe of grinded dry leaves of polyaziridine encapsulated NPND²⁴-*Corchorus Capsularis*; Fig. 1e and f means the trialling conditions of NPND-*Corchorus Capsularis* printing on cotton fabric; Fig. 1g and h shows the pictorial image of NPND-*Swietenia Macrophylla* and NPND-*Corchorus Capsularis* printed fabric after curing.

Mordant free NPND-coloration and NPND-mordanting for natural dyeing with NPND materials on natural fibre. Nine individual NPND was formulated for mordant free coloration on cotton fabric for camouflage textiles. An exhaust method of NPND coloration process was applied for camouflage coloration on cotton fabric. 150 GSM, 100% cotton knitted fabric (scoured, bleached) was washed with 2% detergent. 5 g powdered *Swietenia Macrophylla* (wood/stem) was boiled with 1.5 L water at boiling temperature, run time 120 min in an open bath and continuous method. 10 g cotton fabric was dyed for 90 min in an open bath at boiling temperature and followed a continuous method of coloration. A post mordanting technique was applied with the seed of *Areca catechu* in terms of NPND-mordanting¹⁹. Similarly, a mordant free coloration with processed tea leaves was continued by water medium: water 2.5 L, processed black tea 25 g, Taza, Uniliver Bangladesh Ltd.; extraction, and dyeing time 120 min in an open bath at boiling temperature and followed a continuous method of coloration. Correspondingly, *Mangifera indica* (leaves), *Terminalia arjuna* (bark), *Corchorus Capsularis* (leaves), *Camellia sinensis* (modified leaves powder), *Azadirachta indica* (leaves) with *Areca Catechu* (NPND-mordant/bio-mordant), *Acacia acuminata* (seed), *Cinnamomum Tamala* (leaves) were formulated for NPND dyeing on cotton fabric, separately noted in Tables 1 and 2.

Field trialling segment: 1–6 for camouflage textile assessment against woodland combat background under natural illumination of day light. Practically, visual acuity is the camouflage physics of human perception for visual assessment of CDRI for defence target signature which can be denoted by $\alpha = Y/L$ where α = visual acuity, Y = size of target signature/object, NPND dyed-coated-printed garment and L = distance between object (dyed-coated-printed textiles) and observer/surveillance device^{15,29}. Hence, field trialling of NPND dyed-coated-printed garments was conducted against black and white standard. NPND dyed-coated-printed garments were placed against woodland, wooden bridge, soil bed, concrete bed. Nikon Coolpix s2500, Nikon Corporation, Japan; 74,163,447 was used to capture Vis-photograph under selected distance. A constant measurement of coated and printed garments size was applied for whole experimentation of digital image^{29,30}. Photographs of NPND dyed, coated and printed cotton fabric in the form of stitched garments against woodland CB were captured and considered as real image of object-background reflectance in visible range. Chromatic deviations of target signature against woodland CB were analysed by three dimensional color space mechanism of CIE $L^* = 0$ (black), $L^* = 100$ (white), $+a^*$ (red), $-a^*$ (green), $+b^*$ (yellow), $-b^*$ (blue) and RGB (red, green, blue) trichromatic technique of grey (white–black) chroma saturation¹⁸. Captured RGB images were converted into RGB stack and CIE L^* , a^* , b^* stack for camouflage assessment of individual chromatic hue of CIE red, green, blue, L^* , a^* , b^* against multidimensional CBs. Image functions of ImageJ software were applied for this assessment process. CIE L^* , a^* , b^* values are generated by ImageJ for chromatic values from 0 to 100 where 0 represents black and 100 represents white. RGB values are also generated by ImageJ software for pixel range from 0 to 255 where 0 represents black and 255 represents white⁷. L^* , a^* , b^* , RGB values of NPND textiles against CBs

Name of chemicals	Company	A common formulated recipe was trialed for coating and printing	Fixation
Tubssist Fix 104W	CHT	10–15%	Sun light fixation
NK binder	E-chem	5–10%	30 min; temperature (30–40) °C
F53 glitter paste	E-chem	5–10%	Heat fixation
NPND-powder	–	75–65%	2–4 min; temperature (100–120) °C

Table 2. Chemicals and formulations for coating and printing with NPND materials on cotton fabric.

Figure 1. Preparation and laboratory process for coating and printing with NPND-*Swietenia Macrophylla* and NPND-*Corchorus Capsularis*.

are generated under 'light trapping' limitation of natural illumination, sunlight¹². The imaging of 'light trapping' is considered as an uncontrollable condition of natural illumination for field trialling.

Field trialling segment: 1–3 for camouflage textiles against woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn.*

This experimentation was trialled against woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* during February–March 2022 under natural illumination (sunlight) of morning day light in a forest environment for CDRI of defence target signature¹². A garment of NPND-nine color combination of NPND materials cited in Table 1; a single color coated and printed garment with *Swietenia Macrophylla*; a single color coated and printed garment with *Corchorus Capsularis* were trialled for field experimentation of camouflage target signature against woodland CB. The distance between target textile sample and camera was kept 7 ft and 21 ft for field trialling. For chromatic assessment, 736 × 850 pixels, RGB and CIE L*, a*, b* image were generated by ImageJ software.

Field trialling segment: 4–6 for camouflage textiles against woodland CB; *Musa Acuminata, Bamboo Vulgaris*, wooden bridge made by *Eucalyptus Citriodora* and *Bamboo Vulgaris*; and concrete CB.

Dry wood of *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, Bangladesh origin was purchased from three different tree and three different ages of tree including 40–50% heartwood. For this experimentation, three types of common forest tree were selected as woodland CB such as *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, *Bamboo Vulgaris* and *Musa Acuminata*. A wooden bridge was constructed by the combination of dry wood of *Eucalyptus Citriodora* and *Bamboo Vulgaris*¹⁵. This image of dyed-coated-printed textiles captured against a constructed wooden bridge made by *Euca-*

lyptus Citriodora, *Bamboo Vulgaris*; and woodland CB of *Bamboo Vulgaris* and *Musa Acuminata*. This woodland background additionally covers soil and concrete CB. Images were captured by digital camera under natural illumination of day light on 19 January, 2023 at 2–3 pm. A garment of NPND-nine color combination of NPND materials cited in Table 1; a single color coated and printed garments with *Swietenia Macrophylla*; a single color coated and printed garments with *Corchorus Capsularis* were trialled for field experimentation of camouflage target signature against woodland CB. The distances between target textile sample and camera were kept 6 ft and 22 ft for field trialling. For chromatic assessment, 3161×3807 pixels, RGB and CIE L^* , a^* , b^* images were generated by ImageJ software.

Fabrication and groundwork process of field trialling against woodland CB; NPND treated fabrication and field trialling of nine color combination. Figure 2a–l, fabrication of nine color combination³¹ of NPND against standardized black and white fabric as low reflection and high reflection chromatic hue. a = standardized white fabric, b = *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric, c = *Mangifera Indica* dyed fabric, d = *Terminalia Arjuna* dyed fabric, e = *Corchorus Capsularis* dyed fabric-1, f = standardized black fabric, g = *Camellia Sinensis* dyed fabric, h = *Corchorus Capsularis* dyed fabric-2, i = *Azadirachta Indica* treated fabric

Figure 2. NPND dyed cotton fabric with solid color design compared with standardized white and black fabric (a–l), NPND coated cotton fabric with solid color design (m, o) and NPND printed cotton fabric with leafy design (n, p) including chromatic value of CIE L^* , a^* , b^* .

with *Areca Catechu* as NPND-mordanting/bio-mordanting, j = *Acacia Acuminata* dyed fabric, k = *Swietenia Macrophylla* treated fabric with *Areca Catechu* as NPND-mordanting/bio-mordanting, l = *Cinnamomum Tamala* dyed fabric. The chromatic values (L^* , a^* , b^*) of NPND dyed fabric and standardized fabric (a-l) have been captured by ImageJ software and shown accordingly for chromatic comparison. Hence, nine color-NPND was dyed on cotton fabric, cut in small pieces and stitched by cotton yarn for measurement of optical reflection under natural illumination of day light and Vis imaging principle against woodland CB³².

NPND-*Swietenia Macrophylla* coated and printed fabrication with single color chromatic hue. Figure 2m–n, *Swietenia Macrophylla* wood powder was coated with solid color design and printed with single color leafy design matching with woodland CB. The chromatic values (L^* , a^* , b^*) of *Swietenia Macrophylla* coated and printed fabric have been captured by ImageJ software and shown accordingly for chromatic comparison.

NPND-*Corchorus Capsularis* coated and printed fabrication with single color chromatic hue. Figure 2o and p, *Corchorus Capsularis* leaves powder was coated³³ with solid color design and printed with single color leafy design for woodland CB. The chromatic values (L^* , a^* , b^*) of *Corchorus Capsularis* coated and printed fabric have been captured by ImageJ software and shown accordingly for chromatic comparison.

Testing and measurement process for camouflage textiles assessment with UV–Vis–NIR spectrophotometer

Kubelka–Munk (K–M) diffuse theory of UV–Vis–NIR reflectance spectroscopy. Equation (1), validation of diffuse reflectance using Kubelka–Munk (K–M) theory of scattering between target signature and woodland CB. For camouflage assessment in laboratory stages, K–M theory is a theoretical reference for diffuse reflectance in UV–Vis–NIR spectrum.

$$K/S = \frac{(1 - R_{\infty})^2}{2R_{\infty}} \quad (1)$$

Reflectance (R) is inversely proportional to the light scattering co-efficient (S) and s value is inversely proportional to the particle size of treated textiles and the materials of woodland CB⁷.

Sampling procedure for assessment with UV–Vis–NIR spectrophotometer. Sampling procedure for measurement in UV–Vis–NIR spectrum was conducted under constant reflection of barium sulfate as 100% reflectance materials. Powdered sample and round cut of fabric was placed on standardized glass vial for reflection spectra. In Fig. 3a = powder of *Swietenia Macrophylla*, Fig. 3b = powder of *Areca Catechu*, Fig. 3c = cut pieces of raw knitted fabric before dyeing, Fig. 3d = cut pieces of *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric without mordanting, Fig. 3e = cut species of *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric with *Areca Catechu*-mordanting.

Scanning condition of UV–Vis–NIR spectrophotometer. UV–Vis–NIR spectrophotometer, named UV-2600 spectrophotometer was used for diffuse reflectance from 200 to 1400 nm. This machine was a set-up with integrating sphere. A film plate of standardized barium sulphate was scanned as reference of 100% reflection material in room temperature shown in Fig. 4.

Results and discussion

Assessment of UV–Vis–NIR camouflage properties of *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric against woodland CB materials for concealment of target signature. Figure 5, the reflection% of UV–Vis–NIR spectrum obtained from the standardized barium sulphate, *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric without mordanting, *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric with NPND-mordanting and undyed knitted fabric against the materials of woodland CB. The reflection% of raw *Swietenia Macrophylla* and raw *Areca Catechu* was scanned as the materials of NPND and woodland CB. The reflection deviation of UV spectrums from 220 to 375 nm are found from 5 to 35% but the reflections were found symmetrical. The variation of reflections in Vis from 412 to 685 nm are remarked as 5% to 60% but the reflections were shown symmetrical. The NIR reflections are recorded from 25 to 80% from 716 to 1398 nm. A symmetrical C–O and O–H group stretching have

Figure 3. Samples of NPND-powdered materials (a, b); cut pieces of undyed cotton fabric (c) and cut pieces NPND-dyed cotton fabric (d, e) for measurement with sample port of UV–Vis–NIR spectrophotometer.

Figure 4. Blank sample port (a) and standardized barium sulphate placed on sample port (b) for assessment with UV–Vis–NIR spectrophotometer.

Figure 5. UV–Vis–NIR reflection spectra of undyed cotton fabric, dyed cotton fabric and NPND raw materials of woodland CB against standardized barium sulphate.

been exhibited from 1305 to 1398 nm and 778 nm to 871 nm. The C–O strength is comparatively more vibrated in NIR spectrums. For chromatic explanation of UV to Vis range, the deviation of chromatic reflections are minor in UV and Vis region due to optical scattering and chromatic matching in terms of established chromatic assessment in Vis region related to violet (400–450 nm), indigo (450–500 nm), green (500–550 nm), yellow (550–600 nm), orange (600–650 nm) and red (650–700 nm). Chromatic intensity by reflection% in UV to Vis range from 220 nm 592 nm are comparatively lower due to higher absorption. The reflection% are gradually increased from 530 to 871 nm. From 901 nm, chromatic reflection starts to stabilize into straight direction due to lower absorption under continuous stretching vibrations. The key features of reflection% have been found a harmonized direction in the entire area of graphical stage from 220 to 1398 nm. Hence the entire reflection% of *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric have been demonstrated a graphical matching in UV–Vis–NIR compared with raw *Swietenia Macrophylla* and raw *Areca Catechu* which are signified as camouflage property under symmetrical properties of woodland CB. The compositional structures of cellulosic cotton and cellulosic structure of woodland CB have also been found symmetry in NIR reflection% from 716 to 1398 nm. The graphical line of reflection% of raw *Areca Catechu* was comparatively straight due to hard surface of *Areca Catechu* particles. Hence the darker chromatic hue of reddish tone of *Swietenia Macrophylla* wood (inner side) coated/dyed/printed fabric is correlated with the *Swietenia Macrophylla* tree of woodland CB due to similarities of existing phytochemical properties of chromatic reflection such as tannin, lignin, flavonoids etc. The molecular vibration of *Swietenia Macrophylla* in NIR has been excited associated with C=O, C–H, O–H and N–H bonds due to presence of lignin, cellulose, hemicellulose and phenolic compound. Hence the stretching vibrations are comparatively increased in NIR rather than UV–Vis range. The symmetrical stretching of O–H bond has been found due to cellulosic properties of *Swietenia Macrophylla*-wood and cotton fabric. Consequently, C=O and C–H stretching were also observed due to existing hemicellulose both in cotton fibre and *Swietenia Macrophylla*³⁴. The supporting information of UV–Vis–NIR camouflage assessment from 220 to 1400 nm have been sequentially attached in Tables 1–12 which are remarked as reflection (%) of standardized barium sulphate, *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric without mordanting, *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric with mordanting, undyed knitted cotton fabric, raw *Swietenia Macrophylla* and raw *Areca Catechu*.

Optical assessment of UV-protection property of *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric. Figure 6; possibly, the reflection of raw cotton fibre is critically uncommon due to high exposure of UV light from 220 to 282 nm. It may happen because of acceleration of yellowness and whiteness chroma, increased light energy,

Figure 6. UV-reflection of *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric with NPND mordanting and without mordanting, untreated cotton fabric, raw *Swietenia Macrophylla* and raw *Areca Catechu* compared with standardized barium sulphate.

therefore white fabric looks exceptionally brighter, hence the reflection tends to accelerate more than 100%. The UV parameters from 220 to 406 nm were also remarked based on UV reflection spectra³⁵. UV protection of UV-A and UV-B are comparatively lower of *Swietenia Macrophylla* treated fabric due to minimum percentage of reflectance, from 20 to 30%. Optical properties of light are related to transmission, absorption and reflection. According to established theory of energy, absorptivity + reflectivity + transmittance = 1. Therefore, the total expected absorption and transmittance will be around 70%. Natural illumination of UV is generally classified by UV-A (315–400 nm), UV-B (280–315 nm) and UV-C (below 280 nm) although UV-C was not measured in this experiment. The reflection% of UV-A and UV-B of *Swietenia Macrophylla* treated fabric were analysed by UV spectrum exposed in Fig. 6. The significant variations of UV reflection were observed between NPND dyed fabric and undyed knitted cotton fabric. UV protection of *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric was found 20% to 30%. The supporting information of UV-optical properties have been attached in Tables 1 and 2.

Field trialling segments: 1–3; chromatic analysis of NPND dyed-coated-printed garments, target signature against woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* under natural illumination of day light.

Figure 7A, raw image of NPND-dyed-coated-printed garments have been placed against *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*, woodland CB. Figure 7Aa and Ab depicts target signature of dyed fabric with nine color combination of NPND. Figure 7Ac and Ad remarks target signature of *Swietenia Macrophylla* coated and printed fabric. Figure 7Ae and Af shows the target signature of *Corchorus Capsularis* coated and printed fabric. Therefore, a combat engineering-color engineering-digital camera imaging-image processing technique was applied for Vis-range camouflage textiles assessment against selected CB environment. The target signatures were captured from two selected distances and the pictorial mapping were signified in Figure as 7Aa=7Ac=7Ae=7 ft and 7Ab=7Ad=7Af=21 ft for chromatic variation versus CDRI. Under CDRI evaluation; 7Ab, 7Ad, 7Af located target signature have been found partially camouflage against the materials of woodland CB such as tree stem/bark, green leaves, dry leaves of *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*. Accordingly; 7Aa, 7Ab, 7Ac, 7Ad, 7Ae, 7Af located target signature have been found color matching against woodland CB. Figure 7Aa and Ab, the reflection mechanism of dyed fabric with nine color combination was almost matched with woodland CB (*Shorea Robusta Gaertn*) compared with standardized black and white color fabric. The chromatic hue of NPND-nine color combination has minor difference of reflection compared with tree stem/bark, green leaves, dry leaves of *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*. Therefore, NPND-dyed garment has been found minor difference of chromatic reflection against woodland CB under natural illumination of day light. Figure 7Ac and Ad; the reddish chromatic hue of *Swietenia Macrophylla* coated part of garment was completely matched with the combat bark of *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* due to matching of phenolic pigment, anthocyanin of *Swietenia Macrophylla* treated textiles. Figure 7Ae and Af, the coated and printed fabric with *Corchorus Capsularis* was trialled with field experimentation against *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*, woodland CB and the target signature was also remarked as chromatic matching against woodland CB. The greenish chroma of *Corchorus Capsularis* coated part of garment was completely matched with the green leaves of *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*, possibly the well matching of green pigment named chlorophyll compound. Furthermore, existing protochlorophyll, anthocyanin and catechin in NPND may be the vital reason of reflection matching between woodland CB and target object of coated/printed NPND textiles. Figure 7B–D are remarked for the chromatic hue of CIE L*, a*, b*; generated from raw image mentioned in Fig. 7A. The mapping of Figure has been signified as Aa=Ba=Ca=Da; Ab=Bb=Cb=Db; Ac=Bc=Cc=Dc; Ad=Bd=Cd=Dd; Ae=Be=Ce=De; Af=Bf=Cf=Df; shown in Fig. 7 for photometric and colorimetric comparison of L*, a*, b*. Therefore, white-black/grey scale breakdown of CIE L*, a*, b* of object and background have been found camouflage shown in

Figure 7. NPND-dyed-coated-printed garments placed against woodland CB; shown the photometric versus colorimetric views of CIE L^* (**B**), a^* (**C**), b^* (**D**) in grey scale imaging of RGB raw image (**A**) when the pictorial mapping has been engendered as $Aa = Ba = Ca = Da$; $Ab = Bb = Cb = Db$; $Ac = Bc = Cc = Dc$; $Ad = Bd = Cd = Dd$; $Ae = Be = Ce = De$; $Af = Bf = Cf = Df$ for chromatic comparison.

Fig. 7Ba,Ca,Da,Bb,Cb,Db,Bc,Cc,Dc,Bd,Cd,Dd,Be,Ce,De,Bf,Cf,Df and compared with raw image of target signature against *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*, woodland CB shown in Fig. 7Aa,Ab,Ac,Ad,Ae,Af. Similarly Fig. 8A; raw image of NPND-dyed-coated-printed garments have been positioned against *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*, woodland CB; and RGB chromatic hues have been represented as blue color shown in Fig. 8B, green color shown in Fig. 8C and red color shown in Fig. 8B when $Aa = Ba = Ca = Da$; $Ab = Bb = Cb = Db$; $Ac = Bc = Cc = Dc$; $Ad = Bd = Cd = Dd$; $Ae = Be = Ce = De$; $Af = Bf = Cf = Df$ shown in Fig. 8. White-black/grey scale breakdown of RGB chromatic hue

Figure 8. NPND-dyed-coated-printed garments placed against woodland CB and shown the photometric versus colorimetric views of blue (B), green (C), red (D) in grey scale imaging of RGB raw image (A) when the pictorial mapping has been engendered as Aa = Ba = Ca = Da; Ab = Bb = Cb = Db; Ac = Bc = Cc = Dc; Ad = Bd = Cd = Dd; Ae = Be = Ce = De; Af = Bf = Cf = Df for chromatic comparison.

has also been shown camouflage shown in Fig. 8Ba,Ca,Da,Bb,Cb,Db,Bc,Cc,Dc,Bd,Cd,Dd,Be,Ce,De,Bf,Cf, Df compared with raw image of target signature against woodland CB revealed in Fig. 8Aa,Ab,Ac,Ad,Ae,Af. Figures 7Aa,Ab,Ba,Bb,Ca,Cb,Da,Db and 8Aa,Ab,Ba,Bb,Ca,Cb,Da,Db; dry leaves, seeds, tree bark and wood of NPND materials have presence of tannin (polyphenolic compound) which creates strong complex with OH group of cellulosic cotton fabric. Tannase is the main element of tannin. Tannase may be responsible for matching NPND-color formation of camouflage textile applications against woodland CB³⁶. The chromatic reflection of dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark and wood of woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* are related to chlorophyll/phytochemical in terms of green pigmentation/reddish chromatic hue³⁷. The reflection of NPND dyed textiles have been found almost similar reflection of woodland CB as dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark and wood are the key materials of woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*^{36,37}. Therefore, possible chromatic matching of

phytochemicals exists between NPND dyed-coated-printed garment and woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*. These phytochemicals are classified as swietenimacrophyllanin; catechine; 1,3 dihydroxy 2 methylanthraquinone; tannin and gallotannic acid which are chemically structured in Fig. 9. Furthermore, *Areca Catechu* is a NPND-mordanting agent which has the property of color sensitizing. *Areca Catechu* has coloring agents and color improvement agents due to remaining tannin, gallic acid, catechin, alkanoids, gum, etc. Existing gallotannic acid in *Areca Catechu* is a pigment, it may be responsible for color sensitizer as NPND-mordanting for NPND applications on textile substances^{38,39}. Figures 7Ac,Ad,Bc,Bd,Cc,Cd,Dc, Dd and 8Ac,Ad,Bc,Bd,Cc,Cd,Dc, Dd; the reddish chromatic hue of *Swietenia Macrophylla* is related to “reddish pale compound” named swietenimacrophyllanin has the tendency for reddish chromatic hue of coated cotton textiles as source of NPND. *Swietenia Macrophylla* coated fabric has been found exact matching against woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*⁴⁰. Similarly, Figs. 7Ae,Af,Be,Bf,Ce,Cf,De,Df and 8Ae,Af,Be,Bf,Ce,Cf,De,Df; “greenish hue” of *Corchorus Capsularis*-dry leaves has also been observed color matching against woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* due to crossing of chlorophyll and existing phytochemicals such as tannin and catechine of polyphenol group. Hence a crosslinking of NPND powder-polyaziridine-acrylonitrile copolymer-acrylic copolymer-cellulose may be formed to create a symmetrical chromatic hue of coated and printed textiles against woodland CB. This NPND formulation can be implemented for nature-friendly source of camouflage materials.

Field trialling segments: 4–6; chromatic analysis of NPND dyed-coated-printed garments, target signature against woodland CB, *Bamboo Vulgaris*, *Musa Acuminata*; and wooden bridge made of *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, *Bamboo Vulgaris*; and concrete CB under natural illumination of day light. Figures 10b,d,f and 11b,d,f; RGB raw image of dyed-coated-printed parts of garments have been appeared as concealed against woodland CB compared by standardized black and white. Wood chemistry of wooden bridge relates to cellulose, lignin, hemicellulose and chromatic elements of phytochemicals which have structural, compositional and chromatic similarity with dyed-coated-printed textiles with *Swietenia Macrophylla*. Similarly dry leaves and green leaves chemistry have also chromatic similarity with dyed-coated-printed textiles with NPND materials. Forest tree & wooden bridge may have variety of biological agents such as fungi, bacteria, insects which are uncontrollable parameters for chromatic hue such as blue stain, white rot and brown rot although chromatic compositions are aligned with NPND-dyed-coated-printed textiles. Figures 10a,c and 11a,c; RGB raw image of dyed-coated-printed textiles have been remarked as detected due to lacking of chlorophyll in NPND dyed-coated-printed part of garment but the target signature looks camouflage against soil background and looks detected against concrete background. Figures 10e,f and 11e,f; the chromatic hue of dry leaves of *Corchorus Capsularis* looks greenish to brownish. *Corchorus Capsularis* has existence with greenish tone, hence the coated-printed area of garment looks color matching against woodland CB of *Bamboo Vulgaris* and *Musa Acuminata*. Figures 10a1–f1; L* image of dyed-coated-printed garment looks color matching and completely concealed against a constructed wooden bridge made by *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, *Bamboo Vulgaris*; woodland CB of *Bamboo Vulgaris* and *Musa Acuminata*, soil and concrete CB; compared by standardized white and black. Figure 10a2,b2,e2,f2,a3,b3; similarly, a* & b* image of dyed-coated-printed parts of garments looks concealed and Fig. 10c2,d2,c3,d3,e3,f3; a* & b* image of coated-printed parts of garments looks detected against woodland CB. Figure 11a1–f1,a2–f2,a3–f3; under RGB image analysis, the image of dyed-coated-printed textiles looks exceptionally color matching & camouflage against a constructed wooden bridge made by *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, *Bamboo Vulgaris*; woodland CB of *Bamboo Vulgaris* and *Musa Acuminata*; soil and concrete CB; compared by standardized white and black.

Figure 9. Phytochemicals of NPND materials responsible for camouflage coloration against woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*.

Figure 10. NPND-dyed-coated-printed garments placed against woodland CB and wooden bridge; and shown the photometric versus colorimetric views of L^* (a1–f1), a^* (a2–f2), b^* (a3–f3) in grey scale imaging of RGB raw image (a–f) when the pictorial mapping has been engendered as $a1 = a2 = a3 = a4$; $b1 = b2 = b3 = b4$; $c1 = c2 = c3 = c4$; $d1 = d2 = d3 = d4$; $e1 = e2 = e3 = e4$; $f1 = f2 = f3 = f4$ for chromatic comparison.

Chromatic analysis of L^* , a^* , b^* , RGB of NPND-dyed-coated-printed garments against combat backgrounds. Figure 12A, CIE L^* , a^* , b^* values of NPND-coated-printed textiles are more symmetrical with CB materials in general rather than NPND-dyed textiles due to chromatic matching between treated textiles and CB materials. There are also exceptions of symmetric matching of L^* , a^* , b^* for colorful dyed fabric such as *Swietenia Macrophylla*, *Mangifera Indica*, *Terminalia Arjuna*, *Camellia Sinensis* and *Acacia Acuminata*. L^* value of *Corchorus Capsularis* and *Cinnamomum Tamala* are comparatively higher due to lower interactions of dye-fibre and mordant free coloration in NPND-dyebath. L^* , a^* , b^* values of *Swietenia Macrophylla* and *Corchorus Capsularis* coated fabric are exceptionally matching against woodland CB of *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* (green leaves) and *Bamboo Vulgaris* (green leaves). L^* value of *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed fabric is comparatively lower due to NPND-mordanting of *Areca Catechu* and comparatively higher dye-fibre interactions in NPND-dyebath¹⁸. Figure 12B, similarly CIE trichromatic intensity of *Swietenia Macrophylla* and *Corchorus Capsularis* coated fab-

Figure 11. NPND-dyed-coated-printed garments placed against woodland CB and wooden bridge; and shown the photometric versus colorimetric views of red (a1–f1), green (a2–f2), blue (a3–f3) in grey scale imaging of RGB raw image (a–f) when the pictorial mapping has been engendered as $a1 = a2 = a3 = a4$; $b1 = b2 = b3 = b4$; $c1 = c2 = c3 = c4$; $d1 = d2 = d3 = d4$; $e1 = e2 = e3 = e4$; $f1 = f2 = f3 = f4$ for chromatic comparison.

ric are mostly matching with the selected CBs of *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* (stem/bark); *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* (green leaves); *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* (soil bed with dry leaves); Dry wood of *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, wooden bridge; Dry wood of *Bamboo Vulgaris*; wooden bridge; Soil background; *Bamboo Vulgaris* and *Musa Acuminata*. The RGB chromatic intensity of *Swietenia Macrophylla*, *Mangifera Indica*, *Terminalia Arjuna*, *Camellia Sinensis*, *Azadirachta Indica*, *Acacia Acuminata*, and *Areca Catechu* dyed fabric have been found comparatively matching with multidimensional CBs related to woodland. The chromatic data information of NPND materials and CB materials have been cited in supporting information, Table 13.

Figure 12. Quantitative comparison of CIE L^* , a^* , b^* (A) and RGB (B) values for NPND dyed-coated-printed part placed against multidimensional CBs.

Concluding remarks

NPND dyeing process can be replaced by coating/printing in terms of higher percentage of NPND deposition/ leafy design development on fabric surface which may have more symmetry between defence target object (camouflage treated textiles) and the materials of woodland CB, this formulation may be a new model of NPND formulated camouflage textiles for concealment of target detection for defence applications in terms of eco-friendly dyes; and NPND-mordanting process for NPND based natural coloration. The phenolic and tannin reflection between *Swietenia Macrophylla* treated fabric and raw *Swietenia Macrophylla* have not been found

any significant difference in terms of UV–Vis–NIR spectrums from 220 to 1400 nm which may signify a symmetrical matching of optical reflection between *Swietenia Macrophylla* treated textiles and woodland CB. The minor deviation of chromatic reflection between woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* and *Swietenia Macrophylla* dyed-coated-printed textiles have also been found in field trialling. *Swietenia Macrophylla* bark has been remarked as good coloration property, applicable for dyeing-coating-printing; and the reflection properties are suitable for camouflage coloration against woodland CB. Waste-NPND powder of wood processing industries may be a good source of combat-NPND. Hence, there is possibility for development of NPND treated camouflage coloration for defence protection such as defence clothing/temporary tents/nets for combat locations against woodland CB; preferred textile technologies are coating/printing for maximum deposition of NPND on textile substances. Furthermore, NPND coated/printed/dyed fabric may be used for manufacture of UV protective clothing for defence protection of simultaneous ‘camouflage textiles’ and ‘UV-protective textiles’. An ecofriendly concept of NPND coloration was applied in addition to mordant free coloration and/or NPND-mordanting/bio-mordanting without applications of any synthetic mordant. Therefore coating/printing method of NPND treated textiles have been found more efficient for camouflage formulation and coloration. NPND-dyed-coated-printed textiles can be formulated for defence clothing, protection net/tent in CB. For photographic reflection of coated and printed textiles as target object and selected woodland background as target woodland CB; coated textile is more suitable but a combination of coated-printed-NPND textiles or dyed-printed-NPND textiles can be recommended for making a leafy design on fabric against woodland CB in terms of defence clothing. NPND coated textiles is more suitable technique for symmetrical reflection with woodland CB. For example: coating of net and tent for defence protection against woodland CB. Hence, there is enormous possibilities of research on natural coloration but the concept of NPND based camouflage textiles is a new experimentation for defence applications and an ecofriendly formulation of NPND coloration. Although NPND-mordanting has been opined in this experiment but the application of synthetic mordant may enhance the functional activity of tannase for more dye-fibre crosslinking of NPND based textile coloration. Furthermore, NPND nanoparticle-synthetic binder-cotton/synthetic fabric can be applied for coated/printed fabrication against selected CB for achievement of desired camouflage textiles. Hence, NPND-natural dyes-natural mordant-natural fibre-cotton can also be implemented/extended for ecofriendly production of fashionable garments specially for production of kid's garments/medical textiles in terms of user's friendly/protection textiles.

It is very critical issue to decide a specific NPND material for a very specific standardizing of concealment against woodland CB due to variation of chromatic chemistry by season; chromatic chemistry by combat location; chromatic chemistry by combat region, chromatic chemistry by multidimensional part of chromatic materials such as dry leaves, green leaves, barks/stems; chromatic chemistry by different species of NPND materials, chromatic chemistry by location of woodland CB against sunlight and chromatic chemistry in multidimensional spectral region in UV–Vis–IR. To avoid difficulties, the multidimensional source of NPND materials can be combined and formulated for coated/printed technique of camouflage textiles for better color matching and spectral matching in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. Under chromatic analysis, it is feasible to implement NPND based textile coloration for chromatic matching against woodland CB. *Swietenia Macrophylla*, *Mangifera Indica*, *Terminalia Arjuna*, *Camellia Sinensis*, *Azadirachta Indica*, *Acacia Acuminata*, *Areca Catechu*, *Cinnamomum Tamala*, *Corchorus Capsularis*, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*, *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, *Bamboo Vulgaris*, *Musa Acuminata* and related species of plants are remarked as NPND materials. Different types of NPND materials, different parts of tree (leaves, wood, bark, root, fruit peel, fruit seed, flower, etc.) and different source of waste NPND materials can be collected, grinded and mixed in textile processing industry as nano particle for even textile dyeing/coating/printing of ‘green coloration’, ‘green mordanting’ and ‘green processing’ in terms of technical property rather than coloration only. Both NPND solid coloration and NPND patterning can be considered for camouflage formulation as per combat environment and/or requirement of defence professional/region related to woodland CB.

Data availability

All data generated or analysed during this experimentation are included in supplementary information file; Tables 1–13, supporting information.

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Research Article

Coloration of Polyamide-6, 6 Fabric with Carbon Black Nano Particle for Camouflage Textiles of Simultaneous Spectrum Probe in Visible and Near Infrared

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Camouflage textiles on simultaneous spectrum probe in Visible-Near Infrared (Vis-NIR) have been explicated under optical mechanism of reflection and chromatic hue. Polyamide 6,6 (PA-6,6) fabric was experimented for liquid phase formulation and coloration in acidic medium of seven standardized P^H (0-6) with Carbon Black Nano Particle (CBNP). International commission on illumination (CIE) color value (L*, a*, b*), Kubelka-Munk (K-M) reflection and reflection (%) of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric was investigated with optical condition of specular reflectance, color measurement spectrophotometer from 400 nm to 700 nm. The K-M reflection and reflection (%) of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric was also measured with optical property of diffuse reflectance, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy from 1000 nm to 2500 nm. Vis-NIR reflection (%) was observed comparatively lower for P^H 4 to 5. Similarly, K-M reflection of simultaneous spectrum probe in Vis-NIR was found higher for P^H 4 to 5. Raw CBNP and CBNP modified PA-6,6 fabric was also examined for oxidation property, aggregation property, coloring property and air permeability by scanning electron microscopy. Hence, this experimentation was only focused on color properties of CBNP modified PA-6,6 fabric in terms of camouflage textiles.

Keywords: Camouflage textiles; Carbon black nano particle; Polyamide-6,6; Coloration; Visible-Near infrared spectrums

Abbreviations: CBNP: Carbon Black Nano Particle; CIE: International Commission on Illumination; FM: Formulation; K-M: Kubelka-Munk; MIR: Medium Infrared; nm: Nanometer; PA-6,6: Polyamide 6,6; NIR: Near Infrared; SEM: Scanning Electron Microscopy; Vis: Visible; T_g: Glass Transition Temperature; KBr: Potassium Bromide; mL: Millilitre

Introduction

The current limitation of camouflage textiles relates to chromatic and/or reflection matching for simultaneous spectrum probe against multidimensional Combat Backgrounds (CBs). There is limited solution and optical approach of adaptive camouflage textiles against CBs. Carbon Black Nano Particle (CBNP) has low reflection effect of simultaneous spectrums in Visible-Near Infrared (Vis-NIR). The combination of CBNP with synthetic dyes will minimize the intensity for camouflage textiles in simultaneous spectrums of Vis-NIR [1-4]. CBNP can be formulated with brown, olive, green and khaki colorants for improvement of camouflage property. Low reflection patterning will improve the camouflaging effect against multidimensional CBs in general. In literature, laboratory stage camouflage assessment is very limited for camouflage applications, but it is

necessary to signify the optical properties of camouflage object against multidimensional CBs [4-10].

Engineering of CBNP for Camouflage Coloration

Liquid phase dyeing is a common process for textile coloration but CBNP based technical Formulation (FM) and camouflage coloration is still a new approach in terms of water bath dyeing [11-17]. Nitric Acid (NA) modified CBNP has liquid phase oxidation property for enhancement of low reflection chromatic hue. CBNP reduces the reflection in Vis-NIR for simultaneous concealment against Vis-NIR surveillance [1,4,16,18-22]. Research is limited to achieve low reflection property of polyamide 6,6 (PA-6,6) fabric in Vis-NIR spectrums[23-25]. CBNP treated fabric reduces reflection than synthetic dyes such as vat

dyes [26]. CBNP is a self-agglomerate material due to existing van der Waals forces. Raw CBNP has hydrophobic property. Oxidation and dispersing agents generate hydrophilicity on CBNP surface [27]. CBNP has different properties in terms of particle size, surface structure, surface size, P^H value and density. These properties of CBNP signify the hydrophobicity, hydrophilicity and dispersibility for textile dyeing-coating-printing [5-8, 28]. Figure 1a shows the structure of CBNP.

Engineering of PA-6,6 Fabric Coloration with CBNP

PA-6,6-CBNP-NA-liquid phase dyeing has been assumed a Brownian movement pattern when dyebath temperature is higher than glass transition temperature T_g . The property of PA-6,6 fabric may follow a physical assumption of rubbery state in dyebath at high temperature. Molecular distance of PA-6,6 fabric increases and CBNP can penetrate inside the fabric. Therefore, a gradual percolation of CBNP into PA-6,6 fabric may formulate the coloration property [15,29-33]. In this experimentation, PA-6,6 fabric used for high temperature dyeing with CBNP, cited the structure in Figure 1 [4]. Figure 1b shows the structure of PA-6,6.

Materials, Methods and Formulations of PA-6, 6 Coloration with CBNP

Three types of laboratory grade CBNP from three different chemical companies were trialed for coloration of 130 gram per square meter (g/m^2) PA-6,6 fabric. CBNP was also used from Cabot corporation Ltd, USA. Laboratory grade 70% NA was used for acidic medium dyeing. Surface modification of CBNP was performed by NA oxidation [4,34]. CBNP-NA-water medium was dispersed by electric blender for 30 minutes and seven standard P^H (0-6) was set in CBNP dye bath by dropping technique of NA addition. Standardized dyeing process was applied for PA-6,6-CBNP-NA-water medium dyeing process without dispersing agent and binder [29,30,34-36]. Material and liquor ratio was kept around 1:18. Dyeing and coating formulations are individually cited in Table 1. Dyeing machine temperature was increased at $2^\circ C/min$ and temperature raised upto $100^\circ C$ and continued the run time of machine for 30 minutes. Figure 2 shows front view of laboratory dyeing machine (a), empty roller of sample dyeing machine before rolling fabric (b), rolled PA-6,6 fabric on roller surface before placing in dyebath (c), dyed PA-6,6 fabric on roller surface after removing from dyebath (d), CBNP dispersed solution without dispersing agent (e) [37], CBNP coating on fabric by laboratory coating machine, CBNP was encapsulated by polyurethane binder (f). Therefore, CBNP dyed samples were proceeded for structural properties, and camouflage analysis of electron imaging, color value and Vis-NIR reflection.

Testing Machines and Methods of Optical Analysis

CIE, color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^*) were measured by Hunter lab reflectance spectrophotometer, Color Flex EZ; model, 45/0

LAV; under testing conditions with geometry, $45^\circ/0^\circ$; viewing area, large; D65 illuminant/ 10° standard observer; room temperature, $18^\circ C$ [4,23,38]. Colorflex EZ was used for the measurement of CIE color parameters of L^* , a^* , b^* and ΔE ; reflection (%) and Kubelka-Munk (K-M) reflection. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, PerkinElmer was used for assessment of reflection (%) and K-M reflection in .5 nm distance [3,38]. Hence, two different geometries of spectroscopic illumination such as specular and diffuse reflection were performed for measurement of Vis-NIR optical properties of CBNP modified PA-6,6 fabric.

Kubelka Munk Reflection Measurement in Vis-NIR Spectrums

K-M and Lord Rayleigh's law are related to refractive index versus wavelength based on assuming two different parameters. K-M theory is mostly defined for particle size and wavelength. As per K-M theory, scattering coefficients are constant throughout the sample of same particle size [39]. Therefore, Vis-K-M-specular reflection and NIR-K-M-diffuse reflection were tested for CBNP dyed and undyed PA-6,6 fabric [36].

Vis-K-M-specular reflection of untreated and treated PA-6,6 fabric samples were determined by K/S equation.

$$\frac{K}{S} = \frac{(1 - R_{\lambda_{max}})^2}{2R_{\lambda_{max}}} \infty C_{CBNP}$$

Where, Where, K = coefficient of absorption, S = coefficient of scattering, $R_{\lambda_{max}}$ = reflectance of the substrate at maximum absorbance wavelength, C_{CBNP} = concentration of nano particle [19, 40-44].

NIR-K-M-diffuse reflection of untreated and treated PA-6,6 fabric samples were also measured by K/S equation [3].

$$K/S = (1 - R_{\infty})/2R_{\infty} \infty C_{CBNP}$$

where K and S represents absorption and scattering coefficients respectively, and R_{∞} denotes reflectance factor from fabric surface, C_{CBNP} = concentration of nano particle [32,75].

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

A table microscope SEM machine, TM4000/TM4000Plus, Hitachi, Japan and SC7620 sputter coater (Figure SI 2), Quorum, UK were used under 25 magnification, 100 magnification, 500 magnification; and 15KV power selection for each scanning. Three categories of acid modified raw CBNP and water modified raw CBNP were scanned by SEM. Acid and water diluted CBNP samples were simply dried in closed chamber at selected temperature and cooled before SEM scanning. RGB intensity of SEM image was measured by ImageJ software to signify oxidation property. The highest CBNP visible area of SEM image was selected by rectangular method, width = 15 pixels and height = 18 pixels under the distances from 0 to 15 pixels captured by ImageJ software. The standardized RGB intensity was followed from the value of 0 to 255. The plot profile of grey value was

Table 1: Seven standard P^H (0-6) in CBNP dyebath of PA-6,6 fabric coloration for formulation 1-7 and CBNP coating with formulation 8.

Formulation-01 (Dyeing)	Formulation-02 (Dyeing)	Formulation-03 (Dyeing)	Formulation-04 (Dyeing)
CBNP: 0.5g	CBNP: 0.5g	CBNP: 0.5g	CBNP: 0.5g
Temperature: $100^\circ C$	Temperature: $100^\circ C$	Temperature: $100^\circ C$	Temperature: $100^\circ C$
Time: 30 min	Time: 30 min	Time: 30 min	Time: 30 min
P^H : 0, Nitric Acid	P^H : 1, Nitric Acid	P^H : 3, Nitric Acid	P^H : 3, Nitric Acid
PA-6,6 Fabric: 11g	PA-6,6 Fabric: 11g	PA-6,6 Fabric: 11g	PA-6,6 Fabric: 11g
Distilled water: 200 ml	Distilled water: 200 ml	Distilled water: 200 ml	Distilled water: 200 ml
Formulation-05 (Dyeing)	Formulation-06 (Dyeing)	Formulation-07 (Dyeing)	Formulation-08 (Dyeing)
CBNP: 0.5g	CBNP: 0.5g	CBNP: 0.5g	CBNP: 5g
Temperature: $100^\circ C$	Temperature: $100^\circ C$	Temperature: $100^\circ C$	5% solution of 70%
Time: 30 min	Time: 30 min	Time: 30 min	Nitric Acid: 1ml
P^H : 4, Nitric Acid	P^H : 5, Nitric Acid	P^H : 6, Nitric Acid	Tubicoat binder: 5g
PA-6,6 Fabric: 11g	PA-6,6 Fabric: 11g	PA-6,6 Fabric: 11g	
Distilled water: 200 ml	Distilled water: 200 ml	Distilled water: 200 ml	

Figure 1: (a) structure of CBNP and (b) structure of polyamide 6,6.

Figure 2: Experimental platform of CBNP formulation and coloration on PA-6,6 fabric.

Figure 3: SEM morphology versus RGB intensity of water and acid modified raw CBNP to signify oxidation property.

Figure 4: SEM morphology versus grey value intensity; undyed PA-6,6 fabric (a), CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric (b-h) and grey value intensity (a1-h1).

Figure 5: CIE color value of undyed PA-6,6 fabric and dyed PA-6,6 fabric with formulation 1-7.

Figure 6: Vis-NIR reflection (%) of undyed and dyed PA-6,6 fabric with formulation 1-7 Assessment of K-M reflection in Vis-NIR spectrums.

Figure 7: Vis-NIR-K-M reflection of undyed and dyed PA-6,6 fabric with formulation 1-7.

Figure 8: Expected applications of CBNP modified camouflage textiles.

also generated under the constant parameters of distances from 0 to 80 pixels captured by ImageJ software; area selected by rectangular method, width = 100 pixels and height = 100 pixels; the standardized intensity of grey value from 0 to 255. The intensity value of 0 denotes minimum intensity/black and the intensity value of 255 denotes maximum intensity/white [10].

It was almost unachievable to generate contrast electron imaging of CBNP dyed and undyed PA-6,6 fabric due to fine particle and lacking of structural deviation. For CBNP dyed and undyed fabric, a thin film thickness of carbon coating was achieved by sputter coater for SEM scanning. Additionally, SEM scanning without carbon coating was also trialed for CBNP dyed and undyed fabric for comparison of electron imaging shown in supporting information, figure SI 1.

Potassium Bromide (KBr) free Diffuse Reflection Measurement by Fourier Transform infrared Spectrometry in Near Infrared Spectrums from 1000 nm to 2500 nm

PerkinElmer is a common manufacturer of Infrared (IR) spectroscopy. This company has different model of IR spectroscopy with versatile configuration of sample port. Every sample port has different mechanism of scanning as directed in application note. In transmission mode, light directed through the sample and captured spectra by the system. So, KBr matrix is used for more accurate result as non-absorbing principle where internal particle is a major influencing factor for optical principle of transmission. KBr matrix is also suitable material for fixing sample in sample port for standardization of optical scanning. KBr is more likely implemented for sample measurement in Medium Infrared (MIR), 2500 nm-25000 nm. KBr is non absorbing material in MIR. Oppositely in reflection mode, light reflected from the surface of the target sample. Diffuse reflectance is a matter of structural geometry on surface area. So, KBr matrix is not a matter of invalid result where reflection of internal particle is very negligible influencing factor. Refractive index of KBr may also issue of reflection accuracy in NIR. As per K-M theory, scattering coefficients are mostly depends on particle size, not absorption. It is also predicted that if particle size is zero, scattering coefficient is also zero [39]. Absorption in the NIR is typically about 100 times weaker than MIR. The very weak absorptions in NIR are reported as small changes in refractive index. KBr is zero absorbance material which minimize the interference of reflection when absorbency is measured in MIR [47]. In this experimenta-

tion, CBNP is an IR absorbing material. The penetration depth of diffuse reflection is almost zero for high IR absorbing materials. Furthermore, this experimentation has been defined for coefficients of reflection. Machine has specific glass vial designed as sample port. In NIR spectroscopy, the core mechanism is glass sample port which is covered by sample cup to create reflection environment under a specified black standard termed as 'spectralon reflection'. Absorption and transmission of rays are not creating reflection of sample. These rays are not participating to make a spectral signal as diffuse reflection [39,47-49]. The whole mechanism is occurring underneath the glass vial. The sample port has sapphire/crystal window to capture reflection of sample. Therefore, KBr free measurement of CBNP dyed and undyed PA-6,6 fabric was experimented for diffuse reflectance measurement in NIR spectrums [4,50].

Results and Discussion

SEM Characterization of Raw CBNP under Heating and Cooling Mechanism to Signify Low Reflection Property

Figure 3a, NA modified CBNP; figure 3b, RGB intensity of NA modified CBNP; Figure 3c, NA modified and oxidized CBNP after two-hour heating in closed chamber at 100°C; Figure 3d, RGB intensity of NA modified and oxidized CBNP after two-hour heating in closed chamber at 100°C; Figure 3e, water modified CBNP; Figure 3f, RGB intensity of water modified CBNP; Figure 3g, water modified and oxidized CBNP after two-hour heating in closed chamber at 100°C; Figure 3h, RGB intensity of water modified and oxidized CBNP after two-hour heating in closed chamber at 100°C; Figure 3i, water diluted CBNP before heating; Figure 3j, RGB intensity of water diluted CBNP before heating; Figure 3k, water diluted and oxidized CBNP after two-hour heating in closed chamber at 100°C; Figure 3l, RGB intensity of water diluted CBNP after two-hour heating in closed chamber at 100°C. Figure 3c, 3g; aggregation of CBNP reduces the surface area due to adsorption of nitrogen. Aggregated CBNP looks like blister in electron imaging. Heated CBNP blister looks comparatively darker than without heated CBNP blister, shown in figure 3c, 3g and 3k. CBNP looks darker due to the enhancement of COOH group on CBNP surface relates to the mechanism of heating-oxidation-COOH formation. NA treatment on CBNP may generate hydrophilicity of CBNP. The particle size of water modified CBNP is lower, shown in figure 3e and 3g and comparatively higher in acid modified CBNP due to hydrophilicity nature of NA modified CBNP shown in figure 3a and 3d. The tendency of aggregation is comparatively higher of acid modified CBNP due to fusing and covalent bond between molecule to molecule [31,34,51,52]. Particle size of CBNP also influences dye aggregation. Higher particle size has a tendency of higher CBNP aggregation due to hydrophilicity nature. RGB intensity of SEM image also signifies lower intensity of oxidized CBNP. RGB intensity of oxidized CBNP, 3d < RGB intensity of non-oxidized CBNP, 3b; RGB intensity of oxidized CBNP, 3h < RGB intensity of non-oxidized CBNP, 3f; RGB intensity of oxidized CBNP, 3l < RGB intensity of non-oxidized CBNP, 3j. Due to oxidation property of CBNP, the RGB intensity of heated CBNP was comparatively lower mentioned in figure 3d, 3h, 3l than the RGB intensity of without heated CBNP mentioned in figure 3b, 3f, 3j [31,53]. This evidence of CBNP oxidation supports for the applications of low reflection chromatic property. Chromatic aberration relates to electron energy. Every image has RGB chromatic hue. Figure 3 denotes the RGB intensity in the form of black and white chromatic hue. Figure 3 explained with ImageJ software for clarification. Therefore, CBNP oxidation and low reflection chromatic

property has been discussed by SEM. The optical theory of image formation between diffused reflection and scattered electron has almost similar action to form an image although the mechanical properties are completely different. Photon relates to reflection for optical imaging. Electron relates to electron imaging in SEM.

Structural Characterization of PA-6,6 Dyed Fabric with CBNP

Figure 4, structural differences relates to the deviation of dyed fabric surface. In general, nano-dyed fabric shows minor deviation in SEM scanning due to unchanging of fabric structure [54]. Figure 4a, SEM morphology of untreated PA-6,6 fabric; Figure 4a1, SEM morphology versus grey value intensity of untreated PA-6,6 fabric; figure 4b, CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-1, P^H:0; figure 4b1, grey value intensity of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-1, P^H:0; figure 4c, CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-2, P^H:1; figure 4c1, grey value intensity of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-2, P^H:1; figure 4d, CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-3; P^H:2; figure 4d1, grey value intensity of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-3, P^H:2; figure 4e, CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-4; P^H:3; figure 4e1, grey value intensity of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-4, P^H:3; figure 4f, CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-5, P^H:4; figure 4f1, grey value intensity of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-5, P^H:4; figure 4g, CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-6, P^H:5; figure 4g1, grey value intensity of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-6, P^H:5; figure 4h, CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-7, P^H:6; figure 4h1, grey value intensity of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-7, P^H:6. The electron imaging of dyed fabric is not standardized way for adsorption of CBNP measurement on PA-6,6 fabric surface. Electron image of dyed and undyed PA-6,6 fabric is not able to compare clearly due to minor structural deviation. There is enormous lacking of significant deviation between dyed and undyed PA-6,6 fabric when structural deviation of knitted fabric looks almost unchanged after dyeing. Hence, it is so tough to identify the deviation of electron imaging between treated and untreated PA-6,6 fabric due to smooth surface [1,55]. The fluctuation of grey value intensity in electron imaging has also been shown in figure 4b, 4d, 4f, 4h, 4l, 4l for more clarification and signification. The highest variation of grey value intensity of dyed PA-6,6 fabric is noted around ± 14 compared with undyed PA-6,6 fabric under the fluctuation of selected pixel area. Oppositely, the lowest variation of grey value intensity of dyed PA-6,6 fabric is also remarked around ± 15 compared with undyed PA-6,6 fabric under the fluctuation of selected pixel area. Accordingly, it can be noted that FM-1, FM-2, FM-3, FM-4 have minor presence of CBNP; and FM-5, FM-6, FM-7 have maximum presence of CBNP due to optimum level of acidic P^H. PA-6,6 fibre forming polymer has free volume in the polymer chain which may retain CBNP through diffusion technique in dyebath when temperature of dyebath raises above T_g [29]. Under this consequence of electron imaging of dyed and undyed PA-6,6 fabric, the air permeability may have in acceptable range without blocking the significant area of fabric pore for clothing comfort. Minor structural deviation in electron imaging signifies the finer particle size which may increase the air permeability. The property of air permeability is the core requirement for defence uniform [1].

Figure 5, comparison of CIE color value of undyed PA-6,6 fabric and CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-1, P^H:0; FM-2, P^H:1; FM-3, P^H:2; FM-4, P^H:3; FM-5, P^H:4; FM-6, P^H:5 and FM-7, P^H:6. L*, a*, b* values are slightly lower for FM-04 and higher for FM-7 due to deviation of existing CBNP on PA-6,6 fabric surface. Color difference, ΔE is almost similar of all formulated CBNP dyed PA-

6,6 fabric rather than FM-1, FM-2 and FM-7 [27,42]. The reaction may happen between -CONH₂ group of PA-6,6 and COOH of oxidized CBNP at selected temperature, 100°C. The supporting information has been cited in table SI 3.

Chromatic Assessment of CIE L*, a*, b* and ΔE from 400 nm to 700 nm

Assessment of Reflection (%) in Vis-NIR Spectrums

Figure 6A, comparison of reflection (%) of undyed PA-6,6 fabric and reflection (%) of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-1, P^H:0; FM-2, P^H:1; FM-3, P^H:2; FM-4, P^H:3; FM-5, P^H:4; FM-6, P^H:5; FM-7, P^H:6. The reflection (%) looks similar when PA-6,6 fabric was dyed with CBNP, FM 1-7. FM-4, P^H:3 looks comparatively lower reflection (%) than FM-1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7. In general, reflection (%) of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric has low reflection property when -CONH₂ group of PA-6,6 is modified by the chromatic property of COOH presence in CBNP. It is a suitable property for camouflage formulation of PA-6,6 fabric [1,21,56]. The supporting information has also been cited in table SI 1.

Figure 6B, comparison of NIR-reflection of undyed PA-6,6 fabric and CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-1, P^H:0; FM-2, P^H:1; FM-3, P^H:2; FM-4, P^H:3; FM-5, P^H:4; FM-6, P^H:5; FM-7, P^H:6. NIR-reflection is comparatively lower for FM 1-7 and remarkably lower for FM-5. CBNP can be formulated for NIR camouflage textiles in terms of low reflection property of CBNP material. Due to lower reflection property of CBNP, the reflection of chromatic compound was not identified by the spectra from 1000 nm to 1700 nm. The reflection of hiding amide group, -CONH₂ was remarked for FM, 1-7. The bending of reflection spectra of untreated PA 6,6 fabric was completely hid for 1200 nm, 1573 nm, 1536 nm and 1750 nm due to the smooth layer of CBNP chromatic compound (COOH, C=O) on the polymeric layer/chain of amide group, -CONH₂ existing in PA-6,6 fabric. The reflection (%) at 1715 nm, 1946 nm, 2052 nm, 2185 nm, 2293 nm, 2375 nm were comparatively lower for CBNP modified PA-6,6 fabric due to chromatic intensity of CBNP on PA 6,6 fabric. The supporting information has been cited in figure SI 3-11 and table SI 5.

Assessment of K-M Reflection in Vis-NIR Spectrums

Figure 7A, comparison of Vis-K-M reflection of undyed PA-6,6 fabric and CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-1, P^H:0; FM-2, P^H:1; FM-3, P^H:2; FM-4, P^H:3; FM-5, P^H:4; FM-6, P^H:5; FM-7, P^H:6. K-M reflection is higher of dyed PA-6,6 fabric; FM-04. The K-M reflection was gradually decreased when the fabric was trialed with higher P^H and lower amount of NA. -CONH₂ group of PA-6,6 fabric is modified by the chromatic property of existing COOH in CBNP. The supporting information has been cited in table SI 2.

Figure 7B, NIR-K-M reflection of undyed PA-6,6 fabric and CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric with FM-1, P^H:0; FM-2, P^H:1; FM-3, P^H:2; FM-4, P^H:3; FM-5, P^H:4; FM-6, P^H:5; FM-7, P^H:6. Comparison of NIR-K-M reflection is higher for FM-04, and comparatively lower for other formulated PA-6,6 fabric. Higher K-M reflection value identifies the coloring property of CBNP on PA-6,6 fabric. The K-M reflection was gradually increased when the existing -CONH₂ compound of PA-6,6 has been modified by COOH and C=O compound of CBNP. The symmetric bending of spectra has been identified and gradually modified for K-M reflection at 1700-1800 nm, 2000-2100 nm, 2200 nm and 2295 nm. The supporting information has been cited in table SI 4 and figure SI 12.

Conclusion

The theory and approach of simultaneous concealment in Vis-NIR is not still established for camouflage applications. There is ongoing research for Vis camouflage and NIR camouflage individually. There is technical difficulties for development of simultaneous camouflage textiles due to deviation of optical response in Vis-NIR spectrums. The low reflection property is a crucial and common unit of camouflage property against multi-dimensional CBs in Vis-NIR spectrums. Therefore, low reflection property of CBNP modified dyed fabric has been logically explained in terms of reflection %, K-M reflection in Vis-NIR spectrums. Therefore, figure 8 shows the summarized applications and scope of CBNP modified camouflage textiles for defence applications in Vis-NIR spectrums although modification of chromatic materials and achromatic design depends on specific combat environment.

CBNP has coloring property of PA-6,6 fabric under standardized matching of P^H in liquid phase oxidation and coloration. CBNP has lower reflection property for simultaneous concealment in Vis-NIR against combat background. The lower reflection property of CBNP dyed PA-6,6 fabric has been supported by the chromatic mechanism of electron imaging; Vis-NIR-reflection (%); Vis-NIR-K-M reflection and CIE L^* , a^* , b^* values. CBNP can also be combined with different dyestuff for color matching against selected combat background. CBNP liquid phase coloration has the feasibility for clothing comfort of defence professional in terms air permeability. This clothing comfort property can be applied for design of defence uniform in addition to camouflage formulation and coloration.

Author Statements

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

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Data Availability

All data generated or analyzed during this experimentation are included in supporting information, Table SI 1-5 and Figure SI 1-12.

Author Contribution

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Author, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain [17,57,58] [40] [3,4,10-15,18-21,38,41-44,46,56,59-66] [9,24,67-69] [3-10,18,19,21,23-25,33,38,41,46,56,58,67-81] Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh acknowledges RMIT University and Australian government for funding through Research Training Program (RTP) stipend scholarship, 2020-2023. Author indebted to 'Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang' for supplying CBNP material from his material laboratory. Author is grateful to 'Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks' for his valuable suggestion of polyamide

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Cr oxide-coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signatures in the UV-Visible-IR spectrums opposing hyperspectral and digital imaging

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Abstract

The chromatic intensity and thermal mechanism are the vital segments for the protection of military targets in ultraviolet (UV)-visible (Vis)-infrared (IR) imaging. Defense operations need to confront the targets with UV-Vis-IR imaging to distinguish or conceal the targets from the combat backgrounds (CB). The key purpose of this experimentation is to develop the imaging and optical intensity concepts of chromatic appearance for the concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI) of target signatures. Cr oxide-coated target signatures have been analyzed against hyperspectral and digital camera imaging in UV-Vis-IR optical signals. The chromatic intensity of Cr oxide-formulated polyamide 6,6 (PA-6,6) fabric was examined by Vis-IR-hyperspectral imaging (HSI) at 400, 500, 600, 700, 1000, 1300, 1600, 1900, 2200, and 2500 nm. UV-Vis-IR-HSI have been experimented by international commission on illumination (CIE), red-green-blue standardized color scale for concealment and detection in UV-Vis-IR optical ranges. Concealment of target signature was observed at 400, 500, 600, 700, 2200, and 2500 nm when Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric was scanned in 22,948 μ s (microsecond)-Vis-HSI and 10,500 μ s-IR-HSI. The optical imaging, optical reflection and CIE-chromaticity of Australian grass (green leaves), *Bothriochloa Pertusa*; and Eucalyptus tree (green leaves), *Eucalyptus Mannifera* woodland CB, and Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric have been found similarity under UV-Vis-IR optical assessment.

Article highlights

1. Both laboratory and field trialing have been investigated for camouflage assessment of Cr oxide-coated textiles.
2. A proposal for UV-Vis-IR camouflage textiles has been demonstrated against woodland combat background.
3. Cr oxide-coated textiles have been found camouflage against selected woodland combat materials.
4. Hyperspectral camera, infrared camera and digital camera have been implemented for UV-Vis-IR surveillance in terms of defence protection in UV-Vis-IR spectrums.
5. The optical mechanism of camouflage physics has been represented in UV-Vis-IR spectrums.

Keywords: Camouflage textiles, camouflage mechanism, combat background, hyperspectral imaging, digital imaging, UV-Visible-NIR.

1 Introduction

Nature is the source of research idea. The concept of camouflaging against a natural background is not a new starting point in research. The natural camouflaging technique of the chameleon

exists in nature. Thermoregulation versus optical physics of skin pigmentation related to the aggregation of pigment in organelles in dermal chromatophore. The skin layers of high and low refractive index materials (guanine: 1.83, cytoplasm:1.33) are responsible for the photonic response in UV-Vis-NIR spectra (*Teyssier et al., 2015; Vatankhah-Varnosfaderani et al., 2018*). Intrinsically and progressively, defence research on camouflage technologies have already been expanded into multidimensional spectrums (*Hossain, 2023ai*). Ultraviolet (UV)-visible (Vis)-infrared (IR) reflection of chromium oxide has similarities with Australian grass, *Bothriochloa Pertusa*; a common material of woodland combat background (CB). Cr pigment shows higher absorbance in the Vis range and maximum reflection in the IR range. For woodland camouflage textiles, the imaging properties of woodland CB should be matched with the reflection profile of pigment-coated textiles. Generally, green pigment and Cr oxide are considered ‘synthetic chlorophyll’ which is responsible for the symmetric chromatic profile of green plants in woodland CB (*Gupta et al., 2016; Hossain, 2023ch; Jose et al., 2019; YingGao et al., 2021*). Camera imaging and the intensity of the target signature are related to photon movements. A photon is massless, chargeless, and moves at the speed of light. The optical mechanism of a photon is represented by the Equ.1 and Equ.2,

$$E = mc^2 \quad \text{Equ. 1}$$

$$E = hv = hc/\lambda \quad \text{Equ. 2}$$

Where E is the electron energy, relativistic mass m, λ is the wavelength, c is the speed of the light wave and h is the plank constant. Photon energy forms imaging signal scanned by a digital camera or hyperspectral camera, carries energy from the target signature to the light source on its intensity, and generates imaging of the target object against CB (*Johansson, ingvar.johansson@philos.umu.se; Tan, 1997*). The distribution of frequencies and intensities of the camera lens allows for image formation. The travel time of a photon between the target signature and the camera light source can alter the target imaging (*"New photon-counting camera captures 3D images with record speed and resolution," 2020*). Hyperspectral versus textile imaging is a new concept of concealment, detection, recognition, and identification (CDRI) for the development of camouflage textiles against CB. Hyperspectral analysis is very new for textile applications and very limited in the literature. Camouflage analysis with a hyperspectral camera is also innovative but very limited in the literature. Therefore, camouflage assessment techniques and right camouflage materials identification may protect the special force of defense for concealment of target signatures against high-performance imaging. Figure 1 summarizes and displays the graphical overview of the article in the vein of camouflage mechanism for camouflage textiles.

Figure 1. Graphical overview of the article on Cr oxide-coated woodland camouflage textiles.

Camouflage material design, aluminium coated textiles (*Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a*), optical properties of carbon black nano particle (*Hossain, 2023am*), carbon black pigment (*M. A. Hossain, 2021c*), Cr oxide coated textiles(*Hossain, 2023ap*) , NPND (natural plant based natural dyes) material (*A. Hossain, 2020; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; Hossain, 2023ci; M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018*), NSSD (natural sand based silicon dioxide) material , adaptive camouflage materials (*M. A. Hossain, 2021a*), thermochromic camouflage textiles (*M. A. Hossain, 2021a*), spectral simulation versus material design (*Hossain, 2023ch*), method design of camouflage assessment (*A. Hossain, 2021c*), suitability of material selection, reflection properties of material for CDRI, color properties of materials for CDRI, hyperspectral imaging and RGB imaging for CDRI, CDRI process for camouflage assessment (*A. Hossain, 2021a*), adaptive camouflage textiles (*M. A. Hossain, 2021a*), color engineering for camouflage textiles, optical engineering for camouflage assessment, camouflage engineering against multidimensional combat backgrounds such as dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark-woodland combat background; water-marine combat background; sand-desertland combat background; stone-stoneland combat background; snow-snowland combat background; sky combat background and ice-iceland combat background, concrete-concreteland combat background (DGTWSICB) , camouflage formulation and textile coloration (*Hossain, 2015a, 2015c, 2023ak, 2023al; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019; Samanta et al., 2016*), advanced defence and surveillance application (*Hossain, 2023ai*), polyamide 6,6 fabric (*Hossain, 2010a; M. A. Hossain, 2021c; Hossain, 2023am, 2023aw*) for camouflage coloration, simultaneous combat background, simultaneous spectrums in UV-Vis-IR (*M. A. Hossain, 2021c*), chromatic and achromatic assessment of camouflage textiles (*Md Anowar Hossain, 2022*), optical engineering , desertland combat background and woodland combat background (*Hossain, 2023ci*) are being upgraded for the invention and expansion in the field of defense engineering (*Hossain, 2023ao*). Figure 1 reflects the assessment and application of camouflage engineering focused on both in laboratory and field trialing.

2 Experimental Design of Materials and Methodologies

2.1 Cr oxide coating on PA-6,6 fabric

130 gram per square metre (g/m^2) polyamide 6,6 (PA-6,6) fabric was selected for this experimentation. Cr oxide was used as alternative of synthetic chlorophyll. Chromacryl binder, polyurethane-based tubicoat (PU-tubicoat) (*M. A. Hossain, 2021c*), a combination of thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU), and N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) were experimented as synthetic binder. A coating paste was prepared with Cr oxide and chromacryl/PU-tubicoat binder/TPU-DMF in a ratio of 1:1 and coated with different techniques. Machine coating, scrubber coating, dip coating and padding methods were followed for making a thin layer of Cr oxide on PA-6,6 fabric surface in the sample development stage (*Hossain, 2023am*).

2.2 Sample preparation for hyperspectral scanning

Table 1, a “red leaf marker 707” made in Japan was used for reddish tone ‘circular area’ and a “good luck marker” made in Bangladesh was implemented for black tone ‘circular area’ on uncoated PA-6,6 fabric. The color properties of selected markers were unknown. Cotton yarn stitched-two-layer PA-6,6-Cr oxide-coated and cotton yarn stitched-two-layer PA-6,6-uncoated fabric were used for hyperspectral scanning. Cotton yarn stitched-two-layer PA-6,6 uncoated and cotton dyed fabric was also designed and standardized for hyperspectral scanning (*Hossain, 2010c*).

Table 1, sample preparation for hyperspectral scanning and CDRI assessment

Sample identification (SID)	Front layer fabric	Back layer fabric	Two-layer fabric joint by front layer and back layer
SID-1 	Uncoated PA-6,6 fabric marked with circular area	Uncoated PA-6,6 fabric	Cotton yarn stitched-two-layer PA-6,6 fabric
SID-2 	Uncoated PA-6,6 fabric	Uncoated PA-6,6 fabric marked with circular area	Cotton yarn stitched-two-layer PA-6,6 fabric
SID-3 	Red color dyed cotton fabric	Uncoated PA-6,6 fabric marked with circular area	Cotton yarn stitched-two-layer fabric of raw PA-6,6 fabric and dyed cotton fabric
SID-4 	Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric	Uncoated PA-6,6 fabric marked with circular area	Cotton yarn stitched-two-layer raw PA-6,6 fabric and Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric
SID-5 	Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric	Uncoated PA-6,6 fabric marked with circular area	Cotton yarn stitched-two-layer raw PA-6,6 fabric and Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric

2.3 Sample collection and preparation of Australian grass, *Bothriochloa Pertusa*; and Eucalyptus tree, *Eucalyptus Mannifera*, as specified sample of the woodland CB

A formal identification of selected Australian grass, *Bothriochloa Pertusa*; and Eucalyptus tree, *Eucalyptus Mannifera* as specified sample of woodland CB by looking foremost properties such as aesthetic appearance, woody stem, root and branches, leaf shape and size, leaf arrangement; and followed general guideline of sample collection applied for this experimentation (*A.*

Hossain, 2020; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018). The average height of the grass sample was selected for this experimentation. Australian grass, *Bothriochloa Pertusa* was used for reflection measurement of woodland CB for comparison with synthetic chlorophyll-coated PA-6,6 fabric. For imaging measurement of *Bothriochloa Pertusa*, fresh green grasses were cut, washed, water extracted, and dried at 40°C for 30 minutes and tested after 4 hours. Fresh green grasses were collected from Princes Park, Melbourne during September-November 2021. Fresh grasses were dried with the natural illumination of sunlight at a window for around three months during September-November 2021(Hossain, 2023ci). Similarly; green leaves, dry leaves, tree bark of *Eucalyptus Mannifera*; Princes Park, Melbourne were collected, prepared and used for the chromatic and reflection references of woodland CB. Green leaves, semi-dried green leaves, dried leaves, dried tree bark were trialed as part of woodland CB materials. First samples of woodland CB materials were collected in Australian Summer, December-February 2020-21 and second samples of woodland CB were collected in Australian Spring, September-November 2021.

2.4 Exemption notes for Australian grass, *Bothriochloa Pertusa* collection, and approval for the assessment as woodland CB materials

A minimum amount (around 200 g) of *Bothriochloa Pertusa* and *Eucalyptus Mannifera* including ‘agricultural waste’ (Linhares & Amorim, 2016) was collected from non-commercial sources and applied for non-commercial application. All experiments were conducted in accordance with relevant regulations and guidelines under the academic platform of camouflage research at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. Therefore, permission of sample collection for *Bothriochloa Pertusa* and *Eucalyptus Mannifera* is not required. This exemption is supported by ‘3.1.2, assessment requirement’ for collection of *Bothriochloa Pertusa* and *Eucalyptus Mannifera* samples quoted below, registered research located in Australia:

“A permit is not required to collect native plant material from private land unless: the species for collection are listed as threatened species or form part of a threatened ecological community under the environment protection and biodiversity conservation (EPBC) Act; under such circumstances, a Commonwealth permit may be required.” (*Native Plant Material Collection Standard; Department of Environment and Heritage, Government of South Australia; National Parks and Wildlife Act, 1972,* 2007)

2.5 Imaging of scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

A table microscope SEM machine was used for electron imaging. TM4000/TM4000Plus, Hitachi, Japan, and SC7620 sputter coater, Quorum, UK were used as the set-up of SEM. 100-magnification SEM imaging was captured by 15KV power selection. In this experiment, 15KV×8.8 mm×500 BSE (back scattered electron) and 15KV×9.8 mm×500 BSE were detected to form SEM image, although the exact brightness or dullness of the material depends on the atomic number in general. Auto contrast imaging was generated to magnify the Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric surface for comparison with uncoated PA-6,6 fabric.

2.6 Color measurement with spectrophotometer

PA-6,6 fabric and woodland combat materials were scanned by colorflex EZ spectrophotometer, Hunter lab EasyMatchQC software under the conditions of viewing area geometry: 45°/0°, photometric reflectance: (0-150)%, port dia: 31.8 mm, view dia: 25.4 mm, light source pulsed xenon, number of layers of fabric: 2.

2.7 Imaging/scanning method of the hyperspectral camera in the IR spectrum at 1000-2500 nm

Figure 2 and Table 1: a hyperspectral camera, SWIR-384, from Raymax Application Ltd. was used for the testing of CDRI properties in laboratory. The lens was a 30 cm focal lens, and the working distance between the camera and textile sample was kept and fixed at 208 millimeters. Every scan of the hyperspectral camera captured the full wavelength of the spectrums. The hyperspectral camera captured 288 bands in the full wavelength of the spectrums, as shown in the supporting information in Table SI 1. The camera was calibrated to measure 288 bands in the wavelength region from 1000 nm to 2500 nm. The closest bands of 1000 (1000.292), 1300 (1301.079), 1600 (1600.866), 1900 (1900.653), 2200 (2200.441), and 2500 nanometers (nm) (2500. 228) were recorded for joint photographic expert group (jpeg) images of the target signature and spectral data information. Each scan was captured including all bands. Each pixel captured includes the full wavelength of the spectrum (*Jianxin et al., 2020*). There was a one-line time frame taken every 30,000 microseconds (μ s) under a stage linear speed of approximately 0.822 cm/sec. Within the time frame of the hyperspectral camera, the integration time was adjusted by two different μ s for the correct imaging signal of PA-6,6 fabric. The timeframe of 7,500 μ s was scanned for the imaging of PA-6,6 uncoated fabric, denoted as PA-6,6 fabric sample-1 and PA-6,6 fabric sample-2. If 10,500 μ s was used for Cr oxide-uncoated PA-6,6 fabric, too many photons would reach the sensor, and the signal would be saturated. A 10,500 μ s timeframe was also selected for imaging of Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric, PA-6,6 fabric sample-3, and PA-6,6 fabric sample-4. When using 7,500 μ s, the Cr oxide-coated fabric was remarked as almost invisible; it was not capturing enough photons for the hyperspectral camera sensor, and the signal would be too low to identify the target object (TOB). The signal level for each wavelength on the images is displayed according to the international commission on illumination (CIE) red, green, and blue (RGB) color scale, where the intensity of the blue hue demonstrates the minimum photon signal and the intensity of the red signifies the maximum photon response to the sensor of the hyperspectral camera. Figure 2 and Table 1: each image and selection of pixels were focused for high contrast. The aperture was expanded to allow more photons to reach the sample, capturing correct signal for the hyperspectral camera. The sensor of the hyperspectral camera was adjusted with an aperture duration of 10,500 μ s to obtain a strong enough photon and maximum pixel saturation from Cr oxide-coated textiles. The hyperspectral camera room was kept a little darker to reduce possible interference with data acquisition. The temperature of the scanning moment was kept at room temperature, around 20°C. Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) was captured around 45° angles to the fabric surface (*A. Hossain, 2021c; Hossain, 2009; M. A. Hossain, 2021a*). HSI was captured by the line scanning method of the hyperspectral camera. A middle line absorption value was implemented for the generation of a graphical correlation between absorption versus wavelength at 1000, 1300, 1600, 1900, 2200, and 2500 nm. The whole absorption value of PA-6,6 fabric samples-01, 02, 03, and 04 scanned by a hyperspectral camera at 1000, 1300, 1600, 1900, 2200, and 2500 nm has been shown in the supporting information in Table SI 2-25.

2.8 Imaging/scanning method of the hyperspectral camera in the Vis spectrums at 400-700 nm

Figure 2 and Table 1: Hyperspectral camera setting and testing conditions in laboratory were recorded for uncoated PA-6,6 fabric (a), Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric (b, c) and test samples before scanning (d). A standardized color scales blue to red (EF) was followed for hyperspectral

imaging. In general, similar observations of IR-HSI were followed for Vis-TOB. This scanning was evaluated by a hyperspectral camera at 400 nm, 500 nm, 600 nm, and 700 nm. HySpex VNIR-1800 was used with a 30 cm focal length. The integration time was applied at 22,948 μ s for every sample measurement. A base fabric PA-6,6, a red color standardized cotton fabric, and Cr oxide-coated-padded PA-6,6 fabric were scanned with Vis-HSI. A standardized red color cotton fabric was used for comparison of reddish tone intensity with Cr oxide-coated and uncoated PA-6,6 fabric in Vis-HSI (M. A. Hossain, 2021a).

Figure 2. Hyperspectral camera setting, fabric sample preparation and scanning conditions in laboratory (a, b, c, d) and hyperspectral scanning scale captured by hyperspectral camera (EF).

2.9 Vis-infrared (IR) camera scanning methods

Assessment of Vis-IR capture was followed by a standard Equ. 3 for the measurement of the photonic response through the imaging signal of Cr oxide-coated fabric against woodland CB, *Bothriochloa Pertusa* and *Eucalyptus Mannifera*.

$$D/S = SSR \quad \text{Equ. 3}$$

Where, D = distance from the camera to the target, S = smallest target dimension of OB, SSR = spot size ratio. The measurement was executed in a D65-UV background ‘light box’ under the protection of outside interference of light. A forward-looking infrared (FLIR) T440 thermal imaging camera, USA; IR lens, focal length (F) = 18 millimeters; calibrated by the national institute of standards and technology (NIST), USA; IR range: 900-14000 nm (approximately) was used for this experimentation of FLIR imaging. The standardized reflectance of black, green, and white backgrounds was used for UV-Vis-IR optical assessment (O’Donnell et al., 2010). Figure 3 shows the standardized chromatic value of standard tiles, experimented for the optical assessment of UV-Vis-IR-TOB-CB (Hossain, 2009).

Figure 3. Standard tiles of black, green, and white background (left) captured by RGB imaging and their color combination of L*, a*, and b* (right).

A field trial of Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric was performed against woodland CB, at grassy ground at RMIT University Campus under the natural illumination of sunlight (A. Hossain, 2021a; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a). A combined ‘dry grass’ and ‘green grass’ of woodland CB was selected for field trailing. The distance between the target-coated fabric and the FLIR camera was kept 18 inches. Practically, there is a possible deviation between the FLIR captured temperature and the original temperature of the captured environment, although FLIR captured temperature was recorded and standardized for imaging properties.

3 Results and Discussion

Figures 4-16: optical phenomenon between target signatures and combat materials is the mechanism of CDRI. Light wave of sunlight and light wave of imaging device control the rotational state and oscillating state of the particles in target materials and combat materials in the UV-Vis-IR spectrums. The rotational state can not be controlled due to the oscillation of the light wave for the optical response between the target signature and combat material. The optical physics of camouflage relates to the electric field behavior of target signatures and combat materials. The polarizability of materials is the optical variation in terms of transmission, absorption, reflection, scattering, refractive index, heat, and optical interference. Therefore, the oscillation of materials tends to cause the light propagation of target signatures and combat materials to the sensor of electric field generation and sensing electrons in the imaging device. Energy generation can also be defined by the particle size of materials shown in Equ. 4,

$$x = 2\pi r/\lambda \quad \text{Equ. 4}$$

Where x is a dimensionless parameter that determines the interaction of energy generation in the target signature and combat materials, r is the particle radius, and λ is the wavelength. Rayleigh scattering (RC) is inversely proportional to the fourth power of wavelength (λ) shown in Equ. 5,

$$RC = \lambda^{-4} \quad \text{Equ. 5}$$

Rayleigh found that a shorter wavelength is more scattered than a longer wavelength. For sun light, blue light is more scattered than red light when the sky is blue. The theory had a limitation when the blue color of the sky was considered for the theory of Rayleigh scattering. There is variation in the sky color and the intensity of sun light. These optical interferences tend to the variation for the consideration of CDR. Practically, the chromatic intensity of the red color is more scattered than the blue color. When the particle size is lower, the light scattering will be higher, the wavelength tends to lower, the chromatic intensity of red will be higher. Oppositely, when the particle size is higher, the light scattering will be lower, the wavelength tends to higher, the chromatic intensity of blue will be higher. Mie theory of scattering states that the particle diameter or geometry (d) changes with the replacement of wavelengths (λ). The relation of CDRI in UV-Vis-IR may be equated and shown in Equ. 6,

$$d \propto \lambda \quad \text{Equ. 6}$$

As a result of the refractive index, it is also a matter of wave deviation versus the photonic response. The polarization of the sky may vibrate the electron signal of the electric field of the

target signature and CBs. The resonance of the wave signal between the target signature and CBs generates a symmetric frequency for the sensor. The wavelength (λ) of a photon relates to the speed of light and frequency of light shown in Equ.7,

$$\lambda = c/v \quad \text{Equ. 7}$$

Where, c is the speed of the light wave and v is the frequency of the light wave. The electron energy relates to the Equ.8,

$$E = hv \quad \text{Equ. 8}$$

Where, h is the plank constant and v is the frequency of the light wave. The phenomenon of electric field in UV-Vis-IR can be ordered as: energy generation in UV spectrums > energy generation in Vis spectrums > energy generation in IR spectrums. Hence, the photonic responses to imaging devices can also be sequenced as: the photonic response in UV spectrums > the photonic response in Vis spectrums > the photonic response in IR spectrums. Optical interference may create ups and downs of the wavelength, there is also influence in photonic response. It can be equated by the relation between electron energy (E) and wavelength (λ), shown in Equ. 9.

$$E \propto 1/\lambda \quad \text{Equ. 9}$$

The deviation of E in the UV-Vis-IR spectrums between Cr oxide-coated textiles and combat materials signifies the CDRI.

Figure 4. Optical mechanism of camouflage physics in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for concealment, detection, recognition & identification of target signature against CB.

Figures 4-16: in general, it is clearly signified and correlated that the temperature of the target signature, Cr oxide-coated textiles, and woodland CB materials influences the energy state (E) at the UV-Vis-IR spectrums. The heating mechanism changes the vibrational state from the minimum (19°C) to maximum (60°C) level. Hence, the chromatic intensity of electron imaging in UV-Vis-IR altered through energy deviation as per the established quantum mechanics shown in Equ. 10 and 11 (Johansson, ingvar.johansson@philos.umu.se; Tan, 1997). Where E is the electron energy, relativistic mass m, λ is the wavelength, c is the speed of the light wave and h is the plank constant.

$$E = mc^2 \quad \text{Equ. 10}$$

$$E = hv = hc/\lambda \quad \text{Equ. 11}$$

Therefore, the mechanism of absorption, transmission, and reflection of PA-6,6-Cr oxide-formulated fabric against woodland CB has been instigated for the optical assessment of camouflage textiles in the UV-Vis-IR spectrums (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a).

Figure 5. SEM image of uncoated PA-6,6 fabric (a) and SEM image of Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric (b).

3.1 Imaging of SEM

Figure 5b, Cr oxide-PU has been well cemented to the PA-6,6 fabric surface. Because of the white chromatic hue, PU presence has been depicted on the PA-6,6 fabric surface, but the maximum percentage of PU has been overlapped by the Cr oxide deposition. The imaging of electron microscopy has confirmed the chromatic replacement when PA-6,6 fabric was coated with Cr oxide. The electron imaging has also indicated the lower reflection of Cr oxide-coated fabric due to the darker chromatic hue. The electron imaging of Cr oxide-coated fabric has been assumed to be similar to the electron imaging of woodland CB material, *Bothriochloa Pertusa* and *Eucalyptus Mannifera* (A. Hossain, 2021b). Therefore, the existing Cr oxide molecule has been approached to have a tendency toward chromatic matching with woodland CB materials, *Bothriochloa Pertusa* and *Eucalyptus Mannifera*.

3.2 Chromatic analysis of Cr oxide coated textiles against combat materials of *Eucalyptus Mannifera* in Vis spectrums from 400-700 nm

Figure 6, the chromatic deviation between Cr oxide coated PA-6,6 fabric and green leaves of *Eucalyptus Mannifera* have been found more color matching with green leaves rather than dry leaves and tree bark. The chromatic properties of L*, a*, b* of Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric displays chromatic matching against green leaves of *Eucalyptus Mannifera* due to the existing Cr element in green leaves of woodland CB material. Figure 7, the reddish curve of Cr oxide coated PA-6,6 fabric is almost showing the nearest reflection of green leaves. The reflection property has (2-5)% deviation between Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric and green leaves of woodland CB. Accordingly, the reflection of dry leaves and tree bark is also crossing with the nearest graphical

lines of Cr oxide coated-padded textiles. The spectral reflection has higher deviation of dry leaves-2 from 550 nm to 700 nm. Possibly, the deviation of reflection of dry leaves-2 relates to the leaves structure and scattering of light in different direction. Figure 8, the red dotted line shows the Kubelka-Munk (K-M) reflection of Cr oxide coated PA-6,6 fabric. K-M reflection has deviation (2-5) at 520 nm to 570 nm. K-M reflection has also deviation (2-20) at 520 nm to 570 nm and 570 nm to 700 nm. K-M reflection relates to the layer density of existing Cr oxide on fabric. Uncoated PA-6,6 fabric shows zero K-M reflection. Hence, the curve of PA-6,6 untreated fabric touching the baseline of graph due to the nil density of Cr oxide on PA-6,6 fabric surface.

Figure 6. Color profile of Cr oxide coated and uncoated PA-6,6 fabric against the materials of woodland CB.

Figure 7. (0-150)% reflection (machine standard) profile of Cr oxide coated and uncoated PA-6,6 fabric against the materials of woodland CB.

Figure 8. K-M reflection of Cr oxide coated and uncoated PA-6,6 fabric against the materials of woodland CB.

3.3 Target assessment of PA-6,6 fabric samples-01, 02, 03, and 04; imaging phase-1 (Vis-HSI, 400-700 nm, optical assessment)

Figure 9. Comparison of Vis-RGB imaging-HSI under different formulations of PA-6,6 fabric in wavelength from 400 nm to 700 nm; Vis-RGB imaging (a, f, k, p, u); Vis image of hyperspectral camera at 400 nm (b, g, l, q, v), 500 nm (c, h, m, r, w); 600 (d, i, n, s, x), and 700 nm (e, j, o, t, y).

Figures 9a, 9f are the uncoated PA-6,6 fabric. Figure 9k shows cotton fabric to remark the reddish intensity for comparison in Vis-HSI. Figures 9p and 9u show the Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6

fabric under two different formulations of coating. 9p shows whitish surface due to the presence of chromacryl binder. In figure 9a, back layer of PA-6,6 fabric was marked by ‘circular area’ with a combination of black and red colors. Figure 9f: the front layer of PA-6,6 fabric was marked by ‘circular area’ with a combination of black and red colors. Figure 9k, back layer of PA-6,6 fabric was marked by ‘circular area’ with a combination of black and red colors. Similarly, figures 9p and 9u; back layer of PA-6,6 fabric was marked by ‘circular area’ with a combination of black and red colors. Figures 9b, 9g, 9i, 9q, and 9v are shown as HSI at 400 nm. Figures 9c, 9h, 9m, 9r, and 9w are marked as HSI at 500 nm. Figures 9d, 9i, 9n, 9s, and 9x are the HSI at 600 nm. Figures 9e, 9j, 9o, 9t, and 9y are identified as HSI at 700 nm. In Vis-HSI, the intensity of black and red ‘circular area’ was detected at 400 nm, figure 9b; at 500 nm, figure 9c; at 600 nm, figure 9d; and at 700 nm figure 9e; but the chromaticity was gradually declining from 400 nm to 700 nm, shown in figures 9b-9c-9d-9e. Similarly, the intensity of black and red, ‘circular area’ was identified at 400 nm, figure 9g; at 500 nm, figure 9h; at 600 nm, figure 9i; and at 700 nm figure 9j but the chromaticity response was gradually weakened from 400 nm to 700 nm, shown in figures 9g-9h-9i-9j. A different chromaticity was visualized at 400 nm, figure 9g and at 500 nm, figure 9h due to the deviation of chromatic intensity. As PA-6,6 fabric has circular cross section, it may have reflection at different angle^(Gupta et al., 2016), the chromatic intensity of ‘circular area’ has also been scattered with background reflection. Hence, the intensity of uncoated PA-6,6 image was almost nil due to the chromaticity signal of Vis-HSI. Figures 9b-9c-9d-9e and 9g-9h-9i-9j; the intensity of black and red chromatic hue was comparatively higher in Vis-HSI, chromaticity assessment was classified on white background, uncoated PA-6,6 fabric. Figure 9o, the chromatic intensity of red background was also higher for standardized red color fabric at 700 nm. Figures 9q-9r-9s-9t and 9v-9w-9x-9y; the intensity of Cr oxide-coated fabric was observed bluish chromatic hue when the Cr oxide was tended to higher in digital imaging shown in figures 9p, 9u. The intensity of back layer ‘circular area’ was completely nil due to the chromaticity signal in Vis-HSI. The intensity of Cr element was completely nil due to the minimum photonic response to the hyperspectral sensor. Hence, the chromatic intensity of Cr oxide-coated fabric was also invisible due to the minimum photonic response to the hyperspectral sensor. The ‘circular mark’ object was concealed due to the greenish reflection of Cr oxide-coated fabric when the backside layer of Cr oxide-coated fabric was also marked with ‘circular area’. Cr oxide-coated fabric has been depicted less reflection to the sensor of hyperspectral camera. Therefore, lower chromatic intensity of Cr oxide in Vis-HSI has been depicted, Cr oxide-coated fabric was compared with woodland CB for the next stage assessment of field trialing.

3.4 Target assessment on PA-6,6 fabric sample-01, imaging phase-2 (IR-HSI, 1000-2500 nm optical assessment)

Figure 10: PA-6,6 fabric background shows the minimum absorption in every spectrum from 1000 nm to 2500 nm. Absorption is higher at 2200 nm and 2500 nm, and comparatively lower absorption is found at 1000-1900 nm, which may signify the lowest reflection of PA-6,6 fabric at 2200 nm and 2500 nm, and comparatively higher reflection is recorded at 1000-1900 nm, as shown in figure 10a, 10b. A gradual decline of reflection has been depicted due to the higher absorbency at 2500 nm and lower absorbency at 1000, 1300, 1600, and 1900 nm. The reflection of the chromatic hue of the red and black circles has been found to be remarkable at 1000-1900 nm. The signified circle has been concealed at 2200 nm and 2500 nm due to the minor photonic signal in IR-HSI. At 2500 nm, there is nil chromatic signal has been detected. It has been confirmed that PA-6,6 fabric and its remarked area of ‘circular mark’ have no identification at

2500 nm. Due to the high reflection of PA-6,6 fabric, the reflection on the IR-HSI has been classified as a concealed object from 1600 nm to 2500 nm. A scattered reflection of a ‘reddish circle’ tone has been identified on the fabric surface from 1000 nm to 2200 nm due to the deviation of the photonic response. The circular reddish tone has been smashed with the base area of the bluish tone due to the movement of photonic responses in IR, but the ‘circular area’ of the reddish tone is almost invisible. The intensity of the black circle is gradually decreasing from 1000 nm to 1900 nm. Furthermore, as the surrounding area of fabric was stitched with 100% cotton yarn, which is also illuminating with higher absorption, it seems a low reflection signal of cotton yarn in the photonic response of IR-HSI.

Figure 10. PA-6,6 fabric with black and red marked ‘circular area’ in the front layer is shown in Vis-RGB imaging at 400-700 nm (a), scanned and shown in IR-HSI at 1000-2500 nm (a), and accordingly shown in IR-HSI absorption spectra at 1000-2500 nm (b).

3.5 Target assessment on PA-6,6 fabric sample-02, imaging phase-3 (IR-HSI, 1000-2500 nm optical assessment)

Figure 11: black circle is identified at 1000 nm and concealed at 1300, 1600, 1900, 2200, and 2500 nm. Absorption is gradually increased from 1000 nm to 2500 nm, and sequentially, it seems that reflection remarkably decreases at 2500 nm. The red circle is scattered and smashed with the base area from 1000 nm to 2200 nm. Hence, the red circle is completely concealed at 1000, 1300, 1600, 1900, 2200, and 2500 nm. A nil-reflection tendency has been noted at 2500 nm. A gradual declining in reflection has been depicted due to the higher absorbency at 2500 nm and lower absorbency at 1000, 1300, 1600, 1900 and 2200 nm.

Figure 11. PA-6,6 fabric with black and red marked ‘circular area’ in the back layer of fabric is shown in Vis-RGB imaging at 400-700 nm (a), scanned and shown in IR-HSI at 1000-2500 nm (a), and accordingly shown in IR-HSI absorption spectra at 1000-2500 nm (b).

3.6 Target assessment on Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric sample-03, imaging phase-4 (IR-HSI, 1000-2500 nm optical assessment)

Figure 12: Cr oxide-coated fabric creates concealed of backside signature of black and red colors, but the chromatic intensity of the reddish signature is prominent from 1000 nm to 2200 nm. Due to lack of reddish combination, the Cr oxide-coated fabric is completely bluish at 2500 nm, it means the invisible surface of Cr oxide-coated surface. A gradual decline of the reflection has been depicted due to the higher absorbency at 2500 nm and lower absorbency at 1000, 1300, 1600, 1900 and 2200 nm.

Figure 12. Cr oxide coated PA-6,6 fabric with black and red marked ‘circular area’ in the back layer of fabric is shown in Vis-RGB imaging at 400-700 nm (a), scanned and shown in IR-HSI at 1000-2500 nm (a), and accordingly shown in IR-HSI absorption spectra at 1000-2500 nm (b).

3.7 Target assessment on Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric sample-04, imaging phase-5 (IR-HSI, 1000-2500 nm optical assessment)

Figure 13: black and red marked ‘circular area’ is completely concealed by the Cr oxide-coated fabric. The tonal area of the red circle has been scattered at 1000, 1300, 1600 and 1900 nm. There is no effect of the black marked area at 1000 to 2500 nm and red marked area at 2200 and 2500 nm. In general, a light greenish intensity has been observed in IR range at 1000-2500 nm due to the chromatic intensity.

Figure 13. Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric with black and red marked ‘circular area’ in the back layer of fabric surface is shown in Vis-IR-HSI at 1000-2500 nm (a), scanned and shown in IR-HSI at 1000-2500 nm (a), and accordingly shown in IR-HSI absorption spectra at 1000-2500 nm (b).

Figure 13: the Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 background shows the minimum absorption in every spectrum from 1000 nm to 2500 nm. The absorption is higher at 2200 and 2500 nm, and comparatively lower absorption is found at 1000-1900 nm, which may signify the lowest reflection of PA-6,6 fabric at 2200 and 2500 nm, and the oppositely highest reflection is recorded at 1000-1900 nm, as shown in figures 13a, 13b. A gradual decline of reflection has been depicted due to the higher absorption at 2200 and 2500 nm, and the lower absorption at 1000, 1300, 1600, and 1900 nm. The reflection of the chromatic hue of the ‘red and black circle’ has found to be remarkable at 1000-1900 nm. The signified circle has been concealed at 2200 and 2500 nm due to the minor photonic signal in IR-HSI. At 2500 nm, no chromatic signal has been detected. It has been confirmed that PA-6,6 fabric and its remarked area have no identification at 2200 and 2500 nm. The reflection to the IR-HSI has been classified as a concealed object of ‘circular area’ from 1000 nm to 2500 nm. A scattered reflection of the reddish circle tone has been identified on the fabric surface from 1000 nm to 1900 nm. As the surrounding area of fabric was stitched with 100% cotton yarn which is also illuminating as higher absorption of the HSI scanned line, it seems a low reflection signal of cotton yarn in IR-HSI at 1000-2500 nm.

3.8 Target assessment of Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric against dry grass, woodland CB, *Bothriochloa Pertusa*; imaging phase-6 (digital imaging in UV-Vis-IR optical assessment)

Figures 14a and 14b: the chromatic intensity of dry grass of woodland CB has been found to have a concealment effect under the optical assessment of D65-UV-Vis rather than exceptional at white background. Figures 14c, 14d, 14e, and 14f; under D65-IR optical assessment, TOB is detected as a bluish chromatic hue due to the deviation of dry grass reflection and synthetic chlorophyll or Cr oxide existing on PA-6,6 fabric surface but the chromatic intensity is almost similar. TOB has been found to be concealed under the low temperature at 19.3°C, and increasing the temperature gradually differentiates the TOB and woodland CB material under D65 background at 25.5°C, 29.4°C and 57.3°C. Figures 14g, 14h, and 14i; similarly, TOB is

concealed under low temperature at 20.3°C and the TOB is detected under high temperature at 42.7°C and 56.6°C under UV-IR lighting assessment.

Figure 14. Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric placed on woodland CB material, dry grass, *Bothriochloa Pertusa* in the Vis- RGB imaging-IR imaging for CDRI assessment under D65 and UV lighting; D65 background Vis-RGB image (a); UV background Vis-RGB image (b); D65 background IR image (c, d, e, f); UV background IR image (g, h, i).

3.9 Target assessment on Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric against green grass, woodland CB, *Bothriochloa Pertusa*; imaging phase-7 (digital imaging in UV-Vis-IR optical assessment)

Figure 15. Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric placed on woodland CB material, green grass, *Bothriochloa Pertusa* in the Vis-RGB imaging-IR imaging for CDRI assessment from low to high temperature ranges at 28.6°C, 30.0°C, 30.7°C, 33.1°C, 57.2°C, and 60.9°C under D65 and UV lighting; D65 background Vis-RGB imaging

(a); UV background Vis-RGB imaging (b); D65 background IR imaging (c, d, e); UV background IR imaging (f, g, h).

Figure 15a shows Vis image of a D65 background, and figure 15b shows Vis image of a UV background. Figures 15c, 15d, and 15e show IR images of D65 background at 30.7°C, 57.2°C, and 60.9°C. Figures 15f, 15g, and 15h identify the IR image of the UV background at 28.6°C, 30.0°C, and 33.1°C. Figures 15a and 15b: both D65-UV backgrounds appeared the chromatically matching with the green grass background in Vis imaging. Figures 15c, 15d, and 15e: Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric shows the matching of the chromatic appearance with the woodland CB without color difference between TOB and CB materials at different temperatures of IR imaging in D65-UV backgrounds. In the photochemical process, Cr is a major element of green grass in woodland CB. Hence, Cr is responsible for the chromatic matching between woodland CB and Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric. The concealment of Cr oxide-coated fabric has been found prominent for its application in UV-Vis-IR imaging.

Figure 16. Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric placed on Australian Grass (combined with dry grass, green grass and soil backgrounds), *Bothriochloa Pertusa*, captured by the Vis-RGB imaging-IR imaging at 17.6°C, 17.2°C, and 17.9°C under natural illumination in a sunny morning of sunlight at 11 November, 2021; Vis-RGB image (a); IR image (b, c, d).

3.10 Target assessment of Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric against green grass woodland CB, *Bothriochloa Pertusa*; imaging phase-8 (digital imaging in Vis-IR optical assessment); a field trial in the grassy ground at RMIT University campus

Figure 16a denotes the Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric, surrounded by uncoated PA-6,6 fabric, placed on a grass surface, a woodland CB. Figure 16b: grass surface generates yellowish and reddish chromaticity due to the light reflection of the soil background. A soil background is a comparatively heated surface than grasses. Similarly, Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric shows a yellowish and reddish color hue, which almost matches the chromaticity of the grass surface, a woodland CB. Figures 16c and 16d: the deviation of temperature, minimum temperature, and maximum temperature influence the spot temperature captured by the IR camera. It is also related to the chromatic hue of the black-to-white coordinates for the concealment and detection of the target signature.

4 Concluding remarks

The optical reflection and CIE-chromaticity of Australian grass, *Bothriochloa Pertusa*, woodland CB and Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric have been observed similarity under UV-Vis-IR optical assessment. An application of synthetic chlorophyll on PA-6,6 fabric can be developed for woodland camouflage textiles against hyperspectral or digital imaging in the UV-Vis-IR spectrum. Cr oxide-coated fabric has been found suitable for concealment against Australian grass, *Bothriochloa Pertusa* and *Eucalyptus Mannifera* due to the existing elements of Cr in green grass, although viewing geometry, sensor, or illumination type of hyperspectral or digital

camera may influence the chromatic and achromatic reflection on PA-6,6 fabric surface for CDRI versus optical assessment. It can be formulated that a photon carries energy or momentum from PA-6,6 fabric surface to the camera lens and generates frequency for imaging. Therefore, the frequency vibrates the photosensitive materials and sensors of the hyperspectral camera, which creates imaging of fabric surface. The direction of the photon may be replaced or controlled by the Cr oxide modification of the textile surface, which can be matched with woodland CB. Furthermore, this study is also extended for future research in different aspects of author.

1. The key advantage of Cr oxide-coated camouflage textiles is the chromatic blending with woodland background. The green camouflaging and Cr oxide coating has been prioritized and experimented in this manuscript. There are different color pigments of oxide such as brown oxide pigment, aluminium oxide, black oxide, iron oxide which can be selected, combined, moderated, trialed to make any combination against selected combat materials and CBs. For example: brown oxide and iron oxide pigment may be more suitable for the chromatic matching with dry leaves of tree, woody stem of tree and reddish color hilly soil of woodland background when dry leaves, woody stem and reddish color hilly soil are also necessary consideration for the camouflage design against woodland CB.
2. Camouflage tents, car cover, weapon cover, cap, and clothing can be developed to promote practical applications of Cr oxide-coated PA-6,6 fabric against woodland CB. Bulletproof camouflage fabric can also be coated by Cr oxide.
3. Raw PA-6,6 fabric may also be used for the design of parachute fabric of special team in defense. 100% uncolored PA-6,6 fabric may be camouflage at IR-HSI due to high reflection in selected range of scanning with HSI when the CB is sky.
4. The patterning principle of parachute fabric can also be implemented by black patterning or low reflection patterning on PA-6,6 fabric for concealment in IR and recognition in Vis. Conversely, defense identification of target signatures can be implemented by red patterning in Vis-IR-HSI.
5. There is also application scope in electroless plating. Cr oxide can also be applied for coating of defence weapon for the defence operation against woodland combat background.

Abbreviations and glossaries

CBs:	Combat backgrounds
CDRI:	Concealment, detection, recognition and identification
CIE:	International commission on illumination
Cr oxide:	Chromium oxide
D65:	CIE standard daylight illuminant
FLIR	Forward-looking infrared
HSI:	Hyperspectral imaging
IR:	Infrared
nm:	Nanometre
PA-6,6:	Polyamide-6,6
PU:	Polyurethane
SEM:	Scanning electron microscopy
TOB:	Target object
UV:	Ultraviolet
Vis:	Visible
µs:	Microseconds

K-M: Kubelka-Munk
SID: Sample identification

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Data availability statement

All data generated or analyzed during this experimentation is included in the supplementary information file in Table SI 1-25. Video of hyperspectral scanning has also been attached in the supplementary information, Video SI 1-4.

Peer review process of institutional review board, RMIT University, Australia

This manuscript was reviewed & passed by the two individual Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) committees of the School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University by the two individual conferences of the School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University by the two individual examinations of the first milestone and second milestones under institutional prerequisites of PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles), RMIT University, Australia.

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Author contribution and authorship status

The author is self-declaring the sole-authorship of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD, Defence Scientist in terms of conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, material managements, project administration, research communications, planning and prediction, experimentation, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

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Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Backgrounds of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine

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Abstract

Natural sand-based silicon dioxide (NSSD) is a common material of multidimensional combat backgrounds (CBs) such as dry leaves/wood, green leaves, tree bark-woodland CB; water-marine CB; sand-desertland CB; rock-rockland CB and concrete-concreteland CB. NSSD was coated, printed and padded on polyamide-6,6 (PA-6,6) and cotton fabric for design of camouflage textiles. NSSD coated and printed textiles have been found very innovative against desertland CB and partially adaptive against woodland, rockland, water/marine CB. The camouflage properties of coated, printed and padded fabric in visible (Vis) wavelength, 400-700 nm were investigated by international commission on illumination (CIE)-color value (L^* , a^* , b^*), Kubelka-Munk (K-M) reflection, reflection (%) and color rendering techniques of color measurement spectrophotometer. The structural properties versus electron imaging were examined by scanning electron microscopy. Electron imaging of scanning electron microscopy (SEM); intensities of grey values; color thresholding images; red, green, blue (RGB) color rendering signifies the chromatic and structural properties which relates to photonic signal to imaging device. Field trialling of NSSD treated camouflage textiles was investigated by Vis imaging under natural illumination, sunlight. The adaptive properties for CIE-chromatic appearance (red, green, blue, L^* , a^* , b^*) and grey value (0-255) of NSSD formulated fabric were analyzed by ImageJ software. This optical assessment of ecofriendly approach of NSSD-camouflage material relates to camouflage signature management for defence threat protection against five-dimensional combat background such as desertland, woodland, rockland, concreteland and water/marine.

Article Highlights

- Natural sand-based silicon dioxide (NSSD) coated textiles is an approach of nature friendly textiles, NSSD is a cheaper and antibacterial than synthetic dyes and coating materials applied to textile substances
- NSSD coated textiles have versatile applications in technical textiles, there is strong technical view of strength improvement
- NSSD can be applied for design of desertland camouflage textiles, rockland camouflage textiles and fashionable printing/design for ready-made garments

Keywords: Camouflage Textiles, Natural sand-based silicon dioxide, Combat backgrounds (CBs), Woodland CB, Desertland CB, Rockland CB, Concreteland CB, and Water/marine CB.

1 Introduction

Camouflage scientists have been suggested synthetic dyes, pigment, nano materials for designing of camouflage textiles in multidimensional spectrums. There is still lacking for achievement of ecofriendly approach of camouflage materials under multidimensional combat backgrounds (CBs) such as woodland, desertland, rockland, concreteland and water/marine. Natural plant-based natural dyes have been implemented for woodland combat background. Hence, there is also possibility of natural sand-based silicon dioxide (NSSD) for desertland camouflage textile applications (*Adeel et al.*; *Fazal-ur-Rehman et al., 2023*; *A. Hossain, 2020*; *A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018*; *A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018*; *M. A. Hossain, 2021a*; *Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c*; *Hossain, 2023c, 2023aj, 2023ap, 2023ci, 2023cj*; *M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018*; *M. A. Hossain et al., 2019*; *M. A. Hossain et al., 2018*; *Vitalija et al., 2009*). Silicon dioxide was coated on cotton fabric for achievement of antibacterial property against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* (*Barani, 2014*). Polypropylene non-woven fabric and polyester woven fabric showed UV protective performance when fabric was coated with silicon dioxide when the refractive index of silicon dioxide is 1.45 (*Huang et al., 2022*). NSSD-coating-printing on cotton textiles enhances fabric strength. NSSD-coated textiles-printed textiles are applicable for design of fashionable garments and clothing of technical properties like fire protective clothing, bullet proof clothing, antibacterial clothing. NSSD material is also non-toxic and ecofriendly material (*M. A. Hossain, 2020b*). Accordingly there is enormous example in nature under the camouflage philosophy of natural background materials (*Hossain, 2023bj*).

1.1 NSSD properties matched with the materials of desertland, rockland and concreteland CBs

Two types of NSSD materials were formulated for two different experimentations although the major properties of marine-NSSD and river-NSSD are dissimilar due to natural phenomenon. Marine-NSSD is finer, yellower and smoother than river-NSSD (*Cui et al., 2014*). There is prospect of zero reflection physical property when the material composition shows symmetric at the interface between target object against selected CBs (*Hossain, 03 February 2023*; *Park & Lee, 2019*). The composition of rock exists around 55% NSSD, composition of concrete exists around 20% NSSD. Hence rock/concrete and NSSD have the structural symmetry for nearest optical properties between rockland/concreteland CB and NSSD formulated textile surface (*Tamilarasan et al., 2022*).

1.2 Chromatic theory of photometry, colorimetry and spectrometry for visible (Vis) camouflage textiles assessment in laboratory scale and field trialling

RGB (red, 700 nm; green, 550 nm; and blue, 500 nm) light theory and three-dimensional CIE (International Commission on Illumination) theory, color space L^* , a^* , b^* were implemented for camouflage assessment in Vis wavelength when $L^* = 0$ signifies total absorption for perfect black, $L^* = 100$ identifies total reflection for perfect white, $+a^* =$ red (700 nm), $-a^* =$ green (550 nm), $+b^* =$ yellow (600 nm), $-b^* =$ blue (500 nm). Therefore, saturation of color has been denoted by CIE red, green, blue, L^* , a^* , b^* under day light illumination and color measurement

spectrophotometer (A. Hossain, 2021a; Hossain, 2009; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022).

1.3 Research gap for application of NSSD material for optical adaptability against CBs

Camouflage assessment techniques in laboratory and field trialing have not been established due to multidimensional interference against multidimensional combat backgrounds. The optical practicability and adaptability of NSSD material has been experimented against multidimensional CBs which is not experimented and published in literature (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022c).

2 Materials, methodology and formulation

2.1 Exemption notes of NSSD materials collection and approval for textile coloration to conduct registered research located in Australia.

Figure 1, a minimum amount of NSSD material, around 250g was collected from non-commercial sources and applied for non-commercial applications. NSSD application for camouflage textile is an academic platform of research to propose a practicability for broader scale implementation in terms of ecofriendly source of camouflage materials. Therefore, permission of NSSD sample collection may not be required to conduct registered research located in Australia. This exemption may be supported by environment protection and biodiversity conservation Act 1999, compilation no: 52 is satisfied that the terms and conditions of the requirement for approval of activities involving the marine environment (23.1) “A person must not take in a Commonwealth marine area an action that has, will have or is likely to have a significant impact on the environment.”

Figure 1, photographs of NSSD sample collection located at Melbourne Sea beach, Australia.

2.2 Coating and printing with marine-NSSD material on PA-6,6 fabric

This experimentation was trialled with the NSSD materials, collected around 250g NSSD sample from four different places of sea bed, Melbourne Sea beach, Australia. Polyurethane (PU) based tubicoat (PU-tubicoat) was supplied by CHT chemical company Ltd.

NSSD materials were washed by overflowing method for removing salt, dust, tiny particles and other impurities. Then NSSD materials were dried with closed dryer under controlled temperature. Dried NSSD and PU-tubicoat were mixed in a beaker by electric blender. Five formulations of NSSD and PU-tubicoat were trialled for coating (*Abid & Rathod, 2022; Hossain, 2023am*) and padding which were noted as 1: 40, 1: 35, 1: 30, 1: 20, 1: 10; and sequentially termed as formulations (FMs) 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 (*Hossain, 2015a; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019; Samanta et al., 2016*). Formulated NSSD paste was coated and padded on 130 gram per square metre (GSM) PA-6,6 fabric. The PU-coated fabric was further padded with 2% PU solution in dimethyl formamide (DMF) followed by two dip and two nip processes of padding technique. TPU-*Texalon 598A* was selected as crosslinking agent of PA-6,6-NSSD materials (*M. A. Hossain, 2021c*). Fabric was dried in drying chamber at 120°C for 30 min. Similarly, formulation-01 (FM-01) and formulation-02 (FM-02) were applied for NSSD-FMs on 310 GSM cotton twill woven fabric. Two types of NSSD-FMs were proceeded for next stage testing which were termed as formulation-01 (FM-01) and formulation-02 (FM-02) for NSSD-FMs on PA-6,6 fabric(*Hossain, 2023am*).

2.3 Coating and printing with river-NSSD material on cotton fabric

This experimentation was trialled with the NSSD materials, collected around 200g NSSD sample from three different places of river bed, Jamuna River, Bangladesh. NSSD materials were washed by overflowing method for removing dust and tiny particles. Then NSSD materials were dried under natural heating process, sunlight. Hence, NSSD was selected as natural source of silicon dioxide.

A composite paste of Tubassist Fix 104W (10-15%), a crosslinking agent of polyaziridine (*Shukla et al., 2016*), CHT chemical company Ltd.; NK binder (5-10%), acrylonitrile copolymer (*Deubel et al., 1974; Vahle et al., 2018*), E-chem Ltd.; F53 glitter paste (5-10%), acrylic copolymer, E-chem Ltd. and selected NSSD material (75-65%) were formulated for coating and printing paste (*A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2019a; Samanta et al., 2016; Shukla et al., 2016*). Firstly, sun light fixation of natural curing process was applied for 30 min at temperature (30-40)°C and heat fixation of curing machine was also applied for 2-4 min at temperature (100-120)°C. Therefore, 150 GSM single jersey knitted cotton fabric was coated with wooden scrubber and printed with rubber scrubber.

3 Testing and field trialling of coated and printed fabric/garment

Two different techniques of spectrometry and digital photographs were applied for whole assessment of camouflage textiles (*Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a*).

3.1 Fastness and thickness property measurement

Color fastness to wash was conducted by American Association of Textile Chemists and Colorist (AATCC) test method 61-2013, name of machine: ATLAS Launderometer. Figure 1, fabric thickness was measured by digital thickness gauge for existence of NSSD on treated fabric, pressure 20 g/cm².

Figure 2, thickness of NSSD formulated PA-6,6 and cotton fabric.

3.2 Color measurement spectrophotometer

Figure 2,3; Kubelka Munk (K-M) reflection was recorded against white and black standard, supporting information (SI) is attached in Table SI 1. Colorflex EZ 45/0, mode of reflectance was used for measurement of color rendering reflection, K-M reflection, reflection (%) and CIE color value (L^* , a^* , b^*) (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022a). NSSD sample was placed by transparent glass vial and every fabric sample was positioned directly on sample port of color measurement spectrophotometer. The color rendering image of spectrophotometer was also converted by ImageJ software for appearing individual chromatic hue of CIE red, green, blue, L^* , a^* , b^* . 1022×642 pixels were captured by ImageJ software (Hossain, 2015c).

Figure 3, standardization of K-M reflection against white and black standard.

3.3 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

SC7620 sputter coater, Quorum, UK was used under the testing conditions of 250 and 100 magnifications; and 15kV. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) machine TM4000/TM4000Plus, Hitachi, Japan was used under the testing conditions of 250 and 100 magnifications. RGB red color thresholding of SEM images, 1280×960 pixels were generated by ImageJ software. The grey value plot profile of 0 to 250 pixels of SEM images were also captured by ImageJ software under the standardization value of grey value intensity from 0 to 255. The intensity value of 0 denotes minimum intensity/black and the intensity value of 255 denotes maximum intensity/white. Area of SEM image was selected by rectangular method, width = 300 pixels and height = 300 pixels ([A. Hossain, 2021a](#)).

3.4 Field trialling phase 1-4 for camouflage textile assessment against multidimensional combat backgrounds

Practically, visual acuity is the camouflage physics of human perception for visual assessment of concealment, detection, recognition and identification of defence target signature which can be denoted by $\alpha = Y/L$ where α = visual acuity, Y = size of target signature/object, NSSD coated and printed garment and L = distance between object and observer ([Friškovec, 2010](#)). Hence, the field triallings of NSSD coated and printed garments were conducted against white standard. NSSD coated and printed garments was placed against sand bed, rock bed, concrete bed, woodland and water background, field trialling phase 1-4. Nikon Coolpix s2500, Nikon Corporation, Japan; 74163447 was used to capture Vis-photographs under selected distances. A constant measurement of coated and printed garments size was applied for whole experimentation of digital image ([Friškovec, 2010](#); [A. Hossain et al., 2019](#); [Hossain, 2010c](#)). Captured sample of RGB image was converted into RGB stacks and CIE L*, a*, b* stacks for camouflage assessment of individual chromatic hue of CIE red, green, blue, L*, a* and b* against multidimensional CBs. Image function of ImageJ software was applied for this assessment process. Sand, rock, concrete and water of riverside were selected as desert, rockland, concrete ground; and water/marine CBs without considering the salinity of marine water and existing sand% in river water.

3.5 Field trialling phase-01 for camouflage textiles against woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*

This experimentation was trialled against woodland CB *Shorea Robusta Gaertn* during July-October, 2022 under natural illumination (sunlight) of morning day light in a forest environment for concealment, detection, recognition and identification of defence target signature. The distances between target textile sample and camera were kept 7 ft and 21 ft for field trialling. For chromatic assessment; 1495×391 pixels, RGB and CIE L*, a*, b* images were generated by ImageJ software.

3.6 Field trialling phase-02 for camouflage textiles against woodland CB, *Eucalyptus Citriodora, Bamboo Vulgaris; and concrete CB*

Dry wood of *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, Bangladesh origin was purchased from three different tree and three different ages of tree including 40-50% heartwood. For this experimentation, three types of common forest tree were selected as woodland CB such as *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, *Bamboo Vulgaris* and *Musa Acuminata*. A wooden bridge was constructed by the combination of dry wood

of *Eucalyptus Citriodora* and *Bamboo Vulgaris*; and trialled against woodland CB of *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, *Bamboo Vulgaris* and *Musa Acuminata* during November, 2022. The distances between target textile samples and camera were kept 9 ft and 5 ft for field trialling. For chromatic assessment; 3899×1529 pixels, RGB and CIE L*, a*, b* images were generated by ImageJ software.

3.7 Field trialling phase-03 for camouflage textiles against desertland CB

This field trialling was investigated, located at Jamuna river, Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh during July-October, 2022. Two backgrounds were selected as desertland CB for this field trialling. The distances between target textile samples and camera were kept 7 ft, 14 ft, 14ft and 21 ft. For chromatic assessment, 3901×2901 pixels RGB and CIE L*, a*, b* images were generated by ImageJ software.

3.8 Field trialling phase-04 for camouflage textiles against simultaneous CBs of rockland and water

This phase of work was also investigated, located at Jamuna River, Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh during July-October, 2022. The distances between target textile samples and camera were kept 7ft and 14ft for this trialling. For chromatic assessment; 4430×963 pixels, RGB and CIE L*, a*, b* images were generated by ImageJ software.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Electron imaging for camouflage textile assessment in grey scale imaging versus chromatic intensity of SEM images versus red color thresholding images

Figure 4; SEM image of NSSD uncoated and coated PA-6,6 fabric (a2-d2) incorporated with color thresholding images (a1-d1) and plot profile of grey values (a3-d3); SEM images of NSSD uncoated and coated cotton fabric (a5-d5) incorporated with color thresholding images (a4-d4) and plot profile of grey values (a6-d6); partially electron imaging versus

color profile has been represented as a1 = a2 = a3; b1 = b2 = b3; c1 = c2 = c3; d1 = d2 = d3; a4 = a5 = a6; b4 = b5 = b6; c4 = c5 = c6; d4 = d5 = d6 for comparison and analysis of electron imaging in terms of chromatic intensity.

SEM image of uncoated PA-6,6 (a2); NSSD-FM-01 coated PA-6,6 fabric (b2); NSSD-FM-02 coated PA-6,6 fabric (c2); five time post washed NSSD-FM-02 coated PA-6,6 fabric (d2); uncoated cotton fabric (a5); NSSD-FM1 coated cotton fabric (b5); NSSD-FM-02 coated cotton fabric (c5) and five time post washed NSSD-FM-02 coated PA-6,6 fabric (d5); red color thresholding of SEM image of uncoated PA-6,6 (a1); red color thresholding of SEM image of NSSD-FM-01 coated PA-6,6 fabric (b1); red color thresholding of SEM image of NSSD-FM-02 coated PA-6,6 fabric (c1); red color thresholding of SEM image of five time post washed NSSD-FM-02 coated PA-6,6 fabric (d1); red color thresholding of SEM image of uncoated cotton fabric (a4); red color thresholding of SEM image of NSSD-FM-01 coated cotton fabric (b4); red color thresholding of SEM image of NSSD-FM-02 coated cotton fabric (c4) and red color thresholding of SEM image of five time post washed NSSD-FM-02 coated PA-6,6 fabric (d4); grey value intensity of SEM image of uncoated PA-6,6 (a3); grey value intensity of SEM image of NSSD-FM-01 coated PA-6,6 fabric (b3); grey value intensity of SEM image of NSSD-FM-02 coated PA-6,6 fabric (c3); grey value intensity of SEM image of five time post washed NSSD-FM-02 coated PA-6,6 fabric (d3); grey value intensity of SEM image of uncoated cotton fabric (a6); grey value intensity of SEM image of NSSD-FM-01 coated cotton fabric (b6); grey value intensity of SEM image of NSSD-FM-02 coated cotton fabric (c6) and grey value intensity of SEM image of five time post washed NSSD-FM-02 coated cotton fabric (d6).

Figure 4b1, 4b2, 4b4, 4b5; a well cementing has been demonstrated without cracking mark for both PA-6,6 and cotton fabric surface which may decline the breathability of fabric but there is possibility of NSSD reflection of chromatic matching against surrounding CB materials of desertland. SEM image of NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric is comparatively lighter than SEM image of NSSD coated cotton fabric due to high reflection of PA-6,6 base surface related to polymeric structure of $-NH_2$ group. Figure 4a1, 4a2, 4a4, 4a5, 4a3, 4a6 defines the comparison between the electron imaging of PA-6,6 and cotton fabric. PA-6,6 fabric has circular cross section than cotton surface. Hence, PA-6,6 fabric may have chromatic reflection at different angle ([Gupta et al., 2016](#)). SEM image of raw cotton image shows comparatively darker than raw PA-6,6 fabric because of chromatic deviation of base fabric. Cotton fabric has cellulosic structure related to existing $-OH$ group. Oppositely PA-6,6 fabric has polymeric structure of $-NH_2$ group. There is deviation of chromatic intensity between $-OH$ group and $-NH_2$ group. The presence of NSSD has been observed after five time washing shown in figure 4d1, 4d2, 4d4, 4d5. RGB red color thresholding has been remarked in figure 4a1, 4b1, 4c1, 4d1, 4a4, 4b4, 4c4, 4d4 for clarification and comparison of lightness and darkness hue and structural deviation of NSSD coated and uncoated PA-6,6; and cotton fabric. These evidences may clarify the exact bonding and chromatic aberration between NSSD uncoated and coated PA-6,6; and cotton fabric surface. Grey value intensities have also been presented in figure 4a3, 4b3, 4c3, 4d3, 4a6, 4b6, 4c6, 4d6 for clarification and comparison of lightness and darkness hue of NSSD coated and uncoated PA-6,6; and cotton fabric under selected pixels of SEM images. In general, NSSD coated and uncoated cotton fabric tends to lower intensity compared to NSSD coated and uncoated PA-6,6 fabric. Raw PA-6,6 fabric

and cotton fabric shows lower grey value intensity rather than NSSD coated fabric. The lower grey values of raw PA-6,6 fabric and cotton fabric are 116 and 92, cited in figure 4a3. The higher grey values of raw PA-6,6 fabric and cotton fabric are 122 and 135, cited in figure 4a4. The lower grey values of NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric are 152, 129, 95 and the higher grey values of NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric are 158, 134, 160, mentioned in figure 4b3, 4c3, 4d3. Similarly, the lower grey values of NSSD coated cotton fabric are 117, 100, 100 and the higher grey values of NSSD coated cotton fabric are 122, 170, 120, mentioned in figure 4b3, 4c3, 4d3. Therefore, NSSD formulated fabric may be proceeded for target application of camouflage textile in terms of reflection matching/chromatic matching against desertland CB.

4.2 Chromatic assessment of CIE L*, a*, b* value for camouflage textiles against desertland CB

Figure 5; CIE L*, a*, b* color value of raw NSSD, NSSD formulated PA-6,6 and cotton fabric.

Figure 5, CIE L* value of NSSD coated PA-6,6 (60.49) and cotton fabric (67.49) have been found almost nearest of raw NSSD material (57.3) denoted as desertland CB although L* value of NSSD coated PA-6,6 and cotton fabric increases after washing compared to white and black standard. Similarly, CIE a* and CIE b* value of PA-6,6 (2.57 and 15.3) and cotton coated fabric (2.6 and 15.26) were also found nearest value compared with raw NSSD material (a* = 4.76, b* = 17.1). Hence, CIE L*, a*, b* value of NSSD coated fabric has been found chromatic matching against desertland CB. Uncoated PA-6,6 (89.64) and cotton fabric (93.04) shows the highest value of CIE L* and lowest value of CIE a* (-0.53, 3.59) and CIE b* (1.75, -8.95) compared to standardized white and black; and coated PA-6,6 and cotton fabric. The SI of CIE L*, a*, b* has been attached in Table SI 2.

4.3 Chromatic assessment of reflection (%) for formulated camouflage textiles against desertland combat background

Figure 6, reflection (%) measurement of NSSD formulated PA-6,6 and cotton fabric against raw NSSD, common material of desertland CB.

Figure 6, a nearest graphical state of reflection (%) has been found for NSSD coated PA-6,6 and NSSD coated cotton fabric against desertland CB. The reflection (%) of FM-01 and FM-02 coated PA-6,6 and cotton fabric has also been found minor variation before washing and after washing against desertland CB. Hence, a symmetric reflection (%) has been investigated for NSSD-FM-2 formulated PA-6,6 fabric (18-46)% and NSSD-FM-2 formulated cotton fabric (23-46)% against desertland CB (11-33)% when the graphical state of reflection was also noted and compared for untreated PA-6,6 fabric (75)%, untreated cotton (31-100)%, black standard 0% and white standard (81-86)% (A. Hossain, 2021b). The SI of reflection (%) has also been attached in Table SI 3.

4.4 Chromatic assessment of K-M reflection for formulated camouflage textiles against desertland combat background

Figure 7, K-M reflection measurement of NSSD formulated PA-6,6 and cotton fabric against raw NSSD, a common material of desertland CB.

Figure 7, partially it may be argued that K-M reflection state is the opposite nature of reflection (%), referred to the graphical state of chromatic property assessment shown in figure 6. The existing percentage of NSSD on fabric surface is related to the alternate reflection property referred to the figure 2 and figure 4. Higher K-M reflection signifies the maximum existence of NSSD material on fabric surface which can be compared and sequenced as raw NSSD, desertland CB>NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric, FM-2>NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric, FM-2, post washing>NSSD coated cotton fabric, FM-2>NSSD coated cotton fabric, FM-2, post washing> NSSD coated cotton fabric, FM-01> NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric, FM-1>NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric, FM-1, post washing>NSSD coated cotton fabric, FM-01, post washing>untreated PA-6,6 fabric>untreated cotton fabric. The imbrication plot of K-M reflection has been observed for NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric, FM-2, post washing; NSSD coated cotton fabric, FM-2 and NSSD coated cotton fabric, FM-2, post washing. Similarly, the overlapping plot of K-M reflection-FM-01 was also investigated for NSSD coated cotton fabric, FM-01; NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric, FM-1; NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric, FM-1, post washing; NSSD coated cotton fabric, FM-01, post washing. There is also similar K-M reflection among untreated PA-6,6 fabric; untreated cotton and white standard referred to figure 3. This explanation of K-M reflection is also supported by electron imaging in terms of existing NSSD on fabric surface shown in figure 4. The SI of K-M reflection has also been attached in Table SI 4.

4.5 Chromatic assessment of color rendering image for formulated camouflage textiles against desertland combat background

RGB-color rendering of NSSD coated cotton fabric, FM-02; RGB-color rendering of NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric, FM-02; RGB-color rendering of NSSD coated cotton fabric after five-time post washing, FM-02; RGB-color rendering of NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric after five-time post

washing, FM-02 have been exposed sequentially in figure 8a, 8b, 8c, 8d. Figure 8a, 8b; RGB Khaki shading was generated by the image of color rendering in Vis wavelength. Figure 8c, 8d; RGB light shading of khaki was also showed after five-time washing. Similarly; CIE RGB, L*, a*, b* chromatic hues of RGB color rendering images have been presented in figure 8a1-8d6.

Figure 8, RGB color rendering image of NSSD coated cotton fabric (a, b) and NSSD coated PA-6,6 fabric (c, d); and shown the photometric versus colorimetric views of red (a1, b1, c1, d1), green (a2, b2, c2, d2), blue (a3, b3, c3, d3), L* (a4, b4, c4, d4), a* (a5, b5, c5, d5), b* (a6, b6, c6, d6) in grey scale imaging of RGB raw image (a, b, c, d) when the pictorial

mapping has been remarked as $a = a1 = a2 = a3 = a4 = a5 = a6$, $b = b1 = b2 = b3 = b4 = b5 = b6$, $c = c1 = c2 = c3 = c4 = c5 = c6$, $d = d1 = d2 = d3 = d4 = d5 = d6$ for chromatic comparison under multidimensional CIE chromatic hue.

4.6 Field trialling (phase 1-4) of coated and printed fabric/garment against multidimensional CBs under Vis imaging

4.6.1 Field trialling phase-01 for camouflage textiles against woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*

Figure 9, NSSD coated and printed garments against woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn*; and shown the photometric versus colorimetric views of L* (b1, b2, b3), a* (c1, c2, c3), b* (d1, d2, d3), red (e1, e2, e3), green (f1, f2, f3), blue (g1, g2, g3) in grey scale imaging of RGB raw image (a1, a2, a3) when the pictorial mapping has been remarked as $a1 = b1 = c1 = d1 = e1 = f1 = g1$; $a2 = b2 = c2 = d2 = e2 = f2 = g2$; $a3 = b3 = c3 = d3 = e3 = f3 = g3$ for chromatic comparison and adaptation under multidimensional CIE chromatic hue.

Figure 9a1, 9a2, 9a3 shows the raw image of digital RGB imaging. Figure 9b1, 9b2, 9b3 individually shows the CIE L* chromatic hue of RGB raw image. Figure 9c1, 9c2, 9c3 denotes the a* stack of digital image. Figure 9d1, 9d2, 9d3 signifies the b* chromatic hue of raw image. Figure 9e1, 9e2, 9e3 are the reddish tone of woodland CB. Figure 9f1, 9f2, 9f3 clarifies the greenish tone against woodland CB. Figure 9g1, 9g2, 9g3 reflects bluish tone of raw image,

captured against woodland CB. In figure 9a2, 9a3, RGB image; a nearest chromatic hue of NSSD coated and printed part has been pictured against woodland CB. CIE L* image of NSSD coated and printed part has been shown in figure 9b2, 9b3; CIE a* image of NSSD coated and printed part has been shown in figure 9c2, 9c3; CIE b* image of NSSD coated and printed part shown in figure 9d2, 9d3; red stack image of NSSD coated and printed part has been shown in figure 9e2, 9e3; green stack image of NSSD coated and printed part has been shown in figure 9f2, 9f3 and blue stack image of NSSD coated and printed part has been shown in figure 9g2, 9g3. NSSD coated and printed fabric appearances blending with background and signified chromatic comparison against wooden bridge, woodland CB and concrete CB due to photonic response to the digital camera sensor relates to lower reflection and higher K-M reflection of NSSD coated and printed fabric, also shown in figure 6 and 7.

4.6.2 Field trialling phase-02 for camouflage textiles against woodland CB, *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, *Bamboo Vulgaris*; and concrete CB

Figure 10, NSSD coated and printed garments against woodland CB; wooden bridge made by combination of *Eucalyptus Citriodora* and *Bamboo Vulgaris*; *Musa Acuminata* and some unknown species; and concrete CB; and shown the photometric versus colorimetric views of L* (b1, b2), a* (c1, c2), b* (d1, d2), red (e1, e2), green (f1, f2) and blue (g1, g2) in grey scale imaging of RGB raw image (a1, a2) when the pictorial mapping has been presented as

a1 = b1 = c1 = d1 = e1 = f1 = g1; a2 = b2 = c2 = d2 = e2 = f2 = g2 for chromatic comparison and adaptation under multidimensional CIE chromatic hue.

Figure 10a1, 10a2 are the raw image of digital RGB imaging; Figure 10b1, 10b2 shows the red chromatic hue against wooden bridge and *Bamboo Vulgaris*, woodland CB; Figure 10c1, 10c2 are the green chromatic hue against woodland CB; Figure 10d1, 10d2 are the blue chromatic hue against woodland CB; Figure 10e1 and 10e2 are the CIE L* chromatic hue against woodland CB; Figure 10f1 and 10f2 are the CIE a* chromatic hue against woodland CB; Figure 10g1 and 10g2 are the CIE b* chromatic hue against woodland CB. Figure 10a1, 10a2; the RGB image of coated and printed part looks blending against wooden bridge made by the combination of *Eucalyptus Citriodora*, *Bamboo Vulgaris*; *Musa Acuminata* and some unknown species of woodland CB; and a concrete road of concrete CB. In RGB imaging, there is lacking of greenish chromatic hue in NSSD coated and printed fabric. Figure 10b1 and 10b2, red stack image; figure 10c1 and 10c2, green stack image; Figure 10d1 and 10d2, blue stack image; figure 10e1 and 10e2, CIE L* stack image; figure 10f1 and 10f2, CIE a* stack image and figure 10g1 and 10g2, CIE b* stack image looks partially camouflage against wooden bridge, woodland and concrete CB due to the response of digital camera sensor relates to lower reflection and higher K-M reflection of NSSD coated fabric, also cited in figure 6 and 7.

4.6.3 Field trialling Phase-03 for camouflage textiles against desertland CB

Figure 11, NSSD coated and printed garments against desertland CB; and shown the photometric versus colorimetric views of red (b1, b2, b3, b4), green (c1, c2, c3, c4), blue (d1, d2, d3, d4) in grey scale imaging of RGB raw image (a1, a2, a3, a4) when the pictorial mapping has been presented as $a1 = b1 = c1 = d1$; $a2 = b2 = c2 = d2$; $a3 = b3 = c3 = d3$; $a4 = b4 = c4 = d4$ for chromatic comparison and adaptation under multidimensional CIE chromatic hue.

Figure 11a1, 11a2, 11a3, 11a4 are the raw image of digital RGB imaging; Figure 11b1, 11b2, 11b3, 11b4 are the red chromatic hue against desertland CB. Figure 11c1, 11c2, 11c3, 11c4 are the green chromatic hue against desertland CB. Figure 11d1, 11d2, 11d3, 11d4 are the blue chromatic hue against desertland CB. Figure 11a1, 11a2, 11a3, 11a4 shows the chromatic hue of RGB image which are signified as RGB blending between NSSD coated and printed part and selected desertland CB. This RGB blending has also been verified by individual chromatic pile of red, green, blue which are remarked as camouflage, shown in individual figure 11b1, 11b2, 11b3, 11b4; figure 11c1, 11c2, 11c3, 11c4; figure 11d1, 11d2, 11d3, 11d4. The RGB blending appears as completely camouflage of coated and printed fabric against desertland CB.

Figure 12, NSSD coated and printed garments against desertland CB; and shown the photometric versus colorimetric views of L^* (b1, b2, b3, b4), a^* (c1, c2, c3, c4), b^* (d1, d2, d3, d4) in grey scale imaging of RGB raw image (a1, a2, a3, a4) when the pictorial mapping has been presented as $a1 = b1 = c1 = d1$; $a2 = b2 = c2 = d2$; $a3 = b3 = c3 = d3$; $a4 = b4 = c4 = d4$ for chromatic comparison and adaptation under multidimensional CIE chromatic hue.

Figure 12a1, 12a2, 12a3, 12a4 are the raw image of digital RGB imaging; Figure 12b1, 12b2, 12b3, 12b4 are the red chromatic hue against desertland CB. Figure 12c1, 12c2, 12c3, 12c4 are the green chromatic hue against desertland CB. Figure 12d1, 12d2, 12d3, 12d4 are the blue chromatic hue against desertland CB.

Considering RGB image, CIE L*, a* and b* of NSSD coated and printed part shows camouflage against desertland CB which are sequentially shown in figure 12a1, 12a2, 12a3, 12a4; figure 12b1, 12b2, 12b3, 12b4; figure 12c1, 12c2, 12c3, 12c4; figure 12d1, 12d2, 12d3, 12d4. Standardized white part of garment and white color of sky background looks bluish hue against desertland CB shown in figure 12d1, 12d2, 12d3, 12d4.

4.6.4 Field trialling phase-04 for camouflage textiles against simultaneous CB of rockland and water/marine

Figure 13, NSSD formulated garments against rockland and marine CB; and shown the photometric versus colorimetric views of red (b1, b2), green (c1, c2), blue (d1, d2), L* (e1, e2), a* (f1, f2), b* (g1, g2) in grey scale imaging of RGB raw image (a1, a2) when the pictorial mapping has been presented as a1 = b1 = c1 = d1 = e1 = f1 = g1; a2 = b2 = c2 = d2

= e2 = f2 = g2 for chromatic comparison and adaptation under multidimensional CIE chromatic hue.

Figure 13a1, 13a2 are the raw image of digital RGB imaging; Figure 13b1, 13b2 shows the red chromatic hue against rockland and water CB. Figure 13c1, 13c2 are the green chromatic hue against simultaneous CB of rockland and water. Figure 13d1, 13d2 are the blue chromatic hue against rockland and water CB. Figure 13e1, 13e2 are the L* chromatic hue against rockland and water CB. Figure 13f1, 13f2 are the a* chromatic hue against rockland and water CB. Figure 13g1, 13g2 are the b* chromatic hue against rockland and water CB.

Under the chromatic assessment of coated and printed part of garment; RGB image, figure 13a1 and 13a2; red stack of RGB image, figure 13b1 and 13b2; green stack of RGB image, figure 13c1 and 13c2; blue stack of RGB image, figure 13d1 and 13d2; and CIE L* stack of RGB image, figure 13e1 and 13e2; looks completely blending against rockland and sandy river water when compared with standardized white part of garment. CIE a* stack of RGB image in figure 13f1 and 13f2 shows blurred and intermingled image against rockland and sandy river water. CIE b* stack of RGB image in figure 13g1 and 13g2 also signifies camouflage of coated and printed part of garment against CBs of rockland and water/marine. Due to discrepancy of refractive index of water and rock at different temperature in Vis wavelength, the chromatic saturation of red, green, blue, L*, a*, b* may be altered for seasonal and sky background variation because of chromatic blending with sky background (*Bashkatov & Genina, 2003; Han et al., 2013*).

5 Conclusion

Results and discussions on NSSD formulated textiles satisfies the research direction mentioned in the literature review (Hossain, 2023). The right development of methodology for camouflage assessment and camouflage materials are the research question for this research outcome. In this experimentation, an ecofriendly concept of NSSD camouflage material was proposed for material design of camouflage textiles against woodland CB, *Shorea Robusta Gaertn; Eucalyptus citriodora* (dry wood only); *Bamboo Vulgaris, Musa Acuminata*, unknown species of woodland CB and concrete CB. Both optical assessment in Vis wavelength was experimented for laboratory and field trialling. NSSD formulated fabric has been found concealing ability in terms of chromatic adaptation against multidimensional CBs. The concealing ability against CBs can be sequentially remarked as desertland>rockland>concrete land >water >woodland. This technology of NSSD formulation of camouflage textiles may be urged for design of defence tents/car covering/location hiding cloth where breathability and aesthetic property have minor requirements, but nano-NSSD may increase the breathability of coated fabric, such as: camouflage coating against multidimensional CBs, camouflage printing for multidimensional CBs. Furthermore, NSSD formulated textiles may be expanded for subsequent purposes in technical textiles such as: bulletproof defence clothing/tent/car covering, fire protective defence clothing, natural glitter for fashionable garments printing, dyes combination with nano-NSSD for value-added textile applications, geotextile applications for strength enhancement and durability improvement when durability is the question mark when durability is the debating fact for the application of geotextile.

Abbreviations

CBs:	Combat backgrounds
CIE:	International commission on illumination
FMs:	Formulations
GSM	Gram per square metre (g/m ²)
K-M:	Kubelka-Munk
NSSD:	Natural sand-based silicon dioxide
PA-6,6:	Polyamide-6,6
PU:	Polyurethane
RGB:	Red, 700 nm; green, 550 nm; and blue, 500 nm
SEM:	Scanning electron microscopy
Vis:	Visible
PhD:	Doctor of Philosophy
SI:	Supporting information
ID:	Identity

Declaration of conflicting interests

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Data availability

All data generated or analyzed during this experimentation are included in SI, Table SI 1-4.

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The author is self-declaring the sole-authorship of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD, Defence Scientist in terms of conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, material managements, project administration, research communications, planning and prediction, experimentation, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

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